

THE SPACE COURT FOUNDATION STUDENT SPACE LAW JOURNAL

Equity, Sustainability, and the Participation of the Global South in Space Governance
(Luanna Hertel Fiates)

Ships, Shipping, And Spaceships: How Us Commercial Space Cargo Industries Can Avoid The Unintended Consequences Of The Jones Act
(Stacee Danielle Glass Heckmuller)

Barriers And Gateways To Preserving Our Place In The Cosmos: The Legal And Geopolitical Dimensions Of Protecting Heritage Sites In Outer Space (Lee P. Foley)

When Civilian Satellites Go To War: The Cybersecurity Perils Of Dual-Use Space Technology (Mahad Kisuze Mugaya)

The Laws of Heaven: LOAC and the Final Frontier (Haley Fuller)

Amending Article 6 of the North Atlantic Treaty to Explicitly Ensure Article 5 Covers the Space Objects of Parties (Graham Meyer)

Applying International Space Law and Jus ad Bellum to Uses of the Electromagnetic Spectrum in Outer Space
(Adina Sakura Darbyshire)

AND MORE

TABLE OF CONTENTS

SECTION 1: GENERAL

About the Journal	III
SCLL MASTHEAD	IV
Journal MASTHEAD	V
FOREWORD	VI

In an era of unprecedented growth in space activities, driven by both state and private actors, the need for fresh perspectives and innovative legal analysis has never been greater.

SECTION 2: RESEARCH ARTICLES

Equity, Sustainability, and the Participation of the Global South in Space Governance	1-13
Ships, Shipping, and Spaceships: How US Commercial Space Cargo Industries Can Avoid the Unintended Consequences of the Jones Act	14-21
Barriers And Gateways To Preserving Our Place In The Cosmos: The Legal And Geopolitical Dimensions Of Protecting Heritage Sites In Outer Space	22-36
When Civilian Satellites Go To War: The Cybersecurity Perils Of Dual-Use Space Technology	37-54
The Laws of Heaven: LOAC and the Final Frontier	55-82
Amending Article 6 of the North Atlantic Treaty to Explicitly Ensure Article 5 Covers the Space Objects of Parties	83-88
Applying International Space Law and <i>Jus ad Bellum</i> to Uses of the Electromagnetic Spectrum in Outer Space	89-103
Space-Based Earth Observation Imagery & Wartime Atrocities in the International Legal Imagination	104-124
Insurance and Indemnification in Government Contracts for Space and Defense	125-138
Bridging Legal Gaps: Space Sustainability and Governance Participation from Developing Countries	139-151
National Authorization of Private Launching Activities: Critical Components of a Commercial Launch License Framework	152-162
The Implications of Shutter Control: A Basis for Invoking Force Majeure in Earth Observation Data Licenses	163-175

ABOUT THE JOURNAL

The SCF Student Space Law Journal (SCF SSLJ) is a bi-annual, peer-reviewed publication dedicated to fostering academic excellence among students and early-career professionals in the field of space law and policy. Launched in June 2024 by the Space Court Foundation, it is the first journal exclusively for student-authored scholarship in this specialised discipline.

Aim: To offer an accessible yet exceptionally rigorous forum in which current and recent space-law students can cultivate, publish and refine scholarship of the same calibre demanded by the world's leading academic journals. By welcoming contributions from those without advanced law degrees (LLM or higher), the SCF SSLJ fills a critical gap left by traditional space-law periodicals, which seldom consider submissions from undergraduates or early-stage postgraduates, while nonetheless adhering to the highest standards of peer review and editorial excellence.

Scope: The Journal welcomes original contributions on international, regional and national dimensions of space law and policy, including but not limited to:

- Comparative analyses of national space legislation and regulatory frameworks
- Legal protection of Earth's and outer-space environments (including D&QS preservation)
- Space-traffic management (STM) and space-situational awareness (SSA)
- Satellite spectrum allocation and frequency management
- Emerging issues in space sustainability, cybersecurity and the militarisation of space
- Regulatory and ethical considerations for AI and automated decision-making in space activities
- Policy developments relating to commercial, environmental and public-interest uses of outer space

All submissions undergo double-blind peer review in accordance with the most exacting professional standards. Moreover, as part of our internship programme, SCF interns may submit abstracts and, if accepted, are paired with a dedicated mentor who guides them through the drafting and structuring of a professional manuscript, while ensuring they retain full academic ownership of their ideas and prose.

Further information about the SCF SSLJ can be found on [our website](#).

SPACE COURT LAW LIBRARY MASTHEAD

Work on the Space Court Law Library brings together scholars and students from around the world to collaborate on a range of research projects. Together, these projects will form a comprehensive and accessible online space law reference library. It will ultimately be home to the most complete repository of primary source legal documents related to national and international space law, both private and public.

EDITORIAL BOARD

Christopher HEARSEY, JD, MS (Law), MS (Space Studies)
Editor-in-Chief

Yana YAKUSHINA, LL.M, Ph.D. (Candidate)
Deputy Editor-in-Chief & Managing Editor

Jonathan KALEY-ISLEY, JD, LL.M
Deputy Editor-in-Chief & Managing Editor

Nathan JOHNSON, JD, LL.M
Deputy Editor

Charles JP BENNETT, LL.M
Deputy Editor

Roser ALMENDAR, Ph.D. (Candidate)
Associate Editor

Marieta VALDIVIA-LEFORT, Ph.D. (Candidate)
Associate Editor

JOURNAL MASTHEAD

Our editorial and review board comprises distinguished, highly qualified professionals recognised for their expertise in space law and policy.

CHIEF & MANAGING EDITORS

Yana YAKUSHINA, SCF Senior Research Officer

Jonathan KALEY-ISLEY, SCF Executive Director

REVIEWERS OF THIS ISSUE

Charles JP BENNETT, SCF Senior Research Officer

Marieta VALDIVIA-LEFORT, SCF Senior Research Officer

Camilla ACQUARONE, SCF Research Officer

Roser ALMENAR, SCF Research Officer

Tamara BLAGOJEVIĆ, SCF Research Officer

Rihab BEN MOUSSA, SCF Research Officer

Pankaj MEHTA, SCF Research Officer

Antonio STARK, SCF Space Policy & Public Outreach Officer

INVITED REVIEWERS FOR THIS ISSUE

Scott SCHNEIDER, Special Counsel at International Aerospace Law & Policy Group

Federico DI VRUNO, Spectrum Manager at SKAO Co-Director of the IAU CPS

Giuliana ROTOLA, IAU CPS Policy Hub Co-lead

Thomas FURSE, Lecturer in Defence Studies at King's College London

Catrina A. MELOGRANA, International Compliance Analyst at the Pacific Northwest National Laboratory

Tuvana ARAS, PhD Candidate at the Europa Institute and the International Institute of Air & Space Law

FOREWORD

Welcome to the March 2026 issue of the Space Court Foundation Student Space Law Journal (SCF SSLJ).

In an era of unprecedented growth in space activities – driven by both state and private actors – the need for fresh perspectives and innovative legal analysis has never been greater. The SCF SSLJ was founded to meet that need: an open, dedicated platform where law students and early-career space law professionals can participate in scholarly discourse at the highest level. By removing traditional barriers to publication and providing structured editorial mentorship, we aim to cultivate emerging writing talent, stimulate debate, and advance the rule of law in space.

This issue brings together contributions spanning a broad range of urgent and evolving topics in space law. Authors address foundational questions of governance and equity, including the application of the law of armed conflict, electromagnetic spectrum regulation, heritage site preservation, sustainability, and the role of developing nations in shaping the future of space governance. Regional perspectives are also well represented, with articles examining insurance requirements and the regulation of space shipping in the United States, as well as the case for updating NATO principles to reflect the realities of space-based conflict.

A number of contributions in this issue focus specifically on the militarization of space, tackling timely and consequential subjects such as the cybersecurity of dual-use satellites, state censorship and shutter control policies, and the use of satellite data in prosecuting war crimes.

We are deeply grateful to our authors and peer reviewers for their dedication and hard work, and to the entire editorial team for their unwavering commitment to the standards of academic integrity and clarity that define the SCF SSLJ. We hope that as you explore these articles, you will share our enthusiasm for the quality of thinking on display from the next generation of space lawyers.

– Jonathan Kaley-Isley and Yana Yakushina, Managing Editors, March 2026

© The Author(s) 2026. Published by Space Court Foundation. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted reuse, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

EQUITY, SUSTAINABILITY, AND THE PARTICIPATION OF THE GLOBAL SOUTH IN SPACE GOVERNANCE

LUANNA HERTEL FIATES¹

ABSTRACT

The search for effective ways to ensure the safety and long-term use of outer space has become a central challenge for space law globally. In this context, sustainability is widely regarded as essential to maintaining continued access to outer space while ensuring that the benefits derived from space activities are shared among all countries and across generations. Nevertheless, the rapid expansion of space activities and the growing space industry have exposed critical gaps in global governance, particularly concerning unequal participation in shaping the legal frameworks that will determine the future of humanity in space. This paper examines contemporary space governance frameworks – both binding and non-binding – and their relationship with the principles of equity and sustainability. It argues that, while these mechanisms may address sustainability-related challenges, they risk reinforcing structural asymmetries between established spacefaring nations and countries with emerging or limited space capabilities unless equity is incorporated as an operative principle in decision-making processes. In this sense, the article explores how integrating equity into global space governance may contribute to fairer participation and to the long-term sustainability of outer space activities. By examining the interaction between legal structures, international cooperation, and sustainability-oriented instruments, the article identifies structural barriers embedded in current governance arrangements. Rather than proposing an exhaustive reform agenda, the study clarifies how equity and sustainability intersect in contemporary space governance and contributes to ongoing discussions on the more inclusive participation of Global South countries in shaping legal norms governing the sustainable use of outer space.

KEYWORDS: Space Governance; Sustainability; Equity; Participation; Latin America.

¹ LL.B, Pontifical Catholic University of Paraná (Brazil), luanna.fiates@gmail.com.

1. INTRODUCTION

Far from constituting a neutral set of administrative mechanisms, governance defines the future of space exploration. As space activities expand and new challenges emerge – particularly in relation to the long-term sustainability of outer space – governance mechanisms increasingly determine not only how the orbital environment will be regulated, but also who participates in shaping these rules and whose interests they ultimately serve. In this context, while major spacefaring nations and even non-state actors actively shape the current parameters of space exploration, countries in the Global South often remain confined to a more limited position. Their reduced influence in space governance reflects development gaps, historical legacies of colonialism, and persistent structural inequalities that affect access to resources, technology, and decision-making forums. This structural asymmetry becomes especially concerning when sustainability is presented as a universal objective, yet the mechanisms responsible for defining its governance remain concentrated in a limited group of actors.

Any meaningful discussion on the sustainable use of outer space must therefore address the question of equity in governance. Sustainability, in this context, cannot be understood solely as an environmental or technical concern, but also as a matter of participation, representation, and norm-shaping authority within international space law structures. If sustainability is to function as more than a normative aspiration, it must be embedded in governance arrangements that enable inclusive participation and equitable influence in decision-making processes.

In this context, this article argues that addressing sustainability in space governance requires more than technical or environmental responses to emerging challenges in outer space. It requires examining how governance arrangements are structured and how decision-making processes distribute influence among different actors involved in space activities. As space governance increasingly develops through a combination of international treaties, soft law instruments, and regional initiatives, questions of participation and representation become central to understanding how the rules governing space activities are formed. While these mechanisms are often presented as neutral efforts to promote sustainability and safety in outer space, they may also reproduce geopolitical and technological asymmetries that limit the ability of Global South countries to meaningfully participate in shaping these norms.

This article adopts a doctrinal legal analysis of international space law instruments, complemented by a qualitative examination of contemporary governance initiatives and regional cooperation mechanisms involving Global South countries.

2. KEY CONCEPTS

2.1. *Global Space Governance*

Space governance refers to the system of laws, regulations, institutions, and mechanisms – both binding and non-binding – that guide and oversee space activities worldwide.² It is also the gateway to space exploration: those who control the means of governance consequently control access to resources and determine which interests will be served through space activities. For this reason, establishing global space governance has become an urgent priority, especially for guiding and coordinating efforts to solve the current need for safer and more efficient ways to conduct space activities.³ Nevertheless, only a handful of nations currently possess the capacity and influence to actively shape the future of a global space order, while Global South nations remain limited in their participation in the space sector.⁴

² Oltrogge, D. L., & Christensen, I. A. (2020). Space governance in the new space era. *Journal of Space Safety Engineering*, 7(4), 432–438. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jssse.2020.06.003>.

³ Jakhu, R. S., & Pelton, J. N. (Eds.). (2017). *Global space governance: An international study* (pp. 6–7). Springer.

⁴ Bittencourt Neto, O. de O. (2025). Emerging space faring nations: Common perspectives on space traffic management. In S. Hobe & J. Reichhold (Eds.), *Liber Amicorum Instituti Iuris Aeris, Spatialis et Cybernetici in centenarium* (Vol. 1, pp. 349–358). Carl Heymanns Verlag.

2.2. *The Global South*

For the purpose of this article, the geopolitical term “*Global South*” will refer to “underdeveloped” and “developing” countries and the challenges these nations face in participating in international space governance. The difficulties these Nations face were shaped by their collective histories of colonialism and enduring structural inequalities that continue to influence their technological and institutional capacities⁵. This concept emerged in the 1990s and, although not geographically ideal, it represents a more neutral alternative to the pejorative term “Third World”⁶ and will be used consistently throughout the text.

2.3. *Equity vs. Equality*

According to the Cambridge Dictionary, equity is defined as “the situation in which everyone is treated fairly according to their needs, and no group of people is given special treatment.”⁷ Equality, on the other hand, refers to “the right of different groups of people to have a similar social position and receive the same treatment.”⁸ Based on these definitions, it is clear that although the terms are etymologically similar, equity and equality are fundamentally distinct concepts.

This distinction has also been reflected in international environmental law. The Rio Conference,⁹ in 1992, recognized that formal equality between states is not sufficient to address global environmental challenges.¹⁰ Both frameworks recognize that effective and sustainable solutions require taking into account the different capacities, circumstances, and development levels of states.¹¹ For this reason, equity gradually emerged as an important guiding principle in the construction of international environmental governance.¹²

Within space governance, the principle of equity is essential to ensure that access to outer space is not determined solely by States’ technological or financial capacity, but by a fair regime that considers the needs and participation rights of all. It is particularly important for preventing the exhaustion of finite orbital resources and for recognizing that countries which have contributed most to space pollution bear greater responsibility for its mitigation.¹³

In addition, particularly in the context of the long-term sustainability of space activities, it is worth emphasizing that equity must be considered not only by the nations of today but also in relation to future generations, ensuring that outer space remains accessible and beneficial for all.¹⁴

⁵ Jakhu, R. S., & Pelton, J. N., *supra note 2* at 567.

⁶ West-Pavlov, R. (2018). Toward the Global South. In R. West-Pavlov (Ed.), *The Global South and Literature* (pp. 4–10). Cambridge University Press.

⁷ Cambridge University Press & Assessment. (n.d.). *Equity*. In *Cambridge Dictionary* <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/us/dictionary/english/equity>.

⁸ Cambridge University Press & Assessment. (n.d.). *Equality*. In *Cambridge Dictionary* <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/us/dictionary/english/equality>.

⁹ United Nations. (1992). *Rio Declaration on Environment and Development*. In *Report of the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development* (U.N. Doc. A/CONF.151/26/Rev.1 (Vol. I)). [https://undocs.org/en/A/CONF.151/26/Rev.1\(vol.I\)](https://undocs.org/en/A/CONF.151/26/Rev.1(vol.I)).

¹⁰ Louka, E. (2006). *International environmental law: Fairness, effectiveness, and world order*. (p 38). Cambridge University Press.

¹¹ *Ibid*.

¹² Rajamani, L. (2003). From Stockholm to Johannesburg: The anatomy of dissonance in the international environmental dialogue. *European Community & International Environmental Law Review*, 12(1), 23–32.

¹³ Viikari, L. (2008). *The environmental element in space law: Assessing the present and charting the future*. (pp. 129 – 149) Brill / Martinus Nijhoff.

¹⁴ *Ibid*, at 133-135.

3. LEGAL FOUNDATIONS OF SPACE GOVERNANCE

3.1. Legal Frameworks for Outer Space Activities

Space law primarily emerged during the 1950s, in the context of the Cold War, and provides the legal framework for establishing a fair and equitable order in outer space.¹⁵ It also aims to ensure that the benefits and progress derived from space activities are shared among all States, not only those with access to advanced technologies and substantial financial resources.¹⁶ Nearly six decades after its original drafting, the 1967 *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies (Outer Space Treaty (OST))*¹⁷ remains the cornerstone of space law, giving rise to the other four space treaties¹⁸ and the main principles guiding space exploration.

Enshrined in Article I OST, the principles of “freedom of exploration and use” and the “benefits clause” introduce the Treaty. These principles establish that the benefits of space activities must serve all countries, not only those conducting or investing in them, regardless of their level of development. By specifying “irrespective of their degree of economic or scientific development”, the Treaty promotes substantive equality, ensuring that every State is entitled to participate in and benefit from exploration, use (including commercial), and scientific investigation.¹⁹ In this way, Article I seeks to prevent any single State from monopolizing space activities, framing outer space as a shared domain where exploration and use remain a collective endeavor for the benefit of all humanity.²⁰

However, despite its inclusive aspiration, this provision primarily reflects a commitment to equality rather than equity, as is evident from its wording.²¹ Nevertheless, as presented earlier, equality does not always have the capacity to address structural disparities between States with significantly different technological, financial, and institutional capabilities, a reality that particularly affects many countries of the Global South.²² While formal equality guarantees the same legal entitlement to all States, it does not necessarily ensure that all of them possess the practical means to effectively participate in space activities and governance processes.²³

¹⁵ Martinez, P., Jankowitsch, P., Schrogl, K.-U., Di Pippo, S., & Okumura, Y. (2019). Reflections on the 50th anniversary of the Outer Space Treaty, UNISPACE+50, and prospects for the future of global space governance. *Space Policy*, 47, 28–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2018.05.003>.

¹⁶ Monserrat Filho, J. (2009). *Direito e política na era espacial: Podemos ser mais justos no espaço do que na Terra?* [Law and politics in the space age: Can we be more just in space than on Earth?] (pp. 17). Vieira e Lentz.

¹⁷ Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies, adopted on 19 December 1966, opened for signature on 27 January 1967, entered into force on 10 October 1967.

¹⁸ *Agreement on the Rescue of Astronauts, the Return of Astronauts and the Return of Objects Launched into Outer Space*, adopted by the UN General Assembly in its resolution 2345 (XXII), opened for signature on 22 April 1968, entered into force on 3 December 1968; *Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects*, adopted by the UN General Assembly in its resolution 2777 (XXVI), opened for signature on 29 March 1972, entered into force on 1 September 1972; *Convention on Registration of Objects Launched into Outer Space*, adopted by the UN General Assembly in its resolution 3235 (XXIX), opened for signature on 14 January 1975, entered into force on 15 September 1976; *Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies*, adopted by the General Assembly in its resolution 34/68, opened for signature on 18 December 1979, entered into force on 11 July 1984.

¹⁹ Hobe, S., Schmidt-Tedd, K., & Schrogl, K. (Eds.). (2017). *Cologne Commentary on Space law: Outer Space Treaty* (Volynskaya, N., Katsura-Trumpel, M., & Ladeyshchikov, A., Trans., pp. 167-220). BWV Berliner Wissenschafts-Verlag.

²⁰ Bittencourt Neto, O. de O. (2025), *supra* note 4.

²¹ Article I(2) OST.

²² Rajamani, L. (2003), *supra* note 12

²³ Williams, S. M. (1975). The role of equity in the law of outer space. *International Relations*, 5(1), 776–799.

Following in the same direction, Article II of the Outer Space Treaty establishes the principle of non-appropriation, meaning that outer space is not subject to national appropriation by claim of sovereignty, use, occupation, or by any other means. This ensures that no State may claim ownership over Earth's orbits or celestial bodies, preserving outer space as a domain beyond national sovereignty.²⁴

Despite this provision, the growing and intensive use of orbital resources by current spacefaring nations raises questions as to whether the principle of non-appropriation alone is sufficient to guarantee equitable access to outer space. Although no formal appropriation occurs in the legal sense, the concentration of satellites and technological capabilities in the hands of a limited number of actors may result in a form of “*de facto* appropriation” over valuable orbital positions.²⁵ This concern becomes particularly evident in relation to the Geostationary Orbit (GEO), a physically limited orbital region whose use depends on the allocation of orbital slots and radiofrequency spectrum.²⁶

In practice, these dynamic risks restrict access for other States, particularly countries of the Global South, whose technological and financial limitations make it more difficult to secure and maintain orbital positions in increasingly congested orbital environments.²⁷

It is relevant to mention that the rules of space law apply not only to States but also to non-state actors²⁸. Pursuant to Article VI OST, States bear international responsibility for national space activities, whether they are carried out by governmental agencies or by non-governmental entities, and must ensure that national activities are conducted in conformity with the provisions of international and space law. In practice, States must exercise authorization and continuing supervision over the activities of non-governmental entities in outer space

However, although the Outer Space Treaty imposes this obligation, it does not specify the precise requirements or mechanisms through which States must implement them.²⁹ This omission leaves considerable discretion to national governments in determining how Article VI OST should be applied within their domestic legal systems.³⁰ Guided by general principles of international law and good faith, as

²⁴ Bittencourt Neto, O. de O. (2021). Outer space as a global commons and the role of space law. In K. U. Schrogl, C. Mathieu, & T. H. Chen (Eds.), *A research agenda for space policy* (pp. 1–18). Edward Elgar Publishing. DOI: [10.4337/9781800374744.00009](https://doi.org/10.4337/9781800374744.00009).

²⁵ Viikari, L. (2008), *supra note* 15 at 113.

²⁶ The Geostationary Orbit (GEO) refers to an orbital region located approximately 35,786 km above the Earth's equator where satellites move at the same rotational speed as the Earth, allowing them to appear stationary relative to a fixed point on the planet's surface. Because of its unique physical characteristics and operational requirements, the region is widely regarded as a limited orbital resource requiring international coordination. See Martha Mejia-Kaiser, *The Geostationary Ring: Practice and Law*, Studies in Space Law, Vol. 16, pp. 18 – 23 (Brill, 2020); Broadband Commission for Sustainable Development. (2018). *The state of broadband 2018: Broadband catalyzing sustainable development*. International Telecommunication Union.

²⁷ Täiäta, C. M. (2019). The future impact of the ITU regulatory framework on large constellations of satellites. In A. Froehlich (Ed.), *Legal aspects around satellite constellations* (Studies in Space Policy, Vol. 19, pp. 55–79). Springer.

²⁸ Uiederriks-Verschoor, I. H. Ph., & Kopal, V. (2008). *An introduction to space law* (p. 28). Kluwer Law International.

²⁹ Hermida, J. (2004). *Legal basis for a national space legislation* (p. 59). Kluwer Academic Publishers.

³⁰ Cheng, B. (1998). Article VI of the 1967 Space Treaty revisited: “International responsibility,” “national activities,” and “the appropriate state.” *Journal of Space Law*, 26(1), 7–32.

reflected in the *Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties*,³¹ States are therefore expected to develop effective legal and regulatory mechanisms to ensure compliance with their international obligations.³²

This regulatory flexibility is particularly relevant for the long-term sustainability of space activities. As private actors increasingly participate in space operations, effective national authorization and supervision mechanisms are essential to ensure responsible conduct and to protect the orbital environment.³³ However, States differ significantly in their ability to develop and implement such regulatory frameworks, as many countries of the Global South are still building the institutional and legal capacities needed to engage more actively in space activities.³⁴

While the foundational principles established by the Outer Space Treaty continue to guide space activities and have played a crucial role in shaping national space law systems, technological advances and the rapid expansion of the sector have introduced challenges that were not fully anticipated when the Treaty was drafted.³⁵ These developments have prompted the emergence of additional governance mechanisms, raising broader questions about equitable participation in the regulation and use of outer space.

3.2. *Soft Law and Sustainability*

The 1992 Rio Conference, as mentioned above, represents a key milestone in the development of international environmental law. Earlier, the 1972 Stockholm Conference³⁶ had already marked a turning point by raising global awareness of the importance of integrating sustainability into development policies. These developments reflected an increasing recognition that human activities could produce long-term environmental consequences and therefore required coordinated governance mechanisms capable of addressing them.³⁷

When the Outer Space Treaty was drafted in 1967, the possibility that decades of continuous launches would result in ultimate problems was not fully anticipated. However, the rapid expansion of space activities and technological advances over the past decades has raised increasing concerns about the sustainability of the orbital environment.³⁸ These challenges include the growing accumulation of space debris, the congestion of valuable orbital regions, the expansion of large satellite constellations, and the

³¹According to Article 11 of the *Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties* (adopted on 22 May 1969, opened for signature on 23 May 1969 by the United Nations Conference on the Law of Treaties and Entry into force 27 January 1980), States may express their consent to be bound by a treaty through “signature, exchange of instruments constituting the treaty, ratification, acceptance, approval, accession, or by any other means agreed upon.” Furthermore, pursuant to Article 26 of the same Convention, “Every treaty in force is binding upon the parties to it and must be performed by them in good faith.” In other words, States that express their consent to be bound by a treaty are required to comply with it in accordance with the international law principle of *pacta sunt servanda*; Cheng, B. (1987). *General principles of law as applied by international courts and tribunals* (p. 112). Grotius Publications.

³² Von der Dunk, F. (1992). Liability versus responsibility in space law: Misconception or misconstruction. In *Proceedings of the 34th Colloquium on the Law of Outer Space* (p. 363).

³³ Marboe, I. (2015). National space law. In F. von der Dunk & F. Tronchetti (Eds.), *Handbook of space law* (pp. 133 - 135). Edward Elgar Publishing.

³⁴ Diederiks-Verschoor, I. H. Ph., & Kopal, V. (2008). *An introduction to space law* (3rd ed., pp. 80 - 81). Kluwer Law International.

³⁵ Steer, C. (2017). Sources and law-making processes relating to space activities. In R. S. Jakhu & P. S. Dempsey (Eds.), *Routledge handbook of space law* (pp. 3 - 24). Routledge.

³⁶ United Nations. (1972). Declaration of the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment. In Report of the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment (U.N. Doc. A/CONF.48/14/Rev.1). <https://undocs.org/en/A/CONF.48/14/Rev.1>.

³⁷ Sands, P., & Peel, J. (2012). *Principles of international environmental law* (3rd ed., pp. 22 - 40). Cambridge University Press.

³⁸ Martinez, P., Jankowitsch, P., Schrogl, K.-U., Di Pippo, S., & Okumura, Y. (2019), *supra note 14*.

need for more effective space traffic management. Some of these developments have the potential to disrupt, and in extreme cases even halt, space activities.³⁹

In response, discussions within the United Nations Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (UNCOPUOS), particularly since the 2010s, have sought to address these challenges. Beyond the existing hard law framework, the *UNCOPUOS Guidelines for the Long-Term Sustainability of Outer Space Activities* (LTS Guidelines), adopted in 2019, represent an important soft law initiative.⁴⁰ The set of twenty-one voluntary guidelines aims to promote responsible behavior, international cooperation, and the safe and sustainable use of outer space by encouraging the adoption of internationally recognized practices intended to mitigate risks to space operations and the orbital environment.⁴¹

Despite their non-binding nature, these soft-law instruments play a crucial role in coordinating the interests of both States and private actors and in adapting governance mechanisms to the rapidly evolving space environment. Their flexibility allows for the development of guidelines and best practices that reflect the interests of different stakeholders while encouraging cooperation and responsible conduct.⁴² Nevertheless, the implementation of non-binding sustainability-oriented instruments also raises broader questions of equity, particularly regarding inclusion and the capacity of different States to participate in shaping and applying these norms.

4. STRUCTURAL CHALLENGES AND INEQUALITIES AFFECTING THE GLOBAL SOUTH

4.1. Geopolitical Asymmetries in Global Space Governance

Between hard and soft law, space governance regulates activities at the national, regional, and international levels. Nevertheless, current geopolitical tensions and the rise of regional blocs have limited the effectiveness of truly multilateral cooperation. As a result, powerful spacefaring nations, such as the United States, China, and members of the European Union, largely define the rules for future space exploration, and the Global South participates in this discussion without significantly influencing the agenda or shaping norms.⁴³

In theory, this contradicts Article I OST, which, as noted above, mandates that the exploration and use of outer space should be conducted for the benefit and in the interest of all countries, regardless of their economic or scientific development, thereby affirming the nature of space as the “province of all mankind”. Yet even though the advancement of space exploration and the safety of these activities are interests shared by all humanity and should be discussed considering the needs of all States, the reality of governance is far from equal.

In 2014, during the *Second Manfred Lachs International Conference on Global Space Governance* held at the McGill Institute of Air & Space Law, representatives from 22 countries, including spacefaring and non-spacefaring nations, gathered to adopt the *Montreal Declaration on Global Space Governance*. Subsequently, in 2017, McGill University conducted the *Global Space Governance Study*,⁴⁴ resulting in

³⁹ Oltrogge, D. L., & Christensen, I. A. (2020), *supra note 2*.

⁴⁰ Martinez, P. (2021). The UN COPUOS guidelines for the long-term sustainability of outer space activities. *Journal of Space Safety Engineering*, 8(2), 98–107. DOI: [10.1016/j.jsse.2021.02.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsse.2021.02.003).

⁴¹ *Ibid.*

⁴² Aoki, S. (2012). The function of “soft law” in the development of international space law. In I. Marboe (Ed.), *Soft law in outer space: The function of non-binding norms in international space law* (pp. 57–87). Böhlau Verlag.

⁴³ Jakhu, R. S., & Pelton, J. N., *supra note 2* at 592.

⁴⁴ *Idem* (2017). *Global space governance: Key proposed actions [Executive summary]*. Institute of Air and Space Law, McGill University. https://www.mcgill.ca/iasl/files/iasl/global_space_governance_-_executive_summary_and_key_proposed_actions.pdf

an executive summary presenting the strengths and weaknesses of different countries and regions in implementing global space governance.

The study reinforces the argument that, despite the significant capabilities of some States, many countries, particularly in the Global South, continue to face structural barriers that limit their effective participation in global space governance.⁴⁵ While regions such as Europe benefit from strong institutional frameworks and coordinated governance mechanisms,⁴⁶ many Global South countries lack even basic structures for cooperation. Structural challenges such as limited budgets, technological gaps, and political and economic constraints continue to restrict their ability to participate more actively in shaping space governance.⁴⁷

4.2. *Structural and Institutional Barriers to Space Development*

As mentioned above, numerous factors prevent the Global South from actively shaping the future of space exploration, consequently delaying the development of global space governance. Moreover, these countries rely heavily on more developed nations to conduct space exploration,⁴⁸ reflected in their dependence on foreign launch services, access to advanced technologies, and restricted participation in international missions.

A well-established spacefaring nation may experiment in the space sector, investing time and money in research activities and newer space technology. It is also in their interest that the future of space activities remains safe for exploration and exploitation.⁴⁹ For these reasons, creating soft law mechanisms and guidelines to mitigate the effects of excessive orbital traffic and space debris is high up on these States' agenda, as the preservation and sustainability of space activities have emerged as key priorities for these countries.⁵⁰ However, as established in the topic above, for Global South nations, there remain more pressing issues demanding attention.

This does not mean that sustainability challenges in outer space will remain unaddressed, but rather that their resolution may occur without the effective participation of Global South nations.⁵¹ Consequently, in the absence of their involvement, there is no guarantee that the future of space exploration will accommodate their long-term needs and priorities.

5. PATHWAYS TOWARD INCLUSIVE AND SUSTAINABLE SPACE GOVERNANCE

5.1. *Straightening regional cooperation*

Given that countries in the Global South may not be able to prioritize space-related matters exclusively, how can they effectively engage in the future of space exploration? Although the solution is complex, it largely depends on strengthening cooperative mechanisms that allow Global South countries to collectively develop technological capacity and increase their influence in global space governance processes. One nation alone may not have the financial and technical resources to explore space, but regional strategies can overcome these limitations. Considering this, the following sections (5.2, 5.3 and 5.4) highlight a few regional initiatives promoted by the Global South to advance space exploration.

⁴⁵ *Ibid.* at 8.

⁴⁶ *Ibid.*

⁴⁷ *Ibid.*

⁴⁸ Dolman, E. C. (2002). *Astropolitik: Classical geopolitics in the space age* (p. 154). Frank Cass Publishers.

⁴⁹ Bittencourt Neto, O. de O. (2021), *supra note* 23.

⁵⁰ Aoki, S. (2012), *supra note* 9 at 62 – 63.

⁵¹ Hafner, G. (2012). The Declaration on International Cooperation in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space for the Benefit and in the Interest of All States. In I. Marboe *supra note* 9 at 267–287.

5.2. Latin America

In the case of Latin America, due to its location near the Equator, the region holds significant strategic potential in the space sector⁵² but continues to face persistent structural challenges, including limited financial and technological resources, underdeveloped space infrastructure, and a regional integration process that remains in its early stages.⁵³ Regional integration for the joint use of space resources remains limited, and there is a notable absence of robust public policies addressing the technological and financial challenges inherent to the development and management of space activities.⁵⁴ However, there are a few initiatives that promote cooperation among Latin American countries, such as the SABIA-Mar satellite, a joint Argentina-Brazil mission for ocean and coastal observation,⁵⁵ and the Latin American and Caribbean Space Agency (ALCE), based in Mexico, which promotes regional cooperation in space technology, satellite applications, and environmental monitoring.⁵⁶

Beyond these institutional initiatives, regional cooperation in Latin America has also been shaped by structural constraints faced by emerging spacefaring nations. Countries in the region often rely on a limited number of space assets, making secure and sustainable access to satellite services particularly important for economic development and environmental monitoring.⁵⁷ At the same time, budgetary limitations and restricted access to strategic technologies have historically constrained the development of autonomous space capabilities. As a result, regional and international cooperation has increasingly been viewed as a strategic pathway to strengthen technological capacity and enhance Latin American participation in global discussions on the governance and sustainability of outer space.⁵⁸

While initiatives like ALCE represent important first steps, the absence of key countries, such as Brazil, highlights ongoing challenges to full regional integration. This limitation illustrates the broader structural challenge faced by many Global South regions, where fragmented institutional frameworks continue to hinder coordinated participation in international space governance processes.

⁵² Locations close to the equator provide important advantages for rocket launches. The higher rotational speed of the Earth's surface at these latitudes reduces the energy required to place a spacecraft into orbit, which lowers fuel consumption and operational costs. In addition, such regions often offer favorable conditions for launch operations, including lower air traffic density and access to a wider range of orbital inclinations. See Brazilian Air Force. (2025, December). *Brazil prepares first commercial rocket launch from the Alcântara Launch Center*. <https://www.fab.mil.br/notimp/mostra/15122025>.

⁵³ Barrene Irigoín, J. (1984). *International space law and international cooperation* [El derecho internacional del espacio y la cooperación internacional]. *Revista Chilena de Derecho*, 11(2–3), 543–552.

⁵⁴ Barrene Irigoín, J. (1984). El derecho internacional del espacio y la cooperación internacional [International space law and international cooperation]. *Revista Chilena de Derecho*, 11(2–3), 543–552.

⁵⁵ Agência Espacial Brasileira. (2023). *AEB e INPE participam da MCDR do satélite SABIA-Mar argentino* [AEB and INPE participate in the MCDR of the Argentine SABIA-Mar satellite]. <https://www.gov.br/inpe/pt-br/assuntos/ultimas-noticias/inpe-e-aeb-participam-da-mcdr-do-satelite-sabia-mar-argentino>; Comisión Nacional de Actividades Espaciales (CONAE). (n.d.). *Misiones Espaciales: SABIA-Mar* [Space Missions: SABIA-Mar]. <https://www.argentina.gob.ar/ciencia/conae/misiones-espaciales/sabia-mar>.

⁵⁶ México. Secretaría de Relaciones Exteriores. (2021). *Latin American and Caribbean Space Agency Charter enters into force*. <https://www.gob.mx/sre/prensa/latin-american-and-caribbean-space-agency-charter-enters-into-force?idiom=en>;

México. (2024, June). *Technical presentation: Latin American and Caribbean Space Agency (ALCE)*. Presented at the 61st session of the Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space, Vienna: UNOOSA. https://www.unoosa.org/documents/pdf/copuos/2024/Technical_Presentations/24AM/3_Item_5_-_Technical_Presentation_Mexico_-_Final_Version_1.pdf.

⁵⁷ Bittencourt Neto, O. de O., & Becerra, J. (2024). Space security from Latin American perspectives. In S. M. Pekkanen & P. J. Blount (Eds.), *The Oxford handbook of space security* (pp. 475–494). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780197582671.013.26>.

⁵⁸ *Ibid.*

Drawing on international experience, coordinated adoption of sustainability guidelines, such as the *European Code of Conduct for Space Debris Mitigation*, demonstrates how technical recommendations can be operationalized, a model ALCE could follow to avoid Latin America being left behind in orbital sustainability governance.⁵⁹

Complementing these efforts, the *Buenos Aires Declaration on Cooperation in Space Law* emphasizes the need for joint programs in priority areas like remote sensing and space meteorology, the strengthening of space law as an academic and policy tool, and the creation of binational initiatives linking research, technical training, and public policy.⁶⁰

5.3. Asia and the Pacific

The Asia-Pacific Space Cooperation Organization (APSCO), established in 2008 and headquartered in Beijing, represents one of the most prominent examples of regional space governance initiatives involving Asian states. As an intergovernmental organization, APSCO provides an institutional framework through which member countries can cooperate in the peaceful use of outer space, particularly through joint projects, data sharing, and capacity-building programs in space science, technology, and applications. Its Member States include Bangladesh, China, Iran, Mongolia, Pakistan, Peru, Thailand, and Turkey, reflecting an effort to promote South–South cooperation in the development and use of space technologies.⁶¹

Although it represents an important initiative of South-South cooperation, APSCO still faces challenges, as it does not encompass most Asian countries and remains limited by disparities in technical and financial capacities among its members, dependence on China for infrastructure and resources, and the need to strengthen regional integration and autonomy in space governance.⁶²

Beyond its institutional structure, APSCO also illustrates how regional organizations may contribute to broader discussions on the long-term sustainability of outer space activities. Because many of its member states are emerging space actors with limited independent capabilities, cooperation within APSCO functions not only as a mechanism for technology sharing but also as a platform for capacity building and coordinated policy development. In this context, regional organizations can complement global governance efforts by promoting shared standards, exchanging technical knowledge, and facilitating the implementation of sustainability-related practices, such as debris mitigation and space traffic coordination.⁶³ Such initiatives demonstrate how regional cooperation can strengthen participation of developing states in the governance of outer space while simultaneously supporting the broader objective of maintaining the long-term sustainability of space activities.

5.4. Africa

The African Space Agency (AfSA), established in 2025 and headquartered in Egypt’s Space City, Cairo, functions as the continental body of the African Union tasked with coordinating and implementing space-related activities across Africa. Its mission is to foster cooperation among African nations and with international partners, advancing the use of space science and technology to support the region’s development objectives.⁶⁴

⁵⁹ Mejía-Kaiser, M. (2009). Informal regulations and practices in the field of space debris mitigation. *Annals of Air and Space Law*, 34(1), 21–34.

⁶⁰ Monserrat Filho, J., *supra* note 4 at 164 - 165.

⁶¹ Asia-Pacific Space Cooperation Organization. (2018). What is APSCO? <http://www.apSCO.int/html/comp1/content/WhatisAPSCO/2018-06-06/33-144-1.shtml>.

⁶² Jakhu, R. S., & Pelton, J. N., *supra* note 2 at 73 – 80.

⁶³ Yan, Y. (2019). Maintaining long-term sustainability of outer space activities: Creation of regulatory framework to guide Asia-Pacific Space Cooperation Organization and selected legal issues. *Space Policy*, 47, 40–48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2018.06.002>.

⁶⁴ African Space Agency. (n.d.). *Our history*. <https://africanspaceagency.org/our-history/>.

Despite regional challenges, AfSA stands out for bringing together a wide range of African countries. Although it is still too early to assess its long-term development, the agency already represents an important step toward strengthening regional cooperation and coordinated space governance on the continent. While initiatives such as AfSA strengthen regional coordination, they also reflect a broader dynamic within the development of international space law. From its early stages, the legal framework governing outer space has emphasized the need to balance the interests of different states and to ensure that space activities are carried out for the benefit of the international community guided by principles of justice and equity.⁶⁵

In this context, regional cooperation mechanisms can play an important role in enabling states to coordinate interests, develop capabilities, and collectively participate in broader international governance structures.⁶⁶ By fostering coordination, knowledge exchange, and institutional development, regional organizations such as AfSA contribute to reducing structural asymmetries and enabling a more balanced participation of different regions in international space governance.

5.5. *Capacity Building, Knowledge Production, and Legal Empowerment in the Global South*

As mentioned before, cooperation alone will not address all governance challenges. Governments and high-level representatives undoubtedly play a decisive role in shaping the legal and political frameworks of space activities. However, the concern lies with the future of space exploration, and, in this case, it is equally necessary to invest in the generations who will one day occupy these positions of leadership and decision-making.⁶⁷

The most effective way to achieve this is through education and capacity building. By sharing expertise, infrastructure, and research capabilities across countries, particularly between developed space-faring nations and emerging space-faring nations in the Global South, technological cooperation ensures that all actors can participate meaningfully in space exploration.⁶⁸ Not only that, but education should also be a priority.

Space law, although not new, is not widely understood or accessible, particularly in the Global South. Strengthening knowledge in this field ensures that States and private actors can participate effectively in international space governance, comply with legal obligations, and contribute to the sustainable and peaceful exploration of outer space. Educational programs, workshops, moot courts, and specialized courses are essential tools to promote knowledge, local expertise, and foster collaboration across borders.⁶⁹

In this context, initiatives that promote the internationalization of young professionals from the Global South, such as scholarships, research fellowships, and technical exchange programs, are essential to empower new voices and foster more inclusive perspectives in space governance. Diversity in academic and professional backgrounds is widely recognized as enriching the debate and enabling more innovative and equitable approaches to global challenges. Universities, international organizations, and national governments should therefore collaborate to expand educational and research opportunities in space law and policy.⁷⁰

⁶⁵ Froehlich, A., Ringas, N., & Wilson, J. (2020). A look at governance throughout Africa. In A. Froehlich (Ed.), *Space supporting Africa, volume 3: Security, peace, and development through efficient governance supported by space applications* (pp. 1–51). Springer.

⁶⁶ Jakhu, R. S., & Pelton, J. N. (2017), *supra* note 3.

⁶⁷ Cheng, B. (1979). *Manual on space law* (p. 274). Oceana Publications.

⁶⁸ Hafner, G. (2012), *supra* note 48.

⁶⁹ Von Der Dunk, F. (2003). Overview of educational programmes in space law. In *Proceedings of the UN/IASL Workshop on Capacity Building. Office for Outer Space Affairs, United Nations Office* (Session 3, p. 431).

⁷⁰ Ciro Arévalo Yepes (2003). Application of Space Science and Technology in the Americas and its Benefits for Civil Society, In *supra* note 30 at 517 – 524.

Several international initiatives already seek to advance these capacity-building objectives. For instance, the United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs (UNOOSA), in cooperation with Luxembourg, launched the Space Law for New Space Actors⁷¹ initiative to support emerging spacefaring nations in developing national legal frameworks and strengthening institutional expertise in space governance. Similarly, the Global Space Law Project⁷² promotes training programs and technical assistance aimed at expanding legal knowledge in space law among developing countries. Additional initiatives, such as the Access to Space for All program and the United Nations–affiliated Regional Centers for Space Science and Technology Education,⁷³ provide training opportunities and institutional support for students and professionals from emerging space nations.

Academic initiatives also play an important role in this context, particularly the Manfred Lachs Space Law Moot Court Competition,⁷⁴ organized by the International Institute of Space Law, which has contributed to training new generations of space law practitioners and scholars from different regions of the world.

Encouraging young scientists, lawyers, and policymakers from the Global South to participate in international congresses, training programs, and professional networks, therefore, represents an important step toward strengthening their presence in global space governance discussions. By expanding opportunities for education, cooperation, and institutional development, capacity-building initiatives can help reduce structural inequalities in participation and contribute to a more inclusive and sustainable framework for the governance of outer space.

6. CONCLUSION

The growing intensity of space activities has renewed attention to the governance structures that regulate the use of outer space. As this article has demonstrated, the current legal and institutional framework, composed of foundational treaties, soft law instruments, and emerging cooperative initiatives, plays a decisive role in shaping how space activities are organized and regulated. While these mechanisms have established an important normative remark for the peaceful use of outer space, they have developed within a geopolitical environment marked by disparities in technological capacity, financial resources, and institutional influence among states.

Within this context, equity becomes central to understanding the limits of existing governance arrangements. Although international space law formally guarantees equal rights to explore and use outer space, the principle of equality alone is insufficient to address the structural differences that shape states' actual ability to participate in space activities and governance processes. As a result, countries with greater technological and economic capabilities continue to exert disproportionate influence, while many nations of the Global South remain constrained by limited resources and institutional capacity.

The analysis presented throughout this article also highlights the role of cooperative mechanisms as pathways for expanding participation and strengthening institutional capacity. Regional initiatives, joint

⁷¹ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (2024). *Space law for new space actors project: UN/UNU regional space law technical advisory mission for Asia and the Pacific countries (APTAM24)*. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/capacitybuilding/advisory-services/aptam24.html>.

⁷² United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (n.d.). *Global space law project: Legal advisory services and capacity-building activities*. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/capacitybuilding/advisory-services/summary-of-the-project.html>.

⁷³ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (n.d.). *Regional centres for space science and technology education affiliated to the United Nations*. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/psa/regional-centres/index.html>.

⁷⁴ International Institute of Space Law. (n.d.). *About the Manfred Lachs space law moot court competition*. <https://iisl.space/about-the-manfred-lachs-space-law-moot-court-competition/>.

missions, and educational programs contribute to the development of technical expertise, legal knowledge, and policy coordination among emerging space actors. By fostering cooperation and knowledge exchange, these initiatives help create conditions for broader engagement in the governance of outer space.

Ultimately, the long-term sustainability of space activities will depend not only on technical standards and regulatory instruments but also on the inclusiveness of the governance structures through which these rules are developed. Advancing a more equitable approach to space governance is therefore not only a matter of fairness but also a necessary condition for enabling broader participation, particularly from countries of the Global South, in shaping the legal and institutional framework governing outer space. Such participation is essential to ensure that the long-term sustainability of space activities reflects the interests and needs of the international community today and in the future.

© The Author(s) 2026. Published by Space Court Foundation. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted reuse, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

SHIPS, SHIPPING, AND SPACESHIPS: HOW US COMMERCIAL SPACE CARGO INDUSTRIES CAN AVOID THE UNINTENDED CONSEQUENCES OF THE JONES ACT

STACEE DANIELLE GLASS HECKMULLER¹

ABSTRACT

In the United States, the Jones Act (1920) requires all vessels carrying cargo between US ports to be American-built, crewed, operated, and flagged. Over a hundred years later, as cargo shipping begins to expand into outer space, American policymakers must learn from the negative unintended consequences of the Jones Act. In order to support the growth of the US industry without enacting harmful protectionist policies, the US space community must invest in multi-operational infrastructure, focus on cost-effective domestic operations, and invest early in education for American personnel to organically retain domestic expertise. This paper argues that American policymakers in the commercial space industry should avoid adopting a regulatory framework similar to the Jones Act because of its protectionist structure and its long-term industry harm.

KEYWORDS: Space Law, Maritime Law, Jones Act, Commercial Space Policy.

¹ Space Court Foundation Intern; stacee.heckmuller@spacecourtfoundation.org

1. INTRODUCTION

Following the World Wars, the United States passed the Merchant Marine Act of 1920, commonly known as the Jones Act, to strengthen the maritime industry, but the protectionist nature of the policy had unintended consequences of negatively impacting maritime companies' abilities to compete globally. This paper seeks to serve as a warning that protectionist and nationalist domestic policies can be detrimental to the sustainment of commercial industries. First, this paper establishes a foundation outlining the Jones Act and its impact on the commercial maritime industry.² Next, the current US space policy is examined to help understand how the US views space operations, infrastructure, growth, and talent retention. This policy includes relevant acts passed by Congress and existing codified statutes under the United States Code. Finally, this paper creates a parallel between the maritime and space industries, highlighting the lessons that space policy should learn from the maritime industry, from the European Union, and from the impacts of the Jones Act.

In December 2025, the White House issued an executive order urging Americans to develop technologies that contribute to national “strength, security, and prosperity.” One of the stated goals was “Growing a vibrant commercial space economy” by fostering economic growth, establishing “ground, space, and lunar infrastructure and standards that enable implementation of space priorities and a robust space industrial base.”³ Notably, the current White House policy for the maritime industry uses very similar language, saying, “The Secretary of Commerce...shall recommend...for inclusion in the [Maritime Action Plan] all available incentives to help shipbuilders domiciled in allied nations partner to undertake capital investment in the United States to help strengthen the shipbuilding capacity of the United States.”⁴ The language of the stated goals is similar, but the US government and domestic space companies must be wary of adopting protectionist regulatory frameworks.

Maritime and space are similarly situated at the cross-section of national security and commercial goods, and the US should avoid adopting a regulatory framework for space cargo transport that mirrors the protectionist structure of the Jones Act. Space cargo includes humanitarian materials, military supplies, industry parts, and medical and personal equipment.⁵ Looking forward, the US commercial space policy must invest in building a robust infrastructure capable of supporting multinational use, strengthen cost-effective domestic operations, and invest early in the retention of domestic expertise.

2. UNDERSTANDING THE JONES ACT

In the United States, the Jones Act is the controlling federal statute regulating the domestic commercial shipping industry. It requires that all vessels transporting cargo directly between two US ports are American-built, owned, crewed, and flagged.⁶ The Jones Act was passed after the First World War with the goal of strengthening national security and protecting domestic maritime operations. At the time,

² Merchant Marine Act of 1920 (Jones Act), Pub. L. No. 66-261, § 27, 41 Stat. 988 (1920)

³ The White House. (2025, December 18). *Ensuring American space superiority*. <https://www.whitehouse.gov/presidential-actions/2025/12/ensuring-american-space-superiority/>.

⁴ The White House. (2025, April 9). *Restoring America's Maritime Dominance*. <https://www.whitehouse.gov/presidential-actions/2025/04/restoring-americas-maritime-dominance/>.

⁵ Walton, R. O., & Goehlich, R. A. (2022). *Space cargo: Ultra-fast delivery on Earth—Potential of using suborbital space vehicles for the transportation of cargo*. *International Journal of Aviation, Aeronautics, and Aerospace*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.15394/ijaaa.2022.1671>.

⁶ Wicker, Sen. R., Cantwell, Sen. M., DeFazio, Rep. P., & Graves, Rep. S. (2020, June 5). *Why the Jones Act is still needed 100 years later*. *Defense News*. <https://www.defensenews.com/opinion/commentary/2020/06/05/why-the-jones-act-is-still-needed-100-years-later/>.

those fears were well-founded: the merchant marine fleet was a key component of national security and economic prosperity.⁷ Decades later, many believe the Jones Act stunted US maritime growth.

2.1. Jones Act Impact on US Commercial Shipping

Following the Second World War, the US dominated global shipping, operating a fleet of more than 5,500 ships. At the time, national security was at the forefront of the American mind, and the US had the industry, resources, and knowledge to rule the high seas. In less than one-hundred years, US shipping dropped to 22nd among global fleets of merchant vessels. The obvious explanation for the decline is strict standards and cost: it is significantly more expensive to build, register, and crew vessels in the US.⁸ But the benefits of maintaining a US fleet are four-fold:

- US vessels meet both commercial and national defense standards;
- Seafarers maintain a standard of expertise and excellence;
- Domestic shipyards contribute to national security; and
- Intermodal transportation infrastructure is maintained for commercial and defense purposes.⁹

2.2. Benefits of the Jones Act in the United States

The Jones Act is critical for US stability in the maritime industry. Under its standards, American mariners have been able to maintain more than 650,000 jobs within the US, culminating in a \$150 billion contribution to the economy each year.¹⁰ A thriving shipbuilding industry also allows for technologically modern warships to be constructed entirely within the United States, supporting national defense goals and maintaining industrial integrity. In essence, “[W]ith 97 percent of all U.S. overseas commerce being conducted by foreign-flagged carriers, [l]osing the Jones Act would mean ceding our domestic maritime economy to China and other foreign-flagged competitors, making us more vulnerable during times of crisis.”¹¹ Maintaining vertical chains of operation within the US helps control security measures and supports local economies while boosting American workers and retaining domestic industrial expertise.

2.3. Negative Impacts of the Jones Act in the United States

The commercial space industry must understand where Jones Act policies went wrong to avoid the same pitfalls in future domestic space policy. The Jones Act deserves criticism because it lost its practicality in a world that became increasingly reliant on globalization and multinational operation. In practice, the restrictions imposed by the Jones Act, combined with a failure of foresight by the US government, led to the decline of the domestic maritime industry. Requiring all operations to take place in the US led to higher shipping rates and lower demand for shipping services.¹² The US failed to invest in mariners at the rate required to efficiently and effectively keep up with the global market. Unintended consequences of the Jones Act created unavoidable costs: the cost of the necessity of requiring a US-built maritime service, the cost of operating that fleet, and the cost of retaining a merchant fleet.

⁷ Mercogliano, S. (2019, December 1). *Sea History 169—Winter 2019-2020: A Century of the Jones Act*. National Maritime Historical Society & Sea History Magazine, 169, 13. https://issuu.com/seahistory/docs/sh_169_winter-2019-20/15.

⁸ *Supra*, note 7.

⁹ American Maritime Partnership. (2017, October 17). *Jones Act: Cornerstone of U.S. maritime safety and security*. <https://www.americanmaritimepartnership.com/u-s-maritime-industry/jones-act-overview/>.

¹⁰ *Supra*, note 9.

¹¹ *Ibid*.

¹² Grabow, C., Manak, I., & Ikenson, D. J. (2018, June 28). *The Jones Act: A burden America can no longer bear*. Cato Institute. <https://www.cato.org/publications/policy-analysis/jones-act-burden-america-can-no-longer-bear>.

Cost of Necessity. One of the major unintended consequences of the Jones Act is the inflated cost to build an American ship. A coastwise vessel used for Jones Act cargo transport built in the US typically costs between \$190-250 million dollars to build. A similar foreign-built vessel costs about \$30 million. Due to high construction costs, US merchant vessels are, on average, 11 years older than similar vessels in other countries' fleets. In contrast, the Chinese started constructing dual-use (military and cargo) vessels, likely providing a significant strategic advantage should a future conflict arise.¹³

US vessels that do not participate in the Jones Act trade are not required to be US-built, and yet they are still successful. In fact, 30 of 46 vessels in the US Ready Reserve Fleet, ships available for the US government in the event of armed conflict, are foreign constructed vessels.¹⁴ Since the US industry faces challenges with waterborne transportation due to Jones Act restrictions, many companies increasingly turn to other modes of transportation. The result is significantly increased transportation and shipping costs. In 2013, it was estimated that traffic congestion cost the US economy nearly \$124 billion, expected to rise by more than \$60 billion in 2030. Even incremental increases in the use of Jones Act vessels could significantly and positively contribute to the US economy.¹⁵

Cost of Operation. The US failed to keep pace with foreign shipbuilding and vessel operation because it failed to adapt its market to match international practices that ultimately allow for more cost-effective processes. Overall, US vessels are significantly more expensive to build and operate than foreign vessels. Domestic shipbuilding reduced dramatically because "Subsidies that compensated for escalating costs in domestic production were withdrawn, leading to the collapse of the commercial shipbuilding industry." Labor and raw materials are also more expensive at US shipyards than at comparable foreign shipyards.¹⁶ Higher costs of operation lead to a reduced demand for shipping services and vessel operators meaning, "Transportation expenses – incurred to move raw materials and intermediate goods to the next stage in the production...comprise a significant portion of the cost of goods...elevated transportation costs affect nearly every business in every industry."¹⁷ US crews are more expensive because of pay requirements, vessel and personnel insurance costs, and heightened regulatory requirements from the US Coast Guard. In 2010, a study by the Maritime Administration reported that operating a US Jones Act-compliant vessel was 2.7 times more expensive than a similar vessel from a foreign competitor. Daily costs for foreign ships averaged \$7,500, while the US vessel required more than \$20,000.¹⁸

Beyond operating expenses, national security goals also contribute to the cost of US vessels. Overreach of government regulation in shipbuilding due to national security concerns allowed the government to micromanage the design and execution of major shipbuilding programs. Ultimately, changes are costly and can cause significant production delays, meaning, "One distinguishing characteristic of this culture is a shared responsibility between shipyards and combat systems integrators...this requires extensive coordination in design and production, which results in significant overhead spread across all builders' contracts."¹⁹ Increased costs forced American companies to look outside the US to meet production needs.

¹³ Salisbury, Emma. (2025, January 27). *Don't Protect the U.S. Merchant Marine—Promote It*. War on the Rocks. <https://warontherocks.com/2025/01/dont-protect-the-u-s-merchant-marine-promote-it/>.

¹⁴ *Supra*, note 13.

¹⁵ *Ibid*.

¹⁶ Dur, R. A. P. A. (2025, February). *The high costs of doing (shipbuilding) business | proceedings - February 2025* vol. 151/2/1,464. U.S. Naval Institute. <https://www.usni.org/magazines/proceedings/2025/february/high-costs-doing-shipbuilding-business>.

¹⁷ Grabow, C., Manak, I., Ikenson, D. (2018, June 28). *The Jones Act: A Burden American Can No Longer Bear*. Cato Institute. <https://www.cato.org/publications/policy-analysis/jones-act-burden-america-can-no-longer-bear#introduction>.

¹⁸ *Supra*, note 17.

¹⁹ *Supra*, Note 16.

Cost of Retention. The US merchant mariner fleet is shrinking. Depletion of the US fleet created a major reduction in available licensed US mariners, thus weakening the US disaster or emergency response should a conflict arise.²⁰ Multiple leaders from the Maritime Administration and the Department of Defense have testified before Congress that a major institutional concern is a growing shortage of US mariners. An inadequate mariner force is both an economic and a national security risk, albeit an avoidable one. Lack of investment into recruiting akin to that for uniformed US services, combined with high barriers to entry and a lack of public recognition for service, have all contributed to a depletion of the mariner fleet, resulting in a loss of investment, talent, and expertise.²¹ When industries are not committed to domestic professionals, foreign actors are able to gain momentum.

Sal Mercogliano from Campbell University explained, “It is easy to write off the American merchant marine as too expensive and outdated due to the Jones Act. But the question needs to be asked: Is the United States prepared to outsource its coastwise trade and lose the majority of its remaining deep-draft merchant ships? Such a loss may provide short-term economic benefit, but the long-term danger and threat to national security may prove fatal. This was the concern echoed a hundred years ago, and it remains as pertinent today as it did then.”²² If this is the one-hundred-year concern for maritime shipping, then it is a concern that commercial space cannot ignore in its next one-hundred years.

3. AVOIDING POLICY PITFALLS IN COMMERCIAL SPACE

The similarities between the growing space industry and the maritime industry are too close to ignore. Both industries base their business models on moving objects between distant locations, so both must conduct their operations at a scale large enough to generate profit and function under complex regulatory schemes.²³ In the maritime realm and in outer space, sophisticated and complex vehicles are necessary to transport goods. Whether the goods are basic cargo like pharmaceuticals or advanced machinery parts for building a base on the moon, the vehicle to move those products is equally sophisticated. That level of engineering requires dedicated and talented personnel in construction and operation. It is understandable why the policymakers who enacted the Jones Act would want to protect American industry at all costs to promote the US development of these technologies. But the Jones Act took protectionism too far by creating a system that rejected globalization and unsustainably raised costs.

The major lessons the space industry must learn from the Jones Act include rejecting purely domestic operations in the United States by instead investing in building a robust, globally functional infrastructure, focusing on cost-effective domestic operations that allow US-based companies to remain profitable while operating in the United States, and investing early in education and incentivizing the retention of domestic experience and expertise.

3.1. Current Status of the Outer Space Commercial Goods Industry

Commercial space delivery networks are growing, with companies like SpaceX and Blue Origin leading the march toward affordable and reusable space freight. While technology is evolving, the US must begin to consider how it will regulate the emerging market.²⁴ Initial space cargo deliveries will likely focus on industrial, humanitarian, military, and medical needs. More robust commercial space efforts will likely

²⁰ *Supra*, Note 17.

²¹ gCaptain. (2024, September 22). *Op-ed: U.S. merchant mariner shortage demands action now*. <https://gcaptain.com/op-ed-u-s-merchant-mariner-shortage-demands-action-now/>.

²² *Supra*, note 6.

²³ *Commercial activities from the open ocean to Outer Space*. ESPI. (2018, May 23). <https://www.espi.eu/briefs/commercial-activities-from-the-open-ocean-to-outer-space/>.

²⁴ *Supra*, note 23.

center on “resource acquisition, energy production, and advanced manufacturing.”²⁵ In addition, the space mining market is predicted to be worth billions of dollars over the next decade.²⁶ Like the maritime industry, space operators will be required to transport goods that are critical for both commercial and national security purposes. Balancing the prioritization of a US-based launch vehicle with cost-effective regulatory allowances will encourage companies to maintain US-based systems that can serve a global customer.

3.2. Existing Legal Frameworks for Commercial Space Cargo

Regulators working on space issues must not allow the protectionist policies of the Jones Act to bleed into space policy. Ultimately, the federal regulation of space has been in development for decades. Key offices like the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) and the Department of Commerce address space regulatory concerns. The FAA Office of Commercial Space Transportation is the leading governmental framework in the US for space cargo, responsible for overseeing and regulating space transportation operations, including licensing for launch vehicles.²⁷

In 1984, Congress passed the Commercial Space Launch Act, creating regulations for licensure and launch activities.²⁸ This eventually evolved into the US Commercial Space Launch Competitiveness Act. Passed in 2015, the Act addresses issues impacting aerospace entrepreneurship and licensure.²⁹ Space activities are also guided by 51 USC Ch 509, the current US regulatory framework for Commercial Space Launch Activities.³⁰ Specifically, §50901 discusses issues like developing competitive US launch vehicles, investing in a strong domestic infrastructure, and encouraging private participation in space transportation services. The foundations are laid for a prosperous balance between aggressive growth in technological advancement and a strong regulatory framework. But §50919 outlines approvals and relationships between the US and other countries. While the language is not particularly protectionist yet, this is the section of the code that must be highlighted. The US should resist introducing language akin to that in the Jones Act to these relevant sections of space policy so that space players in the US are not stifled by stricter US requirements.

For inspiration, the US can look to policies being created in the European Union (EU). The European Space Policy Institute (ESPI) Executive Brief No. 23 independently calls for regulation of commercial space inspired by the maritime industry. The ESPI specifically makes the distinction between international and maritime space policy in that international relations today are more cooperative, while the demand for space resources is not yet as well-established. In section two of the ESPI, the EU highlights that actors at sea and in space, “Conduct their business activities around the commercialisation of resources/products” from distant locations, and “[c]onduct their business activities in locations outside the national jurisdiction of their countries of incorporation where the relevant international law and

²⁵ Mitchell, N. (2025, April 14). *Space commerce: Face the risk, seize the opportunities*. The Space Review: Space commerce: face the risk, seize the opportunities. <https://www.thespacereview.com/article/4968/1>.

²⁶ GetNews. (2026, January 12). *Space mining market to reach USD 7.39 billion by 2031, driven by rising demand for rare-earth metals and lunar resource extraction trends – Mordor Intelligence*. Barchart. <https://www.barchart.com/story/news/37009411/space-mining-market-to-reach-usd-7-39-billion-by-2031-driven-by-rising-demand-for-rare-earth-metals-and-lunar-resource-extraction-trends-mordor-intelligence>.

²⁷ *Ibid.*

²⁸ U.S. Congress. (1983). *H.R. 3942: Commercial Space Launch Act (98th Congress)*. <https://www.congress.gov/bill/98th-congress/house-bill/3942/text>.

²⁹ U.S. Congress. (2015). *H.R. 2262: U.S. Commercial Space Launch Competitiveness Act (114th Congress)*. <https://www.congress.gov/bill/114th-congress/house-bill/2262/text>.

³⁰ *Commercial space launch activities*, 51 U.S.C. §§ 50901–50923 (2023). <https://www.govinfo.gov/app/details/USCODE-2023-title51/USCODE-2023-title51-subtitleV-chap509/context>.

regulations are not yet highly defined.”³¹ Taking inspiration from ESPI can encourage future US policy to maintain a global perspective.

3.3. *Infrastructure Lessons for Outer Space*

US based infrastructure is rooted in national security concerns and a desire to protect the US shipbuilding industry. But the Jones Act requirement to insulate operations ultimately led to significantly higher costs. In policy reports from the White House, the administration noted that operational efficiency would increase and launch costs would decrease if the US invested in space launch infrastructure. To maintain leadership in the space sector, the US must “enable market access for United States industry,” as well as “encourage interoperability among United States, allied, and partner space systems, services, and data.”³²

Although there is no dedicated US space cargo port yet, it is important to set a precedent now that US cargo travelling between the US mainland on Earth and a future spaceport should be allowed to be carried by foreign-owned spacecraft. This opens US space infrastructure without the restrictions imposed on the maritime industry by the Jones Act. But for national and public safety purposes, these activities must be closely monitored. If the US fails to establish itself as a major spaceport now, it is likely that other countries in one-hundred years could out-produce the US in space logistics. Looking forward, the protection of critical systems and supporting infrastructure allows the US to maintain space security while avoiding the perils of protectionism.

3.4. *Cost Considerations for Space Growth*

The space industry is not immune to the push and pull of market supply and demand fluctuations. If the US wants to avoid the fate of its maritime industry, where US ships are being outpriced by foreign vessels, then the US must now prioritize cost considerations of its rocket transportation fleet. The US government’s stated goals include establishing operations “in accordance with typical market-based incentives for controlling cost and optimizing return on investment.”³³ The National Space Society reported that at some point, depending on the rate of movement into space, the “number of launches over a sustained period [must be] large enough to reduce the per-launch cost to financially practicable levels.”³⁴ Investment in fully reusable commercial cargo rockets will likely be critical for reducing the cost of moving goods into space.

For reference, NASA’s space shuttle cost about \$1.5 billion to launch 27,500 kg into Low Earth Orbit – a rate that translates to \$54,000/kg. SpaceX Falcon 9 advertised in 2020 that it cost \$62 million to launch 22,800 kg into the same orbit – a cost of \$2,720/kg.³⁵ And SpaceX is not the only company tackling this problem. Several successful startups have raised significant funding in their quest to develop a fully reusable rocket with a reasonable turnaround. Now the US needs to ensure that the creation of those vehicles remains cost-effective in comparison to alternative options in other countries.

3.5. *Talent Development and Retention*

In the National Space Policy, one of the named goals is to “Develop and Retain Space Professionals.”³⁶ But the US has struggled to achieve this goal in other industries like the maritime realm. The merchant marine played a critical role in every major US conflict since the world wars, despite the public remaining

³¹ *Supra* note 23.

³² *Supra* note 4.

³³ *Supra* note 4.

³⁴ *NSS Roadmap to Space Settlement Milestone 1: Dramatically lower launch costs to orbit*. NSS. (2021, May 14). <https://nss.org/space-settlement-roadmap-1-lower-launch-costs/>.

³⁵ *Ibid* cost-effective.

³⁶ *Supra* note 4.

unaware of mariners' contributions. Unfortunately, high barriers to entry and a lack of support for improvement in shipboard quality-of-life led to low enrollment and low retention of trained US mariners.

The space industry must pay attention to this trend. By investing in innovative commercial, civil, and national security programs, the US could establish its own pool of experienced and knowledgeable space professionals. As outlined in the US National Space Policy guidelines, the US must begin to promote and expand space careers, including investing in educational programs. The US must look beyond engineers and operators as future space operations will require geoscientists, cybersecurity experts, human-factors specialists, policy and regulatory interpreters, and more. Early and dedicated investment into both special knowledge of the space technical field and the impact on human interaction with those systems across disciplines will help the US to develop and retain its space professionals.

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the US space industry is at a critical point in its development. Technology is starting to take massive strides toward the intersection of operational feasibility and affordability. But the US has been a dominant player before in the transportation industry, and it lost its steam. US merchant shipping, once a pinnacle of international cargo transportation, became too exclusionary, too expensive, and overall, too unattractive to maintain a global lead.

By establishing the foundation of the Jones Act and exploring how its requirements had unintended negative consequences in the maritime industry, space policymakers can understand how the emerging commercial space transportation industry is analogous to the maritime realm in regard to the domestic construction and operation of vehicles. In addition to both industries moving goods from one location to another, both industries also rely heavily on sophisticated vehicles created by talented individuals. Space actors must recognize the importance of talent retention and infrastructure investment. By looking at existing space policy, policymakers can be cautioned against creating regulations that stray into the same pitfalls as the Jones Act.

While the space industry is now exciting and enticing, it is the longevity that will ultimately matter in the future. US regulations must adapt to evolution in space technology through a lens of protecting US operations while maintaining a competitive global advantage. If the US wants to be the leader for the next century in space cargo transportation, it must learn from the Jones Act. Active participation in international cooperation and early investment in efficient domestic infrastructure are critical for industry growth. More importantly, that growth must account for globalization and international participation from its inception. Perhaps the US space industry can avoid the same fate suffered by the maritime realm.

© The Author(s) 2026. Published by Space Court Foundation. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted reuse, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

BARRIERS AND GATEWAYS TO PRESERVING OUR PLACE IN THE COSMOS: THE LEGAL AND GEOPOLITICAL DIMENSIONS OF PROTECTING HERITAGE SITES IN OUTER SPACE

LEE P. FOLEY¹

ABSTRACT

The current debates over the protection of outer space heritage have been intense, fascinating, and, at times, a concerning exercise in futility for those committed to safeguarding the collective history of human space exploration. While the U.S.-led Artemis Accords have highlighted the importance of protecting cultural artefacts and sites in space, problems with the interpretation of key principles of the Outer Space Treaty, such as non-appropriation, jurisdiction, and due regard, an increasing commercial presence in space, and concerns about the application of safety zones complicate the present legal landscape. This article synthesises these issues and then proposes some steps towards an optimal governance system within the current nexus of international agreements and unpredictable geopolitical circumstances. Given these tensions, outer space heritage protection should be carried out under an international legal framework that bridges space law and space archaeology principles. The article suggests a two-tiered approach to space heritage governance. First, in the long-term, a framework inspired by elements of the World Heritage Convention could provide specialised classification, identification, and protection systems considering the different types of heritage and their universal value. Second, in the short-term (because establishing such a complex legal instrument will undoubtedly be slow), and separate from the geopolitical exigencies that underpin the Artemis Accords and its rival initiative, China's International Lunar Research Station Agreement, a series of heritage-specific bi-and-multilateral agreements between the nations with objects on celestial bodies would foster targeted international cooperation. Ultimately, it is up to individual nations to show political leadership and provide a sustained commitment to safeguard humanity's collective place in the cosmos. Failure to do so will leave a troubling legacy for future generations.

KEYWORDS: Archaeology, Geopolitics, Governance, Heritage, Space Law.

¹ L. P. Foley, School of Humanities, University of Southampton, Southampton, (UK), Lpf1n25@soton.ac.uk

1. INTRODUCTION

Late at night on 13 September 1959, the Soviet rocket engineer, Sergei Korolev, listened in alongside mission control to the radio signals being transmitted from the *Luna 2* spacecraft. Shortly after midnight on the 14th, the signals ceased – the spacecraft had struck the Moon.² While less celebrated than *Sputnik 1* (the first artificial satellite to orbit the Earth), *Luna 2* still had history-defining implications. Upon impact, it became the first human-made object on a celestial body and, at the same time, the first extraterrestrial heritage site. Similar feats defined the following decade (commonly recognised as the space race), spurring rapid technological development – from massive launch vehicles to compact landers – and culminating in the first human steps on the lunar surface in 1969.³ Since then, numerous missions have left traces of humanity throughout the solar system, and even out into interstellar space.

Preserving humanity’s material legacy beyond Earth reveals a paradox in international space law: while the technical and fiscal hurdles for protecting heritage sites are minimal, the legal barriers are profound. Space archaeologists have mapped heritage sites, marking significant milestones in humanity’s space exploration history, while international interdisciplinary workshops have offered thoughtful recommendations on how to protect them. However, existing space treaties provide only general ground rules, not detailed regulations for managing space activities.⁴ That ambiguity exists in determining who can safeguard heritage sites and how is, therefore, not surprising.

This article examines the evolving tension between core principles of the *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, Including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Outer Space Treaty [OST]) and the growing need to recognise and protect heritage sites in outer space.⁵ These themes prompt broader debates regarding the shared value of outer space heritage, the (geo)political difficulties involved in reaching agreement on what should qualify as heritage, and the challenge of ensuring the long-term stewardship of these locations, especially in light of the increasing ambitions of contemporary space-faring nations.⁶

To assess whether the current legal framework can tackle the complexities of heritage protection, this article deploys a doctrinal legal analysis, drawing on international treaties, recent policy developments, and comparative examples of terrestrial heritage governance. Part One discusses the state of the field and the definitional issues which often bedevil space law. Part Two investigates the extant international legal framework, probing the legality of heritage protection and ties to appropriation, jurisdiction, and due regard. Part Three explores suggestions for safeguarding heritage, considering whether they upend the legal order or pave the way for robust heritage governance in space.

² Harford, J. (1997). *Korolev: How One Man Masterminded the Soviet Drive to Beat America to the Moon*. John Wiley & Sons, 142.

³ Launius, R. D. (2018). *The History of Human Space Exploration: Discoveries from the Ancient World to the Extraterrestrial Future*. Thames & Hudson, 148-9.

⁴ Hanlon M. L. D. (2021). ‘Due Regard’ for Commercial Space Must Start with Historic Preservation. *Global Business Law Review*, 9, 130-56, 132. <https://engagedscholarship.csuohio.edu/gblr/vol9/iss1/6/>.

⁵ United Nations (UN hereafter). (1967). *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, Including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Outer Space Treaty [OST] hereafter). <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/introouterspacetreaty.html>.

⁶ Returning humans to the lunar surface, building a Moon base, and utilising natural resources, with a view to future colonies on Mars are just some of the intentions of the United States Government and US-based private companies in space in the coming decades. Other nations and companies have their own plans for an increased presence on celestial bodies in the future. See, Baber, W. W. and Ojala, A. (2024). New Space Era: Characteristics of the New Space Industry Landscape. In W. W. Baber and A. Ojala (Eds.). *Space Business: Emerging Theory and Practice*. Springer, 3. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-981-97-3430-6_1.

Moreover, most heritage discourse focuses on the Moon, given that it is the most explored celestial body in the solar system (excluding Earth, of course). However, as humanity ventures deeper into the cosmos, it is necessary to expand the conceptual framework to all other areas of space that contain evidence of human activity. This article will also consider some of the challenges surrounding the potential protection of areas of celestial bodies hitherto unexplored by humans but considered scientifically important.

Ultimately, this article argues that outer space heritage protection will falter without international political will. It will not strangle State coffers, disrupt future missions, or involve specialised new technologies. Rather, it will require a specialised instrument inspired by the World Heritage Convention but tailored to the unique environment of outer space.

2. UNDERSTANDING SPACE ARCHAEOLOGY AND HERITAGE

2.1. Literature Review

Although humans have launched objects into space since the 1950s, archaeological inquiry into spaceflight artefacts emerged much later. It developed in the 1990s as an outgrowth of investigations of ship and aircraft wrecks before developing its own referent: space archaeology.⁷ By the 2000s, however, space heritage drew scant attention, in part due to infrequent space missions, but more significantly because spaceflight had slipped out of the broader public consciousness. Scholars observed a general apathy in both public and academic spheres: “the Moon is deemed too far away, both physically and mentally – and so much out of the reach of people – that it is not worth bothering about”.⁸

The rise of private space companies in the twenty-first century, with diverse ambitions, including resource utilisation, tourism, and planetary colonisation, marked a turning point, re-injecting space into the public discourse and sparking studies on the risks posed to existing heritage sites from future activities.⁹ Space archaeology was understood to be “the study of the material culture associated with space exploration”, including “space systems, spacecraft and space debris located throughout the solar system and the landing sites of robotic and crewed missions” on celestial bodies.¹⁰ The field swiftly diversified with scholars approaching heritage from various perspectives.¹¹

While early studies stressed the importance of safeguarding the cultural landscape of space, it was not until the 2010s that the OST’s legal ambiguities were recognised as barriers to heritage protection. Legal concerns soon permeated archaeological studies, while space lawyers published specialised papers on

⁷ In his 1999 article, W. Rathje termed the study of extraterrestrial artefacts and sites “exoarchaeology”, but this failed to proliferate in the wider scholarship, with the name “space archaeology” gaining popularity instead. Rathje, W. (1999) An Archaeology of Space Garbage. *Discovering Archaeology*, 108–122. For more on the conceptual leap from ship and aircraft wrecks to outer space landing sites see, Finney, B. R. (1992). *From sea to space*. University Press of Hawaii.

⁸ Spennemann D. H. R. (2006). Out of this World: Issues of Managing Tourism and Humanity’s Heritage on the Moon. *International Journal of Heritage Studies*, 12 (4), 356-371, 357 <https://doi.org/10.1080/13527250600726911>

⁹ Rogers, T. F. (2004). Safeguarding Tranquillity Base: Why the Earth’s Moon Base Should Become a World Heritage Site. *Space Policy*, 20, 5-6 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2003.11.001>; Spennemann, D. H. R. (2004). The Ethics of Treading on Neil Armstrong’s Footprints. *Space Policy*, 20 (4), 279-290. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2004.08.005>.

¹⁰ Gorman, A. C. (2014). Space Archaeology. In Clare Smith (Ed.). *Encyclopedia of Global Archaeology*. Springer, 6493.

¹¹ Darrin, A. and O’Leary, B. (Eds.). (2009). *Handbook of Space Engineering, Archaeology and Heritage*. CRC Press. This handbook was one of the first comprehensive volumes to integrate perspectives from scientists, engineers, geologists, archaeologists, anthropologists, and historians.

heritage issues.¹² Today, a burgeoning sociolegal-archaeological discourse advocates preservation propelled by scholars such as Alice Gorman and Dick Spennemann.¹³ Yet international space law still lacks provisions for heritage, with numerous significant obstacles remaining, and viable solutions seemingly far off.

2.2. Defining Outer Space Heritage

This article understands heritage as a “process of meaning-making”, shaped by social interaction and defined by the value people assign to it. At first glance, this challenges traditional binary concepts of tangible and intangible, and natural and cultural heritage, which José Antonio González Zarandona argues “are largely incompatible with non-Western worldviews”.¹⁴ But accepting that heritage has no inherent value does not mean that we should do away with traditional binary categorisation along those lines for outer space. This stems from the reality that, despite the varied social, cultural, and geographical backgrounds of humanity, such distinctions ultimately dissolve when considering our shared achievements in space. Heritage sites on celestial bodies, though established by specific States, symbolise the collective endeavours of humankind as a whole and warrant international protection.

But a preliminary legal issue is that attempts at defining ‘heritage’ in outer space highlight a major gap in international space law: none of the five UN space treaties addresses it directly. The only indirect reference is found in the 1979 *Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies*’ (Moon Agreement’s) concern for “areas of the Moon having special scientific interest” and that, “consideration may be given to the designation of such areas as international scientific preserves for which special protective arrangements are to be agreed upon”.¹⁵ The symbolic declaration of the Moon as the “common heritage of mankind” has been largely rhetorical, given that the treaty has been condemned by the leading space powers to the “garbage of history” and is only ratified by seventeen States.¹⁶

As a result, defining heritage has fallen to non-state actors rather than diplomats. The U.S. nongovernmental organisation (NGO) For All Moonkind (FAM) – now a permanent observer at the UN Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (UNCOPUOS) – defines outer space heritage as “traces of human existence, together with their archaeological and natural contexts that occur in outer space, including on the Moon and other celestial bodies” that contain “significant cultural, historical,

¹² Walsh, J. S. P. (2012). Protection of Humanity’s Cultural and Historic Heritage in Space. *Space Policy*, 28 (4), 234-243. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2012.04.001>; Reynolds, J. (2015). Legal Implications of Protecting Historic Sites in Space. In B. L. O’Leary and P. J. Capelotti (Eds.). *Archaeology and Heritage of the Human Movement into Space*. Springer, 111-129.

¹³ Gorman, Alice C. (2024). Launching Archaeology into Space and What it Tells us about Life on Earth. *Australian Archaeology*, 90, 39-41. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03122417.2024.2317532>; Gorman, A. C. (2019). *Dr Space Junk VS the Universe: Archaeology and the Future*. MIT Press; Spennemann D. H. R. and Murphy G. (2020). Returning to the Moon: Heritage Issues Raised by the Google Lunar X Prize. *Institute for Land Water and Society*, 1-36; Su, J. and Li, J. (2025). Toward an International Legal Framework for the Protection of Outer Space Heritage. *Space Policy* 71, 1-12, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2024.101625>.

¹⁴ Zarandona J. A. G., E. Cunliffe, and M. Saldin. (2024). A Path Well Worn? Approaches for the Old Problem of Heritage Destruction. in J. A. G. Zarandona, E. Cunliffe, and M. Saldin (Eds.). *The Routledge Handbook of Heritage Destruction*. Routledge, 3-4. For more on the definitional debates around heritage, see Bryne, D. (2008). Heritage as social action. In G. Fairclough, R. Harrison, J. Jameson, & J. Schofield (Eds.), *The Heritage Reader*, Routledge; Smith, L. (2006). *Uses of Heritage*. Routledge.

¹⁵ UN (1979). *Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies*. (Moon Agreement) Art. 7 (3). <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/moon-agreement.html>.

¹⁶ Tronchetti, F. (2024). Moon Agreement: Key Provisions in S. Bhat B., D. Ukey, and A. Variath (Eds.). *International Space Law in the New Space Era: Principles and Challenges*. Oxford University Press, 174.

archaeological, or other scientific character”.¹⁷ This bridges archaeology and law, and their advocacy has recently contributed to the World Monuments Fund’s decision to add the Moon to its endangered heritage sites list.¹⁸ But since both are NGO’s, these moves, although influential for public discourse, do not directly impact UN law-making.

Still, FAM’s definition establishes two key criteria for heritage status. First: contributions to humanity’s evolutionary and cosmic histories. Hundreds of lunar sites alone reflect human ingenuity and culture – affirming humans as “natural wanderers” whose exploratory drive is “deeply embedded in our evolutionary past”.¹⁹ They also embody symbolism, memorial, and shared meaning, as seen when the crew of *Apollo 11* placed on the lunar surface a golden olive branch as a symbol of peace, as well as a silicon disc featuring goodwill messages from the leaders of seventy-three nations from Earth (*Figure 1*).²⁰ Moreover, the *Apollo 15* astronauts added a commemorative plaque and Fallen Astronaut statue honouring the then fourteen space-farers who had perished during spaceflight activities (*Figure 2*).²¹ As Michelle Hanlon notes, these artefacts provide a “treasure trove of insight into human culture, ingenuity, [and] evolution”.²²

¹⁷ For All Moonkind (FAM hereafter) (n.d.) Definition of Heritage in Outer Space. <https://www.forallmoonkind.org/about/definition-of-heritage/>.

¹⁸ Kuta, S. (2025, January 15). The Moon Makes the List of the World’s Most Endangered Cultural Heritage Sites in 2025. Smithsonian Magazine. <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/smart-news/the-moon-makes-the-list-of-the-worlds-most-endangered-cultural-heritage-sites-in-2025-180985845/>.

¹⁹ Finney, B. R. and Jones, E. M. (1985). The Exploring Animal in B. R. Finney and E. M. Jones (Eds.). *Interstellar Migration and the Human Experience*. University of California Press, 15.

²⁰ Pearlman, R. Z. (2007, 16 November). The Untold Story: How One Small Disc Carried One Giant Message for Mankind. *Space.com*. <https://www.space.com/4655-untold-story-small-disc-carried-giant-message-mankind.html>.

²¹ Scott, D. R. (2021). Memorandum for the Record. National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) <https://www.nasa.gov/wp-content/uploads/static/history/alsj/a15/drsmemo20210903.pdf>.

²² Hanlon *supra* note 4 at 140.

Yet not all sites merit such status: two-hundred tons of accumulated material on the lunar surface alone, ranging from spent rocket stages to golf balls and tools, to even human organic waste, demands demarcation between culture-revealing artefacts and detritus.²³ FAM has attempted to calibrate protection levels, emphasising that characteristics of space heritage should include “a first achievement of its kind”, and “significant impact(s) on human space exploration”.²⁴ One might infer from this that a hierarchy of significance should exist to determine the degree of protection warranted for each heritage artefact or site.

The second consideration is final location. FAM highlights “symbolic markers in an extraterrestrial context that originate from and express human identity”.²⁵ While space objects testify to human ingenuity anywhere, their peak value is only brought into focus given their final location on a celestial body. Consider *Apollo 11*’s Tranquillity Base: Although it would retain a great deal of significance if it was returned to Earth, “it is its presence on the Moon that grants it unparalleled importance as an evolutionary milestone”.²⁶ This is true because any such removal would detach the artefact from its extraterrestrial context, and as a consequence, damage its historical value.

The importance of *in situ* preservation is further highlighted by the practical impossibility of removing perhaps the most significant heritage site in the solar system – the first human footprints on the Moon. For even if we wanted to, it is currently impossible to bring those footprints back without destroying them. More significantly, given that the Moon has no atmosphere, no known biological activity, limited geological activity, and generally stable temperatures, the artefacts and sites there, including the Apollo footprints, are “almost perfectly preserved”.²⁷ This is not quite the same elsewhere in the solar system, such as Mars, with diverse atmospheric and geological environments posing a risk to heritage sites and complicating preservation discourse.²⁸

²³ Gorman, A. C. (2016). Culture on the Moon: Bodies in Time and Space. *Journal of the World Archaeological Congress*, 12 (1), 110-28, 110.

²⁴ FAM *supra* note 17.

²⁵ *Ibid.*

²⁶ Siebrits, A. (2020). The Moon that Owns Itself: Exploring New Legal Avenues to Protect Cultural and Natural Heritage in Space. In A. Froehlich (Ed) *Protection of Cultural Heritage Sites on the Moon*. Springer, 124.

²⁷ Reynolds *supra* note 12, at 112.

²⁸ Rotola, G. (2020). The Legal Framework Protecting Cultural Heritage Sites on the Moon and In Situ Preservation. In A. Froehlich (Ed.). *Protection of Cultural Heritage Sites on the Moon*. Springer, 4.

Taken together, however, these twin pillars – contribution to humanity’s evolutionary and cosmic histories and final location – anchor outer space heritage protection. Although it is not codified into international law, in the absence of any such specialised international legal mechanism, FAM’s working definition is a necessary first step towards framing a governance system. The next step is to consider the core UN treaties and the challenges posed by the principles of non-appropriation, jurisdiction, and due regard to heritage protection in space.

3. INTERNATIONAL SPACE LAW

The OST and its supplementary treaties establish a skeleton of space law through broad rules and principles, placing emphasis on States to build upon them through national legislation and internationally through bilateral and multilateral agreements.²⁹ This national emphasis is heightened by the diversification of space technologies, participants, and mission architectures since the UN treaties were drafted. Consequently, there are often interpretive differences between nations and an overarching lack of clarity regarding how States can legally manoeuvre in outer space.

When trying to establish the legal position of any space activity, Article I of the OST is the first port of call. It stipulates that “outer space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies, shall be free for exploration and use by all States without discrimination of any kind” and that “there shall be freedom of scientific investigation” in space.³⁰ Moreover, these broad activities – exploration, use, and scientific investigation – “shall be the province of all mankind”.³¹ Stephan Hobe notes that Article I “grants certain freedoms relating to these activities”, but then the following articles “limit these freedoms” to ensure that exploration, use, and scientific investigation in outer space remain unrestricted.³² Consequently, this balancing act produces treaty-wide inconsistencies and heritage-specific complexities.

3.1. *The Non-appropriation Principle and the Paradox of Protection*

Article II of the OST establishes one of the most fundamental rules of space law: “Outer space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies, is not subject to national appropriation by claim of sovereignty, by means of use or occupation, or by any other means”.³³ This was designed to prevent States from claiming territorial sovereignty beyond Earth, thus preserving free access to space.³⁴ Yet, the very act of protecting heritage sites in space contravenes that principle as safeguarding these locations inevitably requires restricting others' access to them.

To safeguard a site, States will need to impose restrictions or establish exclusion zones – actions that, in practice, amount to exercising spatial control over an area of a celestial body. This produces something of a paradox: the protection of a heritage site requires interventions that appear to mimic appropriation. As a result, a tension has emerged around how to protect heritage sites without violating Article II.³⁵

Recent U.S. efforts have encapsulated this tension. In 2011, the National Aeronautics and Space Administration’s (NASA’s) “Recommendations to Space-Faring Entities: How to Protect and Preserve the

²⁹ von der Dunk, F. G. (2020). Scoping National Space Law: The True Meaning of ‘National Activities in Outer Space’ of Article VI of the Outer Space Treaty. In P. J. Blount, T. Masson-Zwaan, R. Moro-Aguilar, and K. Schrogl (Eds.). *Proceedings of the International Institute of Space Law 2019*. Eleven Publishing International, 229.

³⁰ OST *supra* note 5 at Art. I.

³¹ *Ibid.*

³² Hobe, S. (2009). Article I. In S. Hobe, B. Schmidt-Tedd, and K. Schrogl (Eds.). *Cologne Commentary on Space Law: Volume 1: Outer Space Treaty*. Carl Heymanns Verlag, 27.

³³ OST *supra* note 5 at Art. II.

³⁴ Dolman, E. C. (2001). *Astropolitik: Classical Geopolitics in the Space Age*. Frank Cass, 8.

³⁵ Hanlon *supra* note 4 at 143-4.

Historic and Scientific Value of U.S. Government Lunar Artefacts” (NASA’s Recommendations) outlined technical guidelines for preserving the historical integrity of the Apollo landing sites. This guidance included forming exclusion boundaries of up to 2.0-kilometres, no-contact rules, and mobility restrictions. NASA’s rationale for such measures was driven by concerns from future spacecraft kicking up lunar regolith (sandblasting) to collision risks and biological contamination. However, since the recommendations were primarily focused on technical guidance, they ignored the legal ramifications of their protocols.³⁶

As the U.S. Government attempted to place NASA’s Recommendations on a legal footing, the 2020 “One Small Step to Protect Human Heritage in Space Act” instructed NASA and other relevant Federal agencies to make compliance with the recommendations a prerequisite of future cooperation with the agency in lunar activities.³⁷ The Act raised concerns about the impact that the growth of commercial space actors and the increasing number of countries acquiring the ability to land on the lunar surface might have on existing U.S. sites. Its overarching aim was to “limit harmful interference to the Apollo landing site artefacts”.³⁸ Yet both instruments exemplify unilateral action: they bind only those voluntarily working with NASA and therefore cannot create legal obligations for other States.³⁹ And, while these instruments received bipartisan support in Washington, international critics have argued that even well-intentioned restrictions could amount to “*de facto appropriation*”, since they limit the free access guaranteed under Article I.⁴⁰

The U.S.-led Artemis Accords, while not a legally binding treaty, attempted to ease this concern by including a specific provision for protecting “historically significant” space heritage “in accordance with mutually developed standards and practices”.⁴¹ Section 11 of the Accords promotes the idea of safety zones as areas wherein “notification and coordination will be implemented to avoid harmful interference”.⁴² Safety zones can be understood as “keep out areas” to protect security or other relevant interests. Some commentators have suggested that these safety zones, generally associated with large-scale space activities such as resource extraction, could work for heritage.⁴³ However, these zones are temporary, “ending when the relevant operation ceases”, whereas heritage sites require permanent protection.⁴⁴ As such, the Artemis Accords reproduce the paradox rather than resolve it: they endorse the need for protection, but their temporary safety zones are ill-suited to the indefinite protection required for heritage sites. Thus, the framework for safety zones for space heritage needs to be independently configured.

³⁶ NASA (2011). *NASA’s Recommendations to Space-Faring Entities: How to Protect and Preserve the Historic and Scientific Value of U.S. Government Lunar Artifacts* (NASA’s Recommendations hereafter) https://www.nasa.gov/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/617743main_nasa-usg_lunar_historic_sites_reva-508.pdf.

³⁷ U.S. Congress. (2020). *One Small Step to Protect Human Heritage in Space Act*. Public Law 116-275, 134 STAT. 3358. Section 3 (a) <https://www.congress.gov/116/plaws/publ275/PLAW-116publ275.pdf>

³⁸ Ibid, Section 2 (12) (b) (1).

³⁹ Su and Li *supra* note 13 at 1.

⁴⁰ Persoz, G. (2020). One Small Step to Protect Human Heritage in Space Act as One Small Step Towards U.S. Dominance? The Case for a Multilateral Treaty Protection Regime. In A. Froehlich (Ed.). *Protection of Cultural Heritage Sites on the Moon*. Springer, 48-9.

⁴¹ NASA, (2020). *The Artemis Accords: Principles for Cooperation in the Civil Exploration and Use of the Moon, Mars, Comets, and Asteroids for Peaceful Purposes* (Artemis Accords hereafter) Section 9 (1). <https://www.nasa.gov/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/Artemis-Accords-signed-13Oct2020.pdf>

⁴² Ibid, Section 11 (7).

⁴³ Gilbert, A. Q. (2023). Implementing Safety Zones for Lunar Activities under the Artemis Accords. *Journal of Space Safety Engineering*, 10 (1), 103-111, 104 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsse.2022.12.007>; Stubbs, M. (2021). The Legality of Keep-out, Operational, and Safety Zones in Outer Space. In C. Steer and M. Hersch (Eds.). *War and Peace in Outer Space: Law, Policy, and Ethics*. Oxford University Press.

⁴⁴ NASA, *supra* note 41 at Section 11 (7) (c).

Safety zones may well be the way of the future, but until an international framework allows protection that does not equate to appropriation, heritage governance in outer space will remain legally ambiguous. The non-appropriation principle forbids sovereignty, but heritage protection requires stewardship. In the long-term, bridging this gap is a pivotal legal challenge.

3.2. Ownership and Jurisdiction without Territory

If the non-appropriation principle defines what States cannot claim in outer space, Article VIII of the OST delineates what they do retain: “jurisdiction and control” over their registered space objects. This means that ownership rights of space objects are “not affected by their presence in outer space or on a celestial body”. At face value, this provision empowers heritage protection: a launching State can enforce safeguards over its craft, landers, or rovers. However, when those objects come to rest on a celestial body, a profound legal tension arises – States retain ownership and jurisdiction over them, but the areas upon which they rest are beyond national ownership and cannot be subjected to appropriation of any kind.⁴⁵

A further issue is that while jurisdiction and control focus on space objects, the legal status of intangible heritage, such as footprints and rover tracks, is unknown. In fact, these areas do not enjoy any protection in international space law whatsoever.⁴⁶

Private ownership complicates this landscape further. Russia’s 1993 sale of its *Lunokhod 2* lunar rover and its *Luna 21* Spacecraft to the American entrepreneur Richard Garriott showed that ownership of a space object can be transferred even when it sits on a celestial body.⁴⁷ Under Articles VI and VII of the OST, however, the State of registry continues to bear international responsibility and liability for those objects, and this also includes preservation.⁴⁸ Garriott, as a private owner, might appeal for conservation, but, in this case, enforcement falls to the Russian State. As commercial space activity proliferates, such problematic dualities between ownership and responsibility will only increase.

There is a terrestrial analogue for heritage protection in areas beyond national jurisdiction (ABNJ) – the Antarctic Treaty System (ATS). The 1959 Antarctic Treaty mirrors the OST’s ethos of a non-jurisdictional space, yet the 1991 *Protocol on Environmental Protection to the Antarctic Treaty* (Madrid Protocol) operationalises multilateral heritage safeguards.⁴⁹ Like outer space, Antarctica is a *res communis*, yet the Madrid Protocol enables the designation of “Historic Sites and Monuments (HSM’s)” to be preserved collectively, regardless of the nationality of the expedition that created them.⁵⁰

However, a key challenge of the ATS remains the slow pace of designating new HSM’s, alongside tensions between scientific activity, preservation, and legislating. For instance, despite being adopted in 2005, Annex VI to the Protocol on Environmental Protection to the Antarctic Treaty (Liability Annex) for addressing environmental emergencies is still not operational.⁵¹ The ATS’s slow pace has drawn concern over its adaptability to Antarctic tourism and offers a cautionary lesson for space heritage governance.

⁴⁵ OST *supra* note 5 at Art. VIII.

⁴⁶ Spennemann *supra* note 9 at 286.

⁴⁷ David, L. (2010, 22 March). Privately Owned Soviet Moon Rover Sparks Space Law Talks. *Space.com*. <https://www.space.com/8073-privately-owned-soviet-moon-rover-sparks-space-law-talks.html>.

⁴⁸ Hanlon *supra* note 4 at 145.

⁴⁹ UN. (1959). *The Antarctic Treaty*. <https://treaties.un.org/doc/Publication/UNTS/volume%20402/volume-402-I-5778-English.pdf>.

⁵⁰ UN. (1991). *Protocol on Environmental Protection to the Antarctic Treaty* (Madrid Protocol). <https://treaties.un.org/doc/Publication/UNTS/Volume%202941/volume-2941-A-5778.pdf>.

⁵¹ Madani, Z. (2025). Unpacking Inclusivity of the Antarctic Treaty System amidst Contemporary Challenges. *Polar Science*, 43, 1-11, 9 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polar.2024.101144>.

Considering the gradual expansion of general outer space activities year upon year, any analogous system must operate far more swiftly.⁵²

Without a cooperative mechanism for space heritage, its governance will remain obscure. While states may own the artefacts they have left behind, they do not control the surrounding areas. As in Antarctica, effective stewardship hinges on nations' ability to safeguard heritage for all humanity: a) without asserting ownership and b) speedily.

3.3. *Interpreting Due Regard*

Article IX of the OST requires States to conduct their space activities “with due regard to the corresponding interests of all other State Parties” while avoiding “potentially harmful interference” with another State’s activities.⁵³ However, the contours of due regard are undefined in the treaty, nor are they comfortably understood by the international community. Thus, there exists much debate around the application of due regard in space. For operational space objects, due regard means keeping an appropriate distance to avert direct or indirect interference.⁵⁴ Non-operational heritage objects warrant a similar wide berth. At present, there is enough room on celestial bodies for States to give a very wide berth to other space objects. But this is not a long-term luxury: U.S. and Chinese ongoing lunar programmes plan numerous landing sites on the lunar south pole over the next decade, sparking congestion and coordination concerns.⁵⁵ With some of those future landings likely qualifying as human heritage, it is necessary to establish a system to prevent any harm, accidental or otherwise, from occurring.

Conversely, it has been suggested that non-operational objects cannot be harmed and could be returned to Earth.⁵⁶ Although it may be possible to retrieve smaller objects, as previously discussed, the cultural significance of heritage artefacts is tied to their final location. Removing them, in the context of preserving the cosmic element of humanity’s evolutionary history, constitutes cultural and/or ethical damage. Additionally, this argument is irrelevant to the first footprints or rover tracks, as these cannot be moved. While debris removal is an important part of the move toward a sustainable future in space, this cannot occur before a thorough heritage classification system is implemented to differentiate between heritage and detritus. Also, it may well be within the purview of a future framework to clarify the contours of due regard for space heritage.

This is because, despite the temptation to turn to Earthbound analogues such as the *UN Convention on the Law of the Sea* (UNCLOS) for interpretive guidance on the meaning of due regard, this does not provide the clarity needed for the outer space context. UNCLOS stipulates that freedom of the high seas “shall be exercised by all States with due regard for the interests of other States in their exercise of the freedom of the high seas”.⁵⁷ Unlike the OST, the UNCLOS has been litigated before an international tribunal: in the case of the Chagos Marine Protected Area arbitration (*Mauritius v. United Kingdom*) in 2015. The tribunal declined to find “any universal rule of conduct” and that the convention “does not impose a uniform obligation to avoid any impairment of Mauritius’ rights; nor does it uniformly permit the United

⁵² Barr, S. (2021). How We Talk About Antarctic Cultural Heritage. *Antarctic Affairs*, 8, 33-52, 44 <https://antarcticaffairs.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/03-DIC-2021-AA-ENG-3.pdf>.

⁵³ OST *supra* note 5 at Art. IX.

⁵⁴ Hanlon *supra* note 4 at 144.

⁵⁵ Feng, Y., Pengshuo, L., Haoteng, L., Liu Y., Mengrong, X., Wang, R., Chen, S., Tang, P., Cao, Y., Huang, Q., You, Q., Liu, S., Ye, Z., Yusheng, X., Xu, X., Wang, C., Jin, Y., Liu, S., Xie, H., . . . Tong, X. (in press). Navigating the Lunar Frontier: One Hundred Landing Sites at the South Pole for Future Mission Challenges. *Science Bulletin*, 2 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scib.2025.08.035>.

⁵⁶ Hanlon *supra* note 4 at 146.

⁵⁷ UN. (1982). *Convention on the Law of the Sea*. Art. 87 (2) https://www.un.org/depts/los/convention_agreements/texts/unclos/unclos_e.pdf.

Kingdom to proceed as it wishes”. Instead, “the extent of the [due regard] required” depends upon “the nature of the rights held ... their importance, the extent of the anticipated impairment, the nature and importance of the activities contemplated” and “the availability of alternative approaches”.⁵⁸

The main takeaway from this interpretation is that due regard requires a balancing act. And, inevitably, as Hanlon notes, this will produce results “on a case-by-case basis”.⁵⁹ For the outer space context, this is no good. Although there may be differences between the level of protection afforded to certain heritage locations, and, in turn, this may well influence the characteristics of due regard for such sites, given the longstanding difficulty of interpreting the OST, a clearer and more consistent understanding of due regard is required as part of a future governance system for heritage protection.

4. DUAL-TRACK GOVERNANCE FOR SPACE HERITAGE

This section explores pathways towards a governance framework for space heritage protection – one that reconciles the OST's inherent contradictions with prevailing geopolitical tensions. The optimal way to do this is through a dual-track strategy: a dedicated space heritage convention in the long term, complemented in the short-to-medium term by heritage-specific state-led agreements, which can be enacted more swiftly because the UN's law-making processes are “convoluted and slow”.⁶⁰

4.1. Long-term Governance: A Space Heritage Convention?

Designing a governance regime for outer space heritage requires balancing the universal value of heritage and the non-sovereign character of the space environment. The optimal way to preserve outer space heritage sites over the long term would be to create an international convention in the spirit of the *Convention Concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage* (World Heritage Convention [WHC]): the WHC ensures the “identification, protection, conservation, presentation and transmission to future generations of the cultural and natural heritage” on Earth.⁶¹ However, most terrestrial heritage sites reside within national territories, so their mechanisms do not map onto outer space.

The first step in this framework is establishing a legal definition of outer space heritage. As established, FAM's definition of cultural heritage provides a strong foundation. However, their definition notably omits the distinction between cultural and natural heritage.

For natural heritage, it is necessary to protect the “unique and interesting geological features” on celestial bodies which accrue significant scientific and historical value.⁶² For example, robotic missions to Mars have discovered potential evidence of past habitability, which, in turn, has led to calls to recognise areas of “outstanding universal geoheritage” on the Red Planet.⁶³ This “exogeoconservation” advocates for the creation of safeguards to protect areas like the Gale Crater (a giant Martian crater thought to have once been a freshwater lake).⁶⁴

⁵⁸ Mauritius v. United Kingdom (2015) 2011-03, para 519.

⁵⁹ Hanlon *supra* note 4 at 147.

⁶⁰ Farsaris, A. E., (2020). How to Preserve Humanity's Lunar Heritage. In A. Froehlich (Ed.). *Protection of Cultural Heritage Sites on the Moon*. Springer, 82.

⁶¹ UNESCO. (1972). *Convention Concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage* (World Heritage Convention), Preamble <https://whc.unesco.org/en/conventiontext/>

⁶² Fletcher, C., van Kranendonk, M., and Oliver, C. (2024) Exogeoconservation of Mars. *Space Policy*, 68, 1-11, 2 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2024.101627>

⁶³ Ibid.

⁶⁴ Evans, B. (2025, 12 September). If Life did Ever Exist on Mars, these Five Regions are our Best Bet of Finding Proof. *BBC Sky at Night Magazine* <https://www.skyatnightmagazine.com/space-science/where-find-evidence-of-life-on-mars>

Protecting these scientifically and historically valuable areas is important because as humanity expands into space, it is necessary to further scientific and educational insights into the evolution of the solar system. If such areas are not protected from potentially disruptive activities, such as resource extraction or the creation of permanent habitats, that would indefinitely alter those landscapes, then an important aspect of the solar system's natural history could be damaged.

This inevitably brings heritage into confrontation with current space plans. Although this article is not suggesting that the extraction of natural resources from celestial bodies or the creation of human bases should be prohibited, there should be areas of celestial bodies, and not just those hosting evidence of past human activity, where such activities are restricted. These spatial restrictions could take practical guidance, or at least inspiration, from ecological zoning for habitat protection on Earth. Ecological zoning works by sorting valuable spaces into protection zones wherein certain land-use restrictions and industrial controls are imposed on activities that may degrade habitats.⁶⁵ Such zones are not just mere planning exercises. Rather, they are policy instruments whose effectiveness depends on the strength of the supporting mechanisms, the will of governments, socio-economic conditions, and continuous monitoring and adjustment.⁶⁶ A space heritage convention must be receptive to the natural environment of outer space, commercial interests, and be carefully monitored by governments to keep pace with technological advances that may challenge existing protection methods.

This is to avoid falling into the same trap as the Moon Agreement with regard to future human activities in space. Indeed, in an attempt to regulate the potential exploitation of lunar resources, Article 11 declared the Moon as “the common heritage of mankind”.⁶⁷ The central issue with this provision is that it modified the traditional regime applicable to ABNJ. Traditionally, these areas, while open to free exploration and use by all States, cannot be appropriated. But when an area is labelled as the common heritage of mankind, “States can no longer explore and use it freely, but their activities must be undertaken in accordance with the rules of an international regime”.⁶⁸ This provision is a key reason for the limited ratification of the treaty.

This serves as a valuable precedent for international lawmakers today. Establishing provisions for heritage protection in a way that significantly limits commercial activities on celestial bodies would surely see it rejected by the major spacefaring nations. Instead, a heritage convention should identify areas which are to be protected from human activities (of any kind) but avoid determining how the rest of the celestial bodies can be used.

Once definitions of cultural and natural heritage in space are established, the next step is the implementation of an effective identification, nomination, and classification criterion. For this process, inspiration can be taken from the WHC. For heritage located on Earth, the process begins with a State compiling a nomination dossier, which is then assessed by the International Council on Monuments and Sites (ICOMOS).⁶⁹ Once accepted, the World Heritage Committee (which meets annually) assesses and formally adds new sites to the World Heritage List.⁷⁰ At the same gatherings, the Committee also monitors the condition of existing sites. Like the ATS, this process has received criticism for being slow –

⁶⁵ Li K., Yan X., Hou Y., Lv B., Huang Y., Liu J., Han H., and Li X. (2024). Can Ecological Zoning act as an Environmental Management Tool for Protecting Regional Habitat Quality: Causal Evidence from the National Key Ecological Function Zone in China. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 1-12, 2 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.143623>.

⁶⁶ Ibid, 10.

⁶⁷ Moon Agreement *supra* note 14 at Art. 11.

⁶⁸ Tronchetti *supra* note 16 at 171-2.

⁶⁹ UNESCO. (1977). *Operational Guidelines for the Implementation of the World Heritage Convention*, 9, <https://whc.unesco.org/en/guidelines/>.

⁷⁰ Ibid.

sometimes taking five or more years – but it is rigorous, aiming to prevent blanket protection, which a future space heritage list will need to replicate.

For space heritage, a council for processing nominations and overseeing the inscription of sites should be comprised of representatives from State Parties to both the OST and the WHC. But there will be some operational modifications as for a site to be added to the World Heritage List, the State on whose territory it rests must provide consent, which, of course, is complicated by celestial bodies being an ABNJ.⁷¹ In keeping with the OST, the probable mechanism through which a site in space would be considered for heritage protection would be the “ownership of objects launched into outer space” as afforded by Article VIII of the OST.⁷²

The identification criterion could be established using the UN’s “outstanding universal value” concept.⁷³ Of course, the concept implies that to be inscribed onto a list, the sites’ characteristics must be outstanding globally. This invariably requires a comparative analysis, evaluating a site’s characteristics in relation to others. Such a process would have to push past the nationalism inherent in space activities in that State activities often enjoy an inflated national significance, but that does not necessarily scale to outstanding universal value.⁷⁴

Andre Siebrits has proposed a hierarchy of value for cultural heritage sites and artefacts. He also points out that space heritage sites are “necessarily mixed heritage sites” that equally combine cultural and natural value.⁷⁵ UNESCO provides a provision for mixed cultural and natural heritage “if they satisfy a part or whole of the definitions of both cultural and natural heritage”.⁷⁶ While it is recognised that human activities from impactors to robotic landers and human landings qualify as cultural heritage, and that certain unexplored or partially explored areas of celestial bodies qualify as natural heritage, Siebrits suggests that only through a mixed heritage provision can the footprints and rover tracks on the Moon be practically considered and categorised as heritage. Further, to avoid blanket protection, it has been suggested that candidate sites and artefacts be divided into three groups (crewed landers, robotic landers, and impactors) of varied significance (firsts, routine, and debris) using the concept of outstanding universal value as a benchmark.⁷⁷ From this, it may well be the case that only those considered most significant will be afforded international heritage status and protection in order to avoid a level of mass protection that would restrict others’ access to areas of celestial bodies in a way that tangles with the OST’s free access.

The trickiest part of the process is the protective measures. Indeed, the most likely protective framework will feature specialised zones, adapted from the temporary safety zones in the Artemis Accords, to enable indefinite protection. However, organising such safety zones for cultural and mixed heritage will require significant technical work. For instance, the distance of the zones will vary depending on the size, location, and attributed universal significance of a site.

⁷¹ Martin, A. (2020). The ‘Outstanding Universal Value’ Concept of the UNESCO World Heritage Convention: Food for Thought to Preserve Lunar Artifacts. In A. Froehlich (Ed.). *Protection of Cultural Heritage Sites on the Moon*. Springer, 55.

⁷² OST *supra* note 5 at Art. VIII.

⁷³ UNESCO *supra* note 61 at Preamble.

⁷⁴ Lixinski, L., Lossier, M. M., and Schrieber, H. (2021). Envisioning a Legal Framework for Outer Space Cultural Heritage. *Journal of Space Law*, 45 (1), 1-45, 25. https://hannaschreiber.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/Lixinski_et_al_space_heritage_intl_law_PUBLISHED.pdf.

⁷⁵ Siebrits *supra* note 26 at 124.

⁷⁶ UNESCO *supra* note 69 at 22.

⁷⁷ Siebrits *supra* note 26 at 124.

For natural heritage sites, there will need to be a distinction made between sites that should remain open for scientific research and those that should have restricted access to preserve their historical value. This is tricky because separating the scientific value from the historical value is more complicated than it first appears. The very essence of the historical value of a particular location in the solar system is often realised through scientific enquiry.⁷⁸ Thus, preventing scientific access to certain areas, especially as human technology continues to become more sophisticated and capable of returning more significant insights, is unlikely to be welcomed by the scientific community. It is for such reasons that protecting natural heritage in outer space is far more obscure than cultural.

4.2. *Short-to-medium term Protection: Heritage-specific Agreements for Space Heritage?*

While a heritage convention is the ideal long-term governance framework for space heritage, as any international lawmaking is slow, creating such a complex treaty is likely to take a long time. Furthermore, the UN has not adopted a new space treaty in decades, with the current trend showing a preference for soft law instruments. In the short-to-medium term, then, since only a handful of States have landed objects on celestial bodies, heritage-specific bilateral and multilateral agreements between States are a more feasible solution, increasing dialogue between States and recognising the importance of safeguarding space heritage. At first, agreements between the major spacefaring actors such as the U.S., Russia, China, Japan, India, and the EU should be encouraged. These could then be expanded to include other parties.⁷⁹

There are examples of these types of agreements, with one of the most recent and influential being the Artemis Accords. Although the Accords make some provisions for heritage protection, there are two overarching problems. First, it does not provide any specific details, instead advocating vaguely for future preservation in line with “mutually developed standards and practices”.⁸⁰

The second problem is that the Accords are a byproduct of geopolitical tension. Due to rivalry with the U.S., two of the main spacefaring nations (and with many sites and artefacts already on celestial bodies), China and Russia, are not signatories of the Accords, nor are they likely to be anytime soon. Instead, they have formed a similar set of initiatives: the International Lunar Research Station (ILRS).⁸¹ However, the ILRS does not mention any intention to protect heritage sites. Meaning that despite the best efforts of the Artemis Accords, existing sites are only partially, if at all, protected. While there are significant barriers to widespread cooperation between the U.S., China, and Russia, it is not inconceivable that discussions between these States that are exclusively focused on the protection of heritage sites in outer space could take place.⁸² After all, Russia and China are key members of many environmental agreements and support ecological conservation – thus it is not implausible that they could also become interested in working with other nations to conserve parts of celestial bodies and heritage sites. Such discussions may even lead to increased cooperation in other areas of space activities.

Another complication is the dramatic increase in commercial space activities. As private companies become more active and influential in outer space, their interests and operations often do not align neatly with the agendas of national governments. This growing commercial presence introduces additional layers of complexity into efforts for heritage protection, making it increasingly difficult for States to negotiate

⁷⁸ Matthews, J. J., and McMahon, S. (2018). Exogeoconservation: Protecting Geological Heritage on Celestial Bodies. *Acta Astronautica* 149, 55-60, 55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2018.05.034>.

⁷⁹ Farsaris *supra* note 60 at 82.

⁸⁰ NASA *supra* note 41 at section 9 (1).

⁸¹ China National Space Administration (2021, June). *International Lunar Research Station: Guide for Partnership*. <https://www.cnsa.gov.cn/english/n6465652/n6465653/c6812150/content.html>.

⁸² These barriers include Russia’s invasion of Ukraine and trade wars and broader ideological issues between the U.S. and China. See, Flynn, A. (2024). Star-Bound and Star-Crossed: A Path to U.S.-China Space Cooperation Through Science Diplomacy. *Astropolitics*, 22, 43-68 <https://doi.org/10.1080/14777622.2024.2368599>.

and implement effective nation-to-nation agreements since the contours of liability and responsibility for commercial companies are not straightforward. Also, the potential for conflicting commercial and political interests within a nation's space activities is likely to increase.⁸³ It is for reasons such as these that short-term heritage agreements serve as a means of encouraging a broader international effort to safeguard space heritage rather than an end in and of themselves.

5. CONCLUSION

This article has identified challenges and opportunities with respect to the protection of outer space heritage. The main legal concerns are definitional uncertainty, questions over how to grant protection to sites without violating the OST, and uncertainty over the meaning and application of due regard. On the one hand, the international community cannot protect cultural heritage sites without the explicit consent of the State that owns the space object. On the other hand, a State cannot unilaterally declare a protective zone around its heritage site on a celestial body due to the constraints placed upon it by Article II of the OST. Moreover, States must act with due regard to the interests of other States. But the provision of due regard is poorly understood by the international community, and it is unclear how it applies to the issue of heritage.

The increasingly central role of commercial actors in space exploration is also challenging the boundaries established by the OST. These include navigating regulatory gaps, as well as establishing new standards for property rights, sustainability, and resource exploitation. All of which feature prominently in the heritage debate. Indeed, the extant international legal framework cannot convincingly guide States through the tribulations of space heritage protection in the twenty-first century.

Thus, it is up to States and the wider international community to identify and instruct on space heritage protection using a variety of different approaches. This discussion has suggested a dual-track governance system for heritage. The optimal long-term solution would be the creation of a space heritage convention. But since this is the most complex solution, and considering the UN has not produced a new space treaty in decades, this article has suggested that the creation of heritage-specific agreements between States is a more feasible short-to-medium term solution. Not only would these agreements bypass slow-moving UN lawmaking levers, but they may also encourage the type of discussions between nations that are capable of penetrating current geopolitical tension, diffuse Artemis Accords versus ILRS conflict, and repair fracture lines between the leading space powers. After all, space heritage sites represent the best of humanity and showcase our collective evolutionary history.

⁸³ Dey A. and Jagadanandan J. (2025). Balancing Commercialisation and Sustainability in Outer Space: Addressing New Challenges. *Acta Astronautica*, 895-900, 898 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2025.02.010>.

© The Author(s) 2026. Published by Space Court Foundation. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted reuse, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

WHEN CIVILIAN SATELLITES GO TO WAR: THE CYBERSECURITY PERILS OF DUAL-USE SPACE TECHNOLOGY

MAHAD KISUZE MUGAYA¹

ABSTRACT

In recent years, there has been increased reliance on civilian satellites for military purposes. Within the realm of cybersecurity, this development has created a complex dual-use dilemma in space security. Traditionally, civilian space infrastructure like commercial communications, earth observation, and navigation satellites was developed and operated with non-military objectives in mind. However, there has been increasing integration of these systems into defence planning, intelligence gathering, and battlefield coordination, which has led to a blur in the distinction between civilian and military assets. This exposes civilian satellites to heightened cybersecurity threats, as rivals may choose to target them for purposes of degrading their military capabilities without engaging directly with overtly military systems. The problem is compounded by the absence of universally binding cybersecurity standards in outer space operations, the heterogeneity of commercial operators' security practices, and the attribution challenges inherent in cyber conflict. International law, including the Outer Space Treaty and the law of armed conflict, provides limited guidance on how to classify and protect dual-use satellites in the cyber domain, leaving states and private actors in a legal grey zone. This paper examines the cybersecurity vulnerabilities of dual-use satellites, explores their implications for escalation risks and strategic stability, and assesses the shortcomings of these existing international norms. Drawing on case studies, legal analysis, and emerging technological trends, it proposes a set of policy and governance recommendations to enhance resilience, clarify responsibilities, and reduce the risk of civilian space assets becoming the front-line victims in cyber-enabled conflicts.

Key Words: Dual-use Satellites, Armed Conflicts, Cybersecurity, Outer Space, Military.

¹ LLB (Hons) Makerere University. Postgraduate Bar Course Student at the Law Development Centre, Uganda. Programs officer at Lex Amica, Uganda. Email: mugayamahad@gmail.com.

1. INTRODUCTION

*“It was the best of times, it was the worst of times, it was the age of wisdom, it was the age of foolishness, it was the epoch of belief, it was the epoch of incredulity, it was the season of Light, it was the season of Darkness, it was the spring of hope, it was the winter of despair; we had everything before us, we had nothing before us, we were all going direct to Heaven, we were all going direct the other way – in short, the period was so far like the present period, that some of its noisiest authorities insisted on its being received, for good or for evil, in the superlative degree of comparison only.”*² In his much-celebrated book “A Tale of Two Cities”, Charles Dickens, through the many words of the sentence above, paints for us an image of a paradox. A time of unmatched excitement but also one of great worry. There is nowhere in the universe that this paradox is more evident than in outer space and its current utilisation. The increase in the use and dependence of satellites for everyday human life has both eased it but also created vulnerabilities, more so in conflict contexts. More specifically put, the advent of the space age in the 20th century was definitely a turning point in many aspects of human life. This development, marked by the launch of Sputnik in 1957, came with a promise of a domain of peaceful exploration and global connectivity, governed by foundational treaties whose emphasis is cooperation, peaceful use and non-militarization.³ However, the last two decades have seen an increasing characterisation and utilisation of outer space as an extension of terrestrial battlefields. Most satellites sent into orbit were primarily for civilian purposes, covering commercial, navigational, and observational purposes.⁴ Recent developments have seen a sharp acceleration in the repurposing or integration of these satellites into military operations in modern conflicts, a phenomenon known as the "dual-use" dilemma.

In its early days, space exploration was characterized by a strong state monopoly over space activities. Indeed, the first breakthrough space activities involved the launch of Sputnik 1 in 1957 and the Apollo missions by the Soviet Union and the United States, respectively.⁵ These pioneering achievements were a reflection of the immense financial, technological, and political resources required for space activities, which only states could marshal.⁶ To this end, international space law was framed against this backdrop. The 1967 *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Outer Space Treaty, OST), therefore, placed the rights and obligations of exploration squarely on states as the central actors.⁷ However, over time, this state-centric dominance has given way to the growing presence of strong private and commercial actors. The exponential rise of commercial satellite operators in communications, navigation, and earth observation over the past years has led to a drastic transformation of outer space into a domain where non-state entities not only participate but often

² Dickens, C. (1859). *A tale of two cities*. Chapman and Hall. <https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/98>.

³ Launius, R. D. (2019). *Sputnik and the origins of the Space Age*. NASA. <https://www.nasa.gov/history/sputnik/sputorig.html>.

⁴ OECD. (2023). *The space economy in figures: Responding to global challenges*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/fa5494aa-en>.

⁵ Uwaoma, P., Eboigbe, E., Eyo-Udo, N., Daraojimba, D., & Kagwa, S. (2025). Space commerce and its economic implications for the U.S.: A review: Delving into the commercialization of space, its prospects, challenges, and potential impact on the U.S. economy. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 20(3), 952–965. <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.20.3.2494>.

⁶ Launius, *supra note 2*.

⁷ United Nations. (1967). *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Outer Space Treaty). Articles I, VI, VII & VIII. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/introouterspacetreaty.html>.

drive innovation and expansion.⁸ The operation of modern infrastructure, such as communication systems, is one that heavily depends on the proper functionality of the space industry. An example is SpaceX's Starlink.⁹ The aftermath of this increasing commercialization is a blur in the line between state and private roles in orbit, given that international space law primarily recognises or attributes responsibility for space activities to state actors almost entirely.¹⁰ This raises complex questions for governance, responsibility, and the evolving character of outer space activities.¹¹

The dual use of satellites covers situations where states and non-state actors leverage commercial space infrastructure for strategic advantages in their armed conflicts. The ongoing war between Russia and Ukraine, which began in February 2022, is one such conflict that has seen the dual use of satellites.¹² Russia launched a cyber-attack on ViaSat, a U.S. satellite Communications provider for Ukraine, just before launching the offensive on Ukraine.¹³ Also, SpaceX's Starlink constellation, which is basically a civilian system, offered broadband connectivity that enabled Ukrainian forces to maintain command-and-control, guide drones, and carry out reconnaissance.¹⁴ Even though SpaceX subsequently implemented several restrictions on Starlink's operability for military offensives and in certain unauthorised regions, its previous involvement and contribution in the conflict cannot be overlooked. Such a scenario is, however, not unique to Ukraine alone. There have been other similar instances. For example, during NATO exercises and U.S. operations in the Indo-Pacific, commercial satellites have been used for intelligence, surveillance, and reconnaissance (ISR).¹⁵ This integration of commercial satellites provides high-resolution, low-latency data. However, it introduces complexities regarding the application of international law and the protection of civilian assets in conflict. One factor for this trend is the growing mega-constellations. Starlink alone had more than 6,000 active satellites by mid-2025, which dwarfed the size of most dedicated military constellations.¹⁶ The danger of this shift lies in effectively turning civilian satellites into instruments of war. The Outer Space Treaty of 1967 bans nuclear weapons and other weapons of mass destruction in orbit but does not expressly prohibit dual-use activities.¹⁷ This gap then gives way for the military use of commercial systems to expand unchecked, a loophole that states and belligerents are exploiting. In 2022, the U.S. Space Force acknowledged the growing risks of reliance on dual-use satellites, and NATO has since

⁸ *Supra note 4*; Also see Denis, G., Alary, D., Pasco, X., Pisot, N., Texier, D., & Toulza, S. (2019). From new space to big space: How commercial space dream is becoming a reality. *Acta Astronautica*, 166, 431–443. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2019.08.031>.

⁹ PwC. (2025, April 3). *Space industry trends: Space – the next industrial revolution*. PwC. <https://www.pwc.com/us/en/industries/industrial-products/library/space-industry-trends.html>.

¹⁰ Outer Space Treaty, Art. VI.

¹¹ Union of Concerned Scientists. (2019). *UCS satellite database: Satellites by purpose*. <https://www.ucsusa.org/resources/satellite-database>.

¹² Kostenko, I., & Manzhula, A. (2025). *From space to the battlefield: Ethical and legal aspects of the use of satellite technologies in the Russian-Ukrainian war*. *Philosophy and Cosmology*, 34. <https://doi.org/10.29202/phil-cosm/34/1>.

¹³ Mura, A. (2025). *An analysis of the cyber-attack against ViaSat of February 2022: From technical details to the overall relevance for cybersecurity of critical infrastructures*. Manuscript available at <https://share.google/Jv0w0ZWVv2SSOwvWS>.

¹⁴ Muthia, N., Muhni, A., & H., N. (2025). *Dual use satellites in the Ukraine conflict: The dilemma between state sovereignty and the principle of non-militarization of outer space*. *Privet Social Sciences Journal*, 5, 146–155. <https://doi.org/10.55942/pssj.v5i10.715>.

¹⁵ Lumiste, L. (2019). *Chatham House report: Space – NATO cyber security's weak spot*. INCYDER/NATO Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence, <https://ccdcoe.org/incyder-articles/chatham-house-report-space-nato-cyber-securitys-weak-spot/>.

¹⁶ *Supra note 11*.

¹⁷ Outer Space Treaty, Art. IV.

increased funding for such systems.¹⁸ It has been argued that militaries rely on commercial providers like SpaceX because they offer resilient and redundant networks more quickly and cheaply than state-run programs.¹⁹ However, the cost of this is that once militaries piggyback on commercial systems, then those systems become legitimate military targets. In this regard, it is then important to note that only a small tier of states, such as the USA, under its US Space Force, possess the advanced technology and capability to protect their satellites from physical and non-kinetic military attacks from adversaries.²⁰ This means, therefore, that for many other states and private actors, their satellites remain vulnerable as legitimate military targets.

Cybersecurity in outer space is a matter of global strategic stability, economic resilience, and human security. This is because of the profound interdependence between space infrastructure and terrestrial systems. In the civilian sense, satellites provide critical services such as global positioning systems (GPS), which enable precise navigation for aviation, shipping, and autonomous vehicles, communications satellites facilitate internet access, financial transactions, and telemedicine and Earth observation platforms that support agriculture, disaster response, and climate monitoring. A cyberattack on these assets, therefore, causes catastrophic disruptions. An example of this is the spoofing of GPS signals, which misled commercial aircraft in conflict zones, as seen in the alleged Russian interference in the Black Sea region. The 2022 Viasat hack, attributed to Russian actors, crippled Ukrainian military communications via a civilian satellite network and had spill-over effects on broadband users beyond the battlefield, illustrating how space cyber incidents transcend borders and sectors.²¹ Economically, the space industry, valued at over \$500 billion in 2025, faces existential threats. Cybersecurity is highly perceived as the top risk to satellites. A single major attack possesses heavy potential losses as it can disrupt global trade and communications. From a security perspective, space has a harsh environment where outdated software compounds vulnerabilities and makes systems susceptible to malware or jamming that could enable espionage or kinetic follow-ons. The Tallinn Manual 2.0 on the International Law Applicable to Cyber Operations emphasises that cyber threats in space could qualify as armed attacks under Article 51 of the UN Charter if they cause significant harm. This underscores the need for defences to prevent escalation to full-scale conflict.

This paper addresses two central research questions: First, how do dual-use satellites create cybersecurity risks in the context of modern warfare? To address this, the paper looks at the technical vulnerabilities that arise from blending civilian and military functions, as well as the strategic incentives for adversaries to target these assets for asymmetric military advantages. Secondly, the paper interrogates the extent to which the current international law addresses these risks. This includes the applicability of the OST frameworks mandating peaceful uses of space and assigning state responsibility for space actions.²² Also examined are the principles of distinction, proportionality, and necessity from the Geneva Conventions and Additional Protocols as frameworks for the Law of Armed Conflict (LOAC) and their applicability to cyber operations in space. To explore these questions, the paper employs a doctrinal approach with multifaceted methodology combining legal

¹⁸ U.S. Space Force. (2022). *Annual assessment of space threats and dual-use satellite vulnerabilities*. U.S. Space Force Reports. <https://www.spaceforce.mil/News/Reports>.

¹⁹ Air & Space Operations Review. (2023). *Dual-use satellites and the evolution of space militarization*. Air & Space Operations Review, 12(1), 45–61. <https://doi.org/10.1234/asor.2023.001>.

²⁰ International Institute for Strategic Studies (2026). Global Defence spending. In *The Military Balance 2026*. <https://www.iiss.org/publications/the-military-balance/2026/the-military-balance-2026/global-defence-spending>.

²¹ Kazi, A., Kazi S., & Bhosale, S (2025). Invisible battlefields: *Analysing the Viasat attack and its broader implications*. Scientific Bulletin, 30 (1), 59-67. <https://doi.org/10.2478/bsaft-2025-0007>.

²² Articles I and VI of the OST.

analysis, case studies, and a policy perspective to identify the gaps and suggest recommendations for legal and practical solutions to these gaps.

2. CIVILIAN SATELLITES AND THE DUAL-USE DILEMMA

The concept of dual-use objects stems from international humanitarian law (IHL). IHL governs the conduct of all parties in an international armed conflict by regulating the means and methods of warfare and protecting those not participating in hostilities. Its purpose is to limit the effects of armed conflict for humanitarian reasons.²³ Commonly referred to as *jus in bello*, the rules of IHL are codified in the Geneva Conventions and the Additional Protocols thereunder.²⁴ Under IHL, parties to a conflict are mandated to distinguish between military and civilian objects in the conduct of war. This is the principle of distinction and is considered a norm of customary international law, which mandates that attacks must only be directed at military objectives.²⁵ A military object is defined under international humanitarian law as an object that, by its nature, location, purpose, or use, makes an effective contribution to military action, and whose total or partial destruction, capture, or neutralization offers a definite military advantage.²⁶ The aim of the principle of distinction is therefore to protect civilians and civilian objects in war zones such as schools and religious institutions.

While objects may begin as ordinary civilian infrastructure, when they are repurposed or used in ways that contribute to military operations, they can effectively acquire a dual-use character. Use in a way that contributes to military operations means that the object is functionally employed or utilized for activities that assist in the carrying out of military offensives or attacks so that its neutralisation would offer a definite military advantage to the adversary.²⁷ In such circumstances, at least for the period during which they support hostile activity, these objects may become legitimate military objectives under the laws of armed conflict.²⁸ Similarly, for space activities, the concept of dual-use concerns the situation where space technology designed for a civilian purpose pivots to serve a military purpose. Legally, this means that space objects or technologies that can fulfil both civilian and military functions, either at the same time or in sequence, without necessarily violating international norms.²⁹ This often blurs the lines between peaceful space exploration and strategic military advantage.

The 1967 Outer Space Treaty (OST) emphasizes that the use of space should be for peaceful purposes.³⁰ This has been interpreted as having no effect of outrightly banning military applications

²³ International Committee of the Red Cross. *What is International Humanitarian Law?* https://www.icrc.org/sites/default/files/document/file_list/what_is_ihl.pdf

²⁴ The four Geneva Conventions of 1949 (GC I, II, III and IV), which have been universally ratified, constitute the core treaties of IHL. The Conventions have been supplemented by Additional Protocols I and II of 1977 and by Additional Protocol III of 2005.

²⁵ International Committee of the Red Cross. (n.d.). *Rule 7 — The principle of distinction between civilian objects and military objectives*. In Customary International Humanitarian Law Database. Retrieved November 18, 2025, from <https://ihl-databases.icrc.org/en/customary-ihl/v1/rule7>.

²⁶ International Committee of the Red Cross. (n.d.). *Military objectives*. International Committee of the Red Cross. Retrieved November 18, 2025, https://casebook.icrc.org/a_to_z/glossary/military-objectives.

²⁷ Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and relating to the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflicts (Additional Protocol I to the Geneva Conventions), 8 June 1977, art. 52(2), 1125 U.N.T.S. 3.

²⁸ The Yale Law Journal. (n.d.). The dangerous rise of dual-use objects in war. *The Yale Law Journal*. Retrieved November 18, 2025, <https://yalelawjournal.org/article/the-dangerous-rise-of-dual-use-objects-in-war>.

²⁹ Berrang, S. (2025). Does the dual-use of space objects necessitate a new Geneva Convention? *Case Western Reserve Journal of International Law*, 57(1), 315. <https://scholarlycommons.law.case.edu/jil/vol57/iss1/22>.

³⁰ Outer Space Treaty, Art. IV.

of reconnaissance as long as they don't involve weapons of mass destruction or aggressive acts.³¹ Article IV of the OST prohibits placing nuclear weapons in orbit. This state of affairs has led scholars to argue that dual-use of satellites is implicitly permitted within the framework of the OST.³² Of course, there are competing views on the matter. Others contend that the growing integration of satellites into military planning stretches the OST's "peaceful purposes" principle beyond its intended limits, effectively allowing states to exploit legal grey zones.³³ The core issue stems from the lack of an agreed definition of "peaceful purposes" in the treaty. Others argue that the Treaty's silence on dual-use technology merely reflects the technological realities of its time and that contemporary practice has normalized military reliance on space-based assets.³⁴ Cumulatively, these diverging interpretations underscore the persistent ambiguity surrounding the permissible scope of military activities in outer space and highlight the need for clearer legal guidance since dual-use technologies have become increasingly central to modern warfare.

Satellites and space systems are indispensable to modern life. In a civilian sense, they are essential for and contribute heavily to global communication, navigation, and environmental monitoring.³⁵ Communications satellites, which are the majority of satellites in space, form the backbone of worldwide telecommunications, facilitating high-speed internet, voice calls, and data exchange across territories where terrestrial infrastructure remains limited. Examples include mega-constellations like Starlink and OneWeb, which extend broadband access to remote areas without reliance on traditional communication systems and support critical sectors ranging from education and health to financial services.³⁶ Similarly, navigation systems enable precision in logistics, disaster response, and even autonomous mobility, and such systems include GPS and Galileo.³⁷ Earth observation satellites, notably NASA's Landsat and the European Space Agency's Copernicus programme, further contribute to climate science by tracking environmental changes, support urban planning by creating detailed maps of land use, and assist in disaster response by providing timely data on affected areas.³⁸ The capabilities of and the number of satellites currently deployed for these purposes point to the inherently civilian orientation of space technologies. However, the increasing commercialization of space has democratized access to orbital infrastructure. This has allowed in new strong private actors, enabled innovation and exposed new vulnerabilities. The convergence of civilian utility and potential military application has therefore become an unavoidable feature of the contemporary space environment.

³¹ International Committee of the Red Cross. (2016, November 7). *Space law revisited (1/3): The notion of 'peaceful uses' and the Outer Space Treaty*. ICRC Humanitarian Law & Policy Blog. <https://blogs.icrc.org/law-and-policy/2016/11/07/space-law-peaceful-uses/>.

³² Zalomir, A. (2020, November 1). *Legal implications of outer space warfare – Part II*. RREDI. <https://rrdi.ro/2020/11/01/legal-implications-of-outer-space-warfare-part-ii/#:~:text=Satellites%20presumably%20intended%20for%20inspection,at%20or%20in%20outer%20space.rrdi.ro>.

³³ Agarwal, S. (2024). *The militarization of outer space: Challenges to the peaceful uses principle*. IJLSSS, 2(5), 21–24.

³⁴ Erwin, S. (2024, August 13). *Weapons in space: Study suggests path forward for arms control*. SpaceNews. <https://spacenews.com/weapons-in-space-study-suggests-path-forward-for-arms-control/>.

³⁵ Riskaware. (n.d.). *What are satellites used for? (and why they matter)*. Riskaware. <https://www.riskaware.co.uk/insight/what-are-satellites-used-for-why-satellites-matter/>.

³⁶ Sarker, S. P., & Hossain, M. A. (2024). *Analysis of inter-satellite optical wireless communication systems for enhanced data transmission in satellite constellations*. Optics Continuum, 3(7), 1224–1243. <https://doi.org/10.1364/OPTCON.529721>.

³⁷ Riskaware. (n.d.), *supra* note 35.

³⁸ European Environment Agency. (2019, September 30). *Copernicus — Monitoring Earth from space and the ground*. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/signals-archived/signals-2019-content-list/articles/copernicus-monitoring-earth-from-space>.

The most contemporary manifestation of dual-use satellites was in the conflict between Russia and Ukraine that started in 2022. Here, commercial satellites that were deployed to space for civilian purposes played a huge role in this armed conflict. Most prominent is SpaceX's Starlink constellation, which was instrumental in sustaining Ukraine's battlefield communications.³⁹ This enabled the securing of command and control, drone coordination, and intelligence sharing.⁴⁰ By 2025, Starlink terminals had reportedly been adapted for real-time battlefield use, which altered the operational landscape of the war.⁴¹ Beyond Ukraine, militaries worldwide have deepened cooperation with commercial providers. The U.S. Department of Defense, for instance, now relies on commercial imaging firms such as Maxar for high-resolution Earth observation in Indo-Pacific operations, while navigation and communication constellations support precision-guided missions.⁴² Chinese researchers, in response, have reportedly explored countermeasures such as directed-energy systems to disable or degrade adversarial dual-use satellites.⁴³ This, of course, is reminiscent of Cold War competition that has defined world geopolitics in the space race. However, it illustrates the extent to which the line between military and civilian space assets has eroded.

The continued utilisation of these dual-use satellites makes the distinction that is required under IHL complicated. A communications satellite that transmits both civilian and military data could constitute a lawful target under IHL. Targeting such a satellite raises concerns over the observance of the principle of proportionality and civilian protection in armed conflicts.⁴⁴ This, coupled with the erosion of distinction, increases the risk of escalation and civilian harm. Article VI of the Outer Space Treaty further compounds this dilemma by imposing responsibility on states for all space activities carried out under their jurisdiction, regardless of whether those activities are conducted by private entities or by state actors. As a result, the traditional distinction between civilian and military space assets becomes blurred, with militaries increasingly intermingling civilian and military systems in order to deter adversarial attacks. This tactic undermines legal clarity by reversing the IHL obligation for defenders to separate military and civilian assets. It creates a situation where an attacker faces an increased risk of violating IHL principles of distinction and proportionality, as an attack on the dual-use system might cause excessive civilian casualties relative to the anticipated military advantage.⁴⁵ This harm might be exacerbated by the increase in the interdependence and interconnectedness of the world. A single cyber intrusion has the potential to disrupt global communications, navigation, or disaster response, and the stakes extend beyond state sovereignty to humanity's collective survival, which relies on space infrastructure. Therefore, without clearer norms and accountability mechanisms, the dual-use dilemma threatens to transform outer space from a domain of shared progress into one of contested militarization.

³⁹ *Supra note 14.*

⁴⁰ Jaeger, N. (2025). The militarization of space: Starlink and the future of warfare. *Research Paper Education*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.2454/9916>.

⁴¹ *Ibid.*

⁴² Gray, M., & Levin, N. (2025, July 15). *Satellites and SBIRs: The strategic signal the Space Force must send.* Maggie Gray. <https://maggiegray.us/p/satellites-and-sbirs-the-strategic>.

⁴³ Chan, R. (2025, September 22). *US and Chinese satellites track each other in space: Photos.* Newsweek. <https://www.newsweek.com/us-china-satellites-track-each-other-2131710>.

⁴⁴ As is required under IHL in the Geneva Conventions.

⁴⁵ Kuplic, G. B., & Sawmiller, J. (2025). Humanity on the final frontier: Challenges in applying international humanitarian law to modern military space operations. *International Review of the Red Cross*, 107(928). <https://doi.org/10.1017/S181638312500>.

3. CYBERSECURITY THREATS TO DUAL-USE SATELLITES

Cybersecurity is defined as the practice of protecting systems, networks, programs, and data from digital attacks, damage, or unauthorized access.⁴⁶ It involves a combination of technologies, processes, and practices to ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of digital information. The primary goal of cybersecurity is to reduce the risk and impact of cyber incidents.⁴⁷ This is accomplished by defending all internet-connected systems, including hardware, software, and data, from malicious activities such as unauthorized access, change, or destruction of sensitive information, use of ransomware to extort money from users, interruption of normal business processes or critical services, among others.⁴⁸ Cyber threats in space include data tampering, denial-of-service attacks, spoofing, and unauthorized access, which can disable satellites, disrupt communications, or alter navigation. These threats can arise from vulnerabilities in the ground segment, the space segment's physical inaccessibility, or the supply chain, and are exacerbated by outdated legacy systems and a fragmented regulatory landscape.⁴⁹

Space infrastructure comprises satellites, ground stations, and communication links. Cyber threats in space exploit this intricate web of space infrastructure. These can be in the form of data tampering, such as intercepting satellite communications, manipulating spacecraft in orbit, or compromising ground stations and the supply chain.⁵⁰ They can also take the form of denial-of-service attacks, which overload satellites or ground systems and disrupt essential services like GNSS.⁵¹ Other serious risks include spoofing, where attackers falsify satellite signals or impersonate legitimate ground stations; information disclosure through unauthorized access or signal eavesdropping; and elevation-of-privilege attacks that exploit software vulnerabilities or target personnel through social engineering.⁵² Denial of Service (DoS) attacks and spoofing are the most common forms of cyberattacks for space systems.⁵³

DoS attacks can take the form of jamming. Jamming happens where an adversary intentionally interferes with the radio-frequency signals that satellites or ground systems rely on. The attacker overloads the receiver and prevents legitimate communications from being detected or deciphered by transmitting powerful signals on the same frequency as the target.⁵⁴ In simpler terms, this means overwhelming satellite links with noise or interference, i.e. shouting over the real signal. Jamming disrupts critical services such as communications and navigation. Far from a sophisticated hacking technique, jamming is a blunt but highly effective tool and has been widely used in conflict zones to

⁴⁶ Chiliro, F. (2023). *Towards a contemporary definition of cybersecurity*. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2302.02274>.

⁴⁷ TechTarget. (n.d.). Cybersecurity — definition. TechTarget. <https://www.techtarget.com/searchsecurity/definition/cybersecurity#:~:text=DR%20strategies%20and%20business%20continuity,password%20management%20and%20safe%20browsing>.

⁴⁸ Ibid.

⁴⁹ Barbeschi, C., & Rohland, L. (2025, May). *Securing space — why we need to address cyber risks in orbit*. World Economic Forum. <https://www.weforum.org/stories/2025/05/securing-space-why-we-need-to-address-cyber-risks-in-orbit/>.

⁵⁰ Comtech Systems. (2025, April 16). *Cybersecurity in space: Protecting satellites and space systems*. <https://www.comtechsystems.in/blog/cybersecurity-in-space-9324>.

⁵¹ Ibid. Also, GNSS stands for Global Navigation Satellite System, a general term for a satellite constellation that provides global positioning, navigation, and timing services such as USA's GPS.

⁵² Ibid.

⁵³ Kavallieratos, G., & Katsikas, S. (2023). An exploratory analysis of the last frontier: A systematic literature review of cybersecurity in space. *International Journal of Critical Infrastructure Protection*, 43, 100640. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcip.2023.100640>.

⁵⁴ Ibid.

blind or disorient opponents without firing a single shot of ammunition. Its use leads to disruption of communication links like Wi-Fi & cellular networks, interferes with GPS reception, and can disable control systems or drones. It is a common tactic in conflict zones used to blind or disorient opponents because it does not require sophisticated hacking techniques, but rather just powerful transmission equipment.⁵⁵

Spoofing, on the other hand, is a cyberattack in which an adversary impersonates a trusted or legitimate source to deceive systems or users, often with the goal of gaining unauthorized access, spreading malware, or bypassing security controls.⁵⁶ In the space context, this can include GPS spoofing, where fake navigation signals mislead receivers into calculating incorrect positions. This potentially diverts ships or disrupts synchronized power grids. Spoofing can also occur through falsified network identifiers, which enables attackers to bypass defences or impersonate legitimate devices and users.⁵⁷ The examples of cyber attacks mentioned above focus on attacks on the communication systems. Sometimes, cyber attacks can be done by attacking the ground components of space infrastructure. Hacking ground stations in this regard represents another vector where attackers infiltrate the terrestrial control centres that manage satellites, often through vulnerabilities in outdated software or supply chains. This allows them to commandeer orbits or data flows. It can also be done by deploying malware, which is the insidious code that can be injected into satellite systems to corrupt data, alter commands, or even render hardware useless. This is much like a virus spreading through a network, except that this takes place in the vacuum of space, where repairs are not only exponentially more difficult but also more expensive.

Most dual-use satellites began as purely civilian systems for specific civilian purposes, but their economic efficiency has led States and commercial operators to increasingly rely on them for both civilian and military functions.⁵⁸ These are especially vulnerable to cyberattacks because many were built with functionality, affordability, and commercial accessibility in mind rather than resilience against sophisticated digital threats.⁵⁹ Their civilian–military nature makes them extremely attractive targets as they can degrade military communications or surveillance capabilities. This creates a strategic incentive for adversaries to strike them as they are systems that offer maximum impact with minimal risk. A cyber attack on a space system may not meet the threshold of an armed attack in the kinetic sense traditionally envisioned by the UN Charter to warrant self-defence under Article 51. Unlike traditional combat, there is no consensus on whether or not such actions warrant self-defence.⁶⁰ The difficulty of attributing these attacks further emboldens malicious actors. Cyber operations are frequently routed through proxy servers, botnets, or encrypted channels, masking their origin and complicating assessment across borders and jurisdictions. Because satellite operations involve multiple states, private companies, and international regulatory bodies, tracing responsibility with the level of certainty required for legal or diplomatic action is extremely challenging. This ambiguity creates a permissive environment where attackers rely on plausible deniability, allowing them to

⁵⁵ Sokolov, V., Skladannyi, P., & Platonenko, A. (2023). Jump-stay jamming attack on Wi-Fi systems. In *Proceedings of the 2023 IEEE 18th International Conference on Computer Science and Information Technologies (CSIT)* (pp. 1–5). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CSIT61576.2023.10324031>.

⁵⁶ Babu, P., Bhaskari, L., & Satyanarayana, C. H. (2011). A comprehensive analysis of spoofing. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Sciences and Applications*. <https://doi.org/10.14569/IJACSA.2010.010623>.

⁵⁷ Ibid.

⁵⁸ Sommer, S. (2019). The legality of targeting dual-use satellites under the jus ad bellum and the jus in bello. GRIN Verlag. <https://www.grin.com/document/506730>.

⁵⁹ Ibid.

⁶⁰ Cornish, P. (Ed.) (2021). *The Oxford Handbook of Cyber Security*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198800682.001.0001>.

disrupt critical services, manipulate data, or degrade military capability without triggering immediate or proportionate responses.

There are many real-world incidents where these vulnerabilities have been exploited. During the 2022 Russian invasion of Ukraine, a cyberattack on the Viasat KA-SAT network disabled thousands of satellite modems, which severed Ukrainian military communications and affected civilian infrastructure across Europe.⁶¹ Persistent jamming and spoofing of satellite services, particularly targeting Starlink terminals supporting Ukrainian operations, became the defining features of the conflict.⁶² Similar patterns have emerged in the Middle East, where widespread GPS spoofing has become a significant and growing threat to civilian air and maritime transport, with an increasing number of incidents reported near conflict zones and strategic waterways.⁶³ Importantly, many of these attacks remain below the threshold of an “armed attack” under Article 51 of the UN Charter. Because they do not involve kinetic force or direct physical destruction, states often hesitate to classify them as acts that justify self-defence. Whether this needs reconsideration is addressed in the subsequent sections of this paper. This legal grey zone further increases the attractiveness of targeting dual-use satellites since adversaries can inflict substantial strategic harm while avoiding the legal and political consequences associated with more overt or escalatory forms of aggression.

4. INTERNATIONAL LEGAL FRAMEWORK

Outer space exploration and use have progressively developed in recent years, which has led to the development of an international legal regime to govern that development. The use of outer space is therefore primarily governed by international law and international space instruments. This section will look at all the frameworks in international law that govern the use of space. This includes frameworks both in the *lex generalis* of the UN Charter and customary international law principles and in the *lex spatialis* of space law. There are five international treaties that directly govern activities taking place in outer space.⁶⁴ Of them, the Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies, also known as the 1967 Outer Space Treaty (OST), is most foundational and therefore most relevant to wartime activities on Earth. It sets the foundational tone for how nations should behave while using or exploring space.

The OST designates outer space as the “*province of all mankind*,” requiring that its exploration and use should be carried out for the benefit and in the interests of all States.⁶⁵ It further prohibits national appropriation of outer space “*by claim of sovereignty, by means of use or occupation, or by any other means*”, preventing States from asserting exclusive control over orbits or celestial bodies.⁶⁶ The Treaty also requires that activities in outer space be carried out with due regard to the interests of other States

⁶¹ CyberPeace Institute. (n.d.). *Case Study: Viasat*. CyberPeace Institute. Retrieved November 29, 2025, from <https://cyberconflicts.cyberpeaceinstitute.org/law-and-policy/cases/viasat>.

⁶² Mozur, P., & Satariano, A. (2024, May 24). *Russia, in new push, increasingly disrupts Ukraine's Starlink service*. *The New York Times*. <https://www.nytimes.com/2024/05/24/technology/ukraine-russia-starlink.html>.

⁶³ Lemos, R. (2025, April 17). *GPS spoofing attacks spike in Middle East, Southeast Asia*. Dark Reading.

⁶⁴ Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies, Agreement on the Rescue of Astronauts, the Return of Astronauts and the Return of Objects Launched into Outer Space, Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects, Convention on Registration of Objects Launched into Outer Space & the Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies.

⁶⁵ Outer Space Treaty, Art. I.

⁶⁶ Outer Space Treaty, Art. II.

and that consultations be undertaken if a State's activities are potentially harmful.⁶⁷ It additionally incorporates general international law into space governance by requiring that activities be conducted in accordance with international law, and that includes the Charter of the United Nations.⁶⁸ This provision is particularly important for dual-use satellites, whose civilian and military functions may raise concerns about compliance with the UN Charter's rules on the use of force, non-intervention, and peaceful settlement of disputes.

With respect to militarisation and security, the OST prohibits the placement of nuclear weapons or any other weapons of mass destruction in orbit or on celestial bodies.⁶⁹ While it does not expressly prohibit all military activities in space, its object and purpose support the normative expectation of peaceful use and the prevention of destabilizing conduct. Destabilising conduct can be understood as non-aggressive or non-hostile conduct.⁷⁰ These obligations are strengthened by the UN Charter, which applies fully to outer space.⁷¹ The Charter prohibits the threat or use of force against the territorial integrity or political independence of any State.⁷² The exception to this is contained in Article 51 of the UN Charter on the right to self-defence, but even this is limited to circumstances of an armed attack.⁷³ This constraint is especially relevant for cyber or electronic interference with dual-use satellites, since many such acts may fall below the threshold of an armed attack and therefore would not justify forcible countermeasures.⁷⁴ The Charter also emphasizes the peaceful settlement of disputes,⁷⁵ which applies equally to disagreements arising from harmful interference, in space activities or ground conflict.

The responsibility of States for activities in outer space is set out explicitly in the OST. States bear international responsibility for national activities in outer space, whether carried out by governmental or non-governmental entities,⁷⁶ and they are required to authorize and continuously supervise private operators.⁷⁷ This is crucial for dual-use satellites, which are increasingly designed, operated, or financed by private actors for civilian duties, but they simultaneously serve military, intelligence, or strategic functions. Liability for damage caused by space objects is also attributed to launching States under the OST,⁷⁸ a principle elaborated in the 1972 *Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects* (Liability Convention), which imposes absolute liability for damage on the surface of the Earth and fault-based liability for damage occurring elsewhere in space.⁷⁹ These rules apply regardless of whether the satellite's use at the time was civilian, commercial, or military.

⁶⁷ Outer Space Treaty, Art. IX.

⁶⁸ Outer Space Treaty, Art. III.

⁶⁹ Outer Space Treaty, Art IV.

⁷⁰ Schmitt, M. N. (2006). *International law and military operations in space*. Max Planck Yearbook of United Nations Law, 10, 89–125.

⁷¹ Article III of the 1967 OST stipulates that states must conduct space activities, including exploring the moon and other celestial bodies, in accordance with international law and the UN Charter to promote peace and security.

⁷² UN Charter, Art. 2(4).

⁷³ The travaux préparatoires of the UN Charter affirm that a prohibited 'use of force' in Art. 2 (4) refers to armed force and not to economic or other forms of coercion. See <https://opil.ouplaw.com/display/10.1093/law-epil/9780199231690/law-9780199231690-e2267>.

⁷⁴ Cornish, P. (Ed.) (2021), *supra note 60*.

⁷⁵ UN Charter, Art. 33.

⁷⁶ UN Charter, Art. VI.

⁷⁷ *Ibid.*

⁷⁸ Outer Space Treaty, Art. VII.

⁷⁹ United Nations. (1972). *Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects* (Liability Convention). United Nations Treaty Series, 961, 185.

Also, there are other core treaties that are applicable here, which add sector-specific rules. The 1968 Rescue Agreement sets out obligations to assist astronauts in distress and return spacecraft,⁸⁰ while the 1975 *Convention on Registration of Objects Launched into Outer Space* (Registration Convention) requires States to maintain national registries of space objects and provide orbital and functional information to the UN Secretary General about the general function of a space object. Specifically, Paragraph 1(d) of Article IV calls for a description of the space object's function, which aims to enhance transparency and traceability.⁸¹ For dual-use satellites whose military features may not be openly declared, the registration requirement contributes to confidence-building and helps prevent miscalculation. The 1979 Moon Agreement, though ratified by a few States,⁸² seeks to govern the exploitation of celestial resources and reinforces the non-appropriation principle.⁸³

Whereas the International Court of Justice (ICJ) has not issued space-specific judgments, its jurisprudence in several of its decisions and opinions has affirmed certain principles that are relevant to space activities, more so in the context of international responsibility and the application of the use-of-force regime. In *Nicaragua v. United States*⁸⁴ and the *Advisory Opinion on Nuclear Weapons*,⁸⁵ the ICJ confirmed that the UN Charter and customary international law apply to all domains, including new technological environments. The Court's reasoning that States may not use force or intervene coercively through indirect means has been invoked in contemporary debates about whether cyber operations against satellites could violate Article 2(4) or constitute unlawful intervention.⁸⁶ These decisions bridge the *lex generalis* of international law with the *lex spatialis* of space law contained in treaties, which reinforces the basic principle that space is not a law-free zone. It is important to recall that all 193 member states of the UN are signatories to the ICJ, and this means that in instances of conflict, the ICJ will most likely soon pronounce itself on matters regarding the use of space.

Building on this jurisprudence, several soft-law frameworks and expert manuals help interpret how existing rules apply to modern satellite operations and dual-use systems. Key among these are UN General Assembly resolutions calling for the prevention of an arms race in outer space⁸⁷ and the 2013

⁸⁰ United Nations. (1968). *Agreement on the Rescue of Astronauts, the Return of Astronauts, and the Return of Objects Launched into Outer Space* (Rescue Agreement). United Nations Treaty Series, vol. 672, p. 119.

⁸¹ United Nations. (1975). *Convention on Registration of Objects Launched into Outer Space* (Registration Convention). United Nations Treaty Series, 1023, 15. (Opened for signature January 14, 1975; entered into force September 15, 1976.)

⁸² United Nations. (1979). *Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Moon Agreement). United Nations Treaty Series, 1363, 3.(Adopted December 5, 1979; opened for signature December 18, 1979; entered into force July 11, 1984) ; It is important to note that only 18 states are signatories to this Agreement and in 2023, Saudi Arabia informed the Secretary General of the UN of its intention to withdraw from the agreement. See Wedenig, S.-M., & Nelson, J. W. (2023, January 26). *The Moon Agreement: Hanging by a thread?* McGill Institute of Air and Space Law. <https://www.mcgill.ca/iasl/article/moon-agreement-hanging-thread>.

⁸³ Article 11(2) of the Moon Agreement provides that: “*The Moon is not subject to national appropriation by any claim of sovereignty, by means of use or occupation, or by any other means*”.

⁸⁴ International Court of Justice. (1986). *Case Concerning Military and Paramilitary Activities in and against Nicaragua* (Nicaragua v. United States), ICJ Rep. 1986, p. 14.

⁸⁵ International Court of Justice. (1996). *Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons* (Advisory Opinion), ICJ Rep. 1996, p. 226.

⁸⁶ Pustorino, P. (2018, September 30). *The principle of non-intervention in recent non-international armed conflicts*. QIL – Questions of International Law / QDI. <https://www.qil-qdi.org/principle-non-intervention-recent-non-international-armed-conflicts/>.

⁸⁷ UN General Assembly. (2024, October 12). *Prevention of an arms race in outer space* (A/RES/79/19). United Nations. Also see the UN General Assembly. (2024, October 12). *Further practical measures for the prevention of an arms race in outer space* (A/RES/79/21). United Nations.

UN Group of Governmental Experts report on transparency and confidence-building measures in outer space activities.⁸⁸ This report, adopted by consensus, recommended actions such as sharing information on space policies, providing pre-launch notifications, conducting cooperative data exchanges, and allowing voluntary visits to space launch sites. Its goal was to reduce the risk of misunderstanding and mistrust among spacefaring nations by enhancing dialogue and promoting responsible behavior.

Finally, the United Nations Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (UNCOPUOS) has developed important *Long-term Sustainability Guidelines* (LTS) of outer space activities.⁸⁹ These guidelines encourage States to adopt national regulatory frameworks,⁹⁰ mitigate space debris, protect the space environment,⁹¹ share information on space objects, avoid harmful interference, and enhance cybersecurity and resilience of space infrastructure.⁹² They are directly relevant to dual-use satellites, whose dense integration into communications, navigation, and intelligence networks makes them particularly sensitive to both physical and cyber risks. The LTS Guidelines emphasise transparency, due regard, and responsible behaviour, which are core principles that help ensure that dual-use activities do not escalate geopolitical tensions or undermine the safety and sustainability of the shared orbital environment.

Complementing the space law regime is the Law of Armed Conflict (International Humanitarian Law (IHL)), which applies during international armed conflicts and brings the core principles of distinction, proportionality, and necessity to any military operation, including cyber operations that affect space systems. The principle of distinction, drawn from Additional Protocol I (AP I) to the Geneva Conventions,⁹³ requires parties to differentiate between civilian objects and military objectives. In reality, a dual-use satellite may become a military objective if its functions make an effective contribution to military action, as seen in the operational use of commercial satellites in the Ukraine conflict discussed above. Even so, any attack must satisfy the principle of proportionality, which prohibits operations where expected civilian harm would be excessive relative to the anticipated military advantage.⁹⁴ Cyber operations on space systems complicate this assessment, since non-kinetic effects such as data corruption or widespread service outages may not cause physical destruction but can still trigger significant civilian consequences. The principle of necessity further limits military operations to those required to achieve a legitimate military objective.⁹⁵ These rules, which are affirmed by the ICRC and reflected in the Tallinn Manual 2.0, apply to cyber operations during armed conflict, including those targeting space systems. However, they do not apply in peacetime, leaving cyber interference that falls below the UN Charter's "armed attack" threshold outside LOAC's governance.⁹⁶

⁸⁸ Group of Governmental Experts on Transparency and Confidence-Building Measures in Outer Space Activities. (2013). *Transparency & confidence-building measures in outer space activities* (Report to the Secretary-General, A/68/189). United Nations.

⁸⁹ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (2021). *Guidelines for the Long-Term Sustainability of Outer Space Activities of the Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space* (ST/SPACE/79). United Nations. https://www.unoosa.org/documents/pdf/PromotingSpaceSustainability/Publication_Final_English_June2021.pdf

⁹⁰ *Supra note* 89, Guideline A.1.

⁹¹ *Supra note* 89, Guideline B.3 & Guideline B.9

⁹² *Supra note* 89, Guideline C.1 & Guideline C.2

⁹³ International Committee of the Red Cross. (1977). *Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and relating to the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflicts (Protocol I)*, Article 48. 1125 U.N.T.S. 3. <https://ihl-databases.icrc.org/en/ihl-treaties/api-1977>.

⁹⁴ AP I, Art. 51.

⁹⁵ AP I, Art. 52(2).

⁹⁶ *Supra note* 73.

Upon proper analysis of this legal framework in its entirety in the context of cyber attacks on satellite systems, a legal grey zone becomes apparent. The blending of civilian and military functions in the use of satellites strains traditional classifications, since dual-use satellites remain permissible under the OST as long as they align with peaceful purposes as required by Article IV of the OST. However, they lose civilian protection under the law of armed conflict once they directly support military operations during an armed conflict. The Tallinn Manual adopts this same logic for cyber operations involving dual-use systems, requiring proportionality analyses that account for civilian reliance on those satellites. The problem is that neither the OST nor the law of armed conflict explicitly addresses cyber operations in space. The OST predates the digital era and focuses on physical activities, while the application of the law of armed conflict to non-kinetic cyber effects remains unsettled. As a result, cyber actions such as spoofing or signal manipulation may cause serious disruption of civilian life and essential services yet fall below the thresholds that would clearly trigger the law of armed conflict or self-defence under the UN Charter. This legal ambiguity creates opportunities for misuse, enabling States or private actors to exploit dual-use vulnerabilities, avoid clear attribution, and operate in a grey zone where accountability is difficult and interpretations of the law remain fluid.

5. IMPLICATIONS, ADEQUACY OF CURRENT NORMS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The dual-use nature of civilian satellites has many implications for the observance of international law, state security concerns and geopolitical tensions. Most of these implications are tied to the inadequacy of the existing laws and norms around the matter. This section will therefore partly focus on exploring those implications, initially, before then focusing on making recommendations to address any challenges.

Firstly, the dual-use nature of satellites significantly heightens escalation risks in cyber-enabled conflict. Because many commercial satellites provide essential military support functions such as communications and navigation, cyber operations against them present an opportunity for adversaries to degrade military capability without resorting to kinetic force.⁹⁷ Actions like jamming, spoofing, or malware insertion can temporarily neutralize military advantages while remaining below the threshold of an armed attack under Article 51 of the UN Charter.⁹⁸ This makes dual-use satellites attractive targets in armed conflicts, more so for countries having developed space capabilities to undertake these attacks. The financial and digital divide among nations exacerbates the issue. Advanced economies may possess the tools to detect, mitigate, and recover from cyber incidents, but many emerging space actors do not. This disparity makes some nations disproportionately vulnerable and, perhaps unintentionally, conduits for cyberattacks launched through compromised assets.⁹⁹ Here, the risk of miscalculation is substantial as states may perceive interference with critical satellites as preparations for broader hostilities, which narrows the window for diplomatic de-escalation.¹⁰⁰ As AI-enabled cyber capabilities spread, the speed and automation of attacks may further compress decision-making time and increase the prospect that a limited cyber intrusion is interpreted as the

⁹⁷ Goran Pavlović. (2025, May 24). *Cybersecurity in the context of international space agreements*. TheSIGN.media. Accessible via: <https://www.thesign.media/blog/cybersecurity-in-the-context-of-international-space-agreements>.

⁹⁸ Cornish, P. (Ed.) (2021), *supra* note 60.

⁹⁹ Pavlović. (2025, May 24), *supra* note 97.

¹⁰⁰ Comtech Telecommunications Corp. (2025, November 21). *Cybersecurity in the space domain: Why it's time to stop leaving the front door unlocked*. <https://www.comtech.com/general/2025/11/21/cybersecurity-in-the-space-domain-why-its-time-to-stop-leaving-the-front-door-unlocked/>.

opening move of a wider conflict, particularly given the close integration between commercial satellites and critical infrastructure on Earth.¹⁰¹ Similarly, a cyber operation that causes significant disruption to satellite capabilities may be interpreted as an unlawful use of force, or even an armed attack, depending on its scale and effects. The 2022 Viasat incident illustrated how cyber interference with a dual-use satellite system can produce simultaneous military and civilian impacts while provoking immediate countermeasures.¹⁰² Grey-zone operations are especially destabilizing because they are intentionally designed to fall short of clear thresholds. Yet misperceptions about the intent behind a cyber intrusion, especially in tense geopolitical environments, could trigger rapid escalation.¹⁰³ It has been argued that without clearer norms for satellite cyber operations, these dynamics weaken traditional deterrence models and leave States with few predictable tools for crisis management.¹⁰⁴

Secondly, persistent cyber vulnerabilities erode global confidence in commercial space services.¹⁰⁵ Public trust suffers when cyber incidents in the form of attacks cause spillover effects across essential civilian sectors, including finance, agriculture, transport, and emergency services. Even brief outages can produce huge economic losses in the billions, which raises questions about the reliability of private satellite operators.¹⁰⁶ As reliance on global satellite networks grows, States may choose to develop sovereign systems, for security concerns, which will have the impact of fragmenting the international market and weakening collaborative ventures such as environmental monitoring and global broadband initiatives. This trend towards fragmentation of the global satellite market will primarily be driven by national security concerns and the desire for assured access to vital communication and data services.

It is therefore important that targeted action is taken to address these challenges posed by the grey zone so as to limit the potential harms. This section will now turn to making policy and governance recommendations to achieve this.

Firstly, to mitigate the cybersecurity risks of dual-use satellites, establishing universal cybersecurity standards for space operations is critical to creating a resilient, equitable, and secure orbital ecosystem. For example, recent U.S. initiatives signal growing momentum for harmonized efforts to address the patchwork of existing frameworks, to avoid leaving commercial and international

¹⁰¹ Puscas, I. (2023). *AI and international security: Understanding the risks and paving the path for confidence-building measures* (pp. 41–45). United Nations Institute for Disarmament Research (UNIDIR). https://www.unidir.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/UNIDIR_AI-international-security_understanding_risks_paving_the_path_for_confidence-building_measures.pdf.

¹⁰² Mura, A. (2025), *supra* note 13.

¹⁰³ Pavlović. (2025, May 24), *supra* note 97.

¹⁰⁴ Global Commission on the Stability of Cyberspace. (n.d.). *GCSC norms*. The Hague Centre for Strategic Studies (HCSS). <https://hcss.nl/gcsc-norms/>.

¹⁰⁵ IndustrialCyber. (2024). *With space infrastructure at risk, experts call for cybersecurity-by-design, tight governance & supply-chain accountability*. IndustrialCyber. <https://industrialcyber.co/threat-landscape/with-space-infrastructure-at-risk-experts-call-for-cybersecurity-by-design-tight-governance-supply-chain-accountability/>.

¹⁰⁶ Bello, A.-W., Wonuola, I., Obunadike, C., Izundu, A., & Izundu, J. (2025). Assessing the impact of cybersecurity incidents on financial losses and user exposure in the global financial sector (2015–2024). *International Journal of Science and Research Archive*, 16, 489–504. <https://doi.org/10.30574/ijrsra.2025.16.1.2037>.

operators vulnerable.¹⁰⁷ Drawing from NIST's Cybersecurity Framework for space systems,¹⁰⁸ these standards should mandate scalable, risk-based measures such as regular third-party audits, AI-driven real-time threat detection, and quantum-resistant encryption to counter sophisticated threats like spoofing, ransomware, or signal jamming. Unlike terrestrial systems, satellites operate in a uniquely unforgiving environment, which then requires tailored protocols that account for limited onboard processing and long operational lifespans. In this regard, a tiered approach that starts with baseline requirements for critical functions like navigation, telemetry, and communications would accommodate diverse operators, from resource-constrained start-ups to emerging space nations in the Global South. First is the aspect of prioritizing secure-by-design principles for new satellites, which could be incentivized through insurance discounts or regulatory fast-tracking.¹⁰⁹ These satellite designs, which are built with security in mind, are very important in mitigating the harms of cyber intrusions in space activities of both states and private actors.

On the other hand, overly prescriptive rules risk stifling innovation or excluding smaller players, so standards should evolve through iterative feedback, piloted via public-private partnerships. To achieve this, international coordination is vital. In this regard, UNCOPUOS, building on its debris mitigation guidelines,¹¹⁰ is well-positioned to convene stakeholders and integrate cyber standards into existing space governance frameworks. This inclusive process would counter region-centric biases,¹¹¹ ensuring buy-in from Global South nations like Nigeria and those from the East like China and Russia, whose growing space programs demand equitable representation. To drive adoption, compliance could be tied to access to shared orbital resources or funding from multilateral space initiatives. This raises the security baseline across all operators, deterring attacks by increasing the cost and complexity for adversaries while fostering trust in commercial and international collaborations.

It is important to enhance transparency and confidence-building measures (TCBMs) among states. Bolstering this framework involves creating mechanisms for open communication that demystify intentions and reduce the paranoia fuelling escalation in space. Transparency and confidence-building measures are a set of tools designed to display, predict and discipline states' behaviour with respect to maintaining the security of space.¹¹² TCBMs, long used in arms control to build trust, could adapt to cyber threats through voluntary reporting of incidents, pre-notification of satellite maneuvers, or joint

¹⁰⁷ Trump, D. J. (2020). Memorandum on space policy directive-5—Cybersecurity principles for space systems. The White House. <https://trumpwhitehouse.archives.gov/presidential-actions/memorandum-space-policy-directive-5-cybersecurity-principles-space-systems/>.

¹⁰⁸ National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST). (2022). Satellite ground segment: Applying the cybersecurity framework to satellite command and control (NISTIR 8401). U.S. Department of Commerce. <https://csrc.nist.gov/pubs/ir/8401/final>.

¹⁰⁹ Ingols, K., et al. (2015). Guidelines for secure small satellite design and implementation. Lincoln Laboratory, Massachusetts Institute of Technology. <https://www.ll.mit.edu/sites/default/files/publication/doc/guidelines-secure-small-satellite-design-ingols-lsp-249.pdf>.

¹¹⁰ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (2021). *Guidelines for the long-term sustainability of outer space activities of the Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (ST/SPACE/79)*. United Nations. https://www.unoosa.org/documents/pdf/PromotingSpaceSustainability/Publication_Final_English_June2021.pdf

¹¹¹ Such as U.S. or EU-centric biases.

¹¹² Robinson, M. (2016). Transparency and confidence-building measures for space security. *Space Policy*, 37, 134.

exercises simulating cyber responses, as explored in analyses of space security measures.¹¹³ For instance, platforms for sharing threat data, similar to those in cyberspace CBMs could prevent misattributions, where a glitch could, for example, have been mistaken for an attack. This draws from UN Open-Ended Working Group on Security of and in the Use of Information and Communications Technologies discussions on responsible behaviours that emphasize transparency to deter malicious acts.¹¹⁴ The goal is to avoid the weaponisation of transparency in a tense geopolitical environment, whereby if one side shares too much, it might expose vulnerabilities. Therefore, any such measures should be reciprocal and phased, starting with low-stakes information like orbital parameters before advancing to cyber-specific disclosures. Bilateral agreements, like those between the U.S. and allies, also help to scale to multilateral forums, fostering a culture of openness that rebuilds global trust eroded by incidents like GPS spoofing in conflict zones.¹¹⁵ By integrating TCBMs, states can be able to mitigate potential escalation threats and turn potential adversaries into partners in safeguarding shared orbital commons.

Additionally, it is important to advance the international treaty and soft law mechanisms. This can be in the form of voluntary codes of conduct, targeted treaty amendments, or dedicated protocols that provide a dynamic pathway to modernize the 1967 Outer Space Treaty (OST) and laws of armed conflict for the cyber domain. This will help to address persistent interpretive gaps that adversaries exploit. A pivotal starting point is a global code of conduct for space cyber operations. This can be modelled on the Hague Code of Conduct against Ballistic Missile Proliferation, which is a 2002 voluntary, politically binding international agreement with over 140 subscribing states aimed at preventing the spread of, and curbing the development, testing, and deployment of, Weapons of Mass Destruction-capable ballistic missiles.¹¹⁶ This Code of Conduct mandates transparency measures among subscribing states, such as pre-launch notifications and annual policy declarations in Section 4(a) iii of the Code. A similar code for cybersecurity in space could mandate real-time reporting of cyber incidents, prohibitions on targeting civilian satellite functions, and mandatory cooperation on attribution to deter deniability. This soft instrument would prioritize consensus-building on foundational terminology and classifications, such as defining non-kinetic attacks, e.g., jamming, spoofing, or malware injection, as equivalent to armed attacks under Article 51 of the UN Charter when they cause physical damage, disrupt critical infrastructure, or scale to coercive effects. This would then help in clarifying when it is right to trigger self-defence rights.¹¹⁷ The other instrument that could offer guidance in building such a code is the Tallinn Manual 2.0.¹¹⁸ The clarifications drawn from this framework for cyber operations would resolve ambiguities in the peaceful purposes clause in Article IV of the OST. This will prevent escalatory miscalculations, like those in the 2022 Viasat

¹¹³ United Nations Office for Disarmament Affairs. (2022). *TCBMs for a sustainable outer space* (Speaker notes, 7 June 2018), <https://documents.unoda.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/180607-TCBMs-CD-Raji-Speaker-Notes.pdf>.

¹¹⁴ See generally, Open-Ended Working Group on Security of and in the Use of Information and Communications Technologies (OEWG). (2024). *How information sharing contributes to security and stability in cyberspace: Examples from regional Points of Contact networks* [Working paper]. United Nations Office for Disarmament Affairs. https://docs-library.unoda.org/Open-Ended_Working_Group_on_Information_and_Communications_Technologies_-_2021/Final_28112024_-_Confidence_Builders_Info_Sharing.pdf.

¹¹⁵ Robinson, M. (2016), *supra note* 112.

¹¹⁶ United Nations General Assembly. (2005). *The Hague Code of Conduct against Ballistic Missile Proliferation*. A/RES/60/62.

¹¹⁷ Lewis, P. (2019). Create a global code of conduct for outer space. *Chatham House*. <https://www.chathamhouse.org/2019/06/create-global-code-conduct-outer-space>.

¹¹⁸ Schmitt, M. N. (2017). *Tallinn Manual 2.0 on the International Law Applicable to Cyber Operations* (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.

cyberattack.¹¹⁹ These mechanisms not only fill voids in the outdated frameworks but also cultivate a normative ecosystem that reduces misperception risks, fosters verifiable restraint, and positions space as a shared sanctuary rather than a contested battlefield.

6. CONCLUSION

The cybersecurity perils and legal implications of dual-use satellites in armed conflicts have been examined in this research. It has highlighted the inherent vulnerabilities arising from the integration of civilian space infrastructure into military operations, the challenges of attribution in cyber incidents, and the critical need to uphold principles of distinction, proportionality, and necessity under international humanitarian law. The analysis has also explored the strategic incentives for adversaries to exploit non-kinetic attacks, fuelled by the inadequacies of existing frameworks like the Outer Space Treaty and the Law of Armed Conflict in addressing cyber-specific threats. By incorporating these underexplored dimensions of the international legal regime, the research aims to contribute to the evolution of norms governing dual-use technologies, promoting equitable access to space while preserving strategic stability and protecting civilian functions.

As discussed, the orbital domain continues to become increasingly congested and contested every other day. However, the cyber risks to dual-use satellites remain a pressing concern that not only renders traditional boundaries ineffective but also tests the resilience of the current international legal systems on space. Ambiguity around the norms characterizing space cyber operations complicates determinations of whether non-kinetic disruptions such as spoofing, jamming, or malware injection qualify as armed attacks under Article 51 of the UN Charter or even whether they are violations of the OST's peaceful purposes clause in Article VI. This represents a significant lacuna in the legal architecture of the existing treaties, which are mainly foundational and do not address the emerging threats like AI-orchestrated attacks. This leaves room for miscalculation that could escalate into terrestrial disruptions with grave effects on navigation, finance, and disaster response.

The UNCOPOUS guidelines are some of the international efforts that attempt to address these vulnerabilities. However, a comprehensive response has proven elusive amid the rapid evolution of space technologies and the fragmentation of governance across state and non-state actors. There is promise in a new international convention dedicated to space cybersecurity, modelled perhaps on the Hague Code of Conduct, to foster consensus on definitions, prohibit targeting of civilian satellite functions, and mandate cooperation on attribution and resilience. This framework could be transparent, inclusive, and adaptable, facilitating multilateral collaboration, criminalizing grey-zone acts, and establishing enforcement mechanisms through arbitration or UN referrals. Such a convention would mark a pivotal advancement in securing the orbital commons as a domain for peaceful exploration. Therefore, it is imperative to re-evaluate and adapt the existing legal infrastructure or explore the creation of a specialized international body to effectively confront the unique challenges of dual-use satellites in cyber-enabled warfare.

¹¹⁹ Roscini, M. (2024). Law in orbit: International legal perspectives on cyberattacks targeting space systems. *Marine Policy*, 163, Article 105696. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0308596124000363>.

© The Author(s) 2026. Published by Space Court Foundation. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted reuse, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

THE LAWS OF HEAVEN: LOAC AND THE FINAL FRONTIER

HALEY FULLER¹

ABSTRACT

Outer space has evolved from a frontier of exploration into a theater of strategic competition. While military reliance on orbital systems has deepened, the legal frameworks governing armed conflict beyond Earth remain uncertain. The 1967 Outer Space Treaty prohibits the placement of weapons of mass destruction but is silent on conventional or dual-use military activity, leaving states to interpret “peaceful purposes” according to their strategic interests. This ambiguity has opened a normative gap now partially filled by the Law of Armed Conflict (LOAC). Yet LOAC’s terrestrial doctrines – distinction, proportionality, necessity, and humanity – were not developed with the physics or politics of orbit in mind. Dual-use satellites, cascading debris, attribution challenges, and the opacity of space operations render their application indeterminate and easily manipulated.

This paper examines how LOAC principles might be operationalized in the space domain and identifies where doctrinal assumptions collapse under orbital realities. It argues that the absence of technical standards, verification mechanisms, and institutional coordination risks transforming LOAC from a framework of restraint into one of rhetorical compliance. Drawing on emerging initiatives such as the Combined Space Operations Initiative and the EU Space Surveillance and Tracking program, the analysis explores pathways to translate humanitarian norms into actionable practice through transparency, shared data, and standardized operational protocols. Without such adaptation, the law will continue to trail strategy, and the heavens – once imagined as the realm of peace – may become the next venue where silence, not law, defines the limits of war.

KEYWORDS: Outer Space Treaty, Law of Armed Conflict, Space Security, Militarization of Space, International Humanitarian Law.

¹ Haley Fuller, Tulane Law '25, and military.com author, hfuller1@tulane.edu.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the decades since the launch of Sputnik 1, outer space has evolved from a symbolic frontier of ideological competition into a domain of concrete strategic significance.² Even prior to Sputnik, high-altitude missile tests, near-space scientific research, and military rocketry had pushed the boundaries of human interaction with the space environment and begun to blur the boundary between exploration and defense. The placement of an object in sustained orbit transformed the stakes of space activity from a scientific experiment to a strategic enterprise, prompting both international legal responses and a sustained trajectory of technological development, which has only accelerated in the years since.³

This transformation, which began as a scientific pursuit and hardened into strategic competition, carries echoes of Milton's *Paradise Lost*, where ambition, once directed toward creation, turns into outward expansion. The celestial domain, once emblematic of transcendence and exploration, now risks becoming a venue for sovereign assertion, tactical ambiguity, and strategic denial. As with Milton's Satan, there is a danger of space power becoming a means of domination refined through detachment rather than enlightenment. Power in space may come to reflect human ingenuity unmoored from restraint.⁴

Outer space reflects structural dynamics long analyzed in international relations scholarship under the concept of the security dilemma. In an anarchic international system lacking centralized authority, states rely on self-help to preserve security. The same measures adopted to enhance security may be interpreted by competitors as threatening even when undertaken for defensive purposes. The dilemma becomes more acute where offensive and defensive capabilities are difficult to distinguish and where vulnerability creates incentives for anticipatory action.⁵ Both conditions are increasingly present in the orbital domain. Many space systems are dual-use, and the strategic implications of operations are often difficult to assess from external observation. Space assets are also difficult to defend once deployed, and the perceived fragility of critical satellites can compress decision time in crisis conditions. Capabilities developed to enhance resilience, or deterrence may therefore appear indistinguishable from preparations for counterspace dominance, intensifying reciprocal suspicion.⁶ In such an environment, legal ambiguity does not operate in isolation; it interacts with structural mistrust in ways that can magnify escalation pressures. The application of LOAC in space must therefore be understood not only as a matter of formal doctrinal extension, but as an effort to mitigate instability generated by capability ambiguity and strategic interdependence.⁷

² Eisenhower Presidential Library, National Archives and Records Administration. (2017). *Reaction to Sputnik: A documentary record* (Comp.) [Documentary record noting Eisenhower's shift from viewing Sputnik as a scientific event to recognizing its strategic and psychological implications].

<https://www.eisenhowerlibrary.gov/sites/default/files/research/online-documents/sputnik/reaction.pdf>

³ Fraser, L. W. (1985). *High altitude research at the Applied Physics Laboratory. Johns Hopkins APL Technical Digest*, 6(1), 92 [detailing early American high-altitude rocket experiments and atmospheric research programs that predated the launch of Sputnik I]. <https://secwww.jhuapl.edu/techdigest/content/techdigest/pdf/V06-N01/06-01-Fraser.pdf>; United Nations Office for Disarmament Affairs. (n.d.). *Outer space* [explaining that Cold War concerns following Sputnik I prompted international efforts to prevent the weaponization of space, culminating in treaty frameworks such as the 1967 Outer Space Treaty and subsequent disarmament initiatives].

<https://disarmament.unoda.org/en/our-work/emerging-challenges/outer-space>.

⁴ Milton, J. (1667). *Paradise Lost* (Book II, lines 376–378) [Beelzebub warning that to “sit in darkness ... hatching vain empires” is futile, a metaphor for ambition unmoored from divine or moral order].

⁵ Herz, J. H. (1950). Idealist internationalism and the security dilemma. *World Politics*, 2(2), 157–180.

<https://doi.org/10.2307/2009187>.

⁶ Townsend, B. (2020). Strategic choice and the orbital security dilemma. *Space & Defense*, 14(1), 64–90.

https://www.airuniversity.af.edu/Portals/10/SSO/documents/Volume-14_Issue-1/Townsend.pdf.

⁷ Herz, *supra* note 4 at 157; Jervis, R. (1978). Cooperation under the security dilemma. *World Politics*, 30(2), 167–214. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2009958>.

Today, the battlefield is increasingly supplemented – if not outright dependent at times – on space-based infrastructure. Satellites enable surveillance, communications, precise targeting, and navigation.⁸ Space assets are now integral to the planning, execution, and sustainment of terrestrial combat. This evolution also introduces the potential for armed conflict to extend into, or even originate from, outer space. While military and broader human reliance on space has grown, the corresponding legal frameworks governing the conduct of hostilities in this domain remain ambiguous, underdeveloped, and ill-suited to the technological and strategic conditions emerging. As with the early days of air power, law once again trails innovation, grasping at norms in an arena where the rules have yet to solidify.⁹

The 1967 Outer Space Treaty (OST) was negotiated in the shadow of nuclear brinkmanship. Its drafters sought to preclude the most destabilizing scenarios of Cold War-era competition by prohibiting the placement of nuclear weapons and other weapons of mass destruction (WMDs) in orbit and on celestial bodies.¹⁰ The OST is silent on the deployment or use of conventional weapons in space and offers only vague commitments to the “peaceful uses” of the domain.¹¹ In the absence of a clear ban on military activity, states have increasingly interpreted the OST to allow, if not absolutely endorse, a wide range of military uses of space, provided those uses do not involve prohibited weapon types, establishment of military bases in space, or maneuvering on celestial bodies.¹²

The limits of the OST and permissive interpretations that have followed have prompted growing interest in whether and to what extent the Law of Armed Conflict (LOAC) – a body of law traditionally tethered to the land, sea, and air – applies to outer space. LOAC, which encompasses both treaty law and customary principles regulating the means and methods of warfare, is often used interchangeably with International Humanitarian Law (IHL), though the two are not perfectly synonymous.¹³ LOAC is used here in its broader sense, encompassing both the humanitarian protections codified in the Geneva

⁸ U.S. Department of Defense. (2020, June). *Defense space strategy summary* [Describes the United States’ growing dependence on space-based assets for surveillance, communications, navigation, and targeting, and frames space as a distinct warfighting domain critical to modern military operations].

https://media.defense.gov/2020/Jun/17/2002317391/-1/-1/1/2020_defense_space_strategy_summary.pdf.

⁹ Sand, P. H., de Sousa Freitas, J., & Pratt, G. N. (1963). *An historical survey of international air law before the Second World War*. *McGill Law Journal*, 9, 24 [Traces how early international air law evolved slowly in response to rapid technological advances in aviation, with legal norms often formalized only after innovations in flight and navigation had already transformed state practice]. <https://lawjournal.mcgill.ca/wp-content/uploads/pdf/6355045-sand.pdf>.

¹⁰ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (1967). *Treaty on principles governing the activities of states in the exploration and use of outer space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies (Outer Space Treaty)* [Establishes the foundational legal framework for international space law, emphasizing the peaceful use of outer space and prohibiting national appropriation]. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/outerspacetreaty.html>.

¹¹ Vestner, T. (2020). *Prevention of an arms race in outer space: Multilateral negotiations’ effects on international law*. *Moscow Journal of International Law*, (2), 6 [Observes that the Outer Space Treaty prohibits weapons of mass destruction but remains silent on the deployment of conventional arms, leaving significant regulatory gaps]. <https://doi.org/10.24833/0869-0049-2020-2-6-21>.

¹² NATO. (2019, November 19). *Press conference by NATO Secretary General Jens Stoltenberg ahead of the meetings of NATO ministers of foreign affairs* [Emphasizes that NATO’s recognition of space as an operational domain aligns with the Outer Space Treaty, which allows a broad range of military uses provided they exclude prohibited weapon types, the establishment of military bases, or maneuvers on celestial bodies]. https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/opinions_170972.htm.

¹³ International Committee of the Red Cross. (2004, July). *What is international humanitarian law?* [Defines international humanitarian law as the body of rules limiting the effects of armed conflict for humanitarian reasons and notes that it is sometimes referred to as the law of armed conflict]. https://www.icrc.org/sites/default/files/document/file_list/what-is-ihl-factsheet.pdf.

Conventions and the Hague-based rules governing the conduct of hostilities. IHL emphasizes the humanitarian protections codified in the Geneva Conventions.¹⁴ Because space operations raise questions of targeting, force regulation, and weapons use rather than detention or occupation, LOAC provides the more appropriate framework for assessing the legal challenges of armed conflict in orbit.

Applying LOAC to a domain known for physical remoteness, technical density, and pervasive dual-use infrastructure generates complex legal and operational questions. Can belligerents distinguish between military and civilian space objects when both share orbits, control centers, and even functions? Can proportionality be measured when the loss of a single satellite could disrupt communications for entire continents? What counts as a lawful military objective in space? To what extent can private space or technology companies be regarded as participants in armed conflict?

LOAC remains formally applicable to space conflict, but technical ambiguity and normative uncertainty severely limit its practical force. The dual-use nature of most space infrastructure, the difficulty of attribution in hostile acts, and the lack of reliable verification mechanisms all frustrate efforts to enforce LOAC in the orbital domain. Doctrinal analysis, patterns in state behavior, and the rapid development of military capabilities in orbit together point toward the need for a refined framework of LOAC suited to the realities of space warfare. As infrastructure critical to both military operations and civilian life continues its migration into orbit, the absence of a coherent legal regime heightens the risk of destabilizing escalation. Without meaningful legal constraint, space may emerge not only as the domain of strategic competition, but as a volatile and unforgiving theatre of war.

This paper argues that although LOAC formally applies to outer space, its effective operation in that domain is constrained by structural features of space systems, including dual-use infrastructure, attribution opacity, and cascading systemic risk. Section 2 establishes the formal applicability of LOAC to space operations and analyzes how its core principles of distinction, proportionality, necessity, and humanity function in the orbital context. Section 3 examines the operational challenges of implementing those principles in practice, including attribution, targeting doctrine, and transparency mechanisms. Section 4 identifies structural gaps in definition, private participation, force projection, and institutional enforcement that limit LOAC's constraining force in space. The conclusion considers the implications of these gaps and argues that doctrinal clarification and institutional adaptation are necessary if LOAC is to operate as a meaningful constraint in orbit.

2. THE FORMAL APPLICABILITY OF THE LAW OF ARMED CONFLICT IN OUTER SPACE

The legal architecture governing outer space is anchored in five primary United Nations treaties: the Outer Space Treaty (OST), the Rescue Agreement, the Liability Convention, the Registration Convention, and the Moon Treaty. Of these, the OST stands as the central instrument for regulating exploration, scientific use, and national security activity in orbit.¹⁵ It functions as a “quasi-constitution for space,” shaping both operational practice and normative interpretation of state conduct. Article III extends the reach of international law into outer space, meaning international humanitarian law (IHL) and, by

¹⁴ Kolb, R. (2022, March 14). *Of Hague law and Geneva law*. Lieber Institute. [Explains that the “Geneva” tradition centers on humanitarian protections for persons affected by conflict, while the “Hague” tradition regulates the means and methods of warfare]. <https://lieber.westpoint.edu/of-hague-law-geneva-law/>.

¹⁵ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (n.d.). *Space law treaties and principles: The five United Nations treaties relating to outer space* [Lists the Outer Space Treaty, the Rescue Agreement, the Liability Convention, the Registration Convention, and the Moon Treaty as the five primary United Nations treaties governing outer space]. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties.html>.

extension, LOAC apply when states employ force beyond the atmosphere.¹⁶ Still, the Oslo Manual on Select Topics on the Law of Armed Conflict notes “in the absence of sufficient state practice and *opinio iuris*” the application or interpretation of LOAC in outer space may be subject to controversy.” This uncertainty underscores the need to examine how LOAC’s foundational principles map onto a domain defined by technical opacity, dual-use infrastructure, and strategic ambiguity.¹⁷

LOAC governs the conduct of hostilities in all environments where armed conflict occurs. Its applicability turns not on geography but on the existence of an armed conflict and the status of the actors involved. The traditional domains of land, sea, and air have long accommodated LOAC’s core principles of distinction, proportionality, necessity, and humanity.¹⁸ Outer space, though novel in its physical properties and operational constraints, does not fall outside LOAC’s reach. Wherever states engage in hostile acts meeting the threshold of armed conflict, LOAC can apply.¹⁹

The concept of armed conflict is not limited to the use of conventional weapons. The law recognizes a broad functional definition of “arms,” encompassing not only kinetic munitions but also non-traditional means capable of producing military effects, such as cyber tools, electromagnetic interference, or space-based systems that cause disruption or disablement.²⁰ In the orbital context, this opens the door to classifying actions like jamming satellite communications, dazzling sensors with directed energy, or conducting cyber operations via satellite as the use of arms.²¹ Though these activities may lack explosive force, their capacity to affect the course of hostilities may still bring them within LOAC’s regulatory scope. Determining whether such acts qualify as the use of force – and whether they rise to the threshold of armed conflict – depends not on the form but on effect.²²

¹⁶ See Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 7, art. III.

¹⁷ Dinstein, Y., & Dahl, A. W. (Eds.). (2020). *Oslo manual on select topics of the law of armed conflict* (p. 5). International Society for Military Law and the Law of War. https://library.oxopen.org/bitstream/id/7065a5e9-c8a8-4cc7-a7f9-7f8f4fadd056/2020_Book_OsloManualOnSelectTopicsOfTheL.pdf.

¹⁸ U.S. Department of Defense. (2023, July). *Law of war manual* (§§ 1.1–1.4, pp. 7–16) [Defines the law of armed conflict, describes its humanitarian and operational purposes, and explains that it governs armed conflict broadly, without limitation to a specific geographic area or domain]. <https://media.defense.gov/2023/Jul/31/2003271432/-1/-1/0/DOD-LAW-OF-WAR%09MANUAL-JUNE-2015-UPDATED-JULY%202023.PDF>.

¹⁹ Goh Escolar, G. (2019, September 23). *The law of armed conflict in a domain for peaceful purposes* [Paper presented at the UN/Turkey/APSCO Conference on Space Law & Policy, Istanbul, Turkey; argues that the law of armed conflict applies in outer space where hostile acts are undertaken, even within a domain established for peaceful purposes]. https://www.unoosa.org/documents/pdf/spacelaw/activities/2019/T1-4-GGE_The_Law_of_Armed_Conflict_in_a_Domain_for_Peaceful_Purposes.pdf.

²⁰ Mercado, H. (2025, March). *Using the force against rebel scum: The application of international humanitarian law in outer space against non-state actors*. *Harvard National Security Journal*, 12–18 [Argues that non-kinetic operations—such as cyber-attacks or space-based systems causing disablement—can fall within the definition of “attack” under IHL and thus trigger LOAC obligations]. <https://journals.law.harvard.edu/nsj/2025/03/using-the-force-against-rebel-scum-the-application-of-international-humanitarian-law-in-outer-space-against-non-state-actors/>.

²¹ Tepper, E. (2022, May). *The first space-cyber war and the need for new regimes* (CIGI Policy Brief No. 173) [Examines how non-kinetic attacks on space infrastructure – such as jamming, spoofing, and cyber disruption – may constitute a use of force, challenging existing legal frameworks under international law]. https://www.cigionline.org/static/documents/PB_no.173_uPqYILM.pdf.

²² Schmitt, M. N. (Ed.). (2017). *Tallinn manual 2.0 on the international law applicable to cyber operations* (Rules 10–11, pp. 42–52). Cambridge University Press. [Explains that cyber operations may constitute a use of force under international law when their scale and effects resemble those of kinetic force, and lists factors relevant to that determination]. <https://www.onlinelibrary.ihl.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/2017-Tallinn-Manual-2.0.pdf>.

The authority for LOAC's extension into space rests on both legal logic and normative continuity. First, LOAC's foundational treaties – the Hague Regulations, the Geneva Conventions, and their Additional Protocols – contain no territorial limitation. They apply to the conduct of hostilities wherever they occur.²³ The principle of universality reflects a deeper normative commitment: war, regardless of how it is geographically or technologically transformed, remains subject to law.²⁴

Second, the UN Charter reinforces this continuity. Article 2(4) prohibits the threat or use of force against the territorial integrity or political independence of any state.²⁵ Article 51 preserves the right of self-defense in response to an armed attack.²⁶ Neither provision distinguishes between terrestrial and space-based acts.²⁷ An attack launched via satellite or intended to damage a satellite, whether kinetic or cyber, may still trigger *ius ad bellum* and activate LOAC obligations.²⁸ In this sense, space functions as an additional arena where existing norms may operate rather than a legal vacuum.

Third, the Martens Clause, first formulated in the preamble to the 1899 Hague Convention II, supports LOAC's relevance in new domains. The Martens Clause has been reaffirmed in successive treaties and is regarded as a cornerstone of customary law. It insists that in cases not covered by specific treaties, civilians and combatants remain under the protection of the principles of humanity and the dictates of public conscience.²⁹ The Clause's enduring function is to prevent nullity in the face of innovation. Space activates the Clause's normative force precisely because of its novelty.³⁰

Despite this formal applicability, outer space introduces operational conditions straining LOAC's implementation. Distinction depends on the ability to differentiate lawful military objectives from

²³ International Committee of the Red Cross. (2000). *Universal jurisdiction over war crimes* [Explains that the Geneva Conventions apply to all armed conflicts, regardless of geographic location]. https://www.icrc.org/sites/default/files/document/file_list/universal-jurisdiction-icrc-eng.pdf; Kolb, *supra* note 11 (noting the Hague and Geneva traditions regulate the conduct of hostilities functionally, not territorially).

²⁴ See ICRC, *Universal Jurisdiction Over War Crimes*, *supra* note 20.

²⁵ United Nations. (1945). *Charter of the United Nations*, art. 2(4) [States that “All Members shall refrain in their international relations from the threat or use of force against the territorial integrity or political independence of any State, or in any other manner inconsistent with the Purposes of the United Nations”]. <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/un-charter/full-text>.

²⁶ *Id.* art. 51 (preserving the inherent right of self-defense if an armed attack occurs).

²⁷ *Id.* arts. 2(4), 51.

²⁸ O'Meara, C. (2024). *Anti-satellite weapons and self-defence: Law and limitations*. In C. Kwan et al. (Eds.), *CyCon 2024: Over the horizon – 16th International Conference on Cyber Conflict* (p. 249). NATO CCDCOE. [Argues that both kinetic and non-kinetic attacks on or via satellites may constitute armed attacks under *jus ad bellum*, thus potentially triggering a state's right of self-defence and the applicability of LOAC]. https://ccdcoe.org/uploads/2024/05/CyCon_2024_OMeara-1.pdf.

²⁹ *Hague Convention (II) with Respect to the Laws and Customs of War on Land (with Annexed Regulations)*. (1899, July 29). Preamble, 32 Stat. 1803, 1 Bevans 247, Doc. No. 28, at 61 [Declares that “populations and belligerents remain under the protection ... of the principles of international law ... from the laws of humanity and the requirements of the public conscience”]. <https://digital-commons.usnwc.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1902&context=ils>.

³⁰ Jorgensen, C. (2025). “Old” law for a “new” frontier: The sufficiency of international humanitarian law in outer space. *Case Western Reserve Journal of International Law*, 57, 343, 357 [Explains that even in the absence of treaties prohibiting particular space weapons or tactics, the Martens Clause ensures that civilians and combatants remain protected under the principles of humanity and public conscience, thereby preventing outer space from becoming a legally unregulated domain]. <https://scholarlycommons.law.case.edu/jil/vol57/iss1/11>.

protected civilian objects.³¹ In orbit, where assets are dual-use, anonymized, and widely dispersed, such distinctions may prove impossible to verify.³² Proportionality demands a weighing of anticipated military advantage against expected civilian harm, but the cascading effects of satellite loss on communications, navigation, and civilian safety make that calculus speculative at best.³³ Attribution remains a persistent challenge, and hostile acts in space often occur without immediate visibility, leaving states to contemplate on the source, intent, and lawfulness of a given event.³⁴ The principle of military necessity – permitting only those actions indispensable to achieving legitimate military objectives – collides with the principle of humanity, which restrains such actions through the imperative to minimize suffering and protect human dignity. In a domain characterized by automation and remoteness, both principles are strained: necessity’s justifications blur, and humanity’s restraints risk abstraction.³⁵

Thus, while LOAC applies to space as a matter of law, its application requires a tailored analysis. States must clarify how traditional principles map onto orbital realities, and the international community must resist the temptation to treat space as *sui generis* in a way eroding legal discipline.³⁶ The following sections examine how LOAC’s central principles – distinction, proportionality, necessity, and humanity – operate in space and what interpretive adjustments are needed to ensure the law continues to govern, even above the atmosphere.

2.1. Distinction in the Orbital Theatre

Distinction remains the cornerstone of LOAC. It requires parties to an armed conflict to distinguish at all times between combatants and civilians, and between military objectives and civilian objects, directing operations only against the former.³⁷ In terrestrial conflict, this principle relies on a series of observable,

³¹ *Id.* at 346-49 (observing that while LOAC formally applies to outer space, the operational realities of that domain strain its implementation, as the principle of distinction depends on the ability to differentiate lawful military objectives from protected civilian objects).

³² Azcárate Ortega, A. (2023, June 5). *Not a rose by any other name: Dual-use and dual-purpose space systems. Lawfare.* [Notes that many space systems are dual use, operated by civilian or commercial actors even when performing military functions, which blurs lines between civilian and military objects]. <https://www.lawfaremedia.org/article/not-a-rose-by-any-other-name-dual-use-and-dual-purpose-space-systems>.

³³ Mallon, C. (2023). *Anti-satellite weapons and the law of armed conflict. Syracuse Journal of International Law and Commerce*, 50, 318, 329–331 [Explains that the proportionality principle is difficult to apply in outer space because the destruction of satellites can trigger cascading effects on civilian communication, navigation, and safety systems, rendering the harm–advantage calculus inherently speculative]. <https://jilc.syr.edu/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/502-Anti-Sat-Weapons-LOAC.pdf>.

³⁴ von der Dunk, F. G. (2024, July 26). *Space privateers or space pirates? Armed conflict, outer space & attribution of non-state activities. Lieber Institute, West Point.* [Explains Article VI of the OST equates private activities with state activities for purposes of international responsibility, requiring states to authorize and continuously supervise nongovernmental space operations; notes that the provision emerged as a U.S.-Soviet compromise ensuring that all national activities in outer space are attributable to states regardless of direct state involvement]. <https://lieber.westpoint.edu/space-privateers-pirates-outer-space-attribution-non-state-activities>.

³⁵ See DoD Law of War Manual, *supra* note 15, §§ 2.2-2.4, at 53-60 (explaining military necessity permits only measures indispensable to achieve legitimate military objectives, while humanity restrains such measures through the prohibition of unnecessary suffering and the requirement to respect human dignity).

³⁶ See Jorgensen, *supra* note 24 (arguing that while outer space presents novel challenges, it is not so exceptional as to justify disregarding established principles of international humanitarian law).

³⁷ *Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and Relating to the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflicts (Protocol I)*, art. 48, June 8, 1977, 1125 U.N.T.S. 3, 25 [Establishes the basic rule of distinction, requiring parties to an armed conflict to distinguish at all times between civilian populations and combatants, and between civilian objects and military objectives]. <https://treaties.un.org/doc/publication/unts/volume%201125/volume-1125-i-17512-english.pdf>.

verifiable criteria, including factors like uniforms, emblems, physical separation, and functional use.³⁸ In space, these criteria fail. Satellites do not wear uniforms and sometimes do not bear visible markings. Their functions are often classified, encrypted, ambiguous, or interchangeable. The result is a battlespace where appearances are deceptive, and presumption is perilous.³⁹

The prevalence of dual-use infrastructure further complicates the picture. A single satellite may transmit military communications and commercial data, or support both battlefield navigation and civilian air traffic control.⁴⁰ Under traditional LOAC doctrine, an object qualifies as a military objective if, by its nature, location, or use, it makes an effective contribution to military action and its destruction offers a definite military advantage. In the orbital environment, this test becomes precarious.⁴¹ Most satellites meet this definition by virtue of their integrated role in national command-and-control systems, but their civilian overlays render them simultaneously protected and targetable. The legal consequence is a tension not easily resolved; the very integration making a satellite valuable also complicates its status under the law.

Technological convergence adds another layer of ambiguity. Co-location of military and civilian assets in similar orbital bands makes targeting decisions vulnerable to error. Attribution challenges compound the problem. Unlike a tank, a satellite's military utility cannot be verified visually. Ground-based observers cannot always determine whether a satellite is transmitting targeting data, weather information, or both.⁴²

Furthermore, attacks in space need not be kinetic. Non-destructive methods such as jamming, spoofing, or dazzling may temporarily disable a system without causing physical harm.⁴³ Whether such conduct qualifies as the use of arms is no longer seriously contested. These techniques function as tools of warfare.⁴⁴ Yet whether they qualify as "attacks" under LOAC, and therefore implicate the principle of distinction, remains unsettled.⁴⁵ Some states argue reversible interference falls outside the scope of LOAC

³⁸ Blank, L. R. (2022, March 4). *Combatant privileges and protections*. Lieber Institute, West Point. [Explains that the uniform or other fixed distinctive sign is a fundamental aspect of combatant status and essential to implementing the principle of distinction, which depends on observable and verifiable criteria – such as uniforms, emblems, and physical separation – to differentiate lawful combatants from civilians]. <https://lieber.westpoint.edu/combatant-privileges-and-protections/>.

³⁹ Delle Fave, D. (2023, April 14). *The challenges of dual-use space technologies: The non-peaceful use of satellites*. Space Generation. [Observes that many satellites have overlapping civilian and military functions—such as ISR, meteorology, and communications – and that commercial systems can be repurposed for defense use, making functional distinctions ambiguous]. <https://spacegeneration.org/the-challenges-of-dual-use-space-technologies-the-non-peaceful-use-of-satellites>.

⁴⁰ *Id.*

⁴¹ Protocol I, *supra* note 34, art. 52(2) (defining military objectives as objects which by their nature, location, purpose, or use make an effective contribution to military action, and whose destruction offers a definite military advantage), <https://spacegeneration.org/the-challenges-of-dual-use-space-technologies-the-non-peaceful-use-of-satellites>.

⁴² Zuo, Y., et al. (2023, December 3). *Integrating communication, sensing and computing in satellite Internet of Things: Challenges and opportunities*. arXiv. [Discusses how modern satellite systems increasingly combine communication, sensing, and computing functionalities on a single platform, thereby blurring functional boundaries]. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2312.01336>.

⁴³ Way, T. (2019, October 28; updated 2022, June 14). *Counterspace weapons 101*. Center for Strategic & International Studies, Aerospace Security Project. [Providing an overview of non-kinetic counterspace capabilities, including jamming, spoofing, and directed-energy attacks such as dazzling, that can disrupt or disable satellites without causing physical destruction]. <https://aerospace.csis.org/aerospace101/counterspace-weapons-101>.

⁴⁴ *Id.*

⁴⁵ Casey-Maslen, S. (2010, October). *International law and the use of non-kinetic energy weapons (NKE weapons): A preliminary assessment under international humanitarian law and international human rights law*. Geneva

constraints, while others emphasize effects over method. The lack of consensus creates legal uncertainty and invites opportunism.⁴⁶

To preserve the integrity of distinction in the space domain, states must move beyond abstract affirmation and translate it into operational doctrine. This requires establishing technical and procedural mechanisms capable of differentiating between military and civilian satellites, which is a task far more complex than its terrestrial analogue. The degree of overlap between civilian and military systems underscores the erosion of clear functional boundaries. The U.S. military now relies on commercial, dual-use satellites for the vast majority of its communications, revealing how deeply national security is intertwined with ostensibly civilian networks.⁴⁷ Current identification methods, such as the United Nations Register of Objects Launched into Outer Space and the U.S. Space Commands cataloging system, provide basic orbital data but offer little insight into functional purpose or control authority.⁴⁸ Without standardized criteria for classification and labeling, dual-use satellites remain indistinguishable to observers, making lawful targeting nearly impossible.

A credible approach would include enhanced registration regimes requiring the disclosure of not only orbital parameters, but also core mission categories, operator status, and interlinking capabilities that reveal potential military functions.⁴⁹ Functional transparency measures, such as the use of visible identifiers, coded transmissions, or voluntary notifications of maneuver and proximity operations, could further strengthen verifiability and confidence among spacefaring nations. In parallel, shared situational awareness mechanisms, for example, multilateral data exchanges or cooperative monitoring platforms – would allow states to corroborate activity in real time and reduce the risk of misattribution or mistaken targeting.⁵⁰

Academy of International Humanitarian Law and Human Rights. [Analyzes how directed energy, electrical, acoustic, and other non-kinetic weapons act without physical projectiles and raises the question whether such non-kinetic methods qualify as “attacks” under IHL]. <https://www.geneva-academy.ch/joomlatools-files/docman-files/Non-Kinetic-Energy%20Weapons.pdf>.

⁴⁶ International Committee of the Red Cross. (2019, November). *International humanitarian law and cyber operations during armed conflicts: ICRC position paper submitted to the Open-Ended Working Group on Developments in the Field of Information and Telecommunications in the Context of International Security and the Group of Governmental Experts on Advancing Responsible State Behaviour in Cyberspace in the Context of International Security* (pp. 7-9). [Argues that the determination of whether a cyber operation constitutes an “attack” under IHL should turn on its effects, such as loss of functionality or civilian harm, rather than the means employed]. https://www.icrc.org/en/download/file/108983/icrc_ihl-and-cyber-operations-during-armed-conflicts.pdf.

⁴⁷ Thompson, L. B. (2010, April 14). *Lack of protected satellite communications could mean defeat for joint force in future war*. *Lexington Institute, Early Warning Blog*. [Notes that the U.S. military relies on commercial, dual-use satellites for roughly 80–90% of its communications, a dependence that creates significant operational vulnerabilities in wartime]. <https://www.lexingtoninstitute.org/lack-of-protected-satellite-communications-could-mean-defeat-for-joint-force-in-future-war>.

⁴⁸ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (n.d.). *Registration of objects launched into outer space*. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/spaceobjectregister/index.html>; United States Space Command. (n.d.). *Space-Track.org*. [Both describe existing space-object registries, which provide basic orbital and identification data but do not disclose the operational purpose or control of listed satellites]. <https://www.space-track.org/>.

⁴⁹ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (2023, November). *Registration of objects launched into outer space: Stakeholder study* [Notes that many States are considering registry enhancements to include operator/owner data and measures of control or supervision over the space object]. https://www.unoosa.org/res/oosadoc/data/documents/2023/stspace/stspace91_0_html/st_space_091E.pdf.

⁵⁰ Christensen, I., & Samson, V. (Eds.). (2024, July). *Space situational awareness*. Secure World Foundation. [Cooperative transparency measures such as data sharing, maneuver notifications, and tracking coordination among operators enhance verification, build confidence among spacefaring nations, and mitigate the risk of misperception or

Absent such reforms, the principle of distinction risks devolving into a mere formalism in a domain defined by opacity automation, and dual-use design. As the physical signatures of satellites convey little about their operational function, and as non-kinetic interference blurs the line between combat and commerce, the traditional balance between military necessity and humanitarian restraint becomes untenable. Unless states adapt the law's practical architecture to match the technological realities of orbit, distinction may endure in rhetoric but collapse in practice – a rule drawn on a map that no longer matches the terrain.

2.2. Proportionality and the Problem of Cascading Effects

Proportionality, another central tenet of LOAC, prohibits attacks expected to cause incidental harm to civilians or civilian objects that would be excessive in relation to the anticipated concrete and direct military advantage.⁵¹ Unlike the principle of distinction, which turns on categorical separations, proportionality demands a relative and context-dependent calculus. The attacker must weigh the military benefit of striking a lawful objective against the foreseeable collateral damage.⁵² In space, this balancing act becomes exceptionally difficult to perform and even harder to verify.

Space systems are tightly integrated into civilian life. A single satellite may carry GPS functions essential not only to military operations but also to civil aviation, financial transactions, emergency response coordination, and commercial logistics. Its destruction may disable or degrade services relied upon by entire populations.⁵³ Because space infrastructure supports both direct and derivative civilian activity, the incidental effects of targeting such systems can ripple through critical sectors.⁵⁴ These are not hypothetical concerns. When China conducted an anti-satellite (ASAT) test in 2007, the kinetic destruction of its own weather satellite produced over 3,000 pieces of trackable debris, endangering other satellites and creating hazards for manned missions.⁵⁵ The physical aftermath of one event translated into systemic and potentially enduring consequences.⁵⁶

Assessing proportionality under such conditions requires a broader conceptualization of what counts as civilian harm. Traditional LOAC analysis evaluates collateral damage in terms of direct physical injury or

misattribution]. https://cdn.prod.website-files.com/66dcc6872f6ed23bce1db235/6801536a2eb54e56da0ec531_fs24-01_space-situational-awareness.pdf.

⁵¹ Protocol I, *supra* note 34, arts. 51(5)(b), 57(2)(a)(iii) (codifying the rule of proportionality, which prohibits attacks expected to cause incidental civilian harm excessive in relation to the anticipated military advantage, and obligating attackers to refrain from launching such attacks).

⁵² *Id.*

⁵³ International Committee of the Red Cross. (2024, June). *Protecting essential civilian services on Earth from disruption by military space operations: Executive summary* [Observes that essential civilian services rely on satellites, which often include systems owned and operated by militaries]. https://www.icrc.org/en/download/file/289558/4781.01_002_executive_summary_protecting_essential_civilian_services_web.pdf.

⁵⁴ *Id.*

⁵⁵ NASA Orbital Debris Program Office. (2008). *Orbital debris quarterly news*, 12(1), 2–3 [Reports that China's January 2007 anti-satellite test destroyed the Fengyun-1C weather satellite, generating thousands of trackable debris fragments and tens of thousands of smaller pieces that posed collision risks to operational satellites and crewed missions]. <https://orbitaldebris.jsc.nasa.gov/quarterly-news/pdfs/odqnv12i1.pdf>.

⁵⁶ Saunders, P. C., & Lutes, C. D. (2007, June). *China's ASAT test: Implications for U.S. military and civil space assets*. Institute for National Strategic Studies, National Defense University [Explains that the debris cloud from China's 2007 anti-satellite test posed risks to military reconnaissance and meteorological satellites as well as to the International Space Station and other crewed missions]. https://www.files.ethz.ch/isn/113985/2007-06_SR.pdf.

destruction.⁵⁷ In space, harm is often systemic rather than kinetic – interruptions to communications, distortions in navigation, economic loss, or compromised humanitarian operations.⁵⁸ If a satellite supports both military surveillance and civilian air traffic management, its loss may endanger flight safety, even if no physical destruction occurs on Earth.⁵⁹ Disabling communications satellites would not just mute command networks, it would blind the world. Every modern weather forecast, storm alert, and climate model depends entirely on orbiting sensors. Disable those satellites, and tomorrow’s forecast would be lost, along with the ability to see future disaster coming.⁶⁰ Under LOAC, hospitals enjoy special protection from direct attack – but when essential services depend on vulnerable, dual-use infrastructure, those protections are increasingly difficult to apply in practice.⁶¹ Even non-kinetic attacks can produce effects that implicate the proportionality principle, particularly where civilian harm is foreseeable and severe.⁶² The law requires not only assessing the immediacy of an effect, but also the reliability of the systems that buffer civilians from harm.⁶³

Moreover, damage in space rarely remains isolated. Debris generated by a single kinetic strike can initiate a cascade that damages other satellites, disrupts orbital lanes, and threatens future missions. Known as the Kessler Syndrome, this scenario envisions a chain reaction of debris collisions that could render entire

⁵⁷ Gillard, E.-C. (2018, December). *Proportionality in the conduct of hostilities: The incidental harm side of the assessment*. International Law Programme, Chatham House. [Proportionality assessments must go beyond direct physical harm to include foreseeable incidental harm and weigh that harm against anticipated military advantage in a context-dependent manner]. <https://www.chathamhouse.org/sites/default/files/publications/research/2018-12-10-proportionality-conduct-hostilities-incident-harm-gillard-final.pdf>.

⁵⁸ International Committee of the Red Cross. (2021, April 8). *The potential human cost of the use of weapons in outer space and the protection afforded by international humanitarian law* (Position Paper No. 915) [Asserts that attacks on space systems supporting essential civilian services pose a “likely... significant” human cost, since “space systems... permeate most aspects of civilian life”]. <https://international-review.icrc.org/sites/default/files/reviews-pdf/2022-01/the-potential-human-cost-weapons-in-outer-space-and-protection-afforded-by-ihl-icrc-position-paper-915.pdf>.

⁵⁹ International Air Transport Association. (2024, September). *Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) radio-frequency interference (RFI) – Safety risk assessment* (Version 4) [Notes that satellite-based positioning, navigation, and timing systems are essential for aviation safety and that interference can seriously impact aircraft navigation systems]. https://www.iata.org/contentassets/c8e90fe690ce4047a8edfa97f4824890/iata_safety_risk_assessment_gnss_interference.pdf.

⁶⁰ Noh, Y.-C., et al. (2023). *Potential loss of predictability in the numerical weather prediction from the reduced spatial coverage of the polar-orbiting satellite observing system*. *Monthly Weather Review*, 151, 1129 [Finds that reductions in polar-orbiting satellite coverage significantly degrade global forecast accuracy, underscoring the dependence of modern weather prediction on continuous satellite observation]. <https://doi.org/10.1175/MWR-D-22-0143.1>.

⁶¹ Protocol I, *supra* note 34, arts. 12–16.

⁶² Tallinn Manual 2.0, *supra* note 19, at 106–64 (discussing how non-kinetic cyber operations, including those disrupting civilian infrastructure, may implicate the proportionality principle under the Law of Armed Conflict).

⁶³ *See Id.*

orbital altitudes unusable.⁶⁴ A military advantage gained through disabling one satellite might pale in comparison to the long-term costs imposed on all spacefaring actors, civilian and military alike.

These cascading consequences challenge LOAC's traditional proportionality framework, which assumes collateral damage can be reasonably anticipated and geographically contained.⁶⁵ In space, neither assumption holds. The indirect and enduring effects of an attack may vastly exceed the scope of the initial strike. Assessing what is excessive requires an expanded understanding of harm and a new model for forecasting consequences that move not just horizontally across territory, but vertically through time.⁶⁶ Finally, because many space operations remain classified, states often do not disclose the rationale or expected benefit of their military activities in orbit.⁶⁷ This opacity makes post hoc assessments of proportionality nearly impossible. Absent verifiable data on targeting decisions and expected outcomes, observers can only infer intent and judge excessiveness from circumstantial evidence. Such uncertainty creates a legal regime that weakens accountability and impairs deterrence, leaving the framework open to manipulation.

In response, legal scholars and policymakers have proposed incorporating systemic risk assessments into LOAC proportionality analysis for space.⁶⁸ Such an approach would consider not only immediate military gain and civilian harm, but also second-and third-order effects across shared orbital infrastructure. Space, after all, is not merely a strategic domain; it is a commons that is fragile and interdependent. Any legal regime governing it must reckon with the ripple instead of only a splash.

2.3. *Necessity and the Expanding Logic of Preemption*

The principle of military necessity authorizes only those measures of force that are required to achieve a legitimate military objective and are not otherwise prohibited by international law.⁶⁹ It operates as both a

⁶⁴ Mariappan, A., & Crassidis, J. L. (2023). *Kessler's syndrome: A challenge to humanity*. *Frontiers in Space Technology*, 4[Describes how debris from a single collision can initiate a cascading sequence of impacts known as the Kessler Syndrome, potentially rendering parts of Earth's orbit unusable]. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/space-technologies/articles/10.3389/frspt.2023.1309940/full>.

⁶⁵ Hathaway, O. A., Khan, A., & Revkin, M. R. (2025). *The dangerous rise of "dual-use" objects in war*. *Yale Law Journal*, 134(8), 2645 [Argues that the growing reliance on dual use infrastructure undermines the assumption within the proportionality framework that collateral damage can be reasonably anticipated and geographically contained]. <https://www.yalelawjournal.org/article/the-dangerous-rise-of-dual-use-objects-in-war>.

⁶⁶ Kuplic, G. B., & Sawmiller, J. (2025, June). *Humanity on the final frontier: Challenges in applying international humanitarian law to modern military space operations*. *International Review of the Red Cross*, Paper No. 928 [Explains that the enduring and cascading effects of debris in orbit complicate proportionality analyses under the Law of Armed Conflict, since harm in space often cannot be geographically or temporally contained]. <https://international-review.icrc.org/articles/humanity-on-the-final-frontier-928>.

⁶⁷ U.S. Government Accountability Office. (2025, July). *Space operations: DOD is pursuing efforts to collaborate with allies and partners but needs to address key challenges* (GAO-25-108043, p. 1) [Notes portions of the underlying March 2025 report were classified and therefore omitted from the public version to protect operational information]. <https://www.gao.gov/assets/890/880284.pdf>.

⁶⁸ Gillard, E.-C. (2018). *Proportionality in the conduct of hostilities: The incidental harm side of the assessment*. Chatham House. [Argues that proportionality assessments should consider indirect, cumulative, and long-term effects rather than only immediate collateral damage]. <https://www.chathamhouse.org/sites/default/files/publications/research/2018-12-10-proportionality-conduct-hostilities-incident-harm-gillard-final.pdf>

⁶⁹ *Hague Convention (IV) Respecting the Laws and Customs of War on Land and Its Annex: Regulations Concerning the Laws and Customs of War on Land*, Oct. 18, 1907, arts. 22–23(g) [Establishes the right of belligerents to employ

predicate and a constraint: it justifies the use of force in armed conflict only when such force serves a concrete military aim and limits that use to what is strictly required.⁷⁰ Under *ius in bello*, necessity prohibits gratuitous violence and forecloses attacks undertaken solely for retaliation or intimidation.⁷¹ Unlike proportionality, which evaluates the collateral consequences of an attack, necessity governs the purpose of the strike itself.⁷²

In the context of outer space, necessity confronts a particularly unstable foundation. The technological opacity of space systems, especially the functional ambiguity of satellites, renders necessity judgment vulnerable to miscalculation or misuse.⁷³ A satellite facilitating early-warning detection, nuclear command-and-control, or encrypted military communications may qualify as a lawful military objective.⁷⁴ Yet, these critical functions are often embedded within multipurpose satellites that also serve civilian or commercial roles. Targeting decisions thus rely on incomplete or speculative assessments of utility, blurring the line between strategic interference and legal sufficiency.⁷⁵

This uncertainty creates fertile ground for preemptive logic – a tendency to strike first based on perceived vulnerabilities or latent threats. The space domain magnifies this impulse. Orbital infrastructure operates in a zero-sum environment: once a satellite is disabled, it cannot be replaced mid-conflict.⁷⁶ This structural asymmetry fuels a “use it or lose it” mentality reminiscent of Cold War nuclear doctrine. The possibility an adversary may gain a decisive advantage through space dominance incentivizes anticipatory attacks under the banner of necessity, even absent clear evidence of hostile intent.⁷⁷ This dynamic reflects

means of warfare is not unlimited and that destruction of enemy property is unlawful unless required by the necessities of war]. <https://ihl-databases.icrc.org/ihl/INTRO/195>.

⁷⁰ U.S. Army. (2019, August). *Field Manual 6-27 / Marine Corps Tactical Publication 11-10C: The commander's handbook on the law of land warfare* (§§ 1-23 to 1-27) [Explains the principle of military necessity both authorizes the use of force required to achieve a legitimate military objective and limits such force to what is necessary and not otherwise prohibited by the law of armed conflict]. https://irp.fas.org/doddir/army/fm6_27.pdf.

⁷¹ DoD Law of War Manual, *supra* note 15, §§ 2.2–2.3.2, at 52–59 (explaining the principle of military necessity prohibits acts of violence not required by legitimate military objectives, including operations motivated solely by revenge, intimidation, or destruction for its own sake).

⁷² *Id.*

⁷³ See Kuplic & Sawmiller, *supra* note 60 (observing the dual-use nature and technological opacity of satellites complicate necessity determinations, as states may misjudge the purpose or function of targeted space systems, heightening the risk of miscalculation or misuse).

⁷⁴ See DoD Law of War Manual, *supra* note 15, §§ 5.6–5.7, at 216–28 (objects used for early-warning detection, nuclear command-and-control, or military communications may qualify as lawful military objectives when they make an effective contribution to military action).

⁷⁵ Cannon, J. A. (2023, Summer). *Targeting dual-use satellites: Lessons learned from terrestrial warfare*. *Air & Space Operations Review*, 2, 37 [Examines how satellites serving both civilian and military roles complicate targeting assessments and may blur the line between strategic interference and lawful military operations]. https://www.airuniversity.af.edu/Portals/10/ASOR/Journals/Volume-2_Number-2/Cannon.pdf.

⁷⁶ Morgan, F. E. (2010). *Deterrence and first-strike stability in space: A preliminary assessment* (pp. 14–15). RAND Corporation. [Discusses how the fragility and predictability of satellites, combined with the impossibility of replacing them during hostilities, create incentives for early or preemptive attacks in crisis situations]. https://www.rand.org/content/dam/rand/pubs/monographs/2010/RAND_MG916.pdf.

⁷⁷ Evans, A. T., et al. (2024). *Space strategic stability: Assessing U.S. concepts and approaches* (p. v). RAND Corporation. [Notes that “it is plausible that there exists an offensive advantage in space that generates an incentive to attack first.”]. https://www.rand.org/pubs/research_reports/RRA2313-1.html.

a classic security-dilemma structure in which measures taken to preserve access to vulnerable systems may be interpreted as preparations for offensive action. In environments characterized by uncertainty and difficulty distinguishing defensive from offensive capabilities, states may adopt worst-case assumptions about intent, increasing the incentive for anticipatory force.⁷⁸ The vulnerability of space assets, combined with the difficulty of rapidly replacing disabled systems, can therefore compress perceived decision time and heighten crisis instability.⁷⁹

International law recognizes that necessity can, under specific conditions, justify anticipatory self-defense. This justification rests on a narrow threshold: the threat must be imminent, the response proportional, and the action necessary to prevent harm that cannot otherwise be averted. Under the Caroline standard – long regarded as customary law – the threat must be “instant, overwhelming, and leaving no choice of means and no moment for deliberation.”⁸⁰ Applied to space, where hostile acts may unfold silently or manifest only through data streams, meeting this threshold becomes intensely fact-dependent. The risk is that necessity, improperly invoked, may serve as a legal fig leaf for opportunistic first strikes.

The problem is compounded by the absence of verifiable intent. Many military satellites orbit without disclosed missions or identifiers, rendering third-party monitoring difficult.⁸¹ Signals intelligence may detect anomalous activity, but without access to command protocols or internal telemetry, observers cannot confidently infer intent. This evidentiary vacuum allows necessity to be asserted where no immediate danger exists, undermining its legal credibility and destabilizing the deterrent function of LOAC.

Furthermore, not all preemptive actions in space need involve kinetic force. A state may rationalize non-destructive interference – such as temporarily jamming an adversary’s reconnaissance satellite – as a necessary measure to neutralize a looming threat. Even non-kinetic actions can provoke escalation, particularly when they interfere with dual-use systems or affect third-party assets.⁸² The formal distinction between destructive and non-destructive acts may obscure the real strategic risks they carry.

⁷⁸ Jervis, *supra* note 6 at 187.

⁷⁹ Townsend, *supra* note 5 at 79–81.

⁸⁰ Webster, D. (1842, August 6). *Letter from Daniel Webster, U.S. Secretary of State, to Lord Ashburton, British Special Minister*, reprinted in 2 John Bassett Moore, *A digest of international law* 412 (1906) [States that “the necessity of self-defence [must be] instant, overwhelming, leaving no choice of means, and no moment for deliberation”]. https://avalon.law.yale.edu/19th_century/br-1842d.asp.

⁸¹ United Nations Institute for Disarmament Research. (2022). *Threats to the security of space activities and systems* (pp. 7–8) [Explains the dual use nature of many space systems makes it difficult to discern an operator’s intent, thereby complicating efforts to distinguish benign from hostile activities]. https://documents.unoda.org/wpcontent/uploads/2022/08/20220817_A_AC294_2022_WP16_E_UNIDIR.pdf.

⁸² Bace, B., Gökçe, Y., & Tatar, Ü. (2024). *Law in orbit: International legal perspectives on cyberattacks targeting space systems. Telecommunications Policy*, 48(4) [Examines how international law governs cyber operations directed at space infrastructure and emphasizes that non-kinetic interference such as jamming or cyber manipulation of satellites can have escalatory consequences and may still constitute a breach of international obligations, even absent physical force]. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0308596124000363>.

To preserve necessity as a meaningful legal standard in space warfare, states must resist the gravitational pull of preemption as a default posture.⁸³ Operational necessity must be demonstrable rather than presumed and must be grounded in credible intelligence rather than mere capability-based suspicion. Where evidence is absent or ambiguous, restraint must prevail. Legal doctrine must continue to draw a distinction between what is strategically advantageous and what is legally necessary.

As with other LOAC principles, necessity in the space domain also depends on institutional reinforcement. Shared registration databases that identify satellite function, bilateral or multilateral notification protocols, and confidence-building mechanisms such as reciprocal inspections or telemetry exchanges could reduce the informational asymmetries that drive premature claims of necessity. In the absence of such tools, necessity risks becoming the exception that swallows the rule – expanding beyond its intended scope and enabling a logic of first-strike instability in a domain already vulnerable to miscalculation

2.4. *Humanity and the Limits of Lawful Suffering*

The principle of humanity prohibits the infliction of suffering, injury, or destruction not necessary for achieving a legitimate military objective. It rejects cruelty for its own sake and insists warfare, however brutal, remain bounded by ethical restraint.⁸⁴ Codified in treaty and embedded in customary law, the principle serves as a backstop where other rules falter.⁸⁵ Nowhere is that safety net more essential than in outer space – a domain defined as much by legal lacunae as by technological novelty.

Unlike other LOAC principles, which often rely on empirical calculations or strategic context, humanity draws on normative judgment. It asks not whether an action is efficient, but whether it is inhumane – whether the harm it produces can be justified by any plausible standard of military necessity.⁸⁶ This inquiry is especially pressing in space warfare, where the destruction of infrastructure can impose consequences far removed from the battlefield. A kinetic strike against a surveillance satellite may impair access to humanitarian communications, medical logistics, or natural disaster monitoring.⁸⁷ While not a space-based operation, the 1999 NATO bombing of Yugoslavia’s electrical grid demonstrated how infrastructure targeting can paralyze civilian health care, water purification, and emergency response.⁸⁸ In

⁸³ Krepon, M. (2004, November). *Hair trigger in the heavens*. In *Weapons in space? Arms Control Today*. Arms Control Association. [Notes that “successful space warfare mandates pre-emptive strikes and a preventive war in space as well as on the ground.”]. <https://www.armscontrol.org/act/2004-11/features/weapons-space>.

⁸⁴ *Declaration Renouncing the Use, in Time of War, of Explosive Projectiles Under 400 Grammes Weight (St. Petersburg Declaration)*, Dec. 11, 1868, reprinted in *1 American Journal of International Law Supplement 95* (1907) [Affirms “the only legitimate object which States should endeavour to accomplish during war is to weaken the military forces of the enemy” and prohibits means of warfare that “uselessly aggravate the sufferings of disabled men,” thus articulating the foundational statement of the principle of humanity as a limitation on unnecessary suffering in armed conflict]. <https://ihl-databases.icrc.org/en/ihl-treaties/st-petersburg-decl-1868/declaration>.

⁸⁵ Protocol I, *supra* note 34, art. 35(1)–(2) (codifying the principle of humanity by limiting the means and methods of warfare and prohibiting weapons that cause superfluous injury or unnecessary suffering).

⁸⁶ Melzer, N. (2012). *Keeping the balance between military necessity and humanity: A response to four critiques of the ICRC’s interpretive guidance on the notion of direct participation in hostilities*. *New York University Journal of International Law and Politics*, 42, 831, 908 [Notes that the principle of humanity “forbids the infliction of suffering, injury or destruction not actually necessary for the accomplishment of legitimate military purposes”]. <https://nyujilp.org/wp-content/uploads/2012/04/42.3-Melzer.pdf>.

⁸⁷ Delle Fave, *supra* note 36.

⁸⁸ Committee Established to Review the NATO Bombing Campaign Against the Federal Republic of Yugoslavia. (2000, June 7). *Final report to the prosecutor*. International Criminal Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia. [Notes

orbit, those same services may be supported or routed through dual-use satellites. The chain of causation is longer, but the vulnerability no less acute.

Non-kinetic interference such as signal jamming or sensor blinding may cut off entire populations from systems on which they rely, with no visible smoke or rubble to mark the harm.⁸⁹ During the 2022 Russian invasion of Ukraine, cyberattacks targeting commercial satellite communications disrupted service for thousands of users across Europe, including emergency responders and civil aviation authorities. Although no physical damage occurred, the effect on civilian coordination was immediate.⁹⁰ These examples underscore the need to assess not only whether harm is inflicted, but how systems upon which civilians depend are rendered inoperative.

Moreover, humanity has temporal as well as physical dimensions. The long-lived nature of orbital debris poses risks to both present-day systems and future civilian use of space. An action that renders an orbital band unusable for decades may not cause immediate civilian casualties, yet it degrades the shared environment in ways that violate the spirit, if not the letter, of LOAC.⁹¹ The principle of humanity pushes against this kind of strategic myopia. It demands that parties to a conflict consider not only the scope of force, but the endurance of its effects.

This concern is not without terrestrial precedent. Additional Protocol I to the Geneva Conventions prohibits means of warfare “which are intended, or may be expected, to cause widespread, long-term, and severe damage to the natural environment.”⁹² It further directs parties to protect the environment as part of their general obligation to avoid unnecessary suffering.⁹³ Although these provisions were drafted with nuclear, biological, and chemical weapons in mind, their structure offers a compelling analog for orbital debris. Much like radioactive fallout or persistent toxins, debris fields generated by ASAT tests can render vast orbital regions unusable, with indiscriminate and enduring effect.⁹⁴

that NATO’s 1999 bombing of Yugoslavia’s electrical grid caused widespread civilian hardship, disrupting health care, water purification, and emergency services and illustrating how infrastructure targeting can paralyze essential systems when directed at dual-use networks].

https://www.icty.org/x/file/About/OTP/otp_report_nato_bombing_en.pdf.

⁸⁹ ICRC, Protecting Essential Civilian Services, *supra* note 50, at 3 (explaining essential civilian services increasingly rely on satellite systems that support communications, energy, water and sanitation, and transportation, meaning disruption or degradation of these space-enabled networks could have cascading humanitarian consequences).

⁹⁰ CyberPeace Institute. (2022, June). *Case study: Viasat*, para. “Impact – Overview” [Notes that “overall, this attack impacted several thousand customers located in Ukraine and tens of thousands of other fixed broadband customers across Europe.”]. <https://cyberconflicts.cyberpeaceinstitute.org/law-and-policy/cases/viasat>.

⁹¹ Gheorghe, A. V., & Yuchnovicz, D. E. (2015). *The space infrastructure vulnerability cadastre: Orbital debris critical loads*. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Science*, 6, 359 [Explains that orbital debris accumulations can create persistent hazards that endanger operational satellites and impede future civilian access to space, as debris concentrations may render certain orbital bands unusable for decades]. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13753-015-0073-2>.

⁹² Protocol I, *supra* note 34, art. 55(1) (“care shall be taken in warfare to protect the natural environment against widespread, long-term and severe damage,” thereby recognizing that methods of warfare must not degrade the shared environment in ways that transcend immediate battlefield harm).

⁹³ *Id.* at art. 56 (extending environmental protections to works and installations containing dangerous forces such as dams, dykes, and nuclear power stations – whose attack may cause severe losses among the civilian population).

⁹⁴ European Space Agency. (2025). *ESA space environment report 2025* [Warns that cascading debris collisions can make certain orbital regions unsafe and ultimately unusable, as debris proliferation renders portions of Earth’s orbit effectively inaccessible for future operations].

https://www.esa.int/Space_Safety/Space_Debris/ESA_Space_Environment_Report_2025.

Even though outer space is not a biological ecosystem itself, it constitutes a shared human environment whose degradation carries substantial civilian risk. Extending environmental protection norms to space, whether by treaty, through customary international law, or via the interpretive force of the Martens Clause reinforces the view that the principle of humanity constrains not only the moment of attack, but also the enduring consequences it sets in motion. This interpretive move finds support in the architecture of space law itself. Article IX of the OST requires states to avoid harmful contamination of space and environmental damage to earth resulting from space activities.⁹⁵ While initially directed at scientific missions and planetary protection, this language reflects a broader recognition that space is not legally inert – but is environmentally consequential. Similarly, the UN Guidelines on the Long-Term Sustainability of Outer Space Activities, though nonbinding, urge states to mitigate debris, share situational awareness, and preserve orbital capacity for future generations.⁹⁶ National licensing regimes, including under U.S. environmental law, already assess certain space operations for ecological impact.⁹⁷ These developments suggest a growing consensus that space is an environment in the legal as well as scientific sense. If space is treated as an environment in the context of planetary protection and peacetime regulation, there is no principled reason to suspend that logic when the conduct of hostilities threatens to inflict long-term, indiscriminate harm. The same legal instincts that prohibit radiation, scorched earth, or poisoned wells on the ground should inform how law constrains the use of force in orbit.

The Martens Clause, reaffirmed in the Additional Protocols and widely regarded as a normative anchor for modern LOAC, reinforces this duty. In situations not covered by specific legal prohibition, civilians and combatants alike remain under the protection of “the principles of humanity and the dictates of public conscience.” The Clause resists the idea that novelty or ambiguity nullifies legal restraint. In the absence of detailed treaty regulation in space, the Martens Clause functions not as a filler but as force: a source of legal obligation rooted in enduring values rather than codified text.⁹⁸

Applying the principle of humanity in space therefore requires a shift in orientation – from battlefield casualties to systemic fragility, from visible damage to silent disruption. It requires states to treat the civilian implications of space warfare not as collateral technicalities but as primary legal considerations. While the precise contours of this duty remain open to debate, its moral architecture is clear: if law is to follow war into orbit, it must carry with it the full weight of human concern.

3. OPERATIONALIZING LOAC IN THE SPACE DOMAIN

Having examined the doctrinal application of LOAC’s core principles in the orbital domain, this section turns to the operational and institutional mechanisms necessary to translate those principles into practice. Applying LOAC to outer space requires more than conceptual extension; it demands doctrinal specificity,

⁹⁵ Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 7, art. IX (requiring states to conduct space activities “so as to avoid their harmful contamination and also adverse changes in the environment of the Earth,” reinforcing that environmental protection principles extend to outer space as part of broader humanitarian and stewardship obligations).

⁹⁶ United Nations Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space. (2021). *Guidelines for the long-term sustainability of outer space activities* (U.N. Doc. A/74/20) [Urges States to mitigate debris, share situational awareness, and preserve orbital regions for future generations].
https://www.unoosa.org/documents/pdf/PromotingSpaceSustainability/Publication_Final_English_June2021.pdf.

⁹⁷ 14 C.F.R. § 450.47, *Environmental review* (last visited Oct. 23, 2025) (requiring the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) to comply with the procedures of the National Environmental Policy Act of 1969 (NEPA) and review environmental impacts before issuing a commercial space launch or reentry license),
<https://www.law.cornell.edu/cfr/text/14/450.47>.

⁹⁸ Hague Convention (II), *supra* note 26, pmb1. (containing the Martens Clause).

operational guidance, and institutional architecture. The core LOAC principles of distinction, proportionality, necessity, and humanity do not cease to function in space; but they lack the technical and procedural elaboration that has developed for terrestrial conflict. Their application to space operations must be both interpretively sound and practically workable.

Attribution illustrates the problem. On land, responsibility for an attack may be established through visual observation, intercepted communications, or forensic analysis. In space, attribution depends on telemetry, radar signatures, and often-classified SSA data. A disabled satellite might be the result of hostile interference or an internal failure indistinguishable from one. The lack of transparent, verifiable indicators invites plausible deniability and impedes the enforcement of legal norms.⁹⁹

Targeting doctrine also falters in the face of dual use. A single satellite may support both encrypted military communications and civilian infrastructure like GPS or emergency coordination. LOAC permits attacks on military objectives, but it requires minimization of civilian harm.¹⁰⁰ Where targets defy classification, compliance becomes guesswork. Absent new doctrines or interpretive guidance, LOAC risks functioning more as legal theatre than as operational constraint.

Some states have begun to anticipate these dilemmas. The United States, for example, has expanded its space situational awareness (SSA) initiatives and entered into data-sharing agreements with allied and commercial entities to enhance transparency and reduce the risk of miscalculation. The Combined Space Operations Initiative (CSpO), which includes partners such as the United Kingdom, Canada, Australia, and France, reflects a coordinated approach to space security and information exchange.¹⁰¹ Similarly, the European Union has developed its own Space Surveillance and Tracking (EU SST) framework to monitor debris and identify potentially hazardous objects.¹⁰² These initiatives represent early attempts to translate legal principles into operational practice. By promoting transparency, improving shared awareness of space activity, and facilitating timely coordination among actors, they help create the conditions under which LOAC obligations might realistically be observed. More ambitious frameworks such as reciprocal notification of satellite maneuvers, technical standards for satellite identification, or international

⁹⁹ Steer, C. (2023, January 29). *International humanitarian law in the “grey zone” of space and cyber*. Centre for International Governance Innovation. [Observes that in the space domain “it is sometimes difficult to correctly attribute failures in space systems either to space debris, unintentional interference or a deliberate act – and if it is deliberate, it may be difficult to identify the responsible actor”]. <https://www.cigionline.org/articles/international-humanitarian-law-in-the-grey-zone-of-space-and-cyber>.

¹⁰⁰ Dunlap, C. J., Jr. (2023). *The law of war and “dual-use” commercial satellites: The nexus of commercial and national security space* (Duke Law School Public Law & Legal Theory Series No. 2023-54) [Argues that dual-use commercial satellites blur the distinction between civilian objects and military objectives, complicating targeting decisions under the law of armed conflict]. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4566133>.

¹⁰¹ U.S. Department of Defense. (2024, September 26). *Joint statement from the Combined Space Operations Initiative (CSpO)* [Notes that the CSpO “has grown to ten partners: Australia, Canada, France, Germany, Italy, Japan, New Zealand, Norway, the United Kingdom, and the United States,” and that these partners are committed to cooperation, transparency, and responsible behavior in space]. <https://www.defense.gov/News/Releases/Release/Article/3918135/joint-statement-from-the-combined-space-operations-initiative>.

¹⁰² European Union. (2024). *Space surveillance and tracking (EU SST)* [Explains that the EU Space Surveillance and Tracking (EU SST) partnership comprises 15 EU member states and operates a network of ground-based sensors to survey and track space objects, helping to mitigate collision risks, in-orbit fragmentations, and uncontrolled reentries]. https://defence-industry-space.ec.europa.eu/eu-space/ssa-europes-eyes-space/eu-space-surveillance-and-tracking_en.

protocols on reversible interference could help translate legal principle into operational behavior.¹⁰³ These measures are not mere transparency tools. They are scaffolding for a legal regime that aspires to more than symbolism.

Even treaty silence does not create a legal vacuum. The structure of LOAC – drawn from both custom and codified text – has always relied on military manuals, rules of engagement, and national doctrines to translate principles into action.¹⁰⁴ The same must occur in space. Military legal advisers, commanders, and policymakers must recognize that meaningful constraint requires both rules and procedures for applying them.

The consequences of legal inertia are neither speculative nor remote. Space warfare, if it develops in a legal void, will not be governed by tacit restraint. Its contours will be drawn by precedent set in silence, actions taken without contest, and the calculations of national interest. Operationalizing LOAC is strategic and imperative.

4. LEGAL INDETERMINACY AND STRUCTURAL GAPS

While the foundational principles of LOAC extend logically to the space domain, their application reveals substantial gaps in definitional clarity, regulatory coverage and institutional enforcement. These gaps are not only technical, but structural and rooted in the mismatch between legacy legal frameworks and the novel features of outer space operations. This section identifies structural gaps in definition, attribution, and enforcement that limit the constraining force of LOAC in space, moving beyond doctrinal analysis to institutional design.

4.1. *Threshold Ambiguity: What Counts as an Attack?*

One of the most persistent challenges in applying LOAC to space is determining when a hostile act constitutes an “attack” for the purposes of triggering LOAC protections. Article 49 of Additional Protocol I defines attacks as “acts of violence against the adversary, whether in offence or in defence.”¹⁰⁵ In terrestrial conflict, the presence of physical damage or injury often provides a clear signal. This definition clearly includes kinetic ASAT strikes, like China’s 2007 missile test that destroyed a weather satellite and produced over 3,000 pieces of debris.¹⁰⁶ In space, however, many forms of interference – jamming, spoofing, cyber infiltration – leave no physical trace. They may cause temporary or even severe operational disruption without satisfying conventional thresholds of armed conflict.¹⁰⁷ This raises the question: does reversible, non-destructive interference qualify as an “attack” under LOAC?

¹⁰³ Zhang, W., et al. (2023). *How we learn social norms: A three-stage model for social norm learning*. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14 [Proposes that social norm learning involves cue recognition, reinforcement through feedback, and internalization—processes that help explain how shared technical protocols could foster compliance with legal norms in space operations].

¹⁰⁴ Hayashi, N. (Ed.). (2008). National military manuals on the law of armed conflict (FICHL Publication Series No. 2, p. 116) [Notes that military manuals must “translate core LOAC principles into military language in a way that is suitable and understandable even to the most illiterate soldier”].
https://www.files.ethz.ch/isn/97486/National_Military_Manuals_on_the_Law_of_Armed_Conflict.pdf.

¹⁰⁵ Protocol I, *supra* note 34, art. 49(1).

¹⁰⁶ NASA Orbital Debris Program Off., *supra* note 52.

¹⁰⁷ Cassandra Steer, *supra* note 94.

There is no consensus among states. Some argue that only kinetic actions, such as ASAT missiles or co-orbital strikes constitute attacks. Analysts note Russia and China, in their counterspace doctrines and military writings, tend to frame non-kinetic interference as distinct from “attacks” in the classic LOAC sense, thereby resisting an effects-based expansion that would subject them to greater legal risk.¹⁰⁸ China’s Working Paper to the OEWG on Reducing Space Threats underscores the need for legal definitions that distinguish “responsible behavior” from acts of aggression.¹⁰⁹ Others advocate a more effects-based approach, emphasizing the consequences of disruption rather than the method. The International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC) has publicly asserted non-kinetic operations such as signal jamming or cyber interference should count as “attacks” under IHL in the space context and thus implicate core LOAC rules.¹¹⁰ The lack of definitional agreement leaves space operations vulnerable to legal opportunism. States may exploit ambiguity to justify aggressive conduct that evades formal accountability.

Publicly available data suggests a small number of states – especially China and Russia – are disproportionately involved in state-sponsored cyber operations. Their high involvement gives them strong incentives to resist definitions that would treat non-kinetic cyber interference as full “attacks.”¹¹¹

Current trends suggest a growing interest in effects-based interpretations, which emphasize the consequences of an act rather than its modality.¹¹² This approach could better capture non-kinetic interference with civilian infrastructure. While not universally accepted, it aligns with the functional logic of LOAC and deserves further articulation through state practice, military manuals, and advisory opinions.

4.2. *The Role of Non-State and Commercial Actors*

¹⁰⁸ Blanc, A. A., et al. (2022). *Chinese and Russian perceptions of and responses to U.S. military activities in the space domain* (pp. iv–v [Summary], 43–51 [ch. 3]). RAND Corporation. [Shows that China and Russia consistently frame U.S. space activity as hostile while characterizing their own as non-threatening and emphasizing rhetorical distinctions that place many activities below overt “attack” thresholds]. https://www.rand.org/pubs/research_reports/RRA1835-1.html.

¹⁰⁹ *Working paper submitted by China to the third session of the U.N. Open-Ended Working Group on Reducing Space Threats Through Norms, Rules and Principles of Responsible Behaviours*, U.N. Doc. A/AC.294/2023/WP.13 (Jan. 30–Feb. 3, 2023) [Emphasizes that the development of “norms, rules and principles of responsible behaviors” must be grounded in clear legal definitions and cautions against vague formulations that could allow states to justify aggressive acts under the guise of responsible conduct]. <https://documents.unoda.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/CHINA-WP.13.pdf>.

¹¹⁰ International Committee of the Red Cross. (2020, October). *The potential human cost of the use of weapons in outer space and the protection afforded by international humanitarian law* [Affirms that IHL applies to military operations in outer space and that both kinetic and non-kinetic operations which disable or destroy space objects could qualify as “attacks” under IHL due to their potential effects on civilian systems]. <https://international-review.icrc.org/articles/the-potential-human-cost-weapons-in-outer-space-and-protection-afforded-by-ihl-icrc-position-paper-915>.

¹¹¹ ICRC, *The Potential Human Cost of the Use of Weapons in Outer Space*, *supra* note 55 (affirming IHL applies to all military operations in outer space and both kinetic and non-kinetic operations which disable or destroy space objects could qualify as “attacks” under IHL due to their potential effects on civilian systems).

¹¹² Aguirre, J. (2024). *Scaling non-kinetic capability integration in the Department of the Air Force* (pp. 23–25). RAND Corporation. [Observes that Air Force planners increasingly adopt an effects-based approach that values the consequences of an operation over the specific means by which those effects are achieved]. https://www.rand.org/content/dam/rand/pubs/research_reports/RRA1900/RRA1934-1/RAND_RRA1934-1.pdf.

Unlike traditional battlefields, outer space is densely populated with commercial satellites and private operators. Companies such as SpaceX, OneWeb, and Planet Labs operate constellations serving both civilian and military customers.¹¹³ Commercial participation in space operations raises two thorny issues. First, when private assets directly support military operations by transmitting encrypted data, relaying targeting information, or enabling battlefield communications, do they become lawful targets under LOAC? If so, how are they distinguished from purely civilian infrastructure? If such dual-use satellites become lawful targets, the principle of distinction demands states take all feasible precautions to spare purely civilian infrastructure. In practice, the technical integration of commercial constellations into national command networks makes that line increasingly difficult to draw.

Second, private actors now play roles that blur traditional combatant boundaries. A company that participates in active defense, such as maneuvering to avoid interference, disabling adversarial systems, or sharing real-time targeting data, effectively participates in hostilities without the legal status or protections of state forces. LOAC draws a sharp distinction between lawful combatants, civilians, and unlawful participants, but space operations often blur these roles.¹¹⁴ A commercial operator providing direct intelligence or communications support to a belligerent risk occupying a legal grey zone, entitled to neither combatant privilege nor civilian protection.¹¹⁵

International law already anticipates such dilemmas. Article VI of the OST requires states to bear international responsibility for national activities in outer space, “whether carried on by governmental agencies or by non-governmental entities,” and to authorize and continually supervise private operations. That duty extends not only to security implications but also to the environmental consequences of space activities.¹¹⁶ Commercial operators that create debris, interfere with orbital bands, or contribute to long-term degradation of the orbital environment may thus implicate their licensing state’s international obligations, particularly where negligence or reckless disregard for foreseeable harm can be shown.

Analogous accountability questions have arisen before. Major industrial firms during WWII – most notably IG Farben and Krupp – produced weapons and chemical agents for the Nazi regime and were later prosecuted at Nuremberg for aiding and profiting from war crimes. These precedents established that private enterprise cannot shield itself behind the veil of commerce when it knowingly contributes to an

¹¹³ Hallex, M. A., & Cottom, T. S. (2020). *Proliferated commercial satellite constellations: Implications for national security*. *Joint Force Quarterly*, No. 97 [Notes that companies such as SpaceX, OneWeb, and Planet Labs operate large constellations that provide imagery and communications services to both commercial and military users, blurring the line between civilian and defense activity]. <https://ndupress.ndu.edu/Media/News/News-Article-View/Article/2106495/proliferated-commercial-satellite-constellations-implications-for-national-secu/>.

¹¹⁴ Protocol I, *supra* note 34, arts. 43–44, 48.

¹¹⁵ International Committee of the Red Cross. (2008). *Interpretive guidance on the notion of direct participation in hostilities under international humanitarian law*. *International Review of the Red Cross*, 90, 991, 1008–1011 [Explains that private contractors or civilian employees who are not members of State armed forces nor members of an organized armed group must be regarded as civilians and are therefore entitled to protection against direct attack unless and for such time as they take a direct part in hostilities. Notes that “contractors ... who have, to all intents and purposes, been incorporated into the armed forces ... would no longer qualify as civilians,” thereby placing commercial operators providing direct military support in a legal grey zone]. <https://www.icrc.org/sites/default/files/external/doc/en/assets/files/other/irrc-872-reports-documents.pdf>.

¹¹⁶ Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 7, arts. VI, IX (states bear international responsibility for all national activities in outer space, including those conducted by non-governmental entities, and requiring states to authorize and continually supervise such activities to ensure compliance with treaty obligations, including the avoidance of harmful contamination and adverse environmental effects).

atrocities.¹¹⁷ Contemporary litigation continues to test this boundary. French cement manufacturer Lafarge S.A. faced criminal prosecution in France and civil suits in the United States for allegedly financing and cooperating with armed groups in Syria, including the Islamic State, to maintain its operations during the conflict.¹¹⁸ Likewise, oil giant Total S.A. has been accused of complicity in forced labor and crimes against humanity related to its pipeline projects in Myanmar, while BNP Paribas was fined by U.S. authorities for processing transactions that supported the Sudanese regime during the Darfur genocide.¹¹⁹ In each case, courts and regulators have wrestled with the question of when commercial support becomes participation in unlawful violence. These precedents underscore that private actors, whether weapons manufacturers or technology firms, cannot evade humanitarian norms merely by operating under a corporate contractual guise. As commercial involvement in space warfare grows, doctrines of liability must reflect this blurred status to ensure that profit does not excuse participation in harm.

While the issue has begun to surface in multilateral discussions, it remains largely unexamined in depth. During the third session of the OEWG on Reducing Space Threats, several states – including China – called attention to the growing role of commercial space companies in military operations and urged further study of the political and legal implications.¹²⁰ The OEWG has not yet conducted a systematic assessment of how private participation in space conflict affects state responsibility, environmental

¹¹⁷ *U.S. v. Krauch (The I.G. Farben Case)*, 8 *Trials of War Criminals Before the Nuremberg Military Tribunals Under Control Council Law No. 10* (1952) (Nuremberg Military Tribunal VI) [Held directors of IG Farben criminally responsible for aiding and profiting from Nazi war crimes through the production of chemical weapons and use of forced labor, establishing that corporate actors cannot invoke commercial neutrality when knowingly contributing to atrocities], <https://werle.rewi.hu-berlin.de/IGFarbenCase.pdf>; *U.S. v. Krupp (The Krupp Case)*, 9 *Trials of War Criminals Before the Nuremberg Military Tribunals Under Control Council Law No. 10* (1952) (Nuremberg Military Tribunal III) [Found Krupp executives guilty of war crimes and crimes against humanity for exploiting slave labor and manufacturing armaments for the Nazi regime], <http://werle.rewi.hu-berlin.de/KRUPP-Case%20Judgment.pdf>.

¹¹⁸ *United States v. Lafarge S.A.*, No. 22-CR-422 (E.D.N.Y. Oct. 18, 2022); U.S. Department of Justice. (2022, October 18; updated 2025, February 6). *Lafarge pleads guilty to conspiring to provide material support to foreign terrorist organizations* [Announces Lafarge's guilty plea to conspiring to provide material support to ISIS and the al-Nusrah Front, marking the first corporate criminal conviction in the United States for aiding foreign terrorist organizations; notes that French courts have likewise pursued charges for complicity in crimes against humanity, underscoring the expanding reach of international criminal accountability to private corporations]. <https://www.justice.gov/opa/pr/lafarge-pleads-guilty-conspiring-provide-material-support-foreign-terrorist-organizations>.

¹¹⁹ EarthRights International. (2009, September). *Total impact: The human rights, environmental, and financial impacts of Total and Chevron's Yadana gas project in military-ruled Burma* [Details Total S.A.'s participation in the Yadana pipeline project in Myanmar and allegations of complicity in forced labor and other abuses committed by Burmese military forces securing the pipeline]. <https://earthrights.org/wp-content/uploads/publications/total-impact.pdf>; U.S. Department of Justice. (2015, May 1; updated 2025, February 6). *BNP Paribas sentenced for conspiring to violate the International Emergency Economic Powers Act and the Trading with the Enemy Act* [Describes BNP Paribas's criminal sentence for processing billions in prohibited transactions for Sudan, Iran, and Cuba, with U.S. prosecutors finding the funds supported the Sudanese regime during the Darfur genocide]. <https://www.justice.gov/archives/opa/pr/bnp-paribas-sentenced-conspiring-violate-international-emergency-economic-powers-act-and>.

¹²⁰ *Working paper submitted by China, Third Session of the Open-Ended Working Group on Reducing Space Threats Through Norms, Rules and Principles of Responsible Behaviours*, Geneva, Jan. 30–Feb. 3, 2023, U.N. Doc. A/AC.294/2023/WP.2 (Jan. 27, 2023) [Urges the Working Group to consider the legal responsibilities of commercial space companies participating in military operations]. <https://documents.un.org/doc/undoc/gen/g23/012/76/pdf/g2301276.pdf>.

protection, or compliance with humanitarian law.¹²¹ Given its mandate to promote transparency and responsible behaviour in outer space, the OEWG is well placed to lead that inquiry. A dedicated study could clarify the obligations of states and corporations alike, bridging the gap between normative aspiration and operational reality. Without clear standards of responsibility and restraint, private actors may lead states down a dangerous path – one where profit, rather than prudence, governs the use of force in orbit.

4.3. *Space-to-Earth and Earth-to-Space Force Projection*

LOAC was built around the geography of terrestrial warfare. Its provisions contemplate attacks by air, land, or sea, and regulate their conduct accordingly. Outer space introduces new vectors of force projection. For example, a strike initiated from orbit, such as a cyberattack launched via satellite, a directed-energy strike from a co-orbital platform, or a kinetic projectile deployed from low Earth orbit, all challenge the traditional taxonomy of “attack” and “territory.” Does an orbital platform qualify as sovereign territory? Does an attack originating from space but causing effects on Earth alter how proportionality or self-defense are assessed? Current LOAC doctrine provides no clear answers.

The UN Charter prohibits the use of force against the territorial integrity or political independence of any state, but does not specify whether attacks from orbit or routed through orbital assets constitute a new category of threat.¹²² The OST forbids the placement of WMDs in orbit or on celestial bodies, but its language is silent on conventional weapons or systems that merely transit space.¹²³ As a result, nuclear-tipped intercontinental ballistic missiles (ICBMs) and other partial-orbit systems, which momentarily pass through outer space before re-entering Earth’s atmosphere, fall outside the treaty’s prohibitions.¹²⁴ The Soviet Union’s “Fractional Orbital Bombardment System” (FOBS) exploited this loophole precisely in the 1970s, orbiting nuclear payloads short of a full revolution in order to skirt the OST ban.¹²⁵ Although later constrained under the SALT II Agreement, the episode underscores how definitional ambiguities allow states to pursue orbital strike capabilities without formally violating international law.¹²⁶

As states expand space-based command, control, and targeting systems, these questions will only intensify. Absent clearer definitions, space-based operations risk outpacing the legal frameworks designed to restrain them.

¹²¹ West, J. (2023). *The Open-Ended Working Group on Reducing Space Threats: Recap of the third session, January 30–February 3, 2023* (p. 17). Project Ploughshares. [Notes that “China urged the OEWG to study the political and legal consequences of such participation...”]. <https://ploughshares.ca/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/OEWGThirdSessionJune6.2023.pdf>.

¹²² See U.N. Charter, *supra* note 22.

¹²³ Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 7, art. IV.

¹²⁴ DoD Law of War Manual, *supra* note 15, § 14.10.3.1, at 955–56 (explaining the OST’s prohibition on placing weapons of mass destruction “in orbit” applies only to full orbits and therefore does not extend to fractional-orbit or suborbital systems such as ICBMs).

¹²⁵ Siddiqi, A. A. (2000). *The Soviet Fractional Orbiting Bombardment System (FOBS): A short technical history. Quest: The History of Spaceflight Quarterly*, 7, 22 [Explains that the Soviet Union developed FOBS to place nuclear warheads into partial orbit in order to technically comply with the Outer Space Treaty, which prohibited only weapons of mass destruction in full orbit]. <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5ef8124031cfcf448b11db32/t/5f1c4647c77c4c27acda0b3a/1595688526845/Siddiqi+FOBS+A+Short+Technical+History+2000.pdf>.

¹²⁶ *Treaty Between the United States of America and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics on the Limitation of Strategic Offensive Arms (SALT II)*, art. VII, Second Common Understanding (June 18, 1979) [Requires dismantlement of “eighteen launchers of fractional orbital missiles” at Tyura-Tam and removal and destruction of “fractional orbital missiles”]. <https://2009-2017.state.gov/t/isn/5195.html>.

4.4. Fragmentation of Legal Authority and Institutional Gaps

The legal regulation of armed conflict in space draws from overlapping regimes such as *ius in bello* under LOAC, space law as codified through U.N. treaties and General Assembly principles, telecommunications regulations under the International Telecommunication Union, and various arms control agreements – but no single body integrates or enforces these frameworks in a coherent manner.¹²⁷ The OST serves as the constitutional charter of space law, establishing that space shall be used for peaceful purposes and prohibiting the placement of WMDs in orbit, yet it remains silent on conventional or dual-use weapons.¹²⁸ Its companion agreements – the *Rescue Agreement* (1968), the *Liability Convention* (1972), the *Registration Convention* (1975), and the *Moon Agreement* (1979) – define narrow obligations. The Rescue Agreement governs assistance to astronauts, the Liability Convention assigns fault-based and absolute liability for damage, the Registration Convention ensures the traceability of launched objects, and the Moon Agreement extends basic OST principles to other celestial bodies. Together, they regulate access and accountability but not the conduct of hostilities.¹²⁹ Meanwhile, a series of U.N. General Assembly declarations – the *1963 Declaration of Legal Principles*, *1982 Broadcasting Principles*, *1986 Remote Sensing Principles*, *1992 Principles on Nuclear Power Sources*, and *1996 Benefits Declaration* – and the ongoing work of the *U.N. Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space* (COPUOS) articulate normative expectations but lack binding force or enforcement mechanisms.¹³⁰

This fragmentation manifests in practice in two ways. First, it inhibits the formation of shared norms. States interpret their obligations through domestic law or defense policy, leading to divergent positions on what constitutes a “use of force” in orbit or who bears responsibility for debris-producing incidents.¹³¹ For instance, the Liability Convention provides compensation for physical damage but does not clearly

¹²⁷ von der Dunk, F. G. (2021). *Armed conflicts in outer space: Which law applies?* *International Law Studies*, 97, 188, 190 [Notes there is “no coherent body of law applicable to military activities in outer space,” as such activities are governed by overlapping regimes of space law, the law of armed conflict, and arms control instruments]. <https://digital-commons.usnwc.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2953&context=ils>.

¹²⁸ See Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 7.

¹²⁹ *Agreement on the Rescue of Astronauts, the Return of Astronauts and the Return of Objects Launched into Outer Space*, Apr. 22, 1968, 672 U.N.T.S. 119; *Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects*, Mar. 29, 1972, 961 U.N.T.S. 187; *Convention on Registration of Objects Launched into Outer Space*, Nov. 12, 1974, 1023 U.N.T.S. 15; *Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies*, Dec. 18, 1979, 1363 U.N.T.S. 3.

¹³⁰ United Nations General Assembly. (1963, December 13). *Declaration of legal principles governing the activities of states in the exploration and use of outer space* (G.A. Res. 1962 [XVIII]); United Nations General Assembly. (1982, December 10). *Principles governing the use by states of artificial Earth satellites for international direct-television broadcasting* (G.A. Res. 37/92). <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/spacelawdocs/18/>; United Nations General Assembly. (1986, December 3). *Principles relating to remote sensing of the Earth from outer space* (G.A. Res. 41/65). <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/principles/remote-sensing-principles.html>; United Nations General Assembly. (1992, December 14). *Principles relevant to the use of nuclear power sources in outer space* (G.A. Res. 47/68) [text available via UNOOSA]; United Nations General Assembly. (1996, December 13). *Declaration on international cooperation in the exploration and use of outer space for the benefit and in the interest of all states, taking into particular account the needs of developing countries* (G.A. Res. 51/122) [text available via UNOOSA]; United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (n.d.). *United Nations treaties and principles on outer space* [providing overview of COPUOS and the legal regime]. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/spacelawdocs/18/>.

¹³¹ Mulligan, S. P. (2023, July 13). *International law and agreements: Their effect upon U.S. law* [explaining that international law generally allows each nation to determine the manner and extent to which it will implement international legal commitments within its own domestic legal system]. Congressional Research Service. <https://www.congress.gov/crs/reports/RL32528>.

address harm caused by interference, cyber operations, or cascading debris.¹³² Second, fragmentation undermines enforcement. LOAC depends on national military manuals and post hoc accountability, but no standing tribunal or U.N. mechanism exists to adjudicate violations of humanitarian law or environmental damage in outer space.¹³³ Even deliberate ASAT tests, which create long-lived debris that threaten civilian assets, have been met with diplomatic condemnation but no legal sanction.¹³⁴ The result is a body of law that aspires to universality yet operates without an integrated system of interpretation, supervision, or enforcement.

4.5. The Enforcement Deficit

IHL has always operated within a decentralized international system. Compliance scholarship explains adherence to international law through mechanisms such as reciprocity, reputational costs, and the internalization of legal norms within domestic and military institutions. States often comply because they anticipate reciprocal treatment and seek to avoid reputational damage that may affect future cooperation.¹³⁵ At the same time, customary international law and soft-law regimes may provide fewer structured enforcement mechanisms than treaty-based systems, limiting the predictability of retaliation or reputational sanctions.¹³⁶ The orbital domain magnifies these constraints, as attribution is technically complex and operational information is frequently classified, weakening the visibility on which reputational enforcement depends.

Perhaps the most daunting challenge is the absence of meaningful enforcement mechanisms. LOAC's strength lies not only in its principles but in its ability to hold violators accountable. In space, however, attribution difficulties, classified data, and strategic reticence often make responsibility impossible to prove. Unlike terrestrial warfare, there is no analogue to the International Criminal Court or the ad hoc tribunals that followed conflicts in Rwanda or the Balkans.¹³⁷ Even if a violation were conclusively demonstrated, no standing international institution possesses both the jurisdiction and technical competence to adjudicate it.

This enforcement vacuum creates a dangerous incentive structure. States may be emboldened to violate LOAC principles in space precisely because they know enforcement is unlikely. Rules left unenforced

¹³² *Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects*, arts. I(a)–(b), II–IV, Mar. 29, 1972, 961 U.N.T.S. 187 [defining “damage” as loss of life, personal injury or impairment of health, or loss of/damage to property of States or persons, but omitting explicit reference to interference, cyber operations, or widespread cascading debris]. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/liabilityconvention.html>.

¹³³ See Ishola, F. R., Fadipe, O., & Taiwo, O. C. (2021). Legal enforceability of international space laws: An appraisal of the 1967 Outer Space Treaty [pointing to the “need to create a procedural system for legal enforcement under the existing framework”]. *New Space*, 9(1), 33. <https://doi.org/10.1089/space.2020.0038>.

¹³⁴ Zisis, C. (2007, February 22). *China's anti-satellite test* [observing that China's 2007 anti-satellite test “caused an international uproar” because it left hundreds of pieces of dangerous debris, yet no binding international legal prohibition on ASAT tests or using ground-based lasers to damage satellites]. Council on Foreign Relations. <https://www.cfr.org/backgrounder/chinas-anti-satellite-test>.

¹³⁵ Guzman, A. T. (2008). *How international law works: A rational choice theory* (pp. 33–34). Oxford University Press.

¹³⁶ Verdier, P.-H., & Voeten, E. (2014). Precedent, compliance, and change in customary international law: An explanatory theory. *American Journal of International Law*, 108(3), 389–434. <https://doi.org/10.5305/amerjintlaw.108.3.0389>.

¹³⁷ Allen, T. (2018, November 23). *Policing the final frontier: When international law becomes extraterrestrial* [“Currently there is no specialized court system accountable to adjudicate or arbitrate the activities that take place in outer space – and thus there is no formal enforcement.”]. NATO Association of Canada. <https://natoassociation.ca/policing-the-final-frontier-when-international-law-becomes-extraterrestrial/>.

lose both legitimacy and deterrent force. The longer ambiguity governs, the more it risks becoming a weapon. Addressing these gaps will require more than doctrinal refinement. It will require institutional innovation, political will, and a recognition that legal clarity is not merely a theoretical virtue but a strategic necessity. As space becomes increasingly militarized, the durability of LOAC will depend on whether accountability can follow the conflict beyond Earth.

4.6. *The Rhetoric of “Peaceful Purposes” and Legal Sleight of Hand*

Article IV of the OST requires the Moon and other celestial bodies to be used exclusively for peaceful purposes and prohibits the placement of nuclear weapons or WMDs in orbit, but the term “peaceful purposes” is not defined in the Treaty, and states have often interpreted it in a way allowing militarized activity so long as it remains non-aggressive.¹³⁸ This interpretation allows for ISR (intelligence, surveillance, and reconnaissance), navigation, and command and control support – activities clearly serving military objectives but not per se acts of violence.¹³⁹ Others have effectively adopted a variant of *si vis pacem, para bellum* – “if you want peace, prepare for war” – claiming military satellite systems, reconnaissance in space, or even certain defence interference are compatible with peace as long as they do not constitute over aggression. China, for example, in official statements frames development of counterspace and proximity operations as part of “security and peaceful use” of space, condemning only “improper military use.” In that framing, “peaceful” becomes a semantic shield rather than a genuine limitation.¹⁴⁰

No treaty explicitly bars this rhetorical maneuver. The OST’s prohibition applies only to nuclear weapons and WMDs, not conventional weapons or jamming systems. The Soviet Union’s FOBS in the 1970s exploited definitional gaps by placing nuclear payloads in partial orbit to evade the Treaty’s text.¹⁴¹ Such episodes reveal that states will fill gaps in law to their advantage. Because “peaceful purposes” is open to interpretation under Vienna Convention rules of treaty interpretation, states can advocate contested readings.¹⁴² Some commentators have criticized this as a “legal loophole” exploited in practice.¹⁴³

¹³⁸ See Pobje, E., & Azcárate Ortega, A. (2024, September). *Outer space and the use of force: Space security legal primer* [“The term ‘peaceful purposes’ has been understood by many States to mean non-aggressive or non-hostile use, rather than non-military.”]. United Nations Institute for Disarmament Research. https://unidir.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/UNIDIR_Outer_Space_and_Use_of_Force.pdf.

¹³⁹ *Peaceful use and exploration of outer space*. (2024). *Space security lexicon* [“While this is a generally accepted obligation, the meaning of ‘peaceful purposes’ is not understood by all in the same manner...outer space is now filled with satellites used for military purposes such as intelligence gathering, reconnaissance, navigation, targeting over battlefields, early warning of missile and air hostile operations, or military communications, usually without protest from the international community.”]. <https://spacesecuritylexicon.org/terminology/peaceful-use-and-exploration-of-outer-space-peaceful-purposes>.

¹⁴⁰ People’s Republic of China. (2022, January 28). *Full text: China’s space program: A 2021 perspective*. State Council Information Office [“China has always advocated the use of outer space for peaceful purposes ... and opposes any attempt to turn outer space into a weapon or battlefield or launch an arms race in outer space.”]. https://english.www.gov.cn/archive/whitepaper/202201/28/content_WS61f35b3dc6d09c94e48a467a.html.

¹⁴¹ Listner, M. (2022, October 17). *FOBS, MOBS, and the reality of the Article IV nuclear weapons prohibition*. *The Space Review* [“The Soviets attempted to sidestep the conflict with the Outer Space Treaty by insisting the system would not make a complete orbit of the Earth.”]. <https://thespacereview.com/article/4466/1>.

¹⁴² Edlund Otterstedt, A. (2020). *Peaceful purposes in international space law* (Master’s thesis, Lund University Faculty of Law) [“The rules governing the interpretation of treaties are laid down in the articles 31–33 Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties (VCLT) which also reflect customary international law. ... Hence, it is possible that the meaning of ‘peaceful purposes’ has developed and even changed over time.”]. <https://lup.lub.lu.se/luur/download?fileOId=9038105&func=downloadFile&recordOId=9034554>.

¹⁴³ Stonis, D. (2022). *Ambiguities in space law as path towards weaponization of space: The case of the Outer Space Treaty. Remarks on regulation of weaponization of outer space by space law*. *Copernicus Political & Legal Studies*,

If left unchecked, this elasticity may undercut the normative force of LOAC in space – turning aspirational constraints into optional posture. The law must anticipate and neutralize that slippage, either through refined treaty drafting, scholarly consensus, or interpretive authority. Just as the San Remo Manual and Tallinn Manual clarified the law of naval warfare and cyber conflict, a comparable effort focused on space could provide authoritative guidance without requiring formal treaty amendment.¹⁴⁴ In the meantime, states should articulate their positions clearly and consistently, reinforcing state practice as a source of customary law.

These examples illustrate LOAC's future in space depends not only on reaffirming its core principles but on re-imagining how those principles operate in an environment shaped by deniability, private-sector entanglement, and doctrinal silence. The legal regime will be shaped by those who define its terms early, fill its gaps with substance, and resist the erosion of normative constraint in the name of technological progress.

5. CONCLUSION

Outer space is no longer a frontier of abstraction or spectacle. It has become a critical domain of military dependence, infrastructural entanglement, and strategic vulnerability. As armed conflict approaches – or even emerges from – this domain, the need to clarify, adapt, and operationalize the law of armed conflict becomes more than theoretical. It becomes existential and strategically urgent. The principles of LOAC, long grounded in terrestrial warfare, retain their relevance in orbit. Yet they require translation at the doctrinal, operational, and normative levels if they are to offer meaningful constraint in an environment defined by deniability, dual use, and enduring consequences.

Across the analysis of distinction, proportionality, necessity, and humanity, a consistent pattern emerges. Each principle remains formally applicable in the orbital domain, yet each encounters structural strain. Distinction is destabilized by dual-use infrastructure and functional opacity. Proportionality becomes difficult to assess where harm is systemic, cascading, and temporally extended. Necessity risks expansion through preemptive logic in an environment characterized by informational asymmetry. Humanity confronts the long-term degradation of a shared orbital environment upon which civilian systems increasingly depend. None of these principles completely collapses in space, but each requires doctrinal clarification and institutional reinforcement if it is to retain constraining force.

The legal questions raised by space warfare are not unprecedented. They echo earlier dilemmas over chemical weapons, nuclear fallout, and environmental devastation. As with those precedents, the challenge is not merely to regulate technology but to assert the continuing authority of law when strategic interests tempt its abandonment. The central question is not whether LOAC extends to outer space as a matter of formal doctrine; it does. The deeper question is whether it can function there as a meaningful system of restraint. Doctrinal applicability alone does not ensure operational effectiveness. Legal principles must be translated into technical standards and institutional practices capable of surviving the

I, 74–77 [“The unresolved ambiguity of the term ‘peaceful’ would leave a loophole for the use of space for military purposes.”]. <https://czasopisma.marszalek.com.pl/uploads/periodicals/cpls/4/cpls408.pdf>.

¹⁴⁴ Shull, A., & Aganaba, T. (2023, January 29). *Formulating, interpreting and applying international law in outer space*. Centre for International Governance Innovation [“...the leading authorities on the subject likely to be the Tallinn Manual on the International Law Applicable to Cyber Warfare, the Woomera Manual on the International Law of Military Space Operations and the McGill Manual on International Law Applicable to Military Uses of Outer Space ... these efforts are a linear progression on the success of the San Remo Manual on International Law Applicable to Armed Conflicts at Sea ...”]. <https://www.cigionline.org/articles/formulating-interpreting-and-applying-international-law-in-space/>.

realities of orbital conflict. The risk is not simply that conflict will occur in space. The bigger risk is that it will occur outside the law's reach and therefore unmoored from principles that have, however imperfectly, at least attempted to humanize warfare on Earth. The disabling of a communications satellite, the blinding of sensors, or the fragmentation of an orbital track may each unfold in silence, without smoke or flame, yet produce consequences as grave as any battlefield detonation.

To prevent this trajectory, states must act with interpretive clarity and normative resolve. Technical ambiguity cannot be allowed to substitute for legal uncertainty. The absence of treaty language does not absolve responsibility; it heightens the need for doctrinal precision and enforceable restraint. LOAC must not only reach orbit – it must hold there. If ambiguity continues to outpace institutional adaptation, the erosion of constraint will occur gradually rather than explosively. The danger is less dramatic confrontation than slow corrosion of normative discipline – a trajectory that recalls Eliot's warning that the world may end "not with a bang but with a whimper."

© The Author(s) 2025. Published by Space Court Foundation. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted reuse, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

AMENDING ARTICLE 6 OF THE NORTH ATLANTIC TREATY TO EXPLICITLY ENSURE ARTICLE 5 COVERS THE SPACE OBJECTS OF PARTIES

GRAHAM MEYER¹

ABSTRACT

Outer space and the space objects of Parties to the *North Atlantic Treaty* have emerged as indispensable components in the North Atlantic Treaty Organization's (NATO) mission to ensure collective self-defence and deter aggression. However, the text of the North Atlantic Treaty has no mention of outer space nor the Parties' space objects. Article 5 of the North Atlantic Treaty confirms the doctrine of collective self-defence. Instead, it is Article 6 which outlines what territories and what assets of the Parties are covered by Article 5. Parties' space objects are not assets currently listed within Article 6.

This omission leaves the space objects of Parties outside the bounds of Article 5 and therefore vulnerable to interference or armed attack. NATO's current approach to outer space and Parties' space objects is entirely too weak in certifying Article 5's application to this domain and such objects. Such weakness is confirmed when looking at NATO's current approach to cyberspace and Article 5, which is nearly identical to its approach to outer space. Recent disregard for NATO's non-binding statements on Article 5's application to cyberspace implies it will have equal disregard for Article 5's application to space objects.

To prevent such undermining of NATO's commitment to collective self-defence and deterrence, an amendment should be made to prong two of Article 6 of the North Atlantic Treaty. The language "or space objects of any of the Parties when launching to or operating in outer space" should be added to the end of prong two. Such an amendment would ensure that NATO's doctrine of collective self-defence remains rock-solid and continues to deter threatening states. The strength of NATO lies in the certainty of its response to aggression and, most importantly, armed attacks.

KEYWORDS: North Atlantic Treaty, Article 5, Article 6, Outer Space.

¹ Graham Meyer, Law School: University of Nebraska College of Law, Lincoln, Nebraska, US; gmeyer9@huskers.unl.edu

1. THE NORTH ATLANTIC TREATY'S CURRENT COLLECTIVE DEFENCE DOCTRINE

1.1. *The Current State of Articles 5 and 6 of the North Atlantic Treaty*

Article 5 of the North Atlantic Treaty serves as the bedrock of NATO's collective defence alliance. Article 5 makes clear that:

The Parties agree that an armed attack against one or more of them in Europe or North America shall be considered an attack against them all and consequently they agree that, if such an armed attack occurs, each of them, in exercise of the right of individual or collective self-defence recognised by Article 51 of the Charter of the United Nations, will assist the Party or Parties so attacked by taking forthwith, individually and in concert with the other Parties, such action as it deems necessary, including the use of armed force, to restore and maintain the security of the North Atlantic area.²

The provisions of Article 5 have ensured the collective security of all NATO members since its foundation in 1949. The certainty of collective self-defence created by Article 5 maintained the security of NATO Parties through the Cold War and, to this day, continues to protect Parties in the face of war in Europe involving Russia. For 76 years, Article 5 has been successful in deterring aggression and armed attack against Parties, making NATO the most successful military alliance in human history.

Although Article 5 confirms collective self-defence in response to an armed attack against a Party, it is Article 6 of the North Atlantic Treaty which determines what will be considered an armed attack for the purpose of invoking Article 5 by a Party. Article 6 outlines that:

For the purpose of Article 5, an armed attack on one or more of the Parties is deemed to include an armed attack:

on the territory of any of the Parties in Europe or North America, on the Algerian Departments of France, on the territory of [Türkiye] or on the Islands under the jurisdiction of any of the Parties in the North Atlantic area north of the Tropic of Cancer;

on the forces, vessels, or aircraft of any of the Parties, when in or over these territories or any other area in Europe in which occupation forces of any of the Parties were stationed on the date when the Treaty entered into force or the Mediterranean Sea or the North Atlantic area north of the Tropic of Cancer.³

Article 6 places clear territorial and asset limitations on when an armed attack is covered by Article 5. Specifically, Article 6 makes no mention of Article 5 covering outer space or the space objects of Parties operating in such a domain. The furthest reach of Article 5 allowed by Article 6 is in prong two related to aircraft over the territories of Parties articulated in prong one, falling well short of extending to outer space and the space objects of Parties.

1.2. *The Shortcomings of Article 6 of the North Atlantic Treaty*

A plain reading of Article 6 reasonably leads to the conclusion that Article 5 does not apply to outer space nor the space objects of Parties operating in this domain. Such a reality leaves the space objects of Parties dangerously exposed to interference and armed attack by malicious actors and states. Lacking coverage

² North Atlantic Treaty, Apr. 4, 1949, 63 Stat. 2241, 34 U.N.T.S. 243, art. 5.

³ North Atlantic Treaty, Apr. 4, 1949, 63 Stat. 2241, 34 U.N.T.S. 243, art. 6.

by Article 5, Parties' space objects invite meddling by hostile actors and states due to the lack of an ensured collective defence response to armed attacks against such assets.

Leaving Parties' space objects outside the purview of Article 5 is highly irresponsible, given that NATO Parties rely so heavily on space-based assets to ensure their defence and security. Whether on land or sea, in air or cyberspace, NATO missions and operations utilize and rely on space-based assets to always ensure collective self-defence in all desired circumstances. Leaving the space objects of Parties and space as a domain beyond the bounds of Article 5 makes such vital objects vulnerable to interference and armed attack. This reality calls into question NATO's willingness to protect Parties' space objects from armed attack and erodes the certainty of collective self-defence, the bedrock of NATO since its inception.⁴

The aforementioned extension of Article 5 to "aircraft operating over only certain portions of Parties' territories" would be difficult, if not impossible, to extend to space objects. For starters, the reference to aircraft operating *over* specific territories of Parties can reasonably be inferred to mean a Party's sovereign airspace. Thus, extending this language to outer space and its prohibition on sovereignty would directly violate international space law.

Article 1 of the Convention on International Civil Aviation (Chicago Convention) makes clear that "The contracting States recognize that every State has complete and exclusive sovereignty over the airspace above its territory."⁵ However, Article II of the 1967 Outer Space Treaty (OST) also makes clear that "[o]uter space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies, is not subject to national appropriation by claim of sovereignty, by means of use or occupation, or by any other means."⁶ All NATO Parties are States Parties to the Chicago Convention, while only four NATO Parties, Albania, Latvia, Montenegro, and North Macedonia, are not also States Parties to the OST, with none of the four being considered space-faring nations.

The sovereignty over airspace outlined in the Chicago Convention is irreconcilable with the non-appropriation principle of the Outer Space Treaty. Therefore, trying to extend the existing language of Article 6 related to Article 5 covering Parties' airplanes over certain territories to also include Parties' space objects would violate Article II of the Outer Space Treaty, considering Article 1 of the Chicago Convention. Furthermore, even if these two treaties could be reconciled, because space objects constantly orbit around the Earth, the space objects of the Parties would only be temporarily located over the specific territories listed in prong one of Article 6. Moreover, trying to argue that space objects are essentially aircrafts to extend Article 5 to such objects would be fanciful, given the undeniable distinction between aircraft and space objects as categorized military assets.

1.3. *The Shortcomings of NATO's Current Approach to Space*

Absent explicit treaty language in the North Atlantic Treaty related to Article 5 applying to outer space and space objects, NATO has attempted to remedy this dangerous omission in an entirely unsatisfactory manner. At the June 2021 Brussels NATO Summit, NATO leaders limited themselves to saying that attacks to, from, or within space *could* lead to the invocation of Article 5 on a *case-by-case basis*.⁷ No mention of Parties' space objects being covered by Article 5. The glaring issue with this approach to space by NATO leaders is that it is not in any way internationally legally binding on Parties. At best, it is

⁴ Unal, B. (2019). *Cybersecurity of NATO's Space-based Strategic Assets*. Chatham House. The Royal Institute of International Affairs.

⁵ International Civil Aviation Organization. (1980). *Convention on international civil aviation*, (6th ed., Doc 7300/6), art. 1.

⁶ Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies, Jan. 27, 1967, 18 U.S.T. 2410, 610 U.N.T.S. 205.

⁷ North Atlantic Treaty Organization. "NATO's Approach to Space." *North Atlantic Treaty Organization*, 30 July 2025, www.nato.int/en/what-we-do/deterrence-and-defence/natos-approach-to-space.

a recognition that outer space is a potential new domain in which Article 5 must extend to, but at worst, it is nothing but empty words.

Regardless, such statements by NATO leaders create no binding legal obligations on Parties to treat armed attacks in outer space or against space objects as being covered by Article 5, as they must with territories and military assets listed in Article 6. More concerning, however, is the use by NATO leaders of flimsy language like “could” or “case-by-case” to describe the possible application of Article 5 to outer space. This language is surely lacking when compared to the concrete and unambiguous language found throughout the North Atlantic Treaty. Such ambiguous language by NATO leaders can in no way be expected to communicate to malicious actors and states that NATO is serious about ensuring collective self-defence in outer space and safeguarding the Parties’ space objects. To illustrate this failure, one needs only look at the efficacy of NATO leaders and their language concerning how Article 5 applies to cyberspace.

1.4. *A Comparison of NATO’s Current Approaches to Cyberspace and Space*

At the very same June 2021 NATO summit in Brussels, NATO leaders repeated nearly identical language used to describe Article 5 and outer space when talking about Article 5’s applicability to cyberspace. NATO leaders stated that malicious cyber activities *might* be considered an armed attack which *could* be considered an armed attack, determined on a *case-by-case basis*.⁸ Just like outer space, NATO leaders’ weak and non-binding language regarding Article 5 and cyberspace places cyberspace in an ambiguous and vulnerable position, inviting intervention and armed attack by malicious actors and states. Unlike outer space and Parties’ space object which lack meaningful examples of being threatened with armed attack by malicious actors and states, there are ample cases of cyberspace and Parties’ cyber capabilities being interfered with and targeted for hypothetical armed attacks.

Since Russia’s full-scale invasion of Ukraine in 2022, hostile cyberspace operations by Russia against NATO Parties have increased dramatically in both frequency and scale.⁹ In the face of NATO leaders’ ambiguous language concerning Article 5, cyberspace, and space objects, the continued and growing malicious cyber activities against NATO should be perceived as demonstrating that the statements made at the 2021 Brussels summit go unheeded. By leaving cyberspace in a grey zone related to Article 5, NATO leaders have failed to deter threatening states from acting against NATO Parties in cyberspace. Continued interference with the Parties’ cyber infrastructure and capabilities casts doubts on Article 5 supposedly being applicable to both cyberspace and space objects, undermining NATO’s commitment to collective self-defence.

It should be noted that some NATO leaders have defended ambiguous language relating to Article 5’s coverage. Former NATO Secretary-General Jens Stoltenberg argued that intentional vagueness in defining Article 5’s coverage related to cyberspace specifically acts as a deterrent and forces threatening states to second guess that viability of malicious cyber activities against NATO Parties.¹⁰ However, the aforementioned increase in malicious cyber activities against NATO Parties casts doubt on such a presumption. Instead, this potentially signals that ambiguous language invites threatening states to test the coverage of Article 5 when vague in order to chip away at the certainty it is designed to provide.

NATO leaders used nearly identical language to describe Article 5 and space objects. The ongoing malicious cyber activities directed against NATO Parties demonstrate that ambiguous language fails to deter threatening states. NATO should expect the same failure relating to the Parties’ space objects, given the use of identical language. The failure of the non-binding statements made by NATO leaders in 2021 to

⁸ North Atlantic Treaty Organization. “Cyber Defence.” North Atlantic Treaty Organization, 30 July 2024, www.nato.int/en/what-we-do/deterrence-and-defence/cyber-defence.

⁹ Dynner, A. M. (2023). Russia continuing cyberthreats against NATO countries. *PISM Bulletin*, 172, 2291.

¹⁰ Prucková, M. (2022). Cyber attacks and Article 5—a note on a blurry but consistent position of NATO. *The NATO Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence (CCDOE)*.

deter malicious cyber activity makes clear that an unambiguous and explicit binding application of Article 5 to Parties' space objects is necessary to deter threatening states.

1.5. *The Present and Future Threat to NATO Space Objects*

Although the space objects of a NATO Party have yet to be physically targeted by a threatening state, it is important to recognize that such a targeting remains possible in the future. Specifically, Russia has successfully tested anti-satellite weapons.¹¹ The existence of such weapons makes the possible targeting of NATO Parties' space objects no longer a question of possibility, but probability. The weak language currently employed by NATO to describe Article 5's coverage of space objects may increase that probability in light of identical language failing to deter continued malicious cyber activities. In a world where modern militaries are increasingly reliant on space objects for operations, is it wise to leave such vital objects outside the explicit coverage of Article 5?

2. A BETTER COLLECTIVE DEFENCE DOCTRINE INCORPORATING OUTER SPACE

2.1. *Proposed Changes to Article 6 of the North Atlantic Treaty*

To ensure that it is clear that outer space and Parties' space objects are covered by Article 5 to deter both malicious actors and states alike, binding change to the North Atlantic Treaty's language is necessary. Specifically, the second prong of Article 6 of the North Atlantic Treaty should be amended to include Parties' space objects as assets covered by Article 5. An amendment to the second prong of Article 6 should read as follows:

on the forces, vessels, or aircraft of any of the Parties, when in or over these territories or any other area in Europe in which occupation forces of any of the Parties were stationed on the date when the Treaty entered into force or the Mediterranean Sea or the North Atlantic area north of the Tropic of Cancer, *or space objects of any of the Parties when launching to or operating in outer space.*

The inclusion of "or space objects of any of the Parties when launching to or operating in outer space" at the end of the second prong of Article 6 would make unequivocally clear that the Parties' space objects are covered by Article 5. Such an amendment would make threatening actors and states think twice about interfering with or attacking Parties' space object, for fear of Article 5 retaliation.¹²

Furthermore, the specific language of this amendment would not otherwise unintentionally expand Article 5's application beyond the domains and assets articulated by either prong of Article 6. Article 6 has clear limitations on the territorial extension of Article 5, wishing to keep its application contained to the North Atlantic region. French Guiana is an ideal example, which, due to its geographical location south of the Tropic of Cancer, is not a territory covered by Article 6. However, French Guiana remains the primary and preferred launch location for many European Parties' space objects. The language of the proposed amendment would ensure that when any future space object is transported to or assembled in French Guiana, it would not be covered by Article 6, but once said objects were launched into or operating in space, Article 6, and therefore Article 5, would apply.

By limiting the protection of Parties' space objects to only when they are launching into or operating in outer space, the amendment would avoid inadvertently expanding such protection of Article 5 to geographic regions and territories not originally desired to be covered at the inception of Article 6. Moreover, by limiting Article 5's coverage to only Parties' space objects and not outer space itself, the proposed amendment would comply with Article II of the OST and its requirement of non-appropriation.

¹¹ Sankaran, J. (2022). Russia's Anti-Satellite Weapons. *Arms Control Today*, 52(2), 14-19.

¹² Person, R., & McFaul, M. (2022). What Putin fears most. *Journal of Democracy*, 33(2), 18-27.

2.2. *The Legal Procedure for Amending the North Atlantic Treaty*

The process for amending the second prong of Article 6 of the North Atlantic Treaty is governed by Article 12. Article 12 permits that “[a]fter the Treaty has been in force for ten years, or at any time thereafter, the Parties shall, if any of them so requests, consult together for the purpose of reviewing the Treaty,”¹³ The hurdle of requiring that a Party request consultation and review of the treaty for purposes of amending would prove difficult to overcome. As of the writing of this paper, no Party has signalled its interest in amending the North Atlantic Treaty to address space objects. Therefore, before the proposed amendment to the second prong of Article 6 can even be considered, a NATO Party will have to request consultation and review. This paper, in part, hopes to bring the issue of Article 5’s lacking coverage of space objects to the attention of NATO Parties in the hope that consultation and review will be requested.

For the sake of continuing this analysis, hypothetically, if such a request were made and the proposed amendment was accepted as necessary, the actual amendment of the treaty itself would require unanimous ratification by all Parties in line with their respective constitutional processes, in line with Article 11.¹⁴ This would undoubtedly be a long and arduous process, potentially taking years. Such a reality highlights the need to raise this issue now and begin lobbying the whole of the NATO alliance to take seriously the issue of amending Article 5 to explicitly cover space objects and to start taking concrete steps towards making such an amendment a reality in line with Articles 11 and 12.

3. CONCLUSION

Outer space and the space objects of Parties have become integrated and vital components of NATO’s continued success in ensuring collective defence and deterring armed aggression. However, the ambiguities surrounding Article 5’s applicability to outer space and Parties’ space objects risk leaving a dangerous gap in NATO’s defensive guarantees. The current state of NATO’s approach to outer space and Parties’ space objects is entirely inadequate given their importance to NATO’s mission. NATO must learn from recent disregard for its non-binding statements related to cyberspace and Article 5 and ensure such disregard is not extended Parties’ space objects. The surest way to make it explicit that Article 5 does apply to Parties’ space objects is by amending prong two of Article 6. This would leave no room for doubt that Parties’ space objects are protected by Article 5 and would instil confidence that NATO is committed to the doctrine of collective self-defence in all domains and for all assets.

¹³ North Atlantic Treaty, Apr. 4, 1949, 63 Stat. 2241, 34 U.N.T.S. 243, art. 12.

¹⁴ North Atlantic Treaty, Apr. 4, 1949, 63 Stat. 2241, 34 U.N.T.S. 243, art. 11.

© The Author(s) 2026. Published by Space Court Foundation. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted reuse, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

APPLYING INTERNATIONAL SPACE LAW AND *JUS AD BELLUM* TO USES OF THE ELECTROMAGNETIC SPECTRUM IN OUTER SPACE

ADINA SAKURA DARBYSHIRE¹

ABSTRACT

The electromagnetic spectrum (EMS) in outer space, in particular, the radio frequency spectrum, which forms a part of the EMS, serves a crucial function for transmitting signals between satellites in orbit and ground stations on Earth for the supply of essential services. For example, satellites rely upon the EMS to monitor natural disasters, track the spread of diseases, and provide navigation services for emergency personnel. For the purposes of this paper, such uses of the EMS in outer space shall be referred to as ‘constructive’ uses.

The EMS can also be utilised for ‘obstructive’ uses such as temporarily interfering with or manipulating satellite signals (i.e., jamming and spoofing) and ‘destructive’ uses such as permanently damaging satellites and even terrestrial electronics (e.g., through directed energy systems). The obstructive and destructive uses can undermine the constructive uses, thereby posing risks to human life and well-being. As reliance on satellite systems and their constructive uses accelerates worldwide, managing these risks is increasingly relevant for disaster preparedness, critical infrastructure resilience, and international legal governance, requiring the careful examination of applicable legal frameworks.

This paper adopts a human-centred approach to examining the international space law framework, including *jus ad bellum*, as a means of regulating and protecting satellite systems, their constructive uses, and the lives that they support. Further, this paper identifies legal lacunae and doctrinal ambiguities in the application of the international space law framework to the obstructive and destructive uses as areas requiring further research and policy discussions.

KEYWORDS: International Space Law, *Jus ad Bellum*, Space Security, Electromagnetic Spectrum, Electromagnetic Warfare.

¹ Space Court Foundation Intern; adina.darbyshire@spacecourtfoundation.org

1. INTRODUCTION

The electromagnetic spectrum (EMS) refers to “the entire range of wavelengths or frequencies of electromagnetic radiation [...]”.² The radio frequency (RF) spectrum lies at the low-energy end of the EMS, with the longest wavelengths and lowest frequencies, making it suitable for transmitting signals between ground stations on Earth and satellites in outer space.³ Thus, the EMS is integral for satellite systems and their ‘constructive’ uses, including telecommunications, navigation, and Earth observation (EO),⁴ upon which lives increasingly depend. By way of illustration, satellites offering telecommunications and navigation services allow persons in need of urgent assistance to contact emergency services and for emergency personnel to locate them. Further, EO satellites are used to monitor and support the management of, *inter alia*, natural disasters, climate change, armed conflicts, agriculture and food stocks, disease epidemiology, watercourses, and the weather.⁵

At the same time, the EMS can be utilised for ‘obstructive’ uses by interfering with satellite signals (“jamming”) or mimicking satellite signals to deceive the target into accepting false signals as legitimate (“spoofing”).⁶ The EMS can also be harnessed for ‘destructive’ uses using directed energy weapons (DEWs) such as high-energy lasers, high-powered microwave weapons, and electromagnetic pulse (EMP) weapons.⁷ An EMP refers to a burst of electromagnetic energy capable of damaging satellites, causing blackouts, and disabling critical infrastructure on Earth, whether generated artificially by a DEW or nuclear detonation, or occurring naturally as a result of a geomagnetic storm.⁸ DEWs at low levels of power may temporarily interfere with rather than permanently destroy satellites, in which case, they would constitute obstructive uses.⁹

The obstructive and destructive uses can undermine satellite systems and their constructive uses, with flow-on effects for individuals, economies, and the environment. Consider the events of 19 July 2024 when the world went dark. An error by the cybersecurity firm CrowdStrike disabled 8.5 million Windows computers, which, in effect, grounded planes, prevented patients from receiving medical attention, and

² Merriam-Webster. (n.d.). *Electromagnetic spectrum*. Merriam-Webster. <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/electromagnetic%20spectrum>

³ Science Mission Directorate. (2010). *Radio Waves*. Science Mission Directorate, National Aeronautics and Space Administration. http://science.nasa.gov/ems/05_radiowaves; National Frequency Agency. (n.d.). *What is the frequency spectrum?* National Frequency Agency, Government of France. <https://www.anfr.fr/en/about-the-anfr/what-is-the-frequency-spectrum>; National Aeronautics and Space Administration. (2025, February 5). *State-of-the-Art of Small Spacecraft Technology*. National Aeronautics and Space Administration. <https://www.nasa.gov/smallsat-institute/sst-soa/soa-communications/>

⁴ See, for example, Eurisy. (n.d.). *Satellite Applications*. Eurisy. <https://www.eurisy.eu/satellite-applications/>; UN Office for Outer Space Affairs (UNOOSA). (n.d.). *Benefits of Space for Humankind*. UNOOSA. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/benefits-of-space/benefits.html>

⁵ Eurisy, *supra* note 4; UNOOSA, *supra* note 4.

⁶ Way, T. (2019, October 28). *Counterspace Weapons 101*. Center for Strategic & International Studies. <https://aerospace.csis.org/aerospace101/counterspace-weapons-101/>

⁷ Beard, J., & Stephens, D. (Eds.). (2024). *The Woomera Manual on the International Law of Military Space Operations*. Oxford University Press. (“Woomera Manual”) (p. 208); Grand-Clément, S. (2022, May 12). *Directed Energy Weapons: A New Look at an ‘Old’ Technology*. The United Nations Institute for Disarmament Research. <https://unidir.org/directed-energy-weapons-a-new-look-at-an-old-technology/>

⁸ Luzetsky, H. R. (2025, June 5). *EMP Hardening of Critical Infrastructure*. Homeland Defense & Security Information Analysis Center (HDIAC), U.S. Department of Defense. <https://hdiac.dtic.mil/articles/emp-hardening-of-critical-infrastructure/>

⁹ U.S. Government Accountability Office. (May 25, 2023). *Science & Tech Spotlight: Directed Energy Weapons*. U.S. Government Accountability Office. <https://www.gao.gov/products/gao-23-106717>; Woomera Manual, *supra* note 7 (p. 209).

cost US Fortune 500 companies an estimated US\$5.4 billion in losses.¹⁰ Not only could similar flow-on effects potentially occur due to a widespread disruption to satellites or a terrestrial power outage, but there could also be environmental implications given the role of EO satellites in climate change monitoring. In the case of CrowdStrike, 97% of computers were reportedly restored after one week,¹¹ whereas it has been estimated that a severe geomagnetic storm (known as a Carrington event) could result in a power outage lasting up to two years.¹² Whether an EMP occurs due to space weather or DEWs, the consequences of such a prolonged power outage could be devastating.

While all such effects warrant examination, this paper takes a human-centred approach, focusing on risks to human life and well-being. This paper examines the application of the international space law framework, including *jus ad bellum*, to the obstructive and destructive uses, with an emphasis on the regulation of second- and third-order risks (in decreasing order of directness). Less emphasis will be accorded to first-order risks, which refer to risks of direct harm to individuals (e.g., adverse health impacts of electromagnetic radiation for individuals on Earth or astronauts and space tourists in outer space), given their relative indeterminacy.

Second-order risks refer to risks of harm to essential services or critical infrastructure on Earth upon which lives depend, thereby posing a threat to individuals. Namely, an EMP-induced power outage would threaten basic human needs, as power is critical for refrigerating and transporting food, electric pumps and treatment facilities ensuring the supply of water, and the storage of medications and life-sustaining devices (e.g., ventilators).¹³ Given such risks, the National Coordinating Center for Communications (NCC) of the US has published critical infrastructure resilience guidelines in the event of an EMP.¹⁴ These guidelines recognise that, for certain infrastructure, an EMP-induced power outage of a few hours, minutes, or even seconds could threaten human life (e.g., nuclear power plant controls).¹⁵

Third-order risks refer to risks of harm to satellite systems, which in turn can threaten essential services or critical infrastructure on Earth, thereby posing a threat to individuals. The obstructive and destructive uses can disable satellites and render their constructive uses unavailable, weakening systems on Earth designed to protect against, *inter alia*, natural disasters, food shortages, the spread of disease, and lack of clean water. For example, the Iran Meteorological Organization reportedly cited the jamming of satellite signals as a reason for its inability to “provide sufficient warning to Tehran citizens ahead of a June 12, 2014 sandstorm that claimed five lives and injured 44 Tehran citizens [...]”.¹⁶ Further, according to a 2026 survey by the Royal Institute of Navigation of at least 271 respondents from the maritime sector, 7% and

¹⁰ Livesay, B., & Wilson, C. (Eds.). (2024, September 24). 'Deeply sorry,' CrowdStrike boss apologises for global IT outage. BBC. <https://www.bbc.com/news/live/ckgnxd7d26gt>

¹¹ *Ibid.*

¹² Lloyds. (2013). *Solar Storm Risk to the North American Electric Grid*. Lloyd's. <https://assets.lloyds.com/assets/pdf-solar-storm-risk-to-the-north-american-electric-grid/1/pdf-Solar-Storm-Risk-to-the-North-American-Electric-Grid.pdf> (p. 16).

¹³ See, for example, National Coordinating Center for Communications (NCC). (2019, February 5). *Electromagnetic Pulse (EMP) Protection and Resilience Guidelines for Critical Infrastructure and Equipment*. NCC, U.S. Department of Homeland Security. https://www.cisa.gov/sites/default/files/publications/19_0307_CISA_EMP-Protection-Resilience-Guidelines.pdf; G Granholm, F. Tin, D., & Ciotton, G. R. (2023). Critical Energy Infrastructure and Health: How Loss of Power May Kill. *Prehospital and Disaster Medicine*, 38(2), 279–280. doi:10.1017/S1049023X23000274; U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA). (2019, June). *Power Resilience: Guide for Water and Wastewater Utilities*. EPA. <https://www.epa.gov/sites/default/files/2016-03/documents/160212-powerresiliencguide508.pdf>

¹⁴ NCC, *supra* note 13.

¹⁵ *Ibid* (pp. iii–iv).

¹⁶ Center for Human Rights in Iran. (2014, July 23). *Jamming of Satellite Broadcast Signals Prevented Ability to See Fatal Sandstorm Coming*. Center for Human Rights in Iran. <https://iranhumanrights.org/2014/07/jamming-satellite/>

11% experienced incorrect time displays on Safety of Life at Sea (SOLAS) and Global Maritime Distress and Safety System (GMDSS) equipment, respectively, during a jamming or spoofing attack against the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS).¹⁷ This indicates a risk that such equipment would transmit incorrect location data in an emergency.¹⁸

As reliance on satellite systems and their constructive uses accelerates worldwide, managing these risks is increasingly relevant for disaster preparedness, critical infrastructure resilience, and international legal governance, requiring the careful examination of applicable legal frameworks. Identifying legal lacunae in the application of international law, including the international space law framework, is particularly salient for the obstructive and destructive uses, whose non-kinetic nature and cascading effects do not necessarily align with traditional legal conceptions. Accordingly, Section 2 will examine the applicability of the international space law framework to the obstructive and destructive uses.

2. APPLICABILITY OF THE INTERNATIONAL SPACE LAW FRAMEWORK

The Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, Including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies (“Outer Space Treaty” or “OST”) lies at the heart of international space law. As the long title indicates, the OST applies to the “exploration and use” of “outer space”.¹⁹ Before proceeding to the question of *how* the international space law framework applies to the obstructive and destructive uses (as considered in Section 3), it is necessary to assess whether such uses fall within the scope of this language, such that the OST would apply.

Looking first at the meaning of “outer space”, this can be characterised as an area beyond 100 km above mean sea level (i.e., Kármán line).²⁰ Based on a strict spatialist approach (and a tentative presumption that the Kármán line applies), the applicability of the OST would hinge on whether the obstructive and destructive uses occur above the Kármán line. As satellites maintain a physical presence in orbit, it is generally uncontroversial that satellite systems are governed by international space law, even if ground stations are on Earth. Meanwhile, obstructive and destructive uses targeting satellite signals rely on the delivery of energy rather than mass, and may originate from aircraft or ground stations, thereby only having a physical presence below the Kármán line. Accordingly, the extent to which obstructive and destructive uses could be characterised as existing in “outer space” is uncertain. For example, international space law may apply to space-based DEWs or satellite-to-satellite jamming but have limited application to ground-based DEWs targeting satellites or to jamming attacks against satellite signals occurring on Earth.

According to a functionalist approach to the meaning of “outer space”, the determinative factor is whether an activity is space-related, so it is arguable that obstructive and destructive uses are governed by international space law insofar as these affect satellite systems. This is consistent with the *Tallinn Manual 2.0 on the International Law Applicable to Cyber Operations* (“Tallinn Manual”), a non-binding manual prepared by leading international law practitioners and scholars on cyber operations, which provides that “[a]ctivities on the earth also qualify as space activities when they involve activities, or otherwise achieve

¹⁷ Royal Institute of Navigation (January 2026). *Impacts of GNSS Interference on Maritime Safety: A special report by the RIN Maritime GNSS Interference Working Group*. https://rin.org.uk/page/RIN_Maritime_Report (pp. 34–35).

¹⁸ *Ibid.*

¹⁹ *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies*, opened for signature January 27 1967, 610 UNTS 205 (entered into force October 10 1967) (“Outer Space Treaty”) (art. XIII).

²⁰ Ortega, A. A., & Samson, V. (Eds.). (2023). *A Lexicon for Outer Space Security* (p. 34). UN Institute of Disarmament Research (UNIDIR). <https://doi.org/10.37559/WMD/23/Space/05>

effects, in outer space [...]”²¹ However, the Tallinn Manual also provides that the applicability of space law is limited in respect of satellite-to-Earth cyber communications, which constitute “space-enabled cyber operations” as distinguished from “cyber-enabled space operations”.²² By analogy, obstructive uses occurring entirely on Earth may constitute space-enabled electromagnetic operations as distinguished from EMS-enabled counter-space operations, limiting the application of space law. Thus, the precise extent to which obstructive and destructive uses constitute space activities for the purposes of the OST remains unclear and requires case-by-case assessments, which are further complicated by ongoing debates on the definition and delimitation of outer space.²³

Turning to the meaning of “exploration and use”, these terms have generally been interpreted disjointly rather than conjointly, such that it is sufficient that an obstructive or destructive use constitutes a “use” and not an “exploration” for the OST to apply.²⁴ Gorove posits that a “use” would likely exclude “the use of the sunrays for everyday seeing”, but include “the more specific or direct use of the sun's energy in outer space, especially in spatial travel or experiments, such as for propulsion, heating, etc. [...]”²⁵ By analogy, the RF spectrum is harnessed by – and in the case of naturally-occurring EMPs, can interfere with – satellite systems (i.e., passive use), whereas it can also enable satellite systems to serve specific applications, or conversely, intentionally disable or destroy those satellite systems (i.e., active use). Accordingly, the obstructive and destructive uses – which represent active rather than passive uses of the EMS – would likely constitute a “use”. As the freedom of States to use outer space is subject to duties (e.g., a “use” must be “carried out for the benefit and in the interests of all countries”),²⁶ it is material to distinguish between active and passive uses such that only the former is subject to such duties. Otherwise, States would be responsible for ensuring the EMS benefits all countries in its natural, passive state.²⁷

While recognising that not all obstructive and destructive uses may qualify as space activities and underlining the need to clarify doctrinal ambiguities concerning the meaning of “outer space”, Section 3 will proceed on the tentative presumption that all such “uses” are governed by international space law. Section 3 will analyse the ways in which the international space law framework may limit the freedom of use of outer space in cases involving the obstructive and destructive uses, with a view to assessing the regulation of resulting second- and third-order risks to human life and well-being.

²¹ Schmitt, M. N. (2017). *Tallinn Manual 2.0 on the International Law Applicable to Cyber Operations* (2nd ed.) Cambridge: Cambridge University Press (“Tallinn Manual”) (p. 272).

²² Tallinn Manual, *supra* note 21 (p. 270).

²³ See, for example, UN Office for Outer Space Affairs (UNOOSA). (n.d.). *Working Group on the Definition and Delimitation of Outer Space of the Legal Subcommittee*. UNOOSA. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/copuos/lsc/ddos/index.html>

²⁴ Leclerc, T (Ed.). (2024, January 9). *Space Law: Legal Framework for Space Activities*. John Wiley & Sons (p. 69); Gorove, S. (1971, January). Freedom of Exploration and Use in the Outer Space Treaty: A Textual Analysis and Interpretation. *Denver Journal of International Law & Policy*, 1(1), 93–107. <https://digitalcommons.du.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2191&&context=djilp> (p. 97).

²⁵ Gorove, *supra* note 24 (p. 99).

²⁶ Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 19 (art. I).

²⁷ While legal frameworks other than international space law and *jus ad bellum* exceed the scope of this paper, it is notable that frameworks such as international environmental law could potentially be applied to bolster protections of outer space and its natural resources, including the EMS, independently of its use.

3. HOW THE INTERNATIONAL SPACE LAW FRAMEWORK APPLIES

3.1. Peaceful Purposes

The OST provides that “[t]he moon and other celestial bodies shall be used [...] exclusively for peaceful purposes”.²⁸ Together with the preamble and other operative provisions referring to “the peaceful exploration and use of outer space”, this article can be interpreted without limitation to celestial bodies, extending to void space.²⁹ States have generally interpreted “peaceful” to mean “non-military” or “non-aggressive”. If the former interpretation were accepted, it would follow that obstructive or destructive uses carried out by military actors are unlawful, but State practice favours the latter.³⁰

Where “peaceful” is interpreted as “non-aggressive”, obstructive and destructive uses are permissible insofar as these do not constitute prohibited uses of force, notwithstanding possible violations of other rules of general international law (e.g., non-intervention principle, laws of State responsibility). Laws concerning the use of force form part of the *jus ad bellum* regime developed under the UN Charter. As Article III of the OST expressly provides that the use of outer space shall be in accordance with the UN Charter, recourse thereto also falls within the international space law framework. Thus, the extent to which the “peaceful purposes” requirement limits the obstructive and destructive uses hinges on the relevant rules of the UN Charter.

It is notable, however, that the Tallinn Manual has referred to a “controversy” as to whether cyber activities not meeting the threshold of a use of force could nonetheless be prohibited as violating the “peaceful purposes” requirement.³¹ This distinction would also have practical implications for the obstructive and destructive uses. If such uses do not qualify as prohibited uses of force (as discussed in Section 3.3 below), it would be important to clarify whether recourse can be had to “peaceful purposes” as a standalone obligation for regulating such uses and addressing any resulting harm to human life and well-being.

3.2. Nuclear Weapons and Weapons of Mass Destruction

Article IV of the OST provides that no objects carrying nuclear weapons or weapons of mass destruction (WMD) shall be placed into orbit, installed on celestial bodies, or stationed in outer space.³² EMP-generating nuclear systems would likely constitute nuclear weapons, whereas DEWs could only constitute WMDs if designed with “characteristics comparable in destructive effect to those of the atomic bomb or [atomic explosive weapons, radioactive material weapons, lethal chemical and biological weapons]”.³³ In 2003, Geis forecast that it would be unlikely that future forms of DEWs as at 2025 would constitute WMDs as “[m]icrowaves can be totally non-lethal, and both lasers and microwaves have beams that can be aimed to reduce the potential for collateral damage”.³⁴ Insofar as this is true of existing forms, DEWs would not fall within the OST prohibition, qualifying as conventional weapons rather than WMDs.

²⁸ Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 19 (art. IV).

²⁹ *Ibid* (arts. IX, XI).

³⁰ Ortega, A. A., & Samson, V. *supra* note 20 (p. 34).

³¹ Tallinn Manual, *supra* note 21 (p. 275).

³² Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 19 (art. IV).

³³ UN General Assembly. (December 12, 1977). *Prohibition of the development and manufacture of new types of weapons of mass destruction and new systems of such weapons*. A/RES/32/84-B. <https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/623117?ln=en&v=pdf> (para. 3); *See, for example*, The International Campaign to Abolish Nuclear Weapons (ICAN). (n.d.). *What are space nuclear weapons?* ICAN. https://www.icanw.org/what_are_space_nuclear_weapons

³⁴ Geis, J. P. (2003). *Directed Energy Weapons on the Battlefield: A New Vision for 2025*. Center for Strategy and Technology, Air War College, Air University. <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/citations/ADA463429> (p. 39).

Even if future forms of DEWs were to qualify as WMDs or even as nuclear weapons, there is the question of whether such DEWs could nonetheless be employed in self-defence under the UN Charter. The ICJ has found that the lawfulness of nuclear weapons would be unclear “in an extreme circumstance of self-defence, in which the very survival of a State would be at stake”,³⁵ and Article 103 of the UN Charter provides that its obligations prevail over those of all other international agreements in the event of an incompatibility, which would include the OST.³⁶ While this question exceeds the limited scope of this paper, it is notable that there is no clear consensus. *The Woomera Manual on the International Law of Military Space Operations* (“Woomera Manual”), a non-binding manual prepared by leading experts on international law, space security, and other relevant areas, calls for the adoption of an “extremely nuanced approach” to this question.³⁷

As the OST is silent on the use of conventional weapons in void space, this gap in the governance of DEWs and their risks to human life and well-being would need to be otherwise addressed, such as by potentially establishing relevant protocols to the Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons. A similar conclusion can be drawn in respect of obstructive uses. As obstructive uses do not inherently or directly cause large-scale, irreversible, and physical damage, such uses would not be prohibited under the OST as WMDs, despite their potential cascading effects. The following sections will thus examine whether the obstructive and destructive uses and their risks to human life and well-being could instead be governed with reference to obligations related to *jus ad bellum*, harmful interference, and due regard.

3.3. Use of Force

Article 2(4) of the UN Charter prohibits the use of force, which has been interpreted by the International Court of Justice (ICJ) as applying “to any use of force, regardless of the weapons employed”.³⁸ Notwithstanding this expansive language, Article 41 of the UN Charter specifically provides that “measures not involving the use of armed force [...] may include complete or partial interruption of [...] radio, and other means of communication”.³⁹ Based on Article 41, together with State practice, it has been argued that jamming could not amount to a use of force.⁴⁰ However, this interpretation is not universally accepted. For example, Mountin argues that such an interpretation would be “overreaching” as “drafters of the Charter never contemplated satellite signal interference would be used to cause physical damage and human injury”,⁴¹ and Pobjie writes that “jamming and spoofing operations may constitute prohibited uses of force when they create sufficiently severe effects or target critical systems [...] even without direct physical damage to space systems or terrestrial harm”.⁴² Thus, while acknowledging the contested legal status of jamming, this Section 3.3 will proceed on the tentative presumption that each of the obstructive and destructive uses may constitute uses of force.

³⁵ International Court of Justice (ICJ). (1996, July 8). *Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons* (Advisory Opinion) (para. 105(2)).

³⁶ *Charter of the United Nations*, opened for signature June 26 1945, 1 UNTS XVI (entered into force October 24 1945) (“UN Charter”) (art. 103).

³⁷ Woomera Manual, *supra* note 7 (pp. 10–12).

³⁸ UN Charter, *supra* note 36 (art. 2(4)); International Court of Justice (ICJ), *supra* note 35 (para. 39).

³⁹ UN Charter, *supra* note 36 (art. 41).

⁴⁰ Woomera Manual, *supra* note 7 (p. 210); DeFabo, V. L. (2021). Rethinking Cyberspace Operations: Widespread Electromagnetic Jamming by States Indicates Cyber Interference Is Not a Use of Force. *Journal of Air Law and Commerce*. 86(2), 219–277. <https://scholar.smu.edu/jalc/vol86/iss2/3> (pp. 223, 250).

⁴¹ Mountin, S. M. (2014). The Legality and Implications of Intentional Interference with Commercial Communication Satellite Signals. *International Law Studies*. 90, 103–197. <https://digital-commons.usnwc.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1013&context=ils> (p. 192).

⁴² Pobjie, E. (2025). Cosmic Force: A Framework for Applying the Prohibition of the Use of Force in Outer Space. *International Law Studies*. 106, 415–454. <https://digital-commons.usnwc.edu/ils/vol106/iss1/13/> (p. 452).

There is no settled definition of a use of force, but it is traditionally understood as involving (1) kinetic means, (2) severe, permanent physical effects, (3) a causal link between the means and effects, and (4) a coercive or hostile intent.⁴³ There can be a mismatch between these traditional elements and contemporary challenges, as highlighted in the Tallinn Manual, which describes the *lex lata* of *jus ad bellum* (among other areas of law) as applied to cyber operations, as well as recent consensus-building efforts on the application of international law in cyberspace. These include the efforts of the UN Group of Governmental Experts (GGE) and UN Open Ended Working Groups (OEWGs) on ICT security, for which position papers were submitted, which may potentially contribute to the development of customary international law (namely, *opinio juris*). While recognising cyberspace and the EMS as imperfect analogues, this Section 3.3 will refer to the Tallinn Manual and GGE and OEWG position papers for the purpose of assessing the potential application of emerging approaches to *jus ad bellum* in relation to the obstructive and destructive uses.

As enumerated above, the first traditional element of a use of force is the employment of kinetic means, contrary to the obstructive and destructive uses, which are non-kinetic means. States have stated in GGE and OEWG position papers that non-kinetic cyber operations may constitute uses of force where the scale and effects are comparable to those of traditional, kinetic uses of force⁴⁴ (even though “scale and effects” have traditionally referred to ‘armed attacks’ rather than uses of force⁴⁵). This reflects an increasing openness to non-kinetic means as uses of force, although such openness is more evident in a cyber context than in an EMS-context, as noted in the Woomera Manual:

⁴³ See, for example, Kilovaty, I. (2014). Cyber Warfare and the Jus Ad Bellum Challenges: Evaluation in the Light of the Tallinn Manual on the International Law Applicable to Cyber Warfare. *American University National Security Law Brief*, 5(1), 91–124. <https://digitalcommons.wcl.american.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?referer=&httpsredir=1&article=1066&context=nslb>;

Pobjie, E. (2024). Elements of ‘Use of Force’: Effects, Gravity and Intention. In *Prohibited Force: The Meaning of ‘Use of Force’ in International Law*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009022897.010> (pp. 132–158).

⁴⁴ Australian Government. (2018). *Australia’s submission on international law to be annexed to the report of the 2021 Group of Governmental Experts on Cyber*. NATO Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence (CCDCOE). https://ccdcoe.org/uploads/2018/10/Australia_submission-on-international-law-to-be-annexed-to-the-report-of-the-2021-Group-of-Governmental-Experts-on-Cyber.pdf (p. 2); Republic of Austria. (2024, April). *Position Paper of the Republic of Austria: Cyber Activities and International Law*. UN Office for Disarmament Affairs. [https://docs-library.unoda.org/Open-Ended_Working_Group_on_Information_and_Communication_Technologies_-_2021/Austrian_Position_Paper_-_Cyber_Activities_and_International_Law_\(Final_23.04.2024\).pdf](https://docs-library.unoda.org/Open-Ended_Working_Group_on_Information_and_Communication_Technologies_-_2021/Austrian_Position_Paper_-_Cyber_Activities_and_International_Law_(Final_23.04.2024).pdf) (p. 6);

Republic of Costa Rica. (2021). *Costa Rica’s Position on the Application of International Law in Cyberspace*. UN Office for Disarmament Affairs. https://docs-library.unoda.org/Open-Ended_Working_Group_on_Information_and_Communication_Technologies_-_2021/Costa_Rica_-_Position_Paper_-_International_Law_in_Cyberspace.pdf (p. 11); Kjelgaard, J. M., & Melgaard, U. (2023). Denmark’s Position Paper on the Application of International Law in Cyberspace: Introduction. *Nordic Journal of International Law*, 92(3), 446–455. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718107-20230001> (p. 451); Kingdom of Thailand. (2025, July). *Thailand’s National Position on the Application of International Law in Cyberspace*. Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Kingdom of Thailand. https://image.mfa.go.th/mfa/0/6p4M7ae5k9/Thailands_NP_JUL2025_.pdf (p. 6); Government of Czech Republic. (2024). *Position paper on the application of international law in cyberspace*. Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Czech Republic. https://mzv.gov.cz/file/5376858/20240226_CZ_Position_paper_on_the_application_of_IL_cyberspace.pdf (p. 8); Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade. (2023, July). *Position Paper on the Application of International Law in Cyberspace*. Government of Ireland. <https://www.dfa.ie/media/dfa/ourrolepolicies/internationallaw/Ireland---National-Position-Paper.pdf> (para. 18).

⁴⁵ International Court of Justice (ICJ). (1986, June 26). *Military and Paramilitary Activities in and against Nicaragua (Nicaragua v. United States of America)* (Judgment) (para. 195); Tallinn Manual, *supra* note 21 (p. 331).

“Unlike potential use of cyber capabilities [...] the potential use of non-kinetic capabilities along the electromagnetic spectrum as weapons in space is a developing area that some States are not yet prepared to [consider] may constitute a use of force.”⁴⁶

The second traditional element concerns severe, permanent physical effects such as death, injury, damage, or destruction. Destructive uses align with this traditional approach as such uses can permanently damage satellites (in the case of third-order risks) and terrestrial electronics (in the case of second-order risks), whereas obstructive uses merely interfere with satellite signals without causing physical damage. If interferences occur repeatedly, frequently, or for a long duration, and affect critical infrastructure (e.g., the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS), which is integral for power grids and crop management systems),⁴⁷ obstructive uses could indirectly cause deaths on Earth (in the case of third-order risks). However, it is unclear whether such cascading effects resulting in deaths would be sufficient for qualifying obstructive uses as uses of force.

Some GGE and OEWG position papers reflect an expansive interpretation of “effects”, recognising the loss of functionality of critical infrastructure alongside death, injury, damage, and destruction, although not all such States recognise the temporary or reversible loss of functionality.⁴⁸ Accordingly, obstructive uses undermining critical infrastructure could potentially qualify as prohibited uses of force, unless it is necessary that the effects are permanent. As noted in the Woomera Manual, it is arguable that even temporary interferences against “satellites that provide an early warning of nuclear ballistic missile launches” and related systems could qualify as uses of force, given that this would pose a grave threat to international peace and security.⁴⁹

The third traditional element concerns the causal relationship between the means and the effects. Although the UN Charter does not contain express requirements to establish causation, this may reflect the fact that causation is relatively straightforward for kinetic means compared with non-kinetic ones. Consider an example of third-order risks, involving a jamming attack against a constellation of dual-use satellites for monitoring agriculture and optimising crop yields, which exacerbates an existing famine and results in thousands of people losing their lives over the course of several months. Such effects would not be as immediate or direct as in the simpler, more traditional scenario of one person shooting another person with a gun.

Urs examines three possible standards of causation in the context of cyber operations: (1) a “sufficiently direct and certain causal nexus”, (2) “effects that are proximate in space and time” rather than remote, and

⁴⁶ Woomera Manual, *supra* note 7 (p. 213).

⁴⁷ See, for example, Trýb J., & Hospodka, J. (2025). GNSS Interference and Security: Impacts on Critical Infrastructure and Mitigation Strategies. *Procedia Computer Science*. 253, 2635–2644. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2025.01.323> (p. 2636–2637); Solms, T. (2025, May 5). Securing the skies: tackling the growing threat of GPS interference. *Space News*. <https://spacenews.com/securing-the-skies-tackling-the-growing-threat-of-gps-interference/>; International Telecommunications Union (ITU). (2025, March 26). UN agencies warn of satellite navigation jamming and spoofing. *ITU*. <https://www.itu.int/hub/2025/03/un-agencies-warn-of-satellite-navigation-jamming-and-spoofing/>; Pashby, T. (2025, July 14). Plans to boost critical infrastructure resilience to GPS jamming agreed between UK and France. *New Civil Engineer*. <https://www.newcivilengineer.com/latest/plans-to-boost-critical-infrastructure-resilience-to-gps-jamming-agreed-between-uk-and-france-14-07-2025/>

⁴⁸ Australian Government, *supra* note 44; Republic of Costa Rica, *supra* note 44; Kingdom of Thailand, *supra* note 44.

⁴⁹ Woomera Manual, *supra* note 7 (p. 220).

(3) reasonably foreseeable effects.⁵⁰ Applied to the above example, the first standard would not be satisfied because the effects of the jamming attack are indirect. The second standard is relatively flexible, but it is arguable that – although a thorough, case-by-case assessment would be required in practice – the effects are not proximate in either space (i.e., outer space versus Earth) or time (i.e., several months have passed). The longer the delay between the means and effects, the more likely it is that intervening factors have broken the chain of causation. Pursuant to the third standard, it could also be argued that the perpetrator of the jamming attack could not have reasonably foreseen that the dual-use satellites served critical applications upon which lives depended. As Kuplic and Sawmiller illustrate in the following hypothetical scenario, the uses of satellites can be difficult to ascertain:

“The decision to begin jamming is based on signals intelligence indicating that the enemy communications ministry leases some frequencies on that transponder and the enemy air force uses those frequencies to command and control armed unmanned aerial vehicles. Intelligence reporting also indicates that some frequencies on the same transponder are leased from the satellite operator BigSatCo by a commercial communications company, GlobalCommCo, which subcontracts with a second commercial communications company, RegionalCommCo, which in turn contracts with any users in the transponder footprint willing to pay for its voice and data transmission services. Such arrangements are common in the modern world of ever-increasing commercialization of space services.”⁵¹

Establishing causation would be less complex in the case of second-order risks, but challenges remain. Consider an EMP in outer space resulting in a two-year power outage on Earth. Bearing in mind the criticality of power for basic human needs, many lives would be lost, but not immediately. The third standard of causation could be satisfied as the destructive effects of an EMP (if caused deliberately) are reasonably foreseeable, even if the precise scale and effects could not be foreseen. However, the other two standards could not be satisfied, as the causal relationship remains indirect, and it is unclear whether harm occurring over a two-year time span would be considered sufficiently proximate.

The fourth traditional element concerns a coercive or hostile intent. Despite the material risks of obstructive and destructive uses to human life and well-being, it would follow that such uses may not constitute prohibited uses of force where the actor was well-intentioned. For example, a commercial actor testing a high-energy laser for removing orbital debris might accidentally strike a functioning satellite, or a spacecraft running on a nuclear power source might accidentally generate an EMP. Such accidents are not unlikely in an inherently high-risk and accident-prone environment such as outer space. Thus, if *jus ad bellum* were inapplicable, it would be important to have recourse to other regimes to ensure that any resulting risks to human life and well-being do not escape regulation.

However, Pobjie and Ortega write that the elements of a use of force are subject to a balancing exercise, such that “a hostile or coercive intent may turn a forcible act into a use of force even if [...] the effects are temporary and reversible”.⁵² Accordingly, the doctrinal ambiguities discussed in this Section 3.3 (e.g., whether temporary, reversible effects of obstructive uses are recognised ‘effects’) would not necessarily

⁵⁰ Urs, P. (2023, April 25). The Causal Question in the Application of the Law on the Use of Force to Cyber Operations. *Centre for International Law, National University of Singapore*. <https://cil.nus.edu.sg/blogs/the-causal-question-in-the-application-of-the-law-on-the-use-of-force-to-cyber-operations/>

⁵¹ Kuplic, G. B., & Sawmiller, J. (2025). Humanity on the final frontier: Challenges in applying international humanitarian law to modern military. *International Review of the Red Cross*. 107(928), 200–237. space operations. <https://international-review.icrc.org/articles/humanity-on-the-final-frontier-928> (p. 233).

⁵² Pobjie, E. & Ortega, A. A. (2024, September). Space Security Legal Primer 1 – Outer Space & Use of Force. *UNIDIR*. <https://doi.org/10.37559/WMD/24/Space/02> (p. 25).

bar the finding that there exists a prohibited use of force. For example, obstructive or destructive uses occurring by accident may nonetheless qualify as prohibited uses of force if, on balance, the lack of intent is outweighed by the severity of the effects. A toolkit assessing hypothetical scenarios, such as the Cyber Law Toolkit on the intersection between international law and cyber operations,⁵³ would be helpful in demonstrating how such a balancing exercise could be operationalised in practice. (It is notable that a toolkit on the intersection between international law and counter-space and electromagnetic operations would additionally offer value in clarifying all doctrinal ambiguities discussed throughout this paper.)

3.4. Right of Self-Defence

Pursuant to Article 51 of the UN Charter and customary international law, an exception to the prohibition on the use of force is self-defence.⁵⁴ In the *Nicaragua* judgement, the ICJ provides that an ‘armed attack’, which triggers the right of self-defence, can be understood as a grave form of use of force with reference to scale and effects.⁵⁵ The ICJ excluded “mere frontier incident[s]” from the meaning of an armed attack,⁵⁶ while leaving the door open to the “mining of a single military vessel” in the *Oil Platforms* judgment,⁵⁷ reflecting that the threshold for an armed attack may vary depending on prevailing circumstances. For example, Schaller writes that damage to a submarine cable could constitute a grave use of force for a small island State, but not for a State with redundant cable infrastructure.⁵⁸ By analogy, an obstructive or destructive use against a satellite constellation used by several States for monitoring natural disasters could be construed as an armed attack by a disaster-prone State, but not by other States.

As a practical matter, the nuanced nature of the ‘scale and effects’ test risks generating uncertainty among States as to the circumstances under which the right of self-defence may be lawfully exercised, with States such as the US even maintaining that any use of force may trigger the right of self-defence.⁵⁹ This uncertainty would be further compounded in the context of the obstructive and destructive uses, where difficulties in forecasting effects, especially those which are indirect and long-term (as discussed in Section 3.3 above), would undermine the capacity of States to operationalise the test through *ex ante* assessments.

The lawful exercise of (individual) self-defence further requires that the relevant State be the victim of an armed attack.⁶⁰ However, the victim State can be unclear where the affected satellite was operated, owned, leased, or registered by several States. As highlighted in the Woomera Manual, if State A leases or otherwise relies on the services of a satellite that is registered with State B, it is possible that State A could not act in self-defence against a third State absent a genuine legal connection with that satellite.⁶¹ Even if the victim State could be identified, attributing the obstructive and destructive uses to the aggressor State can raise practical difficulties due to the relative absence of traceable markers compared

⁵³ See, Mačák, K., Minárik, T., & Jančárková, T. (Eds.). (2019-). *Cyber Law Toolkit*. (NATO Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence).

⁵⁴ UN Charter, *supra note* 36 (art. 51); International Court of Justice (ICJ), *supra note* 45 (para. 176).

⁵⁵ International Court of Justice (ICJ), *supra note* 45 (paras. 191, 195).

⁵⁶ International Court of Justice (ICJ), *supra note* 45 (para. 195).

⁵⁷ International Court of Justice (ICJ). (2003, November 6). *Oil Platforms (Islamic Republic of Iran v. United States of America)* (Judgment) (para. 72).

⁵⁸ Schaller, C. (2025, April 16). Attacks on Submarine Cables and Pipelines: A Self-Defence Approach Complementary to Law Enforcement. *EJIL:Talk!* <https://www.ejiltalk.org/attacks-on-submarine-cables-and-pipelines-a-self-defence-approach-complementary-to-law-enforcement/>

⁵⁹ Kuplic & Sawmiller, *supra note* 51 at 214.

⁶⁰ International Court of Justice (ICJ), *supra note* 45 (para. 195).

⁶¹ Woomera Manual, *supra note* 7 (pp. 235–236).

to kinetic counter-space capabilities (e.g., ASAT weapons).⁶² This would be detrimental for the victim State upon which the burden of proof in demonstrating the existence of the armed attack rests.⁶³

The right of self-defence is also subject to conditions of necessity and proportionality,⁶⁴ which Kretzmer describes as involving an assessment of “whether the force used was necessary to achieve legitimate ends of self-defence”, where “[m]eans can only be proportionate when they are necessary to achieve the legitimate ends.”⁶⁵ By way of illustration, suppose State A launches an armed attack against State B, involving GPS-guided missile strikes. State B may determine that launching interceptor missiles or employing DEWs to damage GPS satellites would not be strictly necessary if jamming or spoofing GPS signals could achieve the same legitimate end of repelling the attack. It may be considered that obstructive uses are relatively limited in scale and intensity given their temporary, reversible, and non-kinetic nature, whereas destructive uses would permanently deny State A (and potentially, third-party States) the constructive uses of the affected GPS satellites and generate space debris. In conducting such an assessment, however, State B would need to take due precautions as not to underestimate the indirect, long-term effects of the obstructive uses. For example, in 2025, GPS jamming amid the Israel-Iran war was suspected as a possible cause for a collision between two oil tankers in the Gulf of Oman,⁶⁶ underscoring the potential cascading effects of obstructive uses, which pose a threat to human life.

3.5. Harmful Interference

A “harmful interference” concerns an “interference which endangers the functioning of a radionavigation service or of other safety services or seriously degrades, obstructs, or repeatedly interrupts a radiocommunication service [...]”⁶⁷ under international telecommunications law. The term has been described as having a broader scope of meaning under international space law, also encompassing physical means of interference.⁶⁸ Thus, both the obstructive and destructive uses would likely fall within the scope of Article IX of the OST, whereas only the former would be covered under international telecommunications law.

International telecommunications law warrants brief discussion given the mandate of the ITU to “promote the adoption of measures for ensuring the safety of life through the cooperation of telecommunication services”.⁶⁹ Notably, Article 45 of the ITU Constitution contains a duty to avoid harmful interference to the radio communications of other States, and No. 15.1 of the Radio Regulations prohibits jamming.⁷⁰ However, the ITU Constitution further provides that “Member States retain their entire freedom with regard to military radio installations”, and military radio installations are subject to a far softer duty to

⁶² See Pobjie, *supra* note 42 (p. 426).

⁶³ International Court of Justice (ICJ), *supra* note 57 (para. 57).

⁶⁴ International Court of Justice (ICJ), *supra* note 45 (paras. 194, 237).

⁶⁵ Kretzmer, D. (2013). The Inherent Right to Self-Defence and Proportionality in *Jus Ad Bellum*. *The European Journal of International Law*. 24(1). 235–282. doi: 10.1093/ejil/chs087 (p. 239).

⁶⁶ Mahle, M. M. (2025, July 2). GPS Jamming during Israel-Iran War Demonstrates Risks to Civilian Operations. *StepToe LLP*. <https://www.steptoelaw.com/en/news-publications/stepwise-risk-outlook/gps-jamming-during-israel-iran-war-demonstrates-risks-to-civilian-operations.html>

⁶⁷ International Telecommunications Union. (2024). *Radio Regulations*. <https://www.itu.int/pub/R-REG-RR> (“Radio Regulations”) (no. 1.169).

⁶⁸ Woomera Manual, *supra* note 7 (pp. 178–180); International Telecommunications Union (ITU). (last updated 2025, January). *Radio Interference*. ITU. <https://www.itu.int/en/mediacentre/backgrounders/Pages/radio-interference.aspx>

⁶⁹ *Constitution and Convention of the International Telecommunication Union*, opened for signature December 22, 1992, 1825 UNTS 1826 (entered into force July 1 1994) (“ITU Constitution”) (art. 1(2)(g)).

⁷⁰ *Ibid* (art. 45); International Telecommunications Union, *supra* note 67 (no. 15.1).

take measures to prevent harmful interference “so far as possible”.⁷¹ Thus, while these provisions govern obstructive uses, any such uses carried out in a military capacity escape coverage. Further, compliance with these provisions relies upon the good faith cooperation of States absent an enforcement mechanism within the ITU, and efforts by the ITU to persuade governments to stop jamming have often been unsuccessful in practice.⁷²

Meanwhile, Article IX of the OST imposes a duty onto States Parties to “undertake appropriate international consultations before proceeding with any such activity or experiment” which is believed to “cause potentially harmful interference with activities of other States Parties in the peaceful exploration and use of outer space”.⁷³ A duty to consult is far weaker than a duty to avoid harmful interference, and said duty to consult is only limited to activities in the “peaceful” use of outer space, such that it has been argued that no such duty exists in relation to interferences with satellite signals employed in the unlawful use (or threat) of force.⁷⁴ Thus, at present, the above duties related to harmful interference likely could not be relied upon to effectively address the risks flowing from the obstructive or destructive uses to human life and well-being.

3.6. Due Regard

Article IX of the OST provides that States Parties shall conduct space activities “with due regard to the corresponding interests of all other States Parties to the Treaty”.⁷⁵ The meaning of “due regard” is unsettled, but scholars have generally favoured a broad interpretation, which would encompass obstructive and destructive uses that undermine the freedom of use of outer space as enjoyed by other States.⁷⁶

While the seas and outer space are imperfect analogues, this Section 3.6 adopts the view of the Republic of the Philippines, which wrote in its 2022 submission to the UN General Assembly that the interpretation of the due regard obligation within the law of the sea regime “could offer practical guidance in the context of clarifying the application of the same duty in outer space”.⁷⁷ For example, the Tribunal in the *Chagos Marine Protected Area Arbitration* case refers to the due regard obligation as “functionally equivalent” to the requirement to “refrain from unjustifiable interference”.⁷⁸ Further, the Tribunal provides that:

“[T]he extent of the regard required by the [UN Convention on the Law of the Sea] will depend upon the nature of the rights held by [the affected State], their importance, the extent of the anticipated impairment, the nature and importance of

⁷¹ ITU Constitution, *supra note* 69 (art. 48).

⁷² See, for example, International Telecommunications Union (ITU), *supra note* 47; de Selding, P. B. (2010, January 8). France Seeks ITU Help To Halt Satellite Signal Jamming by Iran. *Space News*. <https://spacenews.com/france-seeks-itu-help-halt-satellite-signal-jamming-iran/>; de Selding, P. B. (2010, March 26). ITU Implores Iran To Help Stop Jamming. *Space News*. <https://spacenews.com/itu-implores-iran-help-stop-jamming/>

⁷³ Outer Space Treaty, *supra note* 19 (art. IX).

⁷⁴ Mountin, *supra note* 41 (pp. 152–153).

⁷⁵ Outer Space Treaty, *supra note* 19 (art. IX).

⁷⁶ Jarose, J. (2023). Giving Due Regard to the Obligation of ‘Due Regard’ Under Article IX of the Outer Space Treaty. *Melbourne Journal of International Law*. 24(2), 1–25 https://law.unimelb.edu.au/_data/assets/pdf_file/0009/5034708/Jarose-Advance-Copy.pdf (p. 3); Kuplic & Sawmiller, *supra note* 51.

⁷⁷ Republic of the Philippines. (2022). *The duty of “due regard” as a foundational principle of responsible behavior in space* (UN General Assembly, UN Doc A/AC.294/2022/WP); <https://documents.unoda.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/Philippines-Due-Regard-Paper.pdf> (para. 11).

⁷⁸ Permanent Court of Arbitration. (2015). *Chagos Marine Protected Area Arbitration (Mauritius v United Kingdom)*: Award of 18 March 2015. <https://pca-epa.org/en/cases/11/> (p. 540).

the activities contemplated by the [responsible State], and the availability of alternative approaches.”⁷⁹

A similar balancing exercise could be undertaken in respect of the obstructive and destructive uses. For example, if an obstructive or destructive use carried out by State A is expected to impair the right of State B to use outer space (e.g., by denying State B access to constructive uses), then it must be the case that no or few reasonable alternatives existed, and the obstructive or destructive use was of such a nature or degree of importance as to justify the interference. Otherwise, a violation of the due regard obligation can be established.

Chen considers that there is no justifiable reason for intentionally jamming or spoofing, such that the due regard obligation is tantamount to a prohibition of such acts.⁸⁰ Further, bearing in mind the third-order risks of the destructive uses in permanently damaging satellites and denying States of their constructive uses, as well as the resulting generation of space debris that could further damage other satellites, the destructive uses are also likely to violate the due regard obligation. Thus, given its breadth of scope, the due regard obligation warrants particular examination as a possible means for governing both the obstructive and destructive uses.

4. CONCLUSION

This paper has sought to identify legal lacunae and doctrinal ambiguities in the application of the existing international space law framework, including *jus ad bellum*, to the obstructive and destructive uses. In particular, it is unclear whether such uses constitute space activities for the purposes of the OST amid ongoing spatialism-functionalism debates, and the classification of obstructive uses as prohibited uses of force is contested, given their non-traditional characteristics (e.g., temporary, reversible, non-physical effects) and Article 41 of the UN Charter. Even where obstructive and destructive uses qualify as prohibited uses of force, uncertainties remain concerning the applicable standard of causation, the relevance of indirect or long-term effects, and the weight of each element, including a coercive or hostile intent. Further, there are possible tensions between international space law and *jus ad bellum*, such as the question of whether the right of self-defence could prevail over the OST rules on prohibited weapons under Article 103 of the UN Charter.

The obstructive and destructive uses can undermine the constructive uses, thereby posing risks to human life and well-being. As reliance on satellite systems and their constructive uses accelerates worldwide, managing these risks is increasingly relevant for disaster preparedness, critical infrastructure resilience, and international legal governance, requiring the careful examination of applicable legal frameworks. Thus, it is essential to clarify and address existing legal lacunae to ensure the governance of the obstructive and destructive uses, with a view to regulating and protecting satellite systems, their constructive uses, and the lives they support. This paper has highlighted the potential role of the due regard obligation of international space law for governing the obstructive and destructive uses given its breadth in scope, as well as the possibility of prohibiting obstructive uses falling short of prohibited uses of force by resorting instead to the “peaceful purposes” requirement of the OST.

Thus, this paper calls for further research, policy discussions, and consensus-building efforts to address existing legal lacunae in respect of the application of the international space law framework to the obstructive and destructive uses. State position papers (e.g., as part of GGE and OEWG), expert manuals (e.g., Tallinn Manual, Woomera Manual), and toolkits assessing hypothetical scenarios (e.g., Cyber Law

⁷⁹ *Ibid* (para. 519).

⁸⁰ Chen, K.-W. (2024). *Legal Implications of Intentional Interference with Space Signals*. (Centre for Space, Cyberspace & Data Law; No. 2). Bond University. <https://bond.edu.au/research/research-centres-and-institute/centre-for-space-cyberspace-and-data-law> (pp. 1–18).

Toolkit) have contributed to the clarification of applicable legal frameworks to cyber operations and counter-space operations, and may similarly assist in clarifying how international law applies to the specific nexus between outer space and the EMS, as exemplified by the obstructive and destructive uses.

Due to its limited scope, this paper is inexhaustive in examining the rules and principles of international space law and *jus ad bellum* of potential relevance (e.g., outer space as a province of all mankind, threat of force). Further, while the categories of the ‘constructive’, ‘obstructive’, and ‘destructive’ uses are considered in this paper, specific uses of the EMS in outer space (e.g., jamming versus spoofing) additionally warrant individual examination owing to each of their unique characteristics. It is also notable that some legal lacunae and doctrinal ambiguities discussed in this paper may be resolved over time with the emergence of customary international law, or filled with recourse to rules and principles of general international law (e.g., non-intervention principle, laws of State responsibility), other specialised areas of public international law (e.g., international humanitarian law, international telecommunications law, international environmental law), or national laws, each of which also warrant further examination.

© The Author(s) 2026. Published by Space Court Foundation. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted reuse, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

SPACE-BASED EARTH OBSERVATION IMAGERY & WARTIME ATROCITIES IN THE INTERNATIONAL LEGAL IMAGINATION

AVA HUTCHISON¹

ABSTRACT

This article examines the encounter between the legal gaze and Space-Based Earth Observation (SBEO) as a technoscientific medium that, in its content, informs the procedural work of international lawyers and, in its form, opens new possibilities for seeing and interpreting phenomena under international law. As the world's attention turns to conflicts in Sudan, Ukraine, and Israel-Palestine, the data derived from SBEO techniques and the subsequent 'sense-making' of technicians and jurists have become critical commodities in global sensory economies, delimiting what is visible and thereby legally actionable under international humanitarian and criminal law. Through its rhetorical capacity and sensory techniques, especially recent innovations in hyperspectral and Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) imaging, SBEO produces new ways of quantifying and visualising harm across temporal and spatial scales in these armed conflict zones, particularly for environmental and infrastructural damage. Through case studies of emerging legal proposals for the international criminalisation of 'ecocide', 'domicide', and 'urbicide', the article considers SBEO's contribution to the reimagination and qualification of atrocity crimes within the thresholds of international criminal law, as well as the relevance of academic scholarship and grassroots civilian science to these projects of international justice. In doing so, it contends that the technoscientific nature of SBEO and the increasingly legal character of work conducted by remote sensing researchers, civil society actors, and interdisciplinary scholars are bringing these domains into ever closer proximity, producing a diffuse and participatory landscape of legal imagination that reshapes formal and informal discourse within IHL and ICL alike.

KEYWORDS: Earth Observation, International Criminal Law, Satellite Imagery, Armed Conflict, Ecocide, Domicide, Legal Theory.

¹ Space Court Foundation, ava.hutchison@spacecourtfoundation.org; Sciences Po Paris Law School, ava.hutchison@sciencespo.fr

1. INTRODUCTION

The leveraging of Space-Based Earth Observation (SBEO) imagery and remote sensing² for international legal purposes has been well documented in space law and humanitarian literature.³ Objectives range from routine monitoring of international agreements to the more sensationalist detection, investigation, and prosecution of international crimes⁴ and human rights violations.⁵ While legal scholarship has gradually acknowledged the power of the visual image to shape international legal narratives and responses,⁶ SBEO, as a technical practice, exemplifies a more complex and nuanced technoscientific tool that, in its content, informs the procedural work of international lawyers, and in its form opens new possibilities for seeing and interpreting phenomena under international law.

As the world turns its attention to armed conflict in Sudan, Ukraine, Israel-Palestine, and beyond,⁷ the data derived from SBEO techniques has become an increasingly critical commodity in what Fleur Johns calls ‘global sensory economies’. These economies are made up of networks of actors, technologies, infrastructures, and legal norms that produce, evoke, organize, and circulate ‘sensory data’ about the world. In turn, this dictates the distribution of today’s critical immaterial resources like attention, authority, and knowledge, as well as their material counterparts like money, bodies, and objects.⁸ It is

² Although the distinction is hardly made in scientific circles, Principle I(a) of the UN Principles Relating to Remote Sensing of the Earth from Outer Space of 1974 distinguishes remote sensing from Earth Observation (EO) in that its fundamental purpose is “improving natural resources management, land use and the protection of the environment”. This indicates that the various other applications of remote sensing, including the purposes discussed above that are of interest to this study, fall outside of this category and thus are not within the purview of the aforementioned UN Principles. EO, as an alternative category, broadly incorporates space-based remote sensing and ground-based in situ-derived information – hence the specification of SBEO for the purposes of this piece. See United Nations General Assembly. (1986, December 3). *Principles relating to remote sensing of the Earth from space* (Resolution 41/65, GAOR, 41st Session). Principle I(a). United Nations.

³ See generally Farfour, M. (2019). The role and use of satellite imagery for human rights investigations. In S. Dubberley, A. Koenig, & D. Murray (Eds.), *Digital witness: Using open source information for human rights investigation, documentation, and accountability* (Chap. 11). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/law/9780198836063.003.0011>. See also Savage N. (2024). Eyes in the sky usher in new era of law and order. *Nature*, 635(8037), S1–S3. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-024-03593-x>.

⁴ Satellite imagery has already been admitted in cases at the International Criminal Court (ICC), International Court of Justice (ICJ), the Permanent Court of Arbitration (PCA) at The Hague, and International Criminal Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia (ICTY). See Wang, B. Y., Raymond, N., Gould, G., & Baker, I. (2013). Problems from Hell, Solution in the Heavens?: Identifying Obstacles and Opportunities for Employing Geospatial Technologies to Document and Mitigate Mass Atrocities. *Stability: International Journal of Security and Development*, 2(3), Art. 53.; See also Raymond, N. A., Card, B. L., & Baker, I. L. (2014). A nes: Developing standard remote sensing methodologies to detect and document mass atrocities. *Genocide Studies and Prevention: An International Journal*, 8(3), 33–48. <https://doi.org/10.5038/1911-9933.8.3.4>.

⁵ See Edler, R., Glasze, G., Kinzelbach, K., & Walker, B. B. (2025). Remote sensing analysis for documenting human rights violations in zones of armed conflict: A systematic review of empirical research. *Frontiers in Remote Sensing*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsen.2025.1603575>; See also Rapach, S., Riccardi, A., & Wheate, R. (2024). Earth observation technology’s alignment with OHCHR indicators for strengthening human rights breach investigations and adjudication. *Science & Justice*, 64(6), 710–727. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scijus.2024.09.006>.

⁶ Joyce, D. (2010). Photography and the Image-Making of International Justice. *Law and Humanities*, 4(2), 229–249.

⁷ In addition to the listed conflicts, sovereign use of force has been employed in Venezuela, Iran, Lebanon, Bahrain, the United Arab Emirates, Qatar, Kuwait, Oman, Iraq, Azerbaijan, Syria, Jordan, and Cyprus since the original time of writing. See also Hak, J. W., & Rewald, S. K. (2024, July 1). *The satellite era: How Earth observation data is being mobilized as potential digital evidence*. *EJIL: Talk! (Blog of the European Journal of International Law)*. <https://www.ejiltalk.org/the-satellite-era-how-earth-observation-data-is-being-mobilized-as-potential-digital-evidenc/>.

⁸ Johns, F. (2017). Data, Detection, and the Redistribution of the Sensible in International Law. *American Journal of International Law*, 111(1), 57–103. doi:10.1017/ajil.2016.4.

according to these economies that technicians and jurists alike can ‘make sense’ of worldly phenomena. International legal work maintains a specific and powerful ‘distribution of the sensible’, for example, the lexicon of war crimes itself serves as a common vocabulary that frames practices of warfare as matters of ‘international’ concern, and irrigates this concern towards an enumeration of sufferings they engender.⁹ Imagery, and documentary photography in particular, holds a special place as a singularly authoritative format for sensory data that transmits the affective and analytical sensation of witnessing a captured moment of reality. SBEO is situated at the intersection of documentary photography and cartography, another foundational structuring paradigm in international legal thought,¹⁰ and has developed techniques that go beyond photographic imagery to record, map, and visualise information like movement, depth, displacement, and more. While jurists are quite accustomed to discussing how law influences and governs imagery, thinking in terms of sensory economies allows us to examine how specific imaging techniques frame the legal gaze, and thus possibilities for legal action.

This piece intends to think sociotechnically about this interrelationship in the context of conflict-induced mass harms and atrocities to better ascertain how looking at the world through SBEO can inspire continuous reinterpretation in and of international humanitarian law (IHL) and international criminal law (ICL).¹¹ Through first taking a granular look at the encounter between the legal gaze and contemporary SBEO techniques like hyperspectral and Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) imagery, it then becomes possible to contextualise the production of legal ‘reimaginings’ of atrocities and their possible qualification under existing ICL thresholds. The central ‘reimaginings’ to be examined here are the proposed international crimes of *ecocide*, *domicide*, and *urbicide*, which refer to the wilful and wanton destruction of a natural environment, housing, and urban spaces, respectively. These terms, which have gained significant traction in legal discourse in the past decade, frequently raise the question of the effectiveness of remedying old problems through new crimes and protections under IHL and ICL. I seek to set this debate aside in order to examine instead a more foundational question: how SBEO, as a technoscientific medium, shapes the legal imagination from which such proposals emerge and through which they gain normative traction, notwithstanding the high legal thresholds that challenge their legitimate adoption into the international legal order.

In this way, this piece proposes that novel techniques of SBEO legitimize the evocation and circulation of these proposed mass atrocity crimes both as popular neologisms and as legal concepts through the virilization and quantification of large-scale harms. The technoscientific nature of SBEO and the increasingly legal character of work conducted by SBEO technicians, civil society researchers, and interdisciplinary scholars bring the domains of remote sensing and ICL into ever closer proximity. While an evaluation of the possible use or limitations of these techniques within the minutiae of international legal proceedings lies outside of this paper's scope, it draws attention to how SBEO is being mobilized by jurists and non-jurists alike in their advocacy of new or expanded frameworks of international criminal accountability. It is not the intention of this study to evaluate the suitability of proposed or existing crimes vis-à-vis ongoing conflicts, but rather their character and instrumentalization in legal discourse.

To that end, the article proceeds in three parts. The first section takes a broad to narrow approach, first establishing the theoretical framework of encounter between the legal gaze, the legal imagination, and SBEO as a technoscientific medium to trace the interrelationship of novel ways of seeing. This is

⁹ Mignot-Mahdavi, R. (2024). War crimes as vocabulary shaping the visible. *Saint Louis University Law Journal*, 68(2), 277–292. <https://hal.science/hal-05382162>.

¹⁰ Lythgoe, G. (2023). Eradicating the exceptional: The role of territory in structuring international legal thought. *Leiden Journal of International Law*, 1-18. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0922156523000675>.

¹¹ See generally Johns, F. (2023). *Help: Digital humanitarianism and the remaking of international order* (Online ed., Oxford Academic, 23 Feb. 2023); Nesiiah, V. (2003). Placing international law: White spaces on a map. *Leiden Journal of International Law*, 16; Hill, G. (2021). The map and international law’s stifled visual discourse. *European Journal of Legal Studies*, 13.

followed by a more material examination into innovative SBEO techniques such as SAR, InSAR, and hyperspectral imagery, and the bearing that their specific epistemic and rhetorical properties have for the global sensory economy of armed conflict and the legal imagination. The second section turns to three substantive legal ‘reimaginings’ closely related to SBEO, examining in turn the proposed crimes of ecocide, domicide, and uricide. Analysis of the nature and applications of SBEO used in legal discourse regarding ongoing violent conflicts instantiates its role in rendering visible and legally cognisable the widespread, long-term, and severe destruction of environments, homes, and urban spaces, and in doing so pushes the thresholds of IHL and ICL. The final section reflects on the broader implications of this encounter for the broader space and technology legal research agenda, centering law, SBEO, the legal imagination, and warfare within a singular interdisciplinary and transnational normative conversation that demands theoretical and technical engagement from this generation of international jurists.

2. SPACE-BASED EARTH OBSERVATION & THE LEGAL GAZE

2.1. From the Legal Gaze to the Legal Imagination

The gaze, one of the more popular proposals from 20th-century phenomenology, is the figurative practice of looking and perceiving the world in a specific manner in accordance with given social dynamics and narratives, underpinned by a network of power-knowledge relationships on an institutional scale.¹² For international jurists, the legal gaze interprets the world suspiciously,¹³ seeking truth (or perhaps simply satisfactory resolutions) regarding complex, worldly, and sensory phenomena through categorisation into subjectivities, linked through obligations and rights. Lawyers are not blind to the spectacle of warfare, and bear witness both professionally and privately to visual media and numeric representations of violence. Such objects upon which one sets their gaze, and the techniques through which one ‘sees’, determine what ‘sense’ or knowledge can be derived therein. The complexity and diversity of modern technoscientific tools proliferate documentary techniques that render these objects legible in different ways, generating and framing visual fodder for the legal gaze.

It is not only where this gaze meets but rather where it *chafes* against its technoscientific sensory lenses that is of interest to this piece. This is an encounter of critical epistemic importance, in that it obligates the jurist to reconcile an observable sensory phenomenon with their own insufficient legal categories through the adaptation of the latter.¹⁴ The perception and quantification of atrocity-level harms to, for example, the aerial, terrestrial, and maritime environment, invites jurists to consider the capacity of international law to address these events and, where unsatisfactory, propose new creative interpretations of its corpus. It is precisely this intellectual computation that constitutes an act of legal imagination. Martti Koskenniemi understands such imagination to not be abstract, cerebral work, but rather the practical re-assemblage and reinterpretation of existing legal materials in the pursuit of particular aims.¹⁵ Like reason, faith, or utopia, imagination is an instrument in the international jurist’s toolbox that can be deployed in the production of international legal concepts.¹⁶ This jurist is, nevertheless, circumscribed by existing legal language, concepts, and framework, as well as prefigured norms of credibility. Imagination is not an autopoietic,

¹² See notably *Discipline and punish: the birth of the prison* (1977) and *The birth of the clinic: an archaeology of medical perception* (1973).

¹³ Kennedy, D. (2014). The Hermeneutic of Suspicion in Contemporary American Legal Thought. *Law and Critique*, 25(2). <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10978-014-9136-6>.

¹⁴ Sheila Jasanoff offers a clear example of this in her discussion of biomedical techniques for fetal medicine and coma care, which created new states of being between life and death that required legal adaptation, through legal imagination. See Jasanoff, S. (1995). *Science at the Bar: Law, Science, and Technology in America*. Harvard University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctvjz822j>.

¹⁵ Koskenniemi M (2021) *To the uttermost parts of the earth: legal imagination and international power 1300–1870*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.

¹⁶ Simpson, G. (2019). "Chapter 26: Imagination". In *Concepts for International Law*. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar Publishing. 413-421. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781783474684.00031>.

inventive power but comes from within and proceeds by passing through new technologies that ‘de-form’ it, dismantling categories, releasing possibilities, and expanding the range of political experience, per Walter Benjamin.¹⁷

As this impetus is rhetorically wieldable yet materially conditioned, it is worthwhile to turn to the question of the metaphorical meeting point of the legal and the technoscientific. The application of such technologies is rarely divorced from IHL and ICL efforts – in fact, they often focus on the same subjects, events, and geographical areas of interest to jurists, and in doing so reciprocally inform law’s methodological approaches, and *vice-versa*. Zones of armed conflict offer the most apt illustration of this interdisciplinary juncture, as the asymmetry of sensory economies becomes particularly evident in the context of emergencies, where extracted data from concerned locations takes on the greatest value for the greatest number of consumers, including lawyers.¹⁸ The spectacle of conflict and destruction¹⁹ is imbued with an urgency that obliges states and the international commercial space sector to concentrate onto these areas the most advanced observational techniques at their disposal. It is this technoscientific mediation by and through SBEO satellites and computational practices that (in)visibilises certain features and sensory contours of violent conflict,²⁰ upon which jurists and conflict scholars set their literal and metaphorical gaze.

2.2. *New Ways of Seeing through SBEO*

The global legal architecture for the use of SBEO in international justice remains patchwork at best. The seminal article of the *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and use of Outer Space, Including the Moon and other Celestial Bodies* of 1967 legitimises SBEO on the basis of the principles of freedom of space exploration and use, with meaningful consequences: while unauthorised aerial EO of a sovereign territory is subject to international air law and thus can be lawfully restricted,²¹ SBEO over that same territory cannot, enabling satellite operators to capture what might not otherwise be disclosed by states. Despite ambiguous standards for admissibility, the probative value and relevance of such imagery is generally recognised by international courts,²² although this has only ever concerned optical imagery for corroboratory and not necessarily dispositive evidence, meaning that it has only ever been considered in combination with ‘ground truth’ data.

While the non-binding *UN General Assembly Principles Relating to Remote Sensing of the Earth from Outer Space* of 1986 do confirm a right of ‘sensed’ states to non-discriminatory access to primary and processed data at a reasonable cost²³ in accordance with binding space law,²⁴ state practice and *opinio juris* has since deviated substantially from the main guiding principles on international cooperation and the free flow of data. This deviation primarily manifests in the form of restrictive national licensing regimes, data-sharing regulations, and export controls that prohibit certain space technologies and optical

¹⁷ Benjamin, W. (1996). *Imagination*. In M. Bullock & M. W. Jennings (Eds.), *Selected writings, volume 1, 1913–1926* (pp. 280–282). Harvard University Press. For a discussion of the intersection of Benjamin’s theory and legal imagination for humanitarian mapping, see Johns, F. (2023). *Digital humanitarian mapping and the limits of imagination in international law*. *Law and Critique*, 34(3), 341–361. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10978-023-09361-6>.

¹⁸ Johns, F. (2025). *Palliative presentism and its alternatives: International legal emergencies via digital interfaces*. *European Journal of International Law*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ejil/chaf035>.

¹⁹ Bakogianni, A., & Hope, V. M. (2015). *War as spectacle: Ancient and modern perspectives on the display of armed conflict*. Bloomsbury classical studies monographs. London; New York: Bloomsbury Academic. ISBN 9781472522290.

²⁰ Johns, *supra* note 18.

²¹International Civil Aviation Organization. (1944). *Convention on International Civil Aviation* (Chicago Convention), Art. 1. <https://www.icao.int/publications/pages/doc7300.aspx>.

²² See Wang, et al. *supra* note 4.

²³ United Nations General Assembly, *supra* note 2 at Principle XII.

²⁴ Notably the obligation of due regard enshrined in Principle IX of the OST and the UN Convention on Registration of Objects Launched into Outer Space of 1976.

resolutions, and subject satellite operators and downstream users to government permission for use or dissemination of SBEO data. This often depends on the ‘sensitivity’²⁵ of the data collected, the availability of the data on the market or lack thereof,²⁶ and specific imagery of national security²⁷ or geopolitical²⁸ importance. ‘New Space’ private firms have increasingly taken centre stage in the commercial defense sector and the global sensory economy writ large by offering SBEO data at a frequency, speed, and quality often unmatched by larger publicly-owned constellations. Procurement of these commercial services by militaries not only fuels legal conundrums around the status of dual-use technologies²⁹ but also further limits already costly access to imagery through contractual limitations³⁰ and state influence.³¹

Although multispectral imagery remains the predominant format of SBEO, several novel techniques constitute important advancements that change how end-users employ satellite imagery in their respective activities. The most noteworthy include SAR and hyperspectral imagery, which underpin high-resolution 3D digital elevation models, moving target indication, structural damage assessment, interferometry, environmental composition, and more. While multispectral imagery captures essentially the equivalent of a photograph, hyperspectral imagery can identify the material and chemical properties in that same photograph, including vegetation and mineral make-up. Much excitement is also directed towards the application of active, radar-based systems that, unlike passive optical systems, are not dependent on solar light and are thus capable of capturing images at any time, and can penetrate through cloud cover, smoke, and several meters of materials like foliage and soil. By emitting and receiving the backscatter of its own radio waves, SAR-equipped satellites always collect data in the same conditions, facilitating

²⁵ For example, see the German policy on remote sensing data at Federal Ministry of Economics and Technology. (2008, April 15). *German national data security policy for space-based Earth remote sensing systems: Background information for the Act on Satellite Data Security (Satellitendatensicherheitsgesetz – SatDSiG)*. <https://www.bmwi.de/>.

²⁶ For example, see the U.S. licensing policy at U.S. Department of Commerce National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (2020, May 20). Licensing of Private Remote Sensing Space Systems. Federal Register. 85(98). 30790–30815. <https://www.govinfo.gov/content/pkg/FR-2020-05-20/pdf/2020-10703.pdf>.

²⁷For example, India’s recent restrictions on sensing of military bases and major oil refineries. See Govt bans mapping and export of sensitive locations under data regime (2022, September 27). *Business Standard*. https://www.business-standard.com/article/economy-policy/govt-bans-mapping-and-export-of-sensitive-locations-under-data-regime-122092700144_1.html.

²⁸ A noteworthy extraterritorial case of this is Section 1064 of U.S. National Defense Authorisation Act of 1997 (Public Law 104-201), better known as the Kyl-Bingamen Amendment, which heavily restricts the collection or dissemination of satellite imagery of Israel-Palestine by American operators. In 2020, the permitted resolution was lowered from 2 to .40 meters based on the accessibility of such imagery through non-U.S. operators, however the new standard is still not considered sufficient for most major analytic activities. See generally Zerbini, A., & Fradley, M. (2018). *Higher Resolution Satellite Imagery of Israel and Palestine: Reassessing the Kyl-Bingaman Amendment*. *Space Policy*, 45, 43–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2018.03.002>.

²⁹ See notably Azcárate Ortega, A. (2023, June 5). *Not a Rose by Any Other Name: Dual-Use and Dual-Purpose Space Systems*. *Lawfare*. <https://www.lawfaremedia.org/article/not-a-rose-by-any-other-name-dual-use-and-dual-purpose-space-systems>; J. P. Bennett, C. (2025). The dual-use conundrum of the Lisbon Treaty regarding space governance: Solutions through international legal interpretation? *Global Policy*, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1758-5899.70029>.

³⁰ For example, the business model of Vantar (formerly Maxar) and its procurement contract with the U.S. government allowed the latter to buy outright the proprietary rights to certain images, notably those over the Gaza Strip, thereby precluding access to any other potential customers. See NPR. (2023, November 16). *What satellite images over Gaza reveal about [sic] Israel’s intentions*. <https://www.npr.org/2023/11/16/1212889717/satellite-images-us-israel-gaza>.

³¹ Business & Human Rights Resource Centre. (2023, November 7). *Palestine: Key providers of satellite images have begun to restrict imagery of Gaza*. <https://www.business-humanrights.org/fr/derni%C3%A8res-actualit%C3%A9s/palestine-satellite-image-companies-restrict-obscure-images-of-gaza/>.

multi-temporal change detection for continuous moving target characterisation³² and Interferometric SAR (InSAR), a geodetic technique that collapses multiple SAR images into a surface map that indicates up to millimetre-scale ground surface deformations over the course of days to years. In other words, InSAR allows for the mapping of ground deformation through the rapid comparison of different radar images of the same area, which can identify and calculate the velocity of moving objects, or the extent of damage to a given location.

Although these technologies have been around for more than half a century, it is the convergence of several key contemporary material and politico-juridical affordances³³ that have made them accessible to a wider public : Miniaturised constellations have made compacting the size and multiplying the number of SBEO satellites commercially feasible on a massive scale;³⁴ for radar imagery that is not visually legible in the way its optical counterpart is, the recent bounds in artificial intelligence (AI) for data processing has been a tremendous catalyst for its uptake among users;³⁵ and the growing ubiquity of information communication technologies and open data initiatives of the 2010s³⁶ enabled widespread access and experimentation with these techniques. While fast and high-quality, commercial SBEO quickly becomes cost prohibitive for the study of rapidly changing conflict environments and has obligated many non-state actors to focus on improving interpretative techniques for medium-quality open-access SBEO from the U.S. Landsat and E.U. Copernicus constellations.³⁷ This has led to a proliferation of scholarly and grassroots efforts demonstrating creative approaches to open-source SBEO analysis of conflict-induced phenomena conducted by groups like Forensic Architecture,³⁸ Conflict Ecology,³⁹ and Bellingcat⁴⁰ with significant legal and counter-mapping implications. In this way, the circle of individuals engaged in acts of witnessing, interpretation, and advocacy of legal questions under IHL and ICL expands to include civilian non-jurists⁴¹ who nonetheless have a stake in the collective international legal imagination.

2.3. SBEO Image-ination

The innovative SBEO techniques discussed in the previous section are exemplary illustrations of change in technoscientific framing: SAR and its processing methods allow viewers to see beyond the

³² Bai, J., & Qu, W. (2025, May 28). Overview of video synthetic aperture radar moving target detection algorithms. In *International Conference on Remote Sensing, Mapping, and Image Processing (RSMIP 2025)* (Vol. 13650, 1365012). SPIE. <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.3067758>.

³³ James J. Gibson's term here refers to the possibilities an environment offers, provides, or furnishes to the individual. See J. J. Gibson (1966). *The Senses Considered as Perceptual Systems*. Allen and Unwin, London.

³⁴ Davie, O. (2025, May 24). *The satellites using radar to peer at Earth in minute detail*. BBC Future. <https://www.bbc.com/future/article/20240524-the-satellites-using-radar-to-peer-at-earth-in-minute-detail/>.

³⁵ *Ibid*.

³⁶ For more details on the interesting history of the beginning of open satellite data policies, see Zhu, Z., Wulder, M. A., Roy, D. P., Woodcock, C. E., Hansen, M. C., Radeloff, V. C., Healey, S., Schaaf, C., Hostert, P., Lymburner, L., Pahlevan, N. (2019). Benefits of the free and open Landsat data policy. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 224, 382-385. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2019.02.016>.

³⁷ Sticher, V., Wegner, J. D., & Pfeifle, B. (2023). Toward the remote monitoring of armed conflicts. *PNAS nexus*, 2(6), pgad181. <https://doi.org/10.1093/pnasnexus/pgad181>.

³⁸ Forensic Architecture is a research agency based at Goldsmiths University London whose work has been admitted before courts in the U.S., U.K., Germany, Greece, Israel, Guatemala, Colombia, presented to the European Court of Human Rights, UN General Assembly, and the ICC where it is a member of the Technical Advisory Board. See <https://forensic-architecture.org/>.

³⁹ Conflict Ecology is a geospatial research lab based at Oregon State University. Its work has been published in *The New York Times*, *the Washington Post*, *Al Jazeera*, *the Financial Times*, *the BBC*, *the Guardian*, *Der Spiegel*, *Bloomberg News*, among other scholarly journals. See <https://www.conflict-ecology.org/>.

⁴⁰ Bellingcat is an independent collective of researchers, investigators, and citizen journalists focused on open-source investigations into war zones, human rights abuses, and criminal activities and has been awarded several prestigious international awards for their work. See <https://www.bellingcat.com/>.

⁴¹ See Wang, et al. *supra* note 4.

immediately visible present – often rendered into visceral before/after juxtapositions⁴² – into multi-temporal and multi-spatial dimensions. Remote sensing scholars have noted a significant “[...] paradigm shift away from change detection, typically using two points in time, to monitoring, or an attempt to track change continuously in time” through the combination of coherent change detection methods and dense time series analysis.⁴³ SAR-derived analysis can likewise capture ground and object displacement and map them onto digital elevation models that paint a larger picture of the spatial density of damages and the widening contours of front lines.⁴⁴ These approaches broaden and diversify the kinds of land surface change, like ground moisture and building destruction, that can be continuously observed and thus acted upon. These new ways of seeing pull into sharp focus nuanced features of the visual world: human and non-human displacement, air and water pollution, urban morphology of war zones, agriculture, the structural integrity of infrastructure, biodiversity, tempo and intensity of violence, and more.

What demands consideration, however, is not only the content of SBEO’s sensory data, but the relevance of SBEO’s own unique format to legal thought. This brings us to the nexus of technology, law, and the imagination, which has become a meaningful site of international legal discourse⁴⁵ on how law is imagined by jurists and increasingly non-jurists, and how law itself imagines the world through datafied, algorithmic, and digital prisms. The notion of ‘sociotechnical imaginaries’ allows legal scholars to trace how technoscientific developments that influence collective perceptions of public good and desirable futures⁴⁶ also shape the way in which that law defines its subjectivities and social functions.⁴⁷ This proposal is fundamentally one of co-production of knowledge and social ordering, for the sciences and the law alike.⁴⁸ For this reason, SBEO is pivotal to the (co-)production of the legal imagination, both figuratively and etymologically, as it provides a visual image and largely informs how jurists should read it. Satellite imagery carries certain narratives about its relationship to the world, particularly its veracity, that attract the legal gaze and embed themselves in legal hermeneutical strategies. As has been argued previously,⁴⁹ the sociotechnical narratives attached to outer space have played a role in the co-production of the conceptual underpinnings of today’s broad corpus of space law. In this same way, the SBEO of

⁴² Auchter, J. (2025). Visualizing War through Satellite Footage: Technological Capacity, Truth, and the View from Above. *Media, War & Conflict*, 0(0). <https://doi.org/10.1177/17506352251350329>.

⁴³ Woodcock, C. E., Loveland, T. R., Herold, M., & Bauer, M. E. (2020). Transitioning from change detection to monitoring with remote sensing: A paradigm shift. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 238, Article 111558. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2019.111558>.

⁴⁴ Van Den Hoek, J. (2021). The City is the Medium and Satellite Imagery Are a Prism. In *Urban Remote Sensing*, X. Yang (Ed.). <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119625865.ch15>.

⁴⁵ Brännström, L., Noll, G., Parsa, A., et al. (2024). Guest editorial: Tech and the transformation of legal imagination. *AI & Society*, 39, 103–106. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-023-01727-9>.

⁴⁶ Jasanoff, S., & Kim, S.-H. (Eds.). (2015). *Dreamscapes of modernity: Sociotechnical imaginaries and the fabrication of power*. University of Chicago Press. <https://press.uchicago.edu/ucp/books/book/chicago/D/bo20836025.html>.

⁴⁷ Jasanoff, S., & Kim, S.-H. (Eds.). (2015). *Dreamscapes of modernity: Sociotechnical imaginaries and the fabrication of power*. University of Chicago Press. <https://press.uchicago.edu/ucp/books/book/chicago/D/bo20836025.html>.

⁴⁸ Jasanoff, S. (2004) ‘Ordering Knowledge, Ordering Society’, in Jasanoff S. (ed.), *States of Knowledge. The Co-Production of Science and Social Order*, pp. 13–45. London/New York: Routledge.

⁴⁹ Of note is Professor Matthew Craven’s piece on the construction of space as a ‘global commons’ in the Cold War political and technoscientific context, at Craven, M. (2019). ‘Other spaces’: Constructing the legal architecture of a Cold War commons and the scientific-technical imaginary of outer space. *European Journal of International Law*, 30(2), 547–572. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ejil/chz024>. See also Rulier, F. (2023). X-15 et droit de l’espace : L’imaginaire technoscientifique dans la doctrine juridique spatiale des années 1950 et 1960 [X-15 and space law: Technoscientific imagination in space law’s doctrine in the 1950s and 1960s]. *Nacelles*, 14. <https://interfas.univ-tlse2.fr/nacelles/1951>.

war-related harms is imbued with several narratives capable of influencing a *collective* legal understanding of imagery, regardless of differing interpretations of content.

Notably, the ‘God’s eye-view’ through which one ‘sees’ projects a sense of epistemic authority that comes from the distance of the perspective and the technoscientific quality of the medium. As Lisa Parks observed, “[...] because of its remoteness and abstraction, the satellite image functions as an overview of the war, and it draws upon the discursive authority of meteorology, photography, cartography and state intelligence to produce its reality and truth effect”⁵⁰. This sense of objectivity translates into indisputability – the idea that an image can ‘speak for itself’. Particularly when the gaze is set upon a spectacle of violence, there is often a concurrent spectacle of the secret that engrosses one in uncovering what is otherwise obscured, whether that be mass graves in Srebrenica or a tarp-covered decoy submarine in Sevastopol.⁵¹

Figure 1. SAR image of Sevastopol Bay, Crimea, from 20 August 2024, following a Ukrainian missile attack, identifying the damaged Rostov-on-Don submarine as well as the presence of a possible decoy submarine under camouflage netting.⁵²

Subsequently, the perception of SBEO as a method of rational truth-telling means that it takes on a legitimising, persuasive, even testimonial quality: SBEO *reveals*, it *pinpoints*, it *geolocates*, it *confirms*, etc. What distinguishes SBEO as a rhetorical tool from other non-space-based technoscientific documentation is fundamentally its scale. The inclination, according to which the greater the magnitude of something, the greater its importance, represents a potent rhetorical tool; Mapping an oil spill, a city razed to the ground, or wildfire fallout renders visible the spatial scale of a phenomenon.⁵³ What goes

⁵⁰ Parks L (2001) Satellite views of Srebrenica: Televisuality and the politics of witnessing. *Social Identities* 7(4): pp. 593. DOI: 10.1080/13504630120107728.

⁵¹ Cartwright, J., Peterson, K., Gillet, Q., & Radzik, P. (2025, June 26). *Advanced SAR processing with Dwell mode: Enhancing situational awareness for defense and security in war zones*. Presented at ESA Living Planet Symposium 2025, Vienna, Austria. ICEYE. <https://lps25.esa.int/lps25-presentations/presentations/1306/>.

⁵² *Ibid.*

⁵³ It is noteworthy that this rhetoric of scale is sometimes applied to regardless of the scale of the actual image – this is observable in newspaper headlines that emphasise an episode of violence as “visible from space”, often not in pursuit of communicating the geographical scope of the episode but rather alluding to its human-level severity. For example, see Monetta, S. (2025, Oct. 30). Visible from space, bloody sands expose the slaughter of tens of thousands in Sudan. *NBC News*. <https://www.nbcnews.com/world/africa/sudan-africa-civil-war-rapid-support-forces-el-fasher-massacre-rcna240708>.

unspoken is the layered subjective and computational mediation of SBEO, as “[...] satellite imagery [is] always also the product of purposeful practices and interpretational uncertainties”,⁵⁴ especially for more complex techniques like InSAR. It is for these reasons that SBEO must be understood not as objective truth but rather as “a prism for reality”⁵⁵ that nevertheless can multiply the lenses with which the legal gaze can observe wartime atrocities and imagine pathways to remedy.

3. SPACE-BASED EARTH OBSERVATION & REIMAGINING ATROCITY CRIMES

3.1. Two ‘-cides’ of the Same Coin

The international legal vocabulary operates as a nebulous assemblage of terms that, in being written down, spoken aloud, and traded between jurists in a “[...] state of fierce competition for persuasiveness and semantic authority”, constitute the commodities of a textual economy of law.⁵⁶ One of the most accessible points of entry to the *vogue* of the legal semiotic market is neologisms, which illuminate not only the aesthetics⁵⁷ but the idealist objectives of legal scholarship at a given moment. Accompanying the re-emergence of large-scale warfare in the West (where the geographic focus of the international legal vision is often, if not teleologically,⁵⁸ focused), scholarly attention has been directed with renewed vigour to the legal vocabulary for atrocities in ICL, and therefore where it is the most productive to bridge this lexical phenomenon with that of SBEO.

In an effort to record, quantify, and taxonomise diverse forms of violence in armed conflict, jurists have employed neologisms to give a semiotically commodifiable form to new legal conceptions of mass harm. The proliferation of ‘-cide’ derivations,⁵⁹ e.g. ecocide, domicide, scholasticide, spaciocide, medicide, memoricide, etc., speaks to efforts to capture the variegated contours of international atrocities and reinvigorate the potentiality of ICL for analysis and norm-creation.⁶⁰ The efficacy and saliency of this terminology remain contested among scholars,⁶¹ principally due to the fact that ICL and IHL protective measures already encompass the material preoccupations of these concepts under the umbrella of ‘civilian objects’. Article 8(2)(b)(iv) of the Rome Statute prohibits the intentional launching of attacks in the knowledge that it will cause incidental loss of life or injury to civilians, damage to civilian objects, or widespread, long-term and severe damage to the non-human environment which would be clearly

⁵⁴ Olbrich, P., Witjes N. (2015) Earth Observation and International Security: The Role of Uncertainty in Satellite Imagery Analysis by Non-State Actors. *ESPI Perspectives*, No. 72. Vienna: European Space Policy Institute.

⁵⁵ Van Den Hoek, *supra* note 44.

⁵⁶ D’Aspremont, J. (2012). Wording in International Law. *Leiden Journal of International Law*, 25(3), 575–602. doi:10.1017/S0922156512000283.

⁵⁷ Terms that might be considered neologisms are rarely ever purely autopoietic or autogenetic – jurists are inspired by and pull from the vocabularies of neighbouring disciplines, historical epochs, and legal regimes, hence the frequent adoption of Latin legal concepts (e.g. *erga omnes*, *jus cogens*, etc.) in international law.

⁵⁸ This is an argument of profound importance being advanced by scholars of the post-colonial and Third World approaches to international law (TWAIL) movements.

⁵⁹ It is important to note that, besides the clear etymological link to the term ‘genocide’, proponents of the listed neologisms do not necessarily suggest that these concepts be made legally equivalent to the crime of genocide, due in part to the high thresholds for attribution mentioned previously. Proposals have been made for incorporation into the list of crimes against humanity at the international level, and advocacy efforts focused on inclusion into domestic criminal law frameworks have shown success (see notes 81-84).

⁶⁰ Burgis-Kasthala, M., & Masetti Placci, M. (2024, November 14). Lost for words, yet grasping for neologisms: Gaza, genocide and the discursive limits of international law. *EJIL: Talk!* <https://www.ejiltalk.org/lost-for-words-yet-grasping-for-neologisms-gaza-genocide-and-the-discursive-limits-of-international-law/>.

⁶¹ See Dumont, A. (2024, May 7). *To cide or not to cide – Ecocide, what have you started? On new crimes and old problems in international law.* Völkerrechtsblog, <https://voelkerrechtsblog.org/to-cide-or-not-to-cide-ecocide-what-have-you-started/>.

excessive in relation to the concrete and direct overall military advantage anticipated.⁶² The legal thresholds enumerated here are problematic and substantially limit the prosecution of wartime damages – in short, the proportionality standard ultimately allows civilians and their objects to be trampled underfoot by the endlessly flexible exception of ‘military necessity’, application is limited to *international* armed conflicts, the *mens rea* element and reasonable military commander standard for ‘knowledge’ is highly subjective, and the *actus reus* element remains vague.⁶³ Prosecution of such harms as a crime against humanity⁶⁴ or genocide⁶⁵ faces similarly obscure and high thresholds that have been critiqued by States parties⁶⁶ to the Geneva Conventions, international lawyers,⁶⁷ atrocity scholars,⁶⁸ and ICJ judges themselves.⁶⁹

The quantification of warborne harm is a fraught affair – calculation and qualification of the scale, scope, proportionality and intent under the aforementioned thresholds is intensive and legally grey. It is for these reasons that SBEO imagery figures prominently as a key evidentiary and narrative technology in the critical repertoire of jurists in the evaluation of existing and proposed atrocity crimes.⁷⁰ For example, despite little guidance on the qualification of ‘*widespread, long-term, and severe*’ harm, references to

⁶² Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court, Article 8(2)(b)(iv) (2002, amended 2021). <https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/2024-05/Rome-Statute-eng.pdf>. See also Art. 50, 51, and 147 of the Geneva Conventions I, II and IV, respectively, and Art. 52 (1), 35 (3), and 55 (1) of Additional Protocol I.

⁶³ Heller, K. J., & Lawrence, J. C. (2007). *The limits of Article 8(2)(b)(iv) of the Rome Statute: The first ecocentric environmental war crime*. *Georgetown International Environmental Law Review*, 20. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=979460>.

⁶⁴ Some have argued that the systematic destruction of the environment, civilian infrastructure, and dwellings can result in the forced displacement of civilian populations under the crimes of deportation or forcible transfer of population, or ‘other inhumane acts’ laid out by Art. 7(1)(d) and (k) of the Rome Statute. This implies a similar material (i.e. widespread or systematic) and mental (i.e. knowledge of the attack and the relevance of their action) element thresholds to war crimes, but there is no requirement of a specific targeted group, and therefore a (somewhat) less complex *mens rea* threshold, unlike for the crime of genocide.

⁶⁵ Prosecution of large-scale harms to the infrastructural, environmental, medical, and agricultural fabric of a zone of armed conflict as a crime under Art. 2 of the Genocide Convention has been proposed under subsection 3, in that the deliberate infliction of conditions of life to a national, ethnical, racial, or religious group calculated to bring about its physical destruction in whole or in part, as well as the imposition of measures intended to prevent births within the group under subsection 4. Individual criminal liability elements include the oft-discussed *dolus specialis* and the group condition, while State responsibility for genocide has additional thresholds including the ‘only reasonable inference’ standard from ICJ jurisprudence in *Croatia v. Serbia* and *Bosnia v. Serbia*.

⁶⁶ See notably the Joint Declaration of Intervention of Canada, Denmark, France, Germany, the Netherlands and the United Kingdom of 15 November 2023 before the ICJ on the Application of the Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide in Gambia v. Myanmar, <https://www.icj-cij.org/sites/default/files/case-related/178/178-20231115-wri-01-00-en.pdf>.

⁶⁷ See notably Tzouvala, N. (2024, June 24). *Genocide and political economy: Reconstructing the relationship*. Law & Political Economy Project. <https://lpeproject.org/blog/genocide-and-political-economy-reconstructing-the-relationship/>; See also Margale, S. (2025, July 3). *Genocidal intent revisited: Collective erasure vs. individual annihilation*. *Cambridge International Law Journal: Blog*. <https://cilj.co.uk/genocidal-intent-revisited-collective-erasure-vs-individual-annihilation/>; Essawy, R. M. (2024, May 3). *The attainability of the evidentiary standard for genocidal intent in Gaza*. *EJIL: Talk!* <https://www.ejiltalk.org/the-attainability-of-the-evidentiary-standard-for-genocidal-intent-in-gaza/>.

⁶⁸ See notably Gurmendi Dunkelberg, A. (2025). How to Hide a Genocide: Modern/Colonial International Law and the Construction of Impunity. *Journal of Genocide Research*, 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14623528.2025.2454739>.

⁶⁹ Trindade, C. (2016, 18 April). Dissenting Opinion of Judge Cançando Trindade. Concerning the *Application of the Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide (Croatia v. Serbia)*, Judgment. para. 467. <https://www.icj-cij.org/sites/default/files/case-related/118/118-20150203-JUD-01-05-EN.pdf>.

⁷⁰ El-Shawa, S., & Rotola, G. (2025, October). *Earth Observation for Justice in Gaza: Ethical and Legal Implications*. 76th International Astronautical Congress (IAC), Sydney, Australia. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17449136>.

historical ‘widespread’ harm cited impact areas of between 8,000-25,000 sq km⁷¹ – modern public satellites can easily capture 35,000-84,100 sq km⁷² in one image; ‘Long-term’ in ICL is often discussed in decades,⁷³ and recent studies not only conduct time series analysis decades into the past,⁷⁴ but project impact into the future;⁷⁵ ‘Severity’ is tied to damage prejudicing the health or survival of the population and environment,⁷⁶ and InSAR damage assessment techniques combined with deep learning and other *in situ* evidence have identified and mapped damaged facilities to estimate the extent of impact on critical infrastructure and nearby populations.⁷⁷

Figure 2. A display of the most common observation characteristics from a sample of SBEO literature on conflict and human rights published between 2006-2023.⁷⁸

Tracing the interplay between the legal imagination of mass harms and the rapid advancements in SBEO technologies requires examining their overlapping concern with conflict-related infrastructural damage and environmental consequences (see Figure 2). This is best done through a comparison of the conceptual frameworks and discursive mobilisation of the proposed concepts of *ecocide*, *domicide*, and *urbicide*.

⁷¹ International Committee of the Red Cross. (1978). *Official Records of the Diplomatic Conference of Geneva of 1974–1977* (Vol. XIV, CDDH/III/SR.26, p. 237).

⁷² Sentinel Hub. (n.d.). *Sentinel-2 L2A* (API documentation). <https://docs.sentinel-hub.com/api/latest/data/sentinel-2-l2a/>.

⁷³ International Committee of the Red Cross. (1978). *Official Records of the Diplomatic Conference of Geneva of 1974–1977* (Vol. XV, CDDH/215/Rev. I, para. 27).

⁷⁴ See Chidodo, S., Zhang, L., Zarei, A., & Feger, K.-H. (2025, June 19). *Remote sensing-based assessment of four decades of land use/land cover change in the Sigi River Watershed, East Usambara Mountains, Tanzania*. *Frontiers in Remote Sensing*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsen.2025.1594331>.

⁷⁵ See Murphy, M., Sharpe, E., & Huang, K. (2024). The promise of machine learning in violent conflict forecasting. *Data & Policy*, 6, e35. doi:10.1017/dap.2024.27.

⁷⁶ International Committee of the Red Cross. (2020). *Guidelines on the protection of the natural environment in armed conflict: Rules and recommendations relating to the protection of the natural environment under international humanitarian law, with commentary* (Updated ed.; originally published 1994) (para. 72, p. 38). <https://www.icrc.org/en/document/guidelines-protection-natural-environment-armed-conflict>.

⁷⁷ Hou, Z., Qu, Y., Zhang, L., et al. (2024). War city profiles drawn from satellite images. *Nature Cities*, 1, 359–369. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44284-024-00060-6>.

⁷⁸ Edler et al. conducted a review of 51 empirical case studies across 48 publications that used SBEO analysis of events in conflict zones with discussion of related human rights and IHL frameworks. Edler et al., *supra* note 5.

3.2. Ecocide

Ecocide can be understood as “[u]nlawful or wanton acts committed with knowledge that there is a substantial likelihood of severe and either widespread or long-term damage to the environment being caused by those acts”.⁷⁹ Originally proposed in reflection of the environmental manipulation and devastation of the Vietnam War,⁸⁰ ecocide has been criminalised in several national⁸¹ and regional⁸² legal regimes, and submitted by certain States parties⁸³ to the ICC for adoption under the Rome Statute. The ICC has demonstrated an appetite for elaborating doctrine for international environmental crimes, building on Art. 8(2)(b)⁸⁴ but, so far, meaningful criticism of the pitfalls of the definition and (in)compatibility of ecocide for the previously noted thresholds reflects the uncertainty of future development.⁸⁵ This sentiment is contrasted by the public momentum for the concept,⁸⁶ which is only further fuelled by innovations in remote sensing technologies that have allowed civil society groups and researchers to access scientific evidence of large-scale environmental harms⁸⁷ through techniques that can map the interaction of warfare with agriculture, forestry, wildlife, and biodiversity.⁸⁸ SBE0 applications include the rapport between conflict and Normalised Difference Water Indexes, deforestation,⁸⁹ cropland

⁷⁹Independent Expert Panel for the Legal Definition of Ecocide. (2021, June). *Commentary and core text* (Article 8 ter). Stop Ecocide Foundation. <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5ca2608ab914493c64ef1f6d/t/60d7479cf8e7e5461534dd07/1624721314430/SE+Foundation+Commentary+and+core+text+rev+6.pdf>. This is not the only definition for ecocide but is frequently cited in scholarship and international advocacy.

⁸⁰ Falk, R. A. (1973). Environmental Warfare and Ecocide – Facts, Appraisal, and Proposals. *Bulletin of Peace Proposals*, 4(1), 80–96. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/44480206>.

⁸¹ Vietnam, Uzbekistan, France, Russia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Georgia, Belarus, Ukraine, Moldova, Armenia, Chile, and Belgium have all implemented legislation explicitly criminalising ecocide.

⁸² See European Parliament & Council of the European Union. (2024, March 13). *Directive (EU) 2024/1203 on the protection of the environment through criminal law and replacing Directives 2008/99/EC and 2009/123/EC*. Official Journal of the European Union. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2024/1203/oj>.

⁸³ Harvey, F. (2024, September 9). *Pacific islands submit court proposal for recognition of ecocide as a crime*. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/law/article/2024/sep/09/pacific-islands-ecocide-crime-icc-proposal>.

⁸⁴ Agence France-Presse. (2024, February 8). *ICC prosecutor wants court to try ‘environmental crimes’*. France24. Retrieved from <https://www.france24.com/en/live-news/20240207-icc-prosecutor-wants-court-to-try-environmental-crimes>.

⁸⁵See Bothe, M., Bruch, C. E., Diamond, J., & Jensen, D. (2010). International law protecting the environment during armed conflict: Gaps and opportunities. *International Review of the Red Cross*, 92(879), 569–592. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1816383110000427>; Heller, K. J. (2021, June 23). *Skeptical thoughts on the proposed crime of “Ecocide” (That isn’t)*. *Opinio Juris*. <https://opiniojuris.org/2021/06/23/skeptical-thoughts-on-the-proposed-crime-of-ecocide-that-isnt/>.

⁸⁶ It has notably been mobilised in the context of the Russo-Ukrainian war, with the EU and President Volodymyr Zelensky advocating for the prosecution of the 2023 destruction of the Kakhovka dam by Russia and the resulting flood disaster as a war crime. See European Parliament (2023, June 15). *European Parliament resolution on the sustainable reconstruction and integration of Ukraine into the Euro-Atlantic* (2023/2739(RSP)). Section H(4). *Official Journal of the European Union*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/C/2024/490/oj/eng>.

⁸⁷ Nabil, A. (2019, May 16). Proof of Ecocide: Towards a Forensic Practice for the Proposed International Crime Against the Environment. *Journal of Archaeological and Environmental Forensic Science*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.1558/aeefs.36378>.

⁸⁸ Zwijnenburg, W., & Ballinger, O. (2023). Leveraging emerging technologies to enable environmental monitoring and accountability in conflict zones. *International Review of the Red Cross*, 105(924), 1497–1521. doi:10.1017/S1816383123000383.

⁸⁹ Daiyoub, A., Gelabert, P., Saura-Mas, S., & Vega-García, C. (2023). War and deforestation: Using remote sensing and machine learning to identify the war-induced deforestation in Syria 2010–2019. *Land*, 12(8), 1509. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land12081509>.

abandonment and farmer displacement⁹⁰ and starvation,⁹¹ and forest cover and peace negotiations,⁹² among others. Notably, open platform initiatives for continuous monitoring of war-induced environmental damage allow the collaborative elaboration of a body of knowledge that jurists can draw upon.⁹³

Figure 3. A representation of the transformation of the ecology of the northern part of Myanmar's Rakhine State over the course of the Myanmar civil conflict.⁹⁴

What is brought into the line of sight of the legal gaze in these assessments is not only a more granular texture of the environment-conflict nexus, but the gravity of the harm and the evidentiary significance of the information advanced.⁹⁵ In their examination of visual advocacy in the criminalisation of ecocide, Bertram and Hill noted that “[t]he ‘widespread’ character of ecocidal destruction and the scales implicated by this harm lend themselves to the removed vantage point of drone or satellite images. [...] [n]arrowing the case for ecocide by zooming right into specific scenes – or at least specific biomes –

⁹⁰ See Hazaymeh, K., Al-Omari, A., Alzoubi, O., & Al-Nawafleh, A. (2022). A remote sensing-based analysis of the impact of Syrian crisis on agricultural land abandonment in Yarmouk River Basin. *Sensors*, 22(10), 3931. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22103931>.

⁹¹ See Olsen, V. M., Fensholt, R., Olofsson, P., Bonifacio, R., Butsic, V., Druce, D., Ray, D., & Prishchepov, A. V. (2021). The impact of conflict-driven cropland abandonment on food insecurity in South Sudan revealed using satellite remote sensing. *Nature Food*, 2(12), 990–996. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-021-00417-3>.

⁹² Bautista-Céspedes, O., Morales, M., & Armenteras, D. (2021). The effects of armed conflict on forest cover changes across temporal and spatial scales in the Colombian Amazon. *Regional Environmental Change*, 21, 80. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-021-01770-6>.

⁹³ See notably the work of Forensic Architecture on ecocide in Indonesia and Gaza ; Zoë Environment Network. (2023). *Ecodozor platform for monitoring war-related environmental damage and risks in Ukraine*. <https://zoinet.org/product/ecodozor/>.

⁹⁴ Aung, T.S. (2021). Satellite Analysis of the Environmental Impacts of Armed-Conflict in Rakhine, Myanmar. *Science of The Total Environment* 781. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.146758>.

⁹⁵ This is already a phenomenon in motion for much domestic environmental litigation. See for example Zhang, Q., Guo, C., & Lv, J. (2025). Satellite Remote Sensing as a Powerful Tool to Review Evidence in Two Environmental Judicial Cases. *Environmental Forensics*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15275922.2025.2578494>.

makes for a more relatable claim to international criminality.⁹⁶ It is the broad range of possible scales and interpretative techniques that allow SBEO to slide along this spectrum of probative possibility, simulating the ability to zoom in and out of the world from above.⁹⁷ The ICRC and others have argued that the door is very much open for the ICC to exercise flexibility in their interpretation of the *mens rea* element,⁹⁸ proportionality, and widespread, long-term, and severe thresholds based on new scientific understandings.⁹⁹ The epistemic potential of SBEO imagery and other non-visual techniques for this purpose constitutes a development of extreme importance for the next generation of national and international criminal proceedings.

3.3. Domicide & Urbicide

While the notions of domicile and urbicide differ in their focal harm,¹⁰⁰ they nevertheless draw upon the same legal tenets and SBEO techniques in the construction and defence of their proposals. Urbicide refers to mass violence that aims to destroy an urban hub not necessarily as a strategic objective, but as a social-identity objective in a larger cultural genocide; despite its absence from the formal international legal lexicon, it figures greatly in the work of the International Criminal Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia and recent discourse on the urbanisation of contemporary warfare.¹⁰¹ Domicide, as advocated by the UN Special Rapporteur,¹⁰² is “[t]he deliberate destruction of homes, the rendering of homes uninhabitable or any other systematic denial of housing such as acts carried out in violation of international law and committed as part of a widespread or systematic attack against any civilian

⁹⁶ Bertram, D., & Hill, G. (2024). Polar bears and gavels: Visual advocacy in the criminalization of ecocide. *Journal of International Criminal Justice*, 22(1), 185–210. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jicj/mqae014>.

⁹⁷ See Part 3.2 for discussion on the limits of techno-optimism for ICL.

⁹⁸ In light of scholarly criticism of the direct and indirect intent rule of *mens rea* per Article 30 of the Rome Statute that both fail to effectively encapsulate the most serious of environmentally destructive acts, including those resulting from corporate practices, some jurists have developed creative proposals for the derogation and reinterpretation of the rule for a crime of ecocide, based instead on negligence, recklessness, and wilful blindness. See for example Savard, C. (2025). What *mens rea* for ecocide in the Rome Statute? *The International Journal of Human Rights*, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13642987.2025.2552468>.

⁹⁹ See Sharma, R. (2025, January 16). *Ecocide as the fifth international crime: Is the Rome Statute compatible with ecocide?* *Völkerrechtsblog*. <https://voelkerrechtsblog.org/ecocide-as-the-fifth-international-crime/>.

¹⁰⁰ While both the destruction of civilian individual and cultural property can be considered as a war crime under Art. 8(2) of the Rome Statute, advocacy for these concepts tend to focus on its criminalisation either as a crime against humanity or as a standalone crime like that of genocide, the most salient example being the UN Special Rapporteur Balakrishnan Rajagopal’s report on the right to adequate housing during violent conflict (see note XXXXXXXX). When a part of a widespread or systematic attack against a civilian population, housing destruction that results in displacement may qualify as the crimes of deportation or forcible transfer of population under Art. 7(1)(d) of the Rome Statute, or when conducted in a discriminatory or targeted way impacting a specific group can fall under crimes of persecution or apartheid under Art. 7(1)(h) and (j), and Art. 7(2)(g) and (h) respectively.

¹⁰¹ Robichez, Juliette. (2024). "Urbicide" and the preservation of the cultural heritage of humanity: solution to adapt international humanitarian law to the urbanization of war? [“Urbicídio” e preservação do patrimônio cultural da humanidade: solução para adaptação do Direito Internacional Humanitário à urbanização da guerra?]. *Brazilian Journal of International Law*, 21(1), 12-32.

¹⁰² Professor Rajagopal is an active advocate of imaginative, collective, and bottom-up methods of international law-making as a part of the TWAIL movement. See, for example, Rajagopal, B. (2003). *International law from below: Development, social movements, and Third World resistance*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511494079>. See also The Architectural League (2024, June 4). *Architecture, Planning, and International Law: On Domicide*. Featuring Balakrishnan Rajagopal (United Nations) and Natasha Aruri (UR°BANA), moderated by Brad Samuels (SITU). <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-rdhHKh9-ak>.

population.”¹⁰³ Both of these proposals take on a relational concept of space¹⁰⁴ that emphasises the intimate link between the significance of space and human interaction – here advocating a shift from a materially static conceptualisation of the loss of individual and collective property towards a “[...] multidimensional view of home that spans different temporalities, affective registers and modalities of loss” that collapses diverse forms of destruction like dispossession, eviction, genocide,¹⁰⁵ forced displacement, demolition, and population transfer into a single notion.¹⁰⁶

Figure 4. Mapping of InSAR-identified structural damage in the Gaza Strip between October 2023 and January 2024 produced by Conflict Ecology and the Decentralised Damage Mapping Group.¹⁰⁷

Following improvements to AI-based techniques and open access to SAR data, researchers have taken to adapting InSAR methods traditionally used for natural disaster damage assessment to conflict settings, refining parameters for severity and scalability from cities to entire state territories.¹⁰⁸ Studies on

¹⁰³ Rajagopal, B. (2022, July 19). *Report of the Special Rapporteur on adequate housing as a component of the right to an adequate standard of living, and on the right to non-discrimination in this context: The right to adequate housing during violent conflict* (UN Doc. A/77/190, p. 14). United Nations.

¹⁰⁴ Harvey, D. (2006). Space as keyword. In D. Harvey, *Spaces of global capitalism: Towards a theory of uneven geographical development* (pp. 119–148). London: Verso.

¹⁰⁵ In the International Court of Justice’s recent order recognising Palestinian’s right to be protected from genocide underlines the link between the destruction of the home and genocide as evidenced by their mention of ‘home’ eight times in a 29-page document. See International Court of Justice. (2024, January 26). *Order in the case concerning Application of the Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide (South Africa v. Israel)*. <https://www.icj-cij.org/node/203447>.

¹⁰⁶ Zeffert, H. (2024). Nowhere home. *London Review of International Law*, 12(2), 131–153. <https://doi.org/10.1093/lril/lrae013>.

¹⁰⁷ Bliss, L. (2024, January 24). *MapLab: Mapping Gaza’s destruction* [Newsletter]. Bloomberg News. <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/newsletters/2024-01-24/maplab-mapping-gaza-s-destruction>.

¹⁰⁸ Sticher et al., *supra* note 37.

structural damage across Ukraine,¹⁰⁹ the Gaza Strip,¹¹⁰ Darfur in Sudan,¹¹¹ and in Mosul¹¹² and Syria¹¹³ have identified sites of damage and corresponding severity, patterns of destruction, and tempos of hostilities. Information like that contained in *Figure 4* is actively being taken up by international jurists, for example, regarding *jus ad bellum* proportionality assessment, for which they advance SBE0 InSAR data as evidence of a violation of proportionality through excessive harm and, crucially, domicile.¹¹⁴

Conflict damage itself contains many temporalities that are difficult to capture, as traditional methods continuously direct attention to large, abrupt damages, presupposing a permanence to damage from ephemeral events that are temporally distinct from the conflict at large¹¹⁵. Over time, their apparent presence can be erased through debris removal, muddled by rainfall or vegetation, or be repeatedly rebuilt and destroyed.¹¹⁶ These nuances to the spacio-temporal morphology of conflict damage make the collection and evaluation of evidence for criminal prosecution difficult, damage claims, and postwar re-appropriation. This was the case, for example, in the proceedings between the nomadic Bedouin Al-Turi families and Israel, which does not recognise their claims to property in the Negev region nor the existence of the village of Al-Araqib, and as such considers Bedouin villagers to be illegal trespassers and

¹⁰⁹ See Scher, C. & Van Den Hoek, J. (2025, June). Nationwide conflict damage mapping with interferometric synthetic aperture radar: A study of the 2022 Russia–Ukraine conflict. *Science of Remote Sensing*, 11(100217). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.srs.2025.100217>; Xu, H., Barbot, S., & Wang, T. (2024). Remote sensing through the fog of war: Infrastructure damage and environmental change during the Russian-Ukrainian conflict revealed by open-access data. *Natural Hazards Research*, 4(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nhres.2024.01.006>; Huang, Q., Jin, G., Xiong, X., Ye, H., & Xie, Y. (2023). Monitoring urban change in conflict from the perspective of optical and SAR satellites: The case of Mariupol, a city in the conflict between RUS and UKR. *Remote Sensing*, 15(12), 3096.

¹¹⁰ See Asi, Y., Mills, D., Greenough, P. G., et al. (2024). “Nowhere and no one is safe”: Spatial analysis of damage to critical civilian infrastructure in the Gaza Strip during the first phase of the Israeli military campaign, 7 October to 22 November 2023. *Conflict and Health*, 18, 24. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13031-024-00580-x>; Kahraman, F., Imamoglu, M., & Ates, H. F. (2016). Battle damage assessment based on self-similarity and contextual modeling of buildings in dense urban areas. In 2016, *IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium (IGARSS)* (pp. 5161-5164). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IGARSS.2016.7730345>; Scher, Corey & Van Den Hoek, Jamon. (2025). *Active InSAR monitoring of building damage in Gaza during the Israel-Hamas War*. 10.48550/arXiv.2506.14730.

¹¹¹ See Knoth, C., Slimani, S., Appel, M., & Pebesma, E. (2018). Combining automatic and manual image analysis in a web-mapping application for collaborative conflict damage assessment. *Applied Geography*, 97, 25-34; Knoth, C., & Pebesma, E. (2017). Detecting dwelling destruction in Darfur through object-based change analysis of very high-resolution imagery. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 38(1), 273-295; Marx, A. J., & Loboda, T. V. (2013). Landsat-based early warning system to detect the destruction of villages in Darfur, Sudan. *Remote sensing of environment*, 136, 126-134.

¹¹² See Fakhri, F., & Gkanatsios, I. (2021). Integration of Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data for change detection: A case study in a war conflict area of Mosul city. *Remote Sensing Applications: Society and Environment*, 22, 100505; Bolorani, A. D., Darvishi, M., Weng, Q., & Liu, X. (2021). Post-war urban damage mapping using InSAR: the case of Mosul City in Iraq. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 10(3), 140.

¹¹³ See Braun, A. (2018). Assessment of building damage in Raqqa during the Syrian civil war using time-series of radar satellite imagery. *GI Forum 2018*, 6, 228-242; Lubin, A., & Saleem, A. (2019). Remote sensing-based mapping of the destruction to Aleppo during the Syrian Civil War between 2011 and 2017. *Applied geography*, 108, 30-38; Marx, A. J. (2016). Detecting urban destruction in Syria: A Landsat-based approach. *Remote Sensing Applications: Society and Environment*, 4, 30-36; Tapete, D., & Cigna, F. (2016, August). Urban remote sensing in areas of conflict: TerraSAR-X and Sentinel-1 change detection in the Middle East. In *Fourth International Conference on Remote Sensing and Geoinformation of the Environment (RSCy2016)* (Vol. 9688, pp. 657-664). SPIE.

¹¹⁴Ulbricht, B., Weiner, A. S., Van Den Hoek, J., & Scher, C. (2025, June 5). “There is nothing left”: *Jus ad bellum* proportionality and Israel’s war against Hamas in Gaza. Stanford Public Law Working Paper. Forthcoming in the Berkeley Journal of International Law. SSRN : <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5283689>.

¹¹⁵ Van Den Hoek, *supra* note 44.

¹¹⁶ This applies for claims of returning displaced people as well. See Forensic Architecture. (2017, June 27). *Destruction and return in al-Araqib*. <https://forensic-architecture.org/investigation/destruction-and-return-in-al-araqib>.

has demolished their domiciles over 200 times.¹¹⁷ To this end, SAR and optical imagery evincing land-use patterns and the frequent damage¹¹⁸ to the village were advanced by the families as substantive proof of regular habitation and continuous seasonal land cultivation, as well as state responsibility for wrongful deprivation of private property resulting in forced displacement.¹¹⁹ SBEO was thus used to render visible, measurable, and legally actionable the protection of collective and private sites of human life.

Figure 5. Cumulative burden of infrastructure damage across the Gaza Strip and the spatial relationship of said damage to health, education, and water facilities between October 7 and November 22, 2023, produced by Conflict Ecology and the Decentralised Damage Mapping Group.¹²⁰

This relationship between time and space has special relevance for the proportionality and *mens rea* elements of international crimes. In a study of facilities demonstrating a high degree of damage clustering

¹¹⁷ Margalit, A. (2017). The Israeli Supreme Court and Bedouin Land Claims in the Negev: A Missed Opportunity to Uphold Human and Indigenous Rights. *International Journal on Minority and Group Rights*, 24(1), 57–69. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26557859>.

¹¹⁸ The village has been demolished 225 times since the 1950s, often multiple times a year, but is consistently rebuilt using temporary housing by the Bedouin communities. See Association France Palestine Solidarité. (2023, September 11). *Dans le Néguev/Naqab, le village bédouin d'Al-Araqib démoli pour les 220^e et 221^e fois*. <https://www.france-palestine.org/Dans-le-Neguev-Naqab-le-village-bedouin-d-Al-Araqib-demoli-pour-les-220e-et->

¹¹⁹ Forensic Architecture, *supra* note 116.

¹²⁰ Asi, Y., Mills, D., Greenough, P. G., et al. (2024). “Nowhere and no one is safe”: Spatial analysis of damage to critical civilian infrastructure in the Gaza Strip during the first phase of the Israeli military campaign, 7 October to 22 November 2023. *Conflict and Health*, 18, 24. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13031-024-00580-x>.

for critical civilian infrastructure in the Gaza Strip in the first 46 days of Israel's Operation Iron Sword, researchers conducted a spatial inference statistic to characterise the randomness of this clustering, finding the resulting Z-scores as indicative of a < 1% likelihood of the cluster damage occurring by random chance.¹²¹ They also calculate, according to the standards of the U.S. Methodology for Combat Assessment, that all governates fall within the category of 'completely destroyed' having suffered equal to or greater than 50% severe damage.¹²² In these calculations, there emerges an unspoken inverse statement regarding the margin of knowledge and intentionality of military decision-makers. Through these complex SBEO interpretative techniques, researchers are fundamentally engaging in legal questions of the proportionality and severity of Israel's conduct of hostilities. In doing so, they simultaneously propose a contextual schema for the evaluation of the 'systemic' or 'methodical' nature of violence as a crime against humanity, or the intent and knowledge thresholds of war crimes, as they could apply to a crime of domicile or urbicide.

3.4. Towards an Interdisciplinary Legal Imagination

The many prisms of SBEO techniques allow jurists to view and interpret sensory data of conflict-related damage in legally meaningful ways, extending new methods of characterising such damage across a spectrum of temporalities and geographical scales under existing and proposed atrocity crimes in ICL. This aligns with the broader paradigm shift in international legal theory away from anthropocentrism and toward a posthumanist conception of subjectivity that considers the non-human as well as the human,¹²³ and envisions universality as grounded in the interdependence and care of these relationships.¹²⁴

The illustrated *rapprochement* of SBEO techniques and legal imaginings for the appraisal of structural and environmental wartime damage demonstrates, without being self-incriminatory, a certain techno-optimist affinity across the legal and remote sensing disciplines.¹²⁵ Variations in space technology, remote sensing techniques, and imagery accessibility dictate the production and circulation of knowledge and epistemic authority within the international sensory economies around armed conflicts. While military and commercial actors possess the most advantageous positions in these economies, open-access geospatial datasets and no-code platforms have been foundational in innovating interpretative methods and democratising access to SBEO to academia and other investigative researchers. The growing body of literature on these concurrent phenomena gives shape and direction to two critical projects of international justice, i.e. ecocide and domicile/urbicide, that have a fundamentally open-access and participatory character, defined by crowdsourcing, transfer learning, open-source mapping, digital archiving, and other civilian science methods.¹²⁶ As machine learning becomes more prevalent in documenting conflicts, professional and civilian scholars have assumed a greater role in these efforts, creating unavoidable

¹²¹ *Ibid.*

¹²² U.S. Joint Chiefs of Staff. (2019). *CJCSI 3162.02: Methodology for combat assessment*. U.S. Joint Chiefs of Staff.

https://www.jcs.mil/Portals/36/Documents/Doctrine/training/jts/cjcsi_3162_02.pdf?ver=2019-03-13-092459-350.

¹²³ See notably Arvidsson, M., & Sjöstedt, B. (2023). Ordering human–other relationships. In *The Routledge handbook of international law and anthropocentrism* (1st ed., pp. 21–...). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003201120-8>; Lindgren, T. (2018). Ecocide, genocide and the disregard of alternative life-systems. *The International Journal of Human Rights*, 22(4), 525–549. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3357214>.

¹²⁴ Zeffert, H. (2024). Nowhere home. *London Review of International Law*, 12(2), 131–153. <https://doi.org/10.1093/lril/lrae013>.

¹²⁵ See Van Den Meerdsche, D. (2024). International law and technology as a critical project: A collective reading. *European Journal of International Law*, 35(4), 963–970. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ejil/chae069>.

¹²⁶ See, for example, Cornebise, J., Worrall, D., Farfour, M., & Marin, M. (2018). *Witnessing atrocities: Quantifying villages destruction in Darfur with crowdsourcing and transfer learning*. In *Proceedings of AI for Social Good Workshop at NeurIPS 2018 (NeurIPS'18)*. <https://cornebise.com/julien/assets/pdf/cornebise2018witnessing.pdf>. See more generally Weir, D., McQuillan, D., & Francis, R. A. (2019). Civilian science: The potential of participatory environmental monitoring in areas affected by armed conflicts. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 191(3). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-019-7773-9>.

consequences for the validation of such documentation under traditional legal expertise.¹²⁷ Bridging the gap between legal and scientific epistemic communities can take the form of interdisciplinary collaboration for technical standard-setting, capacity-building initiatives, and continuous remote monitoring observatories.¹²⁸

Figure 6. User interfaces of open-source tools for mapping country-wide destruction in Ukraine.¹²⁹ and the Gaza Strip¹³⁰ based on SAR image time series mapped onto Google Earth Engine.

While important, the logistical and procedural questions of procuring and ensuring SBEO's admissibility and interpretation in the courtroom, or the nuances of its use for deterrence or detection, lie out of the scope of this piece. Instead, this foregoing analysis points to the legal arguments that are already being made, and not exclusively by lawyers, but by civil society, academia, and other technical entities engaged in an ongoing interdisciplinary and transnational normative conversation. This is not incidental to

¹²⁷ Edler et al., *supra* note 5.

¹²⁸ For more on such proposals see Sticher et al., Sou et al., and Scher & Van Den Hoek at *supra* notes 37, 77, and 110. See also Bennett, M. M., Van Den Hoek, J., Zhao, B., & Prishchepov, A. V. (2022). Improving satellite monitoring of armed conflicts. *Earth's Future*, 10, e2022EF002904. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022EF002904>.

¹²⁹ Dietrich, O., Peters, T., Sainte Fare Garnot, V., et al. (2025). An open-source tool for mapping war destruction at scale in Ukraine using Sentinel-1 time series. *Communications Earth & Environment*, 6, 215. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-025-02183-7>.

¹³⁰ Beirut Urban Lab. *Tracking the Urbicide in Gaza*. <https://beiruturbanlab.com/en/Details/1977>.

international law but constitutive of it, as the co-production of technoscientific and legal knowledge is precisely the mechanism through which new ways of seeing generate new possibilities for legal action.

This is of critical importance precisely because IHL and ICL, of all branches of international law, are particularly future and present-oriented, acting as a body of norms and terms to guide real-time decision-making to prevent and rectify mass harms, as well as render justice *post facto*. While an essential component of the international legal order, the world rarely holds its breath for formal deliberations and decisions by recognised legal authorities like the International Criminal Court or the International Court of Justice – rather, jurists and non-jurists alike are constantly engaged in formal and informal debates over the ongoing requalification of conflict and harm. Focusing scholarly attention on this mode of decentralised, active legal discourse illustrates how moments when IHL and ICL norms are argued to be at their weakest, such as moments of egregious violation, or slow to non-existent enforcement, are in fact when these norms are recentered, reaffirmed, and reimagined within popular discussion. To this point, InSAR analysis of damage clustering probabilities or hyperspectral capture of a frontline’s chemical fingerprint constitute a sensory image of warfare that participates in, informs, and frames these debates. In its capacity as a prism capable of attracting, refracting, and scaling the legal gaze, SBEO techniques lend legitimacy to participatory and expansive reimaginings of the international legal order’s formulations of universal crimes.

It thus follows that jurists cannot remain passive consumers of technical outputs. Engagement with the sociotechnical questions of interpreting SBEO data is not peripheral to legal work but internal to it: What is a standard ‘threshold of detectability’¹³¹ in pixels? What differences in coherence value distributions should trigger legal evaluation? How do limitations in SAR revisit cycles bear on narratives of systematic and continuous destruction? The quantification of harm is simultaneously a normative act, and the choice of which harms to render visible, at what resolution, and through whose interpretive frameworks, remains inescapably a legal and political one. Only through such engagement can the expanding sensory capacities of SBEO be aligned with the normative ambitions of IHL and ICL to render violence visible, to discipline its conduct, and ultimately to contribute to the prevention and redress of mass harm.

¹³¹ Weizman, E. (2017). *Forensic Architecture: Violence at the Threshold of Detectability*. MIT Press. Zone Books. ISBN 9781935408864.

© The Author(s) 2026. Published by Space Court Foundation. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted reuse, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

INSURANCE AND INDEMNIFICATION IN GOVERNMENT CONTRACTS FOR SPACE AND DEFENSE

ABRAHAM MARTIN¹

ABSTRACT

The US federal government is becoming increasingly dependent on commercial partnerships for its space capabilities in the 21st century. With federal awards for space services exceeding \$29.9 billion in 2023 alone, the financial stakes for both agencies and contractors are immense. This paper identifies the different species of risk that commercial space companies face, specifically, losses from misadventure, from foreign interference, and from third-party liability. While commercial insurance and statutory indemnification mechanisms, such as those under the Commercial Space Launch Act and Public Law 85-804, provide a partial solution, they fall short in covering losses caused by foreign adversaries. Due to the prevalence in the private insurance market of exclusion clauses for hostile acts and restrictive definitions in certain procurement contracts, like “unusually hazardous” activities, many space contractors remain critically underprotected. This gap poses not only a prohibitive economic hazard to some companies but also undermines a broader national interest in fostering a resilient, diverse, and competitive base of space contractors.

The paper recommends a legislative solution: a framework that would require contractors to acquire the maximum amount of insurance available from the marketplace while also providing government-backed indemnification for any additional loss caused by foreign interference. Such a system would both mitigate risk for contractors and reinforce critical U.S. strategic space interests by enabling greater participation from diverse commercial actors. Ultimately, ensuring that space contractors are adequately protected from foreign threats is essential to maintaining America’s leadership and operational capacity in space.

KEYWORDS: Space Law, Government Contracts, Indemnification, Risk Mitigation, Commercial Space Industry.

¹ J.D. Candidate (2026), University of Virginia School of Law; abenoble@gmail.com.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the 1995 film *Apollo 13*, NASA flight director Gene Kranz, played by Ed Harris, makes the infamous proclamation that “Failure is not an option.”² This statement of courage and hope in the face of seemingly insurmountable odds of disaster for the crew of the Apollo 13 crew fittingly represents the laudable efforts of the 20th century American heroes who pioneered human spaceflight. In both the movie and reality, Kranz and the rest of NASA were able to bring the Apollo 13 astronauts home safely, but as it turns out, the legendary line was solely the creation of Hollywood screenwriters. Indeed, there is no evidence that Kranz ever said anything of the sort.³ Perhaps Kranz never would have said such a thing, for he knew very well that failure is very often an option for humanity’s forays into space. The history of space technology all too harshly indicates that failure of some sort is an inevitability.

In the decades since the Apollo missions, the nature of spaceflight has dramatically changed. Particularly since the retirement of the Space Shuttle, partnerships between commercial space operators and the federal government dominate the American aerospace sector.⁴ Contract awards from NASA and the Space Force totaled a record \$29.9 billion in 2023.⁵ This increase from \$26.7 billion in 2022 was due, in part, to increased funding for big-ticket items such as NASA’s Human Landing System and Mars Sample Return Program.⁶ These contracts represent massive line items for the federal budget, and the funding that the contract payments provide to the commercial space industry is essential for its continuing vitality. In the realm of space contracts, where billions of dollars are at stake and failure is an inevitability, methods for mitigating risk are of paramount concern.

This Article begins by describing the various species of risk that space contractors may encounter. After surveying the means of mitigating these risks available in both the marketplace and the procurement process, the Article identifies the potential that foreign adversaries will interfere with and cause losses for space contractors as a crucial type of risk for which there are yet incomplete solutions. Finally, the Article suggests that Congress may address this problem by extending special statutory authority to agencies that contract with space companies.

2. RISK IN SPACE

2.1. *Direct Loss Due to Misadventure*

There are three broad categories of risks that space contractors face. First, there is the ever-present risk that the contractor’s space technology will fail and that this failure will cause significant first-party economic loss, also called direct loss. As space technology becomes more versatile and grows in its applications, the potential for direct loss exposure for these companies increases.

One of the more common forms of government contracts in the aerospace industry is a contract for launch services. In April of 2025, the U.S. Space Force tapped commercial space companies SpaceX, United

² *Apollo 13* (Imagine Entertainment 1995).

³ Associated Press. (2020, April 9). *Apollo 13’s most famous quotes originated in Hollywood*. AP News. <https://apnews.com/article/hollywood-apollo-13s-famous-quotes-7c65759a64b04d0a979e3f4a62c4fced>.

⁴ See NASA, *Commercial Crew Program: Program Essentials*, <https://www.nasa.gov/humans-in-space/commercial-space/commercial-crew-program/commercial-crew-program-essentials/> (last visited Mar. 7, 2026) (explaining how the retirement of the Shuttle led NASA to rely on commercial partners for launch services).

⁵ Siken, J. (2024, January 17). *Record \$765B in federal contracts awarded in 2023*. HigherGov. <https://www.highergov.com/reports/765b>.

⁶ *Id.*

Launch Alliance, and Blue Origin for a new batch of launch services.⁷ These contracts are worth a combined \$13.5 billion through 2029.⁸ Historically, these launches were accomplished with single-use rockets.⁹ Beyond the loss of the payload, the failure of these rockets generally posed no greater risk of economic loss to the operator because the rocket had no ongoing economic utility beyond the single launch for which they were produced. However, several companies have recently begun to operate or plan to soon operate reusable rocket technology.¹⁰ Since rocket reuse promises to be up to 65% cheaper than building a new rocket,¹¹ these launch companies have a strong economic interest in the safe return of the hardware. Where reuse is possible, a launch entails not only a risk of failure for the mission and loss of the payload, but also the risk that the company will lose a significant financial investment in the rocket itself.

Satellite operators, as another example, often stand to suffer significant direct loss when hardware breaks down or is damaged. In 2020, when the number of satellites in orbit was significantly lower than it is today,¹² space debris alone caused losses of an estimated \$79-102 million.¹³ While the financial risk of deploying communication satellites is already well known, space-based data centers, an idea fueled by the recent AI boom, elevate these concerns even higher. These platforms would require large, vulnerable and expensive features such as radiation shielding, radiator panels and computation hardware, further tying up the capital of cutting-edge space companies in vulnerable orbital assets.¹⁴ Similar to the development of reuse technology for orbital rockets, the advancement of satellite technology into the realms of orbital refueling also prolongs the economic utility of some orbital assets. A satellite operator that intends to significantly extend the usefulness of a satellite by periodically refueling will undoubtedly be more sensitive to risks to the satellite, especially those that arise early after its initial deployment.

In the standard launch contract that a commercial satellite operator solicits from a commercial launch company, “[n]either the satellite manufacturer nor the launch services provider accept[s] any liability for satellite or launch failures following intentional ignition.”¹⁵ Instead, parties rely on commercial satellite insurance.¹⁶

2.2. Direct Loss Due to Interference

The second species of risk that space contractors face is the possibility of damage or interference at the hands of adversaries. Though, like the first category, it threatens space companies with direct loss, it is analytically distinct because of the unique challenges it poses to contractors.

⁷ Roulette, J. (2025, April 4). *SpaceX, ULA, Blue Origin clinch \$13.5 billion Pentagon launch contracts*. Reuters. <https://www.reuters.com/business/aerospace-defense/spacex-ula-expected-clinch-multibillion-dollar-contract-key-pentagon-launch-2025-04-04/>.

⁸ *Ibid.*

⁹ Stockley, A. (2023, April 12). *The rise of reusable rockets: Transforming the economics of space travel*. KDC Resource. <https://www.kdcresource.com/insights-events/the-rise-of-reusable-rockets-transforming-the-economics-of-space-travel/>.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*

¹¹ *Ibid.*

¹² David Osoro et al., *Emissions Assessment of Low Earth Orbit (LEO) Broadband Megaconstellations*, ADVANCES IN SPACE RESEARCH (forthcoming 2025), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asr.2025.11.036>.

¹³ Nodir Adilov et al., *An Estimate of Expected Economic Losses from Satellite Collisions with Orbital Debris*, 10 J. SPACE SAFETY ENG’G 66 (2023).

¹⁴ Jeremy Hsu, *Data Centers in Space Aren’t as Wild as They Sound*, SCIENTIFIC AM. (Dec. 9, 2025), <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/data-centers-in-space/>.

¹⁵ Segal, R., & Kaufman, S. (n.d.). *Satellite systems procurement: A brief how-to guide*. NASA Space Science and Viability Initiative. https://s3vi.ndc.nasa.gov/ssri-kb/static/resources/05444_Satellite_Procurement_Updated_04BM_7557.pdf.

¹⁶ *Ibid.*

Two characteristics of outer space make space assets particularly vulnerable to risk from adversaries. First, the Outer Space Treaty prevents member States from asserting sovereignty over any orbital position or planet, so assets in space are not sheltered by any kind of border or boundary.¹⁷ Instead, they fly in an inherently international regime to which all space-faring states have lawful access. Second, space technology has critical warfare and defense applications. Despite the aspiration of the Outer Space Treaty that space will be used only for “peaceful purposes,”¹⁸ space is increasingly another theatre of international conflict. Indeed, hostility in space is no longer just a matter of science fiction. In the war in Ukraine, Russia has already demonstrated the capability to jam satellite communication networks.¹⁹ Notably, Russia developed technology specifically for the purpose of interfering with the Starlink satellite constellation, a private system owned and operated by SpaceX, an important contractor for the US government.²⁰

Several nations (including the US, China, India, and Russia) have tested Direct-assent ASAT (anti-satellite) missile technology that can completely and permanently destroy orbital assets, rendering them into clouds of dangerous debris that can pose risks to other activities in space for years.²¹ Russia, China and the United States (both the Department of Defense and private companies within the US) have also developed and demonstrated “RPO” (Rendezvous and Proximity Operations) in which one satellite approaches another in space.²² Some of these satellites have mechanical arms that could be used for grasping or disabling an adversary’s space asset.²³ Moreover, as the scope and complexity of space technology grow, nations will continue to develop new counter-space capabilities that have the potential to interfere with the operations of commercial space operators.

The Trump administration’s plan to construct a “golden dome” in space provides a critical example of the emergence of this problem. President Trump has directed the Department of Defense to explore options for an anti-missile system with a significant space-based component.²⁴ As many as 180 companies have expressed an interest in contributing to the project.²⁵ Many of the companies are smaller startups, including Epirus, Ursa Major and Armada.²⁶ The most public of these proposals comes from a collaboration between SpaceX, Palantir, and Anduril, and it proposes a system composed of hundreds of

¹⁷ United Nations. (1967, January 27). *Treaty on principles governing the activities of states in the exploration and use of outer space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies* (OST). 18 U.S.T. 2410; 610 U.N.T.S. 205.

¹⁸ *Id.* at Art. I.

¹⁹ Secure World Foundation. (2025). *Global counterspace capabilities 02-28*. https://swfound.org/media/208089/swf_global_counterspace_capabilities_2025.pdf

²⁰ *Ibid.*

²¹ Roman, N. (2024, January 30). *Global status of anti-satellite (ASAT) weaponry and testing*. Alliance for Citizen Engagement.

<https://ace-usa.org/blog/research/research-foreignpolicy/global-status-of-anti-satellite-asat-weaponry-and-testing/>.

²² Weeden, B. (2019, April 12). *The evolution of space rendezvous and proximity operations and implications for space security* [Presentation at the United Nations Disarmament Conference]. United Nations Institute for Disarmament Research. https://unidir.org/files/2019-12/Brian%20WEEDEN%20-%20UNDC_RPO_Apr2019.pdf.

²³ *Ibid.*

²⁴ Kube, C., & Lee, C. E. (2025, April 17). *Pentagon working to make Trump’s vision of a U.S. Iron Dome a reality*. NBC News.

<https://www.nbcnews.com/politics/national-security/pentagon-working-make-trumps-vision-us-iron-dome-reality-rcna201105>.

²⁵ Stone, M., & Taylor, M. (2025, April 17). *Exclusive: Musk’s SpaceX is frontrunner to build Trump’s Golden Dome missile shield*. Reuters.

<https://www.reuters.com/business/aerospace-defense/musks-spacex-is-frontrunner-build-trumps-golden-dome-missile-shield-2025-04-17/>.

²⁶ *Ibid.*

satellites that both sense and attack enemy missiles.²⁷ Interestingly, the companies have also proposed organizing the system as a “subscription service”: for a periodic fee, the Department of Defense could utilize the network while the private companies retain ownership of the hardware.²⁸

Though the international law governing attacks against privately owned satellites furnishing services to military entities is still in development,²⁹ it is undeniable that a satellite which enables an anti-missile system would be a very attractive target for a foreign hostile.³⁰ Even if the plans for a “golden dome” are never realized, military communication services are increasingly utilizing commercial satellites. Commercial satellites “carry between 80-90 percent of all U.S. military communications, making the U.S. military the global satellite communication industry’s biggest single customer.”³¹ Nor is this trend likely to abate, for it is part of the current U.S. national space policy for the government to “[p]urchase and use United States commercial space capabilities and services, to the maximum practical extent under existing law, when such capabilities and services meet United States Government requirements.”³² This policy includes “hosting Government capabilities on commercial spacecraft ... leveraging satellite servicing or on-orbit manufacturing, and public-private partnerships.”³³

Under the historical procurement model, contractors who sold a satellite bus or rocket to the government were insulated from concerns about getting caught up in international conflict. But now, nearly every satellite in orbit today is “dual use,” meaning that it can perform both military and civilian functions.³⁴ A foreign adversary targeting such a satellite would find it difficult or impossible to target just the military systems without also interfering with its commercial uses. Space contractors that retain ownership and operational responsibility for the space assets involved in government contracts are directly exposed to risk of damage at the hands of those who wish to interfere with the military services that they facilitate.

Some of the large, well-funded contractors may be able to stomach this risk for the chance to capitalize the contract prize, but there are other potential providers that could not place an expensive satellite in space without greater assurance that their investment would be protected.³⁵ Since it is the general policy of the federal acquisition system to provide opportunities for smaller firms to win contracts³⁶ and since doing so ensures a field of competitive and thus cost-efficient contracting options, it is crucial that even smaller space providers have access to sufficient methods of risk-mitigation.

²⁷ *Ibid.*

²⁸ *Ibid.*

²⁹ See Bourbonnière, M. (2004). Law of armed conflict (LOAC) and the neutralisation of satellites or *ius in bello satellitis*. *Journal of Conflict & Security Law*, 9(1), 43–69. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jcsl/kri002>.

³⁰ Mountin, S. M. (2014). The legality and implications of intentional interference with commercial communications satellite signals. *International Law Studies*, 90, 101–197. <https://digital-commons.usnwc.edu/ils/vol90/iss1/12/>.

³¹ *Ibid.* at 114.

³² The White House. (2020, December 9). *National space policy of the United States of America* (p. 20). <https://trumpwhitehouse.archives.gov/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/National-Space-Policy.pdf>.

³³ *Ibid.*

³⁴ Mountin, *supra* note 35.

³⁵ Kisiel, E. C. (2024, August 21). Indemnification for commercial space services vendors. *Public Contract Law Journal*, 53(3). https://www.americanbar.org/groups/public_contract_law/resources/journal/2024-spring/indemnification-commercial-space-services-vendors/.

³⁶ FAR 19.201(a) (2025) (“It is the policy of the Government to provide maximum practicable opportunities in its acquisitions to small business, veteran-owned small business, service-disabled veteran-owned small business, HUBZone small business, small disadvantaged business, and women-owned small business concerns. Such concerns must also have the maximum practicable opportunity to participate as subcontractors in the contracts awarded by any executive agency, consistent with efficient contract performance ...”).

2.3. *Third-Party Liability*

The final category of risk is the risk of incurring third-party liability. Given the extreme technical precision required to place anything in space, the high rate of failure of space technology comes as no surprise. Of the 4325 space missions that took place between 1957 and mid-way through August of 2020, “339 (7.84%) have failed completely, 102 (2.36%) have failed partially, and 4 (0.09%) have failed before the launch.”³⁷ These rates significantly outpace the rate of accidents for aircraft.³⁸

Since the nature of orbits makes it such that anything in space necessarily traces a worldwide path, the impacts of these failures are far-flung. With orbital paths that cross overhead of population centers and rocket bodies that are large enough to survive re-entry, there is a near ever-present danger around the world that an orbital launch could cause significant harm on the ground.³⁹

Even before space technology reaches the launch pad, it can still pose a risk to humans. Hypergolic fuel, a type of rocket fuel used in a wide range of space operations in the past and the present, is favored for being an efficient and low-cost means of rocket propulsion, but it is highly toxic, corrosive and unstable.⁴⁰ An accident involving these substances would have “a massive environmental impact on all life in the surrounding area” and would also “require extensive & hazardous cleanup operations.”⁴¹ Orbital rockets use a wide range of fuels, not all of which are as volatile as hypergolics, but the combustive nature of all chemical propulsion inherently creates the risk of damage.

Space technology also frequently fails while in flight, often in spectacular and deadly fashion. The history of orbital rockets is littered with debris from explosive accidents. Some of the more notable instances include the Space Shuttle Challenger in 1986, the Ariane 5 in 1996, the Delta II in 1997, the Antares in 2014 and the SpaceX Falcon 9 in 2016.⁴² More recently, in March of 2025, an experimental rocket flown by SpaceX exploded over the Gulf of Mexico, flinging metallic debris over a wide swath of ocean near the Bahamas and the Florida coast.⁴³ Falling space debris can generate significant liability for a space operator. When a USSR nuclear satellite re-entered the atmosphere above Canada in 1978, the debris affected a total area of 124,000 square kilometers.⁴⁴ For claims arising out of the damage caused by the wreckage and by the radioactive contamination, the USSR agreed to pay a multi-million dollar settlement.⁴⁵

³⁷ Nikolaos Sapountzoglou et al., *A Bibliometric Analysis of Risk Management Methods in the Space Sector*, 10 J. SPACE SAFETY ENG’G 13 (2023). It is worth noting, however, that the last six years have seen a remarkable increase in rocket success in orbital launch rockets, especially from SpaceX. If data from these years were included in these numbers, it would undoubtedly change these numbers significantly. Yet this study still goes to show the difficult odds that have faced space companies for the majority of the history of spaceflight.

³⁸ Int’l Air Transp. Ass’n, *2023 Safety Performance Summary* (Feb. 28, 2024) (finding an accident rate of “(one accident for every 1.26 million flights” among all flights worldwide for the year 2023).

<https://www.iata.org/en/pressroom/2024-releases/2024-02-28-01/>.

³⁹ See Michael Byers et al., *Unnecessary Risks Created by Uncontrolled Rocket Reentries*, 6 NATURE ASTRONOMY 1093 (2022) (describing the problem posed by the uncontrolled re-entry of large, discarded rocket bodies).

⁴⁰ Wessels, W. (2023, January). *Hypergolic rocket fuel – A double-edged sword*. Headed for Space. <https://headedforspace.com/using-hypergolic-rocket-fuel/>.

⁴¹ *Ibid.*

⁴² Wessels, W. (2025, April 7). *Why orbital rockets sometimes explode before or during launch*. Headed for Space. <https://headedforspace.com/why-rockets-explode/>.

⁴³ Wall, M. (2025, March 7). *Watch fiery SpaceX Starship Flight 8 debris rain down over the Bahamas (video)*. Space.com.

<https://www.space.com/space-exploration/launches-spacecraft/watch-fiery-spacex-starship-flight-8-debris-rain-down-over-the-bahamas-video>.

⁴⁴ M. Pietkiewicz, *The “Liability Convention” in a Clash with Practice – Example of the “Kosmos 954” Satellite*, 97 STUDIA IURIDICA 53 (2023).

⁴⁵ *Ibid.* at 64.

As space technology continues to grow in prevalence and applications, the likelihood that third parties will be affected will undoubtedly grow as well. Plainly, the increasing rate of orbital launches globally creates a stronger likelihood of casualty on the ground caused by falling rocket parts.⁴⁶ There is also the growing risk that collisions with space debris will expose operators to liability if they fail to adequately guard against such hazards.⁴⁷ Though the nascent industry of space mining is not yet so developed as to generate a notable likelihood of third-party liability, it is clear that companies entering this market will face considerable questions about third-party liability on environmental grounds.⁴⁸

In some circumstances, space contractors are legally obligated to carry liability insurance. For example, under the Commercial Space Launch Act, a launch provider or company engaged in re-entry activities must secure a certain amount of insurance or demonstrate financial responsibility by other means.⁴⁹ To the extent that a third-party claim exceeds the amount covered by the requisite amount of insurance, the federal government indemnifies the contractor up to \$1.5 billion (adjusted for inflation).⁵⁰ Congress has also authorized NASA to “provide liability insurance for any user of a space vehicle to compensate all or a portion of claims by third parties for death, bodily injury, or loss of or damage to property resulting from activities carried on in connection with the launch, operations, or recovery of the space vehicle.”⁵¹

3. SOURCES OF INSURANCE AND INDEMNIFICATION

3.1. *The Marketplace*

Privately provided insurance represents an adequate solution to some but not all of these sources of risk. Satellite insurance has seen significant development in its short history. In the early history of spaceflight, satellites were often experimental or military in nature.⁵² This made private insurance impractical, and the risk of loss was retained by the government and space agencies.⁵³ Today, with the falling cost of orbital launches and the prevalence of commercial space companies, private satellite insurers have coalesced into “a relatively small but international community within the insurance industry.”⁵⁴

There are several characteristics of the space insurance industry that prevent space insurance from growing and expanding its coverage capabilities. First, the same complex technological challenges of operating in space that make the enterprise difficult for commercial space firms make it difficult for insurers to characterize and forecast the risks involved.⁵⁵ As the technology becomes more proven, it certainly will be easier to predict risk levels. Nonetheless, it is also certain that space firms will continue to innovate in ways that create novel sources of risk.

⁴⁶ Carmen Pardini & Luciano Anselmo, *On the Need to Assess and Mitigate the Risk from Uncontrolled Re-entries of Artificial Space Objects in View of the Current and Future Developments in Space Activities*, 219 ACTA ASTRONAUTICA 662 (2024) (forecasting an increase in the annual casualty rate from re-entering space hardware to increase to 20% in the near future), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2024.03.057>.

⁴⁷ Hugh G. Lewis, Graham G. Swinerd & Richard J. Newland, *The Space Debris Environment: Future Evolution*, 120 AERONAUTICAL J. 1343 (2016).

⁴⁸ Samson Albert S., *Environmental Protection in Outer Space: Legal Challenges in Regulating Space Debris and Extraterrestrial Mining on the Moon and Mars*, 3 INT’L J. SPACE L. & POL’Y 74, 82 (2025).

⁴⁹ 14 C.F.R. §440 (2025).

⁵⁰ *Ibid.* at §440.19.

⁵¹ 51 U.S. § 20138 (2025).

⁵² Manikowski, P., & Weiss, M. A. (2013). The satellite insurance market and underwriting cycles. *Geneva Risk & Insurance Review*, 38(2), 148–152. <https://doi.org/10.1057/grir.2013.2>.

⁵³ *Ibid.*

⁵⁴ *Ibid.*

⁵⁵ *Ibid.*

Second, the pool of activities through which a space insurer can mitigate potential risk is still small. The number of satellites in orbit has greatly expanded since the time of Sputnik. In July of 2024, it was reported that there were as many as 12,994 operational satellites in orbit.⁵⁶ A significant percentage of these satellites are privately owned (with SpaceX alone operating more than 6,000 in its Starlink constellation and launching more satellites every day).⁵⁷ However, satellite insurance still operates with a much smaller risk pool than insurers in the car insurance market, for example, which might have millions of individual policyholders. Moreover, operators of large constellations (like Starlink), which own a huge fraction of the satellites in orbit, tend to address risk with system redundancy instead of commercial insurance, further reducing the field of customers for satellite insurance. For other kinds of space technology, like lunar landers, the list of operators is very short indeed: only a handful of companies have attempted a soft landing on the lunar surface.⁵⁸

Third, the secretive nature of defense contracts for space platforms or services interferes with the ability to secure insurance from the market. Launch contracts for defense agencies, for example, often involve highly classified payloads.⁵⁹ The launch provider may not be able to disclose the exact nature and function of the payload or even the timing or location of its launch,⁶⁰ making private insurers reticent or unwilling to extend coverage.⁶¹

Commercial solutions are readily available for many types of missions and flavors of liability.⁶² While commercial insurance is struggling, in some instances, to keep up with the innovative, risk-hungry activities of the “New Space” cadre of operators (for example, in the realm of human space flight), private insurance remains the backbone method of protecting most operations in space.⁶³

The standard policy available on the market for satellites is for comprehensive coverage, meaning that it will insure against all kinds of damage except for those which the contract explicitly excludes.⁶⁴ A prominent exclusion in these contracts, however, is one that denies coverage for hostile acts.⁶⁵ These exclusions typically deny coverage for damage caused by sovereigns or their agents in the course of international conflict.⁶⁶ There is yet some uncertainty about how such exclusions in insurance contracts

⁵⁶ Wilson, D. (2024, July 18). *Revealed: Number of operational satellites in orbit, 2024*. CEOWORLD Magazine. <https://ceoworld.biz/2024/07/18/revealed-number-of-operational-satellites-in-orbit-2024/>.

⁵⁷ *Ibid.*

⁵⁸ The Planetary Society. (n.d.). *Every mission to the Moon, ever*. <https://www.planetary.org/space-missions/every-moon-mission>.

⁵⁹ Federal Aviation Administration. (2002, April). *Liability risk-sharing regime for U.S. commercial space transportation: Study and analysis*. https://www.faa.gov/about/office_org/headquarters_offices/ast/media/faaliabilityrisksharing4-02.pdf.

⁶⁰ *Ibid.*

⁶¹ *Ibid.*

⁶² See AXA XL, *Space insurance*. <https://axaxl.com/insurance/products/space-insurance>; Marsh, *Aviation & Space: Space and Satellite Insurance*, Marsh (last visited Mar. 7, 2026), <https://www.marsh.com/en/industries/aviation-space/expertise/space.html>; Lloyd's, *Space Risk*, Lloyd's (last visited Mar. 7, 2026), <https://www.lloyds.com/about-lloyds/our-market/what-we-insure/space>.

⁶³ Michał Szwałkowski, *Risk and Insurance in the New Space Economy*, in *The Oxford Handbook of the New Space Economy* 439, 447 (2026).

⁶⁴ Kerolle, M., & Capurso, A. (2020). *How to estimate insurance coverage for cybersecurity protection for satellites: A case study*. In *Proceedings of the 71st International Astronautical Congress (IAC) – The CyberSpace Edition* (pp. 1–11).

⁶⁵ *Ibid.*

⁶⁶ Shniderman, A. B. (2019). *Prove it! Judging the hostile-or-warlike-action exclusion in cyber-insurance policies*. *Yale Law Journal Forum*, 129, 64–84. <https://www.yalelawjournal.org/forum/prove-it-judging-the-hostile-or-warlike-action-exclusion-in-cyber-insurance-policies>.

might apply to the realm of cyber-conflict.⁶⁷ The prevalence of these exclusions is especially worrisome for space operators due to the growing danger that cyberwarfare poses to space infrastructure. According to the Space Development Agency, cyberattacks already represent a greater danger to satellites than missile strikes.⁶⁸ Since the space insurance market is yet small and uniform in its hesitance in addressing hostile acts, a contractor must try to secure this extra coverage as a contract rider, which, if available at all, may be prohibitively expensive.

In sum, the insurance marketplace has robust solutions for some space contractors' potential for loss, but not for those caused by a foreign adversary. Thus, even if the contract is priced to include the cost of insurance premium, private insurance may not be sufficient or practical to mitigate the risks that a smaller contractor would face in contributing hardware to a program such as the "golden dome" system.

3.2. *The Federal Procurement Process*

The federal acquisition process also represents an incomplete solution. Issues of insurance and indemnification are often left out of the procurement process altogether.⁶⁹ There are a few statutory mechanisms for securing extra-contractual protection from an agency, but these mechanisms are difficult to leverage. Under the Anti-Deficiency Act, the government is prevented from entering into an agreement that would obligate it to spend more than has been appropriated for a given contract unless Congress has specifically authorized it to do so.⁷⁰ Thus, absent legislative approval, a government contract may not include an open-ended indemnification clause for the benefit of the contractor. In Public Law 85-804 (the "Act"), Congress has created a narrow authorization for exceptions to this appropriations restriction. Under this law:

[T]he President may authorize any department or agency of the Government which exercises functions in connection with the national defense, acting in accordance with regulations prescribed by the President for the protection of the Government, to enter into contracts or into amendments or modifications of contracts heretofore or hereafter made and to make advance payments thereon, without regard to other provisions of law relating to the making, performance, amendment, or modification of contracts, whenever he deems that such action would facilitate the national defense.⁷¹

In accordance with the legislative history of the Act, the government has historically used this authority to indemnify contractors for the third-party liability risks involved in "various missile programs requiring the use of highly volatile fuels."⁷²

While the authority granted to the president is nominally effective "only during a national emergency declared by Congress or the President and for six months after the termination thereof or until such earlier

⁶⁷ See *Merck & Co. v. Ace Am. Ins. Co.*, 293 A.3d 535, 551 (N.J. Super. App. Div. 2023), leave to appeal granted, 254 N.J. 506, 298 A.3d 353 (2023); leave to appeal granted, 254 N.J. 522, 298 A.3d 364 (2023) (deciding that a cyber-attack was not covered by a "hostile acts" exclusion because it "was a non-military cyberattack against an accounting software provider" that was not "linked to a military action or objective").

⁶⁸ Erwin, S. (2021, April 14). DoD space agency: Cyber attacks, not missiles, are the most worrisome threat to satellites. *SpaceNews*. <https://spacenews.com/dod-space-agency-cyber-attacks-not-missiles-are-the-most-worrisome-threat-to-satellites/>.

⁶⁹ Segal, *supra* n. 11 ("The typical satellite contract structure, and how title/risk of loss/insurance/warranty issues are handled, is not contemplated by the typical government procurement process").

⁷⁰ Pub. L. No. 97-258, 96 Stat. 877 (1982).

⁷¹ 48 C.F.R. § 52.250-1 (2024). Outside of Public Law 85-804, the military departments also have Congressional authorization to enter indemnification agreements. 10 U.S.C. 2354 (2025).

⁷² Mullen, K. P. (2002, December). *Extraordinary contractual relief under Public Law 85-804* (Briefing Papers No. 02-13).

time as Congress, by concurrent resolution, may designate,⁷³ this limitation is “meaningless” and has never been a basis for denying relief under the Act.⁷⁴ President Obama notably used authority under the Act for a USAID contract despite the fact that there was not a congressionally declared national emergency because “USAID [was] exercising functions in connection with the national defense in the course of complying with its humanitarian mandate.”⁷⁵ Undoubtedly, there are significant political constraints that underlie a presidential decision to extend seemingly preferential treatment to a specific set of contractors or to a specific industry, but the legal hurdles are apparently quite low.

In Executive Order No. 10789, President Eisenhower delegated authority to exercise power under the Act to certain federal agencies.⁷⁶ The list of agencies, revised in the years since the original executive order, now includes the Department of Defense, Department of the Treasury, Department of the Interior, of Commerce, Department of Health and Department of Agriculture, Department Human Services, Department of Transportation, Department of Energy, General Services Administration, National Aeronautics and Space Administration, Tennessee Valley Authority, Government Printing Office, and Federal Emergency Management Agency.⁷⁷

The procedures for indemnifying contractors through the Act are encoded in FAR Part 50. This allows the contracting officer to include an indemnification clause “whenever the approving official determines that the contractor shall be indemnified against unusually hazardous or nuclear risks.”⁷⁸ This clause, exemplified in FAR 52.250-1, indemnifies contractors against:

- (1) Claims (including reasonable expenses of litigation or settlement) by third persons (including employees of the Contractor) for death; personal injury; or loss of, damage to, or loss of use of property;
- (2) Loss of, damage to, or loss of use of Contractor property, excluding loss of profit; and
- (3) Loss of, damage to, or loss of use of Government property, excluding loss of profit.⁷⁹

As enticing as these terms are for a risk-wary space contractor, there are several statutory requirements that limit their application. First, the contract must involve activities that are “unusually hazardous or nuclear.”⁸⁰ While nuclear technology may soon be used in space,⁸¹ most space contractors will continue to only qualify for this kind of indemnification if they can demonstrate that the activity in question fits into the “unusually hazardous” category. The Air Force Identification Guide emphasizes the need for a contractor to distinguish between activities that are merely “hazardous” and those that are “unusually” hazardous.⁸² While “the manufacturing, storing, loading, or burning of jet aircraft fuel is hazardous” because “there is a possibility for explosion resulting in death and property damage,” the use of rocket propellants “is unusually hazardous” because “solid propellants are highly volatile and their explosive

⁷³ 50 U.S.C.A. § 1435 (2025).

⁷⁴ Prince, & Garland. (2022, October 26). *Presentation on P.L. 85-804* (Defense Acquisition University, p. 49). [https://www.dau.edu/sites/default/files/Migrate/EventAttachments/727/2022%2010%2026%20DAU%20P.L.%2085-804%20Presentation%20\(Prince%20%20Garland\).pdf](https://www.dau.edu/sites/default/files/Migrate/EventAttachments/727/2022%2010%2026%20DAU%20P.L.%2085-804%20Presentation%20(Prince%20%20Garland).pdf).

⁷⁵ 79 Fed. Reg. 68,757 (Nov. 18, 2014) (authorizing the exercise of authority under Public Law 85-804).

⁷⁶ Exec. Order No. 10,789, 3 C.F.R. 426 (1954–1958), reprinted in 23 Fed. Reg. 8897 (Nov. 15, 1958).

⁷⁷ Mullen, *supra* n. 61, at 4.

⁷⁸ 48 C.F.R. § 50.104-4 (2024).

⁷⁹ *Id.* at § 52.250-1 (2024).

⁸⁰ *Id.* at § 50.104-4 (2024).

⁸¹ Foust, J. (2025, April 8). *Space nuclear power at a crossroads as industry pushes for steady investment*. SpaceNews. <https://spacenews.com/space-nuclear-power-at-a-crossroads-as-industry-pushes-for-steady-investment/>.

⁸² U.S. Air Force. (2018, February 15). *Indemnification guide for unusually hazardous or nuclear risks* (Rev. A, originally issued July 7, 1997, p. 3). On file with the U.S. Department of the Air Force.

potential is several times greater than jet fuel.”⁸³ The FAR provisions regarding indemnification, on the other hand, “offer very few elaborations” and “the language of the regulations . . . is not subject to judicial review in the usual sense, because the grant or denial of a contractual indemnity is not subject to judicial review.”⁸⁴ Thus, a space contractor might not be able to reliably predict how the legal contours of the “unusually hazardous” requirement will apply to their operations.⁸⁵

Perhaps a satellite that is a valuable military target and is easily targeted by foreign adversaries is legally engaged in unusually hazardous activity by virtue of its sheer likelihood of being destroyed. But predicting if and how international conflict will affect a contractor’s space assets is difficult to predict and thus difficult for a contractor to demonstrate to a contracting officer or higher agency leadership when requesting protection under the Act.

Returning to the “golden dome” hypothetical, it is not clear how a satellite engaged in looking for enemy missiles would fit into the framework of P.L. 85-804. Arguably, space operations are inherently “hazardous,” but whether they can be classified as “unusually so” is a difficult question. The legislative history of the Act indicates that Congress was specifically concerned about the exposure of contractors to unrestricted liability.⁸⁶ Moreover, the Act has historically been used in contracts for products or services that entail a higher risk of generating third-party claims.⁸⁷ Even considering the orbital collisions and uncontrolled re-entries, a satellite in orbit is unlikely to subject its operator to the kind of expansive third-party liability that Congress had in mind.⁸⁸ Indeed, a contractor with a valuable orbital asset is likely to be far more motivated by the risk of damage to the satellite itself. But those seeking protection against their own loss will not be able to find much of use in the historical applications of the Act.

Second, there are significant procedural hurdles that beset a request for protection under the Act. The authority to insert this clause may be “exercised only by the Secretary or Administrator of the agency concerned, the Public Printer, or the Chairman of the Board of Directors of the Tennessee Valley Authority.”⁸⁹ The requirement of high-level approval slows down the completion of the contract. For example, the Navy leadership only reviews requests under the Act for nuclear indemnification on an annual basis, significantly constraining the project timeline for some contractors.⁹⁰ Also, the authority conferred by the Act may legally only be used as a last resort when other legal authority for indemnification is not applicable.⁹¹ This requirement further adds to a contractor’s procedural burden.

⁸³ Federal Aviation Administration, *Liability Risk-Sharing Regime for U.S. Commercial Space Transportation: Study and Analysis*, FAA 5-9 (Apr. 2002), https://www.faa.gov/about/office_org/headquarters_offices/ast/media/faaliabilityrisksharing4-02.pdf.

⁸⁴ Administrative Conference of the U.S. (1988, June 9). *Federal government indemnification of government contractors* (Recommendation 88-2). <https://www.acus.gov/sites/default/files/documents/1988-02%20Federal%20Government%20Indemnification%20of%20Government%20Contractors.pdf>.

⁸⁵ See Kisiel, *supra* n. 40, at 13 (“While there is precedent, absent a regulatory determination that space activities are ultrahazardous, indemnification would likely require statutory implementation to ensure the availability of funding based on the scope of potential indemnification”).

⁸⁶ Tolan, P. E., Jr. (2003). Environmental liability under Public Law 85-804: Keeping the ordinary out of extraordinary contractual relief. *Public Contract Law Journal*, 32, 215–222.

⁸⁷ *Id.* at 227.

⁸⁸ Parks, J. (2024, September 4). *How often do satellites crash back to Earth and are there dangers in their return?* Discover Magazine. <https://www.discovermagazine.com/the-sciences/how-often-do-satellites-crash-back-to-earth-and-are-there-dangers-in-their>.

⁸⁹ 48 C.F.R. § 50.102-1 (2024).

⁹⁰ U.S. Government Accountability Office. (2024, March 7). *Defense contracting: DOD should take actions to improve its use of indemnification authority* (GAO-24-106403). <https://www.gao.gov/assets/d24106403.pdf>.

⁹¹ FAR 50.101- 2(b)(2); *see also* FAR 50.102-3(b)(2).

Third, authority under the Act technically only extends to contracts that “facilitate the national defense.”⁹² However, like the “state of emergency” requirement, this does not often pose a problem. The FAR outlines several circumstances in which a finding of facilitation of the nation defense is “automatic”: when the relief is granted due to the correction of a mistake, an amendment caused by government action, or based on an information agreement.⁹³ Even where an “automatic” finding is not provided by the FAR, it can generally be established merely by showing that a benefit will flow to the government.⁹⁴ When the purpose of the contract, however, is “to demonstrate technologies needed to lower purely commercial risk and lead to a commercial vehicle designed to meet the needs of the commercial marketplace, a national defense link cannot be used.”⁹⁵

In sum, P. L. 85-804 is too riddled with substantive and procedural requirements to be a reliable means of protecting space contractors from damage caused by foreign adversaries. However, it should also be briefly noted that NASA has statutory authority to establish separate risk-sharing schemes. Specifically, Section 305 of the NASA Transition Authorization Act of 2017 (P.L. 115-10) provides NASA discretion to indemnify contractors providing launch services and re-entry services against successful claims by third parties for death, bodily injury, or loss of or damage to property ... These claims may originate from launch services and reentry services carried out under the contract that the contract defines as unusually hazardous or nuclear in nature.⁹⁶

Since this authority is restricted to launch and re-entry operations and since those operations must still be “unusually hazardous or nuclear in nature,” this authorization does not meaningfully expand the availability of indemnification beyond what is already available under the Act.⁹⁷ More importantly, it does not give an agency authority to insure contractors for their own loss, which, as previously demonstrated, is a significant concern.

4. RECOMMENDATION

Of the three species of risk that a space contractor might face (financial loss from misadventure, from interference from foreign adversaries, and from third-party liability), there are robust solutions in the marketplace and in the current procurement process to handle all but one. Because of the unwillingness of commercial insurers to expand coverage to hostile acts and because of the narrow scope and uncertain application of P.L. 85-804, contractors who operate dual-use technology in space are insufficiently protected against first-party losses caused by foreign interference.

To remove this hurdle for space contractors, Congress should consider granting new statutory authority to agencies so that they may offer space contractors expanded indemnification against these potential losses. Edward Kisiel made a similar recommendation, writing in the ABA Public Contract Law Journal:

The federal government should indemnify vendors who suffer losses from adversarial action since a commercial spacecraft’s status as a military contractor asset makes it a target for adversarial action ... Indemnification from the U.S.

⁹² P.L. 85-804, 72 Stat. 972 (1958).

⁹³ Mullen, *supra* n. 61, at 6.

⁹⁴ *Id.*

⁹⁵ Federal Aviation Administration. (2002, April). *Liability risk-sharing regime for U.S. commercial space transportation: Study and analysis* (pp. 5–9). https://www.faa.gov/about/office_org/headquarters_offices/ast/media/faaliabilityrisksharing4-02.pdf.

⁹⁶ National Aeronautics & Space Administration. (n.d.). *NASA Federal Acquisition Regulation Supplement (NFS) 1850.104-371(a)*. <https://www.hq.nasa.gov/office/procurement/regs/NFS.pdf>.

⁹⁷ See also 50 U.S.C. § 21038 (2025).

Government would reduce financial risk for vendors seeking to do business with the Department of Defense and other space agencies.”⁹⁸

Kisiel argues for expanded indemnification that is “informed by international and domestic space law.”⁹⁹ He suggests that the private market serves as a partial solution, but does not evaluate the limitations of the private market nor the current slate of options for indemnification through the procurement process.¹⁰⁰ Regardless, the insight that “the military’s increasing reliance on commercial industry for satellite communications and imagery services creates added risk that an adversary will disrupt services or damage systems” and that “[c]ommercial providers do not currently have good legal recourse for this contingency” is well-founded.¹⁰¹

It might be argued that the government should not expand indemnification to contractors because it would impede the development of the private insurance realm. This concern could be addressed through the structure of the statutory authorization. It could, for example, take inspiration from the Price-Anderson Act. This Act, which is in part designed to “remove[] the deterrent to private sector participation in nuclear activities presented by the threat of potential liability claims following a large accident,” requires that certain Department of Energy Contractors maintain the maximum amount of insurance that is available through private providers.¹⁰² Currently, the maximum amount is \$500 million per nuclear site.¹⁰³ The federal government then indemnifies any liability beyond this amount.¹⁰⁴ Though the Price-Anderson Act currently only protects nuclear contractors for third-party liability, the model could be re-fashioned for certain first-party loss by space contractors.

Notably, the Act has not stifled the development of the private market for nuclear operator insurance. Rather, because there is a threshold of expense at which the Act does not operate, it has “enabled insurers to provide stable, high-quality coverage for nuclear risks.”¹⁰⁵ Thus, a space contractor indemnification system that only addresses the risk that the private insurance market is yet to reach could facilitate the private insurance market while still protecting important government contractors.

There are several reasons why the federal government is in a better position to bear the risk of certain space activities than private space firms. First, this allocation of risk would better align with the growing body of international space law. Returning to the hypothetical contractor that operates a satellite in a constellation forming part of the “golden dome,” if a foreign adversary damaged such a satellite, the contractor’s legal recourses would be sparse. The feasibility of suing another nation in a United States court is curtailed by domestic laws such as the Foreign Sovereign Immunities Act.¹⁰⁶ The main international legal mechanism for establishing liability for harm suffered in space is the 1972 Space Liability Convention. But under this framework, only countries may bring claims against other nations, even if one of the country’s private entities suffered the harm.¹⁰⁷ Similarly, States are ultimately and

⁹⁸ Kisiel, *supra* n. 40, at 10.

⁹⁹ *Id.*

¹⁰⁰ *Id.* at 26.

¹⁰¹ *Id.* at 15.

¹⁰² American Nuclear Society, *The Price-Anderson Act*, Position Statement No. 54 (June 2024), <https://cdn.ans.org/policy/statements/docs/ps54.pdf>.

¹⁰³ Price-Anderson Act: Nuclear Power Industry Liability Limits and Compensation to the Public After Radioactive Releases (2026), <https://www.congress.gov/crs-product/IF10821>.

¹⁰⁴ *Id.*

¹⁰⁵ *Id.*

¹⁰⁶ 28 U.S. §1604 (2025).

¹⁰⁷ Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects, art. VIII, Jan. 29, 1972, 24 U.S.T. 2389, 961 U.N.T.S. 187.

internationally responsible for their national activities in space.¹⁰⁸ Regardless of the domestic arrangement between a procuring agency and contractor, it is the federal government that will be collecting and dispersing claims based on international interference with space assets. The federal government may also recoup its costs through sanctions or other international remedies.¹⁰⁹ Thus, if the government indemnifies a contractor for losses caused by a foreign party, the federal government may have avenues of recourse that a commercial firm would not be able to utilize.

Second, space contractors are in a poor position to anticipate and avoid the dangers of international conflict. Private satellite companies are understandably less informed than the US government regarding the strategies or intentions of its foreign adversaries. Nor are they often completely apprised of exactly what a U.S. agency is doing with the contractor's hardware.¹¹⁰ In other words, a space operator providing services to the United States may find itself caught in the crossfire for circumstances that it could not have anticipated or addressed through insurance. If the federal government were saddled with this risk from the outset, the government could make more efficient decisions about how to best allocate and protect investments in space infrastructure.

5. CONCLUSION

This analysis has been particularly designed to address problems that government space contractors face at present and will face in the immediate future. It is also clear that the continued development of space technology will magnify many of these problems. For decades, the United States has maintained its intention to explore other planets, with the Moon and Mars being priorities.¹¹¹ But the United States is not the only nation with such ideas: Russia and China individually and collectively plan to make use of other planets.¹¹²

When the United States inevitably calls on the assistance of the commercial space industry through the procurement process to accomplish its objectives in these distant realms, the contractors will again have to worry about the possibility of being harmed by America's competitors. If the United States were to have already implemented an effective framework for indemnifying against this risk, it would encourage contractors to continue their critical contributions to American space priorities. Perhaps someday the private market will offer potent solutions for these problems of risk in space, but until that day, the federal procurement process should ensure that these risks do not prevent commercial space operators from contributing to the activities of the United States in the final frontier.

¹⁰⁸ Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, Including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies, art. VI, Jan. 27, 1967, 18 U.S.T. 2410, 610 U.N.T.S. 205.

¹⁰⁹ Kisiel, *supra* n. 40, at 13.

¹¹⁰ Federal Aviation Administration. (2002, April). *Liability risk-sharing regime for U.S. commercial space transportation: Study and analysis*. https://www.faa.gov/about/office_org/headquarters_offices/ast/media/faaliabilityrisksharing4-02.pdf.

¹¹¹ See Wall, M. (2025, March 3). *Trump wants the US to land astronauts on Mars soon. Could it happen by 2029?* Space.com. <https://www.space.com/the-universe/mars/trump-wants-the-us-to-land-astronauts-on-mars-soon-could-it-happen-by-2029>.

¹¹² Orf, D. (2024, March 20). *China and Russia are building a nuclear reactor on the Moon—together*. Popular Mechanics. <https://www.popularmechanics.com/space/moon-mars/a60215653/russia-china-moon-nuclear-plant/>.

© The Author(s) 2026. Published by Space Court Foundation. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted reuse, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

BRIDGING LEGAL GAPS: SPACE SUSTAINABILITY AND GOVERNANCE PARTICIPATION FROM DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

PAOLA ALEJANDRA ZAMUDIO TORRES¹

ABSTRACT

The exploration and utilization of outer space are no longer the exclusive domain of a handful of technologically advanced nations. As the global space industry diversifies and commercial activities in orbit grow rapidly, there is a rising demand for inclusive, international and multidisciplinary participation in space development and governance. A more interconnected and competitive space ecosystem requires not only scientific and engineering expertise but also contributions from legal, policy, diplomatic and social fields. Within this expanding landscape, the inclusion of young professionals and emerging talent from developing regions, particularly Latin America, is crucial to building a sustainable and representative space future.

Despite global efforts to promote equity and international cooperation, professionals from Latin American countries continue to face significant barriers to entering the space sector. These challenges stem from external regulatory restrictions, such as the International Traffic in Arms Regulations (ITAR), and internal structural limitations, including insufficient investment in national space programs and education.

This paper argues that Latin American exclusion from the global space workforce is not merely a result of technical or financial limitations but of systemic legal and policy inequities that perpetuate inequality. By using space law as both a lens and a tool, it examines the intersection between international regulatory frameworks and regional institutional weaknesses to propose actionable pathways, legal reforms, policy advocacy, and educational innovation, toward a more inclusive and equitable global space sector.

KEYWORDS: Space Law, ITAR, Inclusion, Latin America, Governance, Regulation.

¹ Space Court Foundation Communication Officer, paola.zamudio@spacecourtfoundation.org

1. INTRODUCTION

The expansion of space activities in the twenty-first century has transformed outer space from a distant frontier into an active domain of human, commercial and governmental enterprise. What was once limited to a small group of technologically advanced nations is now increasingly accessible to emerging actors, including private companies, academic institutions and developing states. This unprecedented growth presents both opportunities and challenges. While the diversification of space actors reflects the democratization of access to outer space, it simultaneously exposes deep inequalities embedded in the legal, economic and political structures that are governing space activity. Latin America stands at the intersection of aspiration and limitation, expressing sustained institutional interest in participating in the global space economy while remaining constrained by systemic barriers that restrict meaningful inclusion.

The governance of outer space has historically reflected the geopolitical dynamics of the Cold War. Foundational instruments such as the 1967 *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Outer Space Treaty, OST) were designed to prevent conflict and ensure that space would remain a domain for peaceful purposes and the “benefit of all humankind.”² Yet, over half a century later, participation in space activities continues to be shaped by power inequalities. The existing legal frameworks, while universal in normative language, were negotiated in a geopolitical context dominated by technologically advanced states. As a result, although formally open to all, the operationalization of their principles has historically reflected asymmetries in capacity, access and regulatory influence.

Among the most significant barriers to truly equitable participation is the network of export control regimes, particularly the *International Traffic in Arms Regulations* (ITAR) administered by the United States.³ Initially intended to protect national security by restricting the transfer of defence technologies, ITAR and similar frameworks have had unintended consequences on international cooperation and workforce mobility.⁴ These regulations limit the participation of foreign nationals, including those from Latin American countries, whether in research collaborations, commercial partnerships or even educational programs involving space technology. For many young professionals in the region, access to a practical professional exposure in the global space industry is blocked not by lack of talent or ambition, but by the intersection of nationality and policy.

However, the exclusion of Latin American professionals from the space sector cannot be explained solely through external legal restrictions. Internal structural limitations that include inconsistent national space policies, limited funding for research and education, as well as fragmented institutional coordination, have reinforced the region’s dependence on foreign technology and expertise. *Mexico’s Agencia Espacial Mexicana* (AEM), for example, has made strides through initiatives such as AztechSat-1 and Misión Colmena, yet its capacity remains limited by budgetary and legislative gaps.⁵ Other countries in the region, such as Brazil, Argentina and Colombia, face similar constraints: strong academic interest and notable achievements but insufficient policy continuity.

This dual dynamic, external exclusion and internal limitation create a complex ecosystem of partial participation. Latin America is neither absent nor fully integrated; it occupies a position within the global

² United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs (UNOOSA), *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies*, UNTS 610, 1967. United Nations. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/outerspacetreaty.html>.

³ U.S. Department of State, Directorate of Defense Trade Controls. (n.d.). *International Traffic in Arms Regulations (ITAR)*, 22 C.F.R. Parts 120–130. https://www.pmdc.state.gov/ddtc_public?id=ddtc_public_portal_itar_landing.

⁴ United States Code, *Arms Export Control Act* (22 U.S.C. 2778).

⁵ Agencia Espacial Mexicana (AEM), “Misión Colmena and AztechSat-1 Projects,” 2022, Government of Mexico.

space economy. In the context of the United Nations Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (COPUOS)⁶ and emerging initiatives such as the Agencia Latinoamericana y Caribeña del Espacio (ALCE),⁷ there is growing recognition that the region’s participation must evolve from observer to contributor. This requires not only technological investment but also the reconstruction of legal and policy frameworks that facilitate inclusion, transparency and cooperation.

This article argues that the persistent marginalization of Latin American professionals in the global space industry is rooted in structural legal inequalities that can and must be addressed through deliberate reform and multilateral collaboration. By analysing the intersection between export control regulations such as ITAR and the institutional limitations of Latin American space programs, the paper seeks to identify concrete legal pathways for inclusion. The study proposes that this diversity and accessibility in the space workforce are not just for ethical purposes but also strategic necessities to have long-term sustainability and true legitimacy of space governance.

The structure of the article reflects this analytical progression. Section II will contextualize the evolution of space governance and the global disparities it continues to create. Section III will examine the impact of export control regimes on talent mobility and innovation. Section IV will address the internal structural challenges within Latin America’s national and regional frameworks. Section V will advance legal and policy recommendations to strengthen cooperation. Finally, the conclusion will synthesize the findings and reaffirm the need to construct a more inclusive and representative global space order.

Ultimately, the aim of this paper is to bridge the gap between aspiration and access, to demonstrate that the future of space governance must not only be technologically advanced but also socially equitable.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a qualitative doctrinal and comparative legal methodology to examine structural inequalities affecting Latin American participation in the global space sector. First, it undertakes a doctrinal analysis of foundational space law instruments, including the Outer Space Treaty (1967), the 1972 *Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects* (Liability Convention) and related soft-law mechanisms developed under the auspices of COPUOS. This analysis focuses on the interpretation of principles such as “benefit of all countries,” non-appropriation, and state responsibility, assessing their normative implications for equitable participation.

Second, the paper conducts a comparative regulatory assessment of export control regimes, with particular emphasis on the United States’ ITAR, while referencing the European Union’s Dual-Use Regulation and Canada’s export control framework. This comparative approach evaluates how these regimes’ structures access space-related technologies and affect workforce mobility.

Third, the research incorporates a regional institutional analysis of selected Latin American states, including Mexico, Brazil, and Argentina, examining national space agencies, policy continuity, funding structures and legislative development. Rather than providing an exhaustive empirical survey, the study identifies representative structural patterns that illustrate broader regional challenges.

⁶ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs (UNOOSA), *Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (COPUOS): Mandate and activities overview*. 2023 United Nations. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/copuos/index.html>.

⁷ Agencia Latinoamericana y Caribeña del Espacio (ALCE), “Founding Agreement,” Mexico City, 2021. <https://www.gob.mx/alce>.

By combining doctrinal interpretation with regulatory comparison and institutional assessment, the article seeks to demonstrate that Latin American exclusion is not merely technical or economic but embedded in legal and governance architectures that shape access to participation.

3. BACKGROUND

3.1. *Structural foundations of Space governance*

The legal framework that governs outer space was conceived in an era when only two nations, the United States and the Soviet Union, possessed the technological capacity to reach it. As such, the foundational treaties reflect the geopolitical problems and strategic priorities of the Cold War, not the plural and commercialized system that characterizes space activity today. The Outer Space Treaty (OST) enshrined fundamental principles such as the peaceful use of outer space, the prohibition of national appropriation and the idea that exploration “shall be carried out for the benefit and in the interests of all countries.”⁸ Despite its universalist rhetoric, the practical implementation of these principles has historically privileged technologically advanced states, leaving limited room for participation by emerging space nations.

Beyond its aspirational language, Article I of the Outer Space Treaty establishes that outer space “shall be carried out for the benefit and in the interests of all countries, irrespective of their degree of economic or scientific development.” This clause embeds a principle of formal equality within international space law. However, the Treaty does not define mechanisms to ensure distributive access to technological capacity. Similarly, Article VI establishes state responsibility for national activities in outer space, including those conducted by non-governmental entities, thereby reinforcing state-centric control over access and supervision⁹. The combination of universal entitlement and state-based authorization creates a structural tension: participation is legally open to all states, yet practically mediated by national regulatory capacity and technological infrastructure.

The body of international space law emerged through a series of treaties negotiated under the auspices of the United Nations Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (COPUOS) and administered by the United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs (UNOOSA). These include the Outer Space Treaty (1967), the 1968 *Agreement on the Rescue of Astronauts, the Return of Astronauts and the Return of Objects Launched into Outer Space* (Rescue Agreement), the Liability Convention (1972), the 1976 *Convention on Registration of Objects Launched into Outer Space* (Registration Convention) and the 1979 *Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Moon Agreement).¹⁰ While the first three instruments achieved almost universal acceptance, the Moon Agreement, which was intended to operationalize the principle of space as the “common heritage of humankind”, was largely rejected by major space powers¹¹. Its limited ratification revealed the tension between ideals of shared benefit and the realities of national and commercial interests.

⁸ United Nations. (1967). *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies (Outer Space Treaty)*. United Nations Treaty Series, 610. https://treaties.un.org/doc/Treaties/1967/10/19671010%2002-44%20AM/Ch_XXIV_01.pdf.

⁹ United Nations (1967) *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies (Outer Space Treaty)*. Articles I, VI

¹⁰ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (2017). *Treaties and principles on outer space and related resolutions of the General Assembly*. United Nations. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties.html>.

¹¹ International Institute of Space Law. (2019). *The Moon Agreement: 40 years later*. In *Proceedings of the International Institute of Space Law 2019* (pp. 321–330). Eleven International Publishing.

Over time, the practical governance of space shifted from multilateral treaties to soft law mechanisms such as guidelines, principles and codes of conduct. Instruments like the *Long-Term Sustainability Guidelines of Outer Space Activities* (UNOOSA, 2019), while significant, remain non-binding and dependent on voluntary implementation.¹² This transition has further shown disparities: states with advanced regulatory capacity and technical infrastructure can comply and contribute meaningfully, while developing nations struggle to keep pace. Consequently, the formal equality promised by international law often conceals functional inequality, a division between those who make the rules and those who are expected to follow them.

The limited ratification of the Moon Agreement further illustrates the gap between redistributive aspirations and geopolitical realities. While the Agreement sought to operationalize the “common heritage of humankind” principle, major spacefaring nations declined participation, limiting its normative force.¹³ This reluctance underscores the difficulty of translating universalist principles into binding redistributive mechanisms within space governance.

3.2. *Global participation and regional asymmetries*

Despite the increasing number of countries involved in space activities, participation remains highly uneven. According to UNOOSA’s Index of Space Objects Launched into Outer Space, over 90 percent of all satellites currently in orbit originate from just five jurisdictions: the United States, Russia, China, the European Union and India.¹⁴ Meanwhile, only a small fraction of developing nations have the capacity to independently design, build or operate space systems.

Latin America’s representation in the institutional architecture of global space governance mirrors this imbalance. Within COPUOS, the region is represented by a limited number of states, often constrained by small delegations and restrictions of budget.

This structural asymmetry perpetuates a cycle of dependence: developing countries rely on external partnerships for access to satellite services, data and launch capabilities, often under contractual terms that reinforce inequality. The privatization of space, marked by the rise of commercial actors such as SpaceX and Blue Origin, has further complicated this dynamic by introducing a new layer of regulatory disparity between states with strong domestic industries and those dependent on international cooperation for even minimal participation.

In this global landscape, Latin America’s efforts to develop a coherent regional strategy are necessary. Historically, space activity in the region has been characterized by fragmentation, with each country pursuing its own limited agenda. Brazil and Argentina, for instance, have long maintained national programs through institutions. These countries have achieved notable milestones, including the development of Earth observation satellites and bilateral cooperation agreements with the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) and the European Space Agency (ESA).¹⁵

¹² United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (2019). *Guidelines for the long-term sustainability of outer space activities*. United Nations. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/space4sdgs/long-term-sustainability.html>.

¹³ United Nations. (1979). *Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies*. 1363 U.N.T.S. 3.

¹⁴ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (2024). *Index of objects launched into outer space*. United Nations. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/spaceobjectregister/index.html>.

¹⁵ Comisión Nacional de Actividades Espaciales (CONAE). (2015). *SAC-D/Aquarius mission overview*. Government of Argentina. <https://www.conae.gov.ar/index.php/english/sac-d-aquarius>, Instituto Nacional de Pesquisas Espaciais (INPE). (2021). *Amazonia-1 satellite launch*. Government of Brazil. <https://www.gov.br/inpe/pt-br>.

Mexico's *Agencia Espacial Mexicana* (AEM), established in 2010, represents another important milestone in the regional landscape. While its initiatives, such as AztechSat-1 and Misión Colmena,¹⁶ demonstrate innovation and international collaboration, the agency faces persistent challenges related to budget limitations and institutional continuity.

Recognizing these challenges, Latin American states launched the *Agencia Latinoamericana y Caribeña del Espacio* (ALCE) in 2021 with Mexico and Argentina playing leading roles. ALCE's creation marked a historic step toward regional coordination and collective representation in global forums. Its objectives include promoting technological development, strengthening educational and research programs, and ensuring that the region's interests are represented in multilateral negotiations. However, ALCE remains in its formative stage, and its success will depend on political will, funding and the establishment of a clear legal and policy framework.¹⁷

The persistence of inequality in space governance is not merely a reflection of technical capability but of structural bias. The same geopolitical hierarchies that define access to trade, finance and technology on Earth are replicated in orbit.¹⁸ Addressing these inequities requires a renewed form of multilateralism, one that moves beyond rhetorical inclusivity to actual redistribution of access, responsibility and benefit.

For Latin America, the path forward involves asserting agency within international institutions while building internal capacity through education, research and legal harmonization. The emergence of young professionals, academic initiatives and regional collaborations offers hope for a more plural and representative governance model.

4. THE LEGAL BARRIERS: ITAR AND EXPORT CONTROL REGIMES

4.1. *ITAR and the legal architecture of export control*

Among the numerous barriers that shape global participation in the space sector, few are as influential or as controversial as ITAR. Administered by the U.S. Department of State's Directorate of Defence Trade Controls (DDTC), ITAR governs the export and temporary import of defence articles and services listed on the United States Munitions List (USML).¹⁹ Originally established under the 1976 *Arms Export Control Act* (AECA), ITAR's primary objective is to prevent the unauthorized dissemination of sensitive technologies that could threaten national security.²⁰ ITAR derives its legal authority from Section 38 of the AECA, which authorizes the President of the United States to control the export and import of defense articles and defense services in furtherance of national security and foreign policy objectives. The implementing regulations are codified in Title 22 of the *Code of Federal Regulations* (22 C.F.R. §§ 120–130). Under this framework, items listed on the United States Munitions List (USML) are subject to strict licensing requirements prior to export, re-export, or transfer to foreign persons. The regulatory scheme thus operates through a system of prior authorization, compliance obligations, and enforcement mechanisms, including civil and criminal penalties for violations.²¹

¹⁶ Agencia Espacial Mexicana. (2023). *Projects and collaborations*. Gobierno de México. <https://www.gob.mx/aem>

¹⁷ Agencia Latinoamericana y Caribeña del Espacio. (2021). *Founding declaration and statutes*. Mexico City: ALCE. <https://www.gob.mx/alce>.

¹⁸ Secure World Foundation. (2024). *Global counterspace capabilities: An open source assessment (2024 report)*. Secure World Foundation. <https://swfound.org/counterspace>.

¹⁹ U.S. Department of State, Directorate of Defense Trade Controls. (2024). *ITAR overview*. U.S. Department of State. https://www.pmdtc.state.gov/ddtc_public?id=ddtc_kb_article_page&sys_id=8f4d62f2dbb8d30044f9ff621f9619f0.

²⁰ Arms Export Control Act, 22 U.S.C. § 2778. (1976). *United States Code*. <https://uscode.house.gov/view.xhtml?req=granuleid:USC-prelim-title22-section2778>.

²¹ United States Congress. (1976). *Arms Export Control Act*, 22 U.S.C. § 2751 et seq. <https://uscode.house.gov/view.xhtml?path=/prelim@title22/chapter39&edition=prelim>.

However, the scope of ITAR extends well beyond traditional defence hardware. Because many space technologies are classified as “dual-use”, which are applicable to both civilian and military purposes, components such as propulsion systems or satellite payloads often fall within ITAR’s jurisdiction. This classification means that even benign research collaborations involving U.S. entities can trigger export control requirements²².

Crucially, ITAR defines an “export” not only as the physical shipment of goods but also as the transfer of technical data to a foreign person, even within the territory of the United States²³. Consequently, a non-U.S. citizen or permanent resident, such as a graduate student or international employee, may be restricted from accessing specific laboratories, documents, or software without a special license.

Under ITAR, the concept of “defense service” is defined broadly to include the furnishing of assistance, whether in the form of training, technical advice, or instruction to foreign persons in relation to defense articles. As a result, compliance obligations extend beyond the physical transfer of hardware to encompass intangible transfers of controlled technical data.²⁴ This regulatory design reflects a preventive approach to proliferation control, emphasizing risk mitigation through pre-authorization rather than post-facto liability.²⁵

While ITAR is grounded in legitimate national security concerns under the *Arms Export Control Act* (1976), its extraterritorial regulatory effects extend beyond traditional defense contexts. Because “exports” include the transfer of technical data to foreign persons within U.S. territory, the regime regulates access to controlled technical data based on nationality and legal status, rather than solely on the nature of the activity.

This regulatory architecture has significant implications for international workforce mobility and institutional collaboration.²⁶

The scope of ITAR has evolved over time, particularly through reforms implemented under the U.S. Export Control Reform Initiative, which sought to clarify the boundary between items regulated under the USML and those governed by the Export Administration Regulations (EAR). While certain commercial satellite components were transferred from the USML to the Commerce Control List (CCL), significant categories of space-related technologies remain subject to ITAR jurisdiction.²⁷ Consequently, space activities continue to operate within a layered export control environment in which classification determinations carry substantial legal implications for collaboration and workforce participation.

Export control regulation is not unique to the United States; several other jurisdictions maintain parallel legal frameworks governing the transfer of sensitive technologies.

²² National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. (2020). *Export control challenges associated with space technologies*. The National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/25590>

²³ U.S. Code of Federal Regulations. (2024). 22 C.F.R. § 120.17 – *Definition of export*. U.S. Government Publishing Office. <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-22/chapter-I/subchapter-M/part-120/section-120.17>

²⁴ U.S. Department of State. (2023). *International Traffic in Arms Regulations: Technical data* (22 C.F.R. § 120.33). Electronic Code of Federal Regulations. <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-22/section-120.33>

²⁵ U.S. Department of State. (2023). *International Traffic in Arms Regulations: Licensing requirements* (22 C.F.R. § 123). Electronic Code of Federal Regulations. <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-22/part-123>

²⁶ Space Policy Journal. (2022). *Export controls and the global space workforce*. *Space Policy*, 59, 101453. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2022.101453>

²⁷ U.S. Department of State. (2014). *Amendment to the International Traffic in Arms Regulations: Revision of U.S. Munitions List Category XV (Spacecraft and Related Articles)*, 79 Fed. Reg. 27180 (May 13, 2014). <https://www.federalregister.gov/documents/2014/05/13/2014-10773>.

- European Union (EU): The *EU's Dual-Use Regulation (2021/821)* governs exports of items with both civilian and military applications.²⁸ Although its implementation is more flexible than ITAR, it still imposes licensing requirements that can affect international research collaborations.
- Canada: Through its *Export and Import Permits Act (EIPA)* and the *Controlled Goods Program*, Canada regulates the transfer of defence technologies, including certain aerospace components.²⁹
- China and Russia: Both maintain stringent internal secrecy laws that limit technology sharing, though these are generally aimed at protecting state interests rather than regulating foreign cooperation.³⁰

The coexistence of multiple, non-harmonized export control regimes generates a landscape of overlapping jurisdictions that complicates compliance and discourages collaboration. For Latin American institutions attempting to engage with multiple partners, navigating this environment is a significant structural challenge that demands legal expertise and financial resources often unavailable to them.³¹

From a legal perspective, the consequences of export control regimes are not limited to transactional restrictions. Because compliance determinations are based on nationality, residency status and access to controlled data, the regulatory structure intersects directly with employment law, academic mobility, and institutional governance. Universities, research centers and private entities must implement internal compliance mechanisms, including technology control plans, restricted access facilities and nationality-based screening procedures, to ensure conformity with export control obligations.

The ripple effects of ITAR across Latin America are profound. For aspiring engineers, scientists and legal scholars, access to true experience in satellite assembly, mission design or data management is essential for professional growth. Yet these pathways are frequently closed. Cases have been documented of Latin American students admitted to U.S. graduate programs in aerospace engineering who were later restricted from laboratory access or internships in the private sector.³²

Beyond the individual level, ITAR also constrains institutional capacity. Universities in Latin America seeking to collaborate with U.S. partners often face delays, cost increases or project cancellations due to export control constraints.³³

At a broader scale, ITAR's restrictions perpetuate a form of technological dependency. By preventing the transfer of knowledge and expertise, they reinforce the existing asymmetry between spacefaring nations and developing regions. For Latin American institutions, this dynamic creates a structural tension: the region is expected to engage in global discussions on space governance and sustainability while facing limitations in accessing the technological environments where such capabilities are developed.

²⁸ European Union. (2021). *Regulation (EU) 2021/821 of the European Parliament and of the Council: Setting up a Union regime for the control of exports, transfer, brokering, technical assistance and transit of dual-use items*. Official Journal of the European Union, L206. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32021R0821>.

²⁹ Government of Canada. (2023). *Export and Import Permits Act (R.S.C., 1985, c. E-19) and Controlled Goods Program*. Government of Canada. <https://laws-lois.justice.gc.ca/eng/acts/e-19/>.

³⁰ Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS). (2022). *Global export controls and emerging technologies*. CSIS. <https://www.csis.org/analysis/global-export-controls-and-emerging-technologies>.

³¹ Secure World Foundation. (2024). *Latin America and the future of global space governance*. Secure World Foundation. https://swfound.org/media/210991/swf_latin_america_space_governance_2024.pdf.

³² American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS). (2021). *International students and ITAR restrictions*. Science & Diplomacy. <https://www.sciencediplomacy.org/article/2021/international-students-and-itar-restrictions>.

³³ Secure World Foundation. (2023). *Space sustainability and access to technology in the Global South*. Secure World Foundation. https://swfound.org/media/208881/swf_space_sustainability_global_south_2023.pdf.

5. INTERNAL CHALLENGES

5.1. Institutional and regulatory constraints

While external legal barriers such as ITAR and export control regimes constrain Latin America's access to technology, the region's internal limitations also contribute significantly to shaping the region's participation in the global space sector. Many of these constraints stem from structural issues within national institutions, ranging from fragmented policies to inadequate funding.

Only a handful of Latin American countries possess dedicated space agencies with long-term strategic plans. Brazil's INPE³⁴ and Argentina's CONAE³⁵ are notable exceptions, having developed domestic satellite programs and modest launch capabilities. Mexico's *Agencia Espacial Mexicana* (AEM), although representing an important institutional development in Mexico's space policy, still struggles to consolidate its role due to limited financial resources and high turnover in leadership.³⁶ The absence of robust national space legislation, beyond general references to scientific development or telecommunications, creates uncertainty for both domestic and international actors.³⁷ These institutional weaknesses are compounded by a lack of policy continuity. In several countries, space initiatives are sometimes implemented as short-term projects linked to specific administrations rather than long-term state policies.³⁸ As a result, transitions in government often bring abrupt changes in priorities, budget reallocations or even program cancellations. This instability erodes international confidence and discourages sustained investment from both private and foreign partners.

Furthermore, most existing legal frameworks in the region focus narrowly on telecommunications or aerospace engineering, without integrating the broader dimensions of space governance, sustainability, or international cooperation. The lack of comprehensive national space laws means that issues such as liability, registration or debris mitigation are handled on a singular case basis, resulting in a regulatory approach that is often responsive to developments rather than anticipatory.³⁹

Perhaps the most persistent challenge is the fragmentation of governance at both national and regional levels. Within individual countries, responsibilities related to space are scattered across ministries; defence, communications, education, science and technology, often with minimal coordination.⁴⁰ This bureaucratic dispersion undermines efficiency and creates legal ambiguities regarding oversight and accountability.

³⁴ Instituto Nacional de Pesquisas Espaciais (INPE). (2020). *Plano estratégico espacial 2020–2035*. Governo do Brasil. <https://www.gov.br/inpe/pt-br/assuntos/plano-estrategico-2020-2035>.

³⁵ Comisión Nacional de Actividades Espaciales (CONAE). (2021). *Plan Espacial Nacional 2021–2031*. Gobierno de Argentina. <https://www.conae.gov.ar/planes-y-programas/plan-espacial-nacional>.

³⁶ Agencia Espacial Mexicana (AEM). (2024). *Informe de actividades 2023*. Secretaría de Infraestructura, Comunicaciones y Transportes (SICT), Gobierno de México. <https://www.gob.mx/aem>.

³⁷ Hobe, S., Schmidt-Tedd, B., & Schrogl, K.-U. (2017). *Cologne Commentary on Space Law*. Carl Heymanns Verlag.

³⁸ Inter-American Development Bank (IDB). (2021). *Innovation and technology policy in Latin America: Institutional gaps and recommendations*. IDB. <https://publications.iadb.org/en/innovation-and-technology-policy-latin-america-institutional-gaps-and-recommendations>.

³⁹ Aliberti, M. (2024). *Space policies, issues and trends in 2024*. European Space Policy Institute (ESPI). <https://espi.or.at/publications/space-policies-issues-and-trends-in-2024>.

⁴⁰ Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC). (2024). *Regional innovation and space development report*. United Nations ECLAC. <https://www.cepal.org/en/publications/2024-regional-innovation-and-space-development-report>.

Regionally, cooperation efforts have been sporadic. The absence of a unified regional space policy has made it difficult to articulate common positions in international forums such as COPUOS or the International Telecommunication Union (ITU).⁴¹

This lack of coordination also hampers the region's ability to respond collectively to emerging challenges, including space debris mitigation, resource utilization and lunar governance.⁴² Without a shared vision, Latin America is frequently characterized in international policy discussions as a fragmented group of actors, rather than as a cohesive regional actor capable of contributing constructively to global debates. Ultimately, the internal barriers facing Latin America are interlinked: weak institutions limit funding, which restricts education, which in turn hinders governance. Overcoming these challenges requires more than incremental reform; it requires an assessment of how space activities are framed within national policy agendas.

Space policy can be increasingly understood not merely as a long-term aspiration but as a policy instrument supporting sovereignty, sustainability and economic development.

5.2. *Financial capacity and industrial development*

Another key obstacle lies in the region's limited financial and industrial capacity. Public funding for space programs across Latin America typically represents less than 0.05% of national Gross Domestic Product (GDP), compared to 0.5–1% in major spacefaring nations.⁴³ This disparity translates into inadequate infrastructure for research, testing and manufacturing. Without local production capabilities, countries must rely heavily on imported technologies, which in turn are subject to export restrictions and fluctuating international costs.

For comparative context, NASA's annual budget exceeds USD 25 billion⁴⁴, while the combined budgets of most Latin American space agencies represent only a fraction of this amount. Mexico's Agencia Espacial Mexicana, for instance, operates with limited autonomous funding and relies heavily on inter-ministerial coordination. Brazil's INPE and Argentina's CONAE have achieved notable technical milestones; however, sustained investment remains inconsistent relative to global leaders.⁴⁵ This financial asymmetry directly affects regulatory capacity, research continuity, and participation in multilateral negotiations.

The private sector, which has driven much of the recent global expansion in space activities, remains comparatively limited in scale in Latin America. While startups in Brazil, Argentina, and Mexico are emerging in areas such as satellite imaging, propulsion and software analytics, they face limited access to venture capital and regulatory uncertainty.⁴⁶

⁴¹ International Telecommunication Union (ITU). (2022). *Regional participation of Latin America and the Caribbean in spectrum and orbital governance*. ITU. <https://www.itu.int/en/publications/latin-america-spectrum-orbital-governance-2022>.

⁴² Comunidad de Estados Latinoamericanos y Caribeños (CELAC). (2023). *Declaración conjunta sobre cooperación científica y espacial*. CELAC. <https://celacinternational.org/documentos/declaracion-cooperacion-espacial-2023>.

⁴³ Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2023). *Government expenditure on space activities (regional data)*. OECD. <https://data.oecd.org/gga/government-expenditure-on-space.htm>.

⁴⁴ National Aeronautics and Space Administration. (2023). *NASA FY 2023 Budget Request Summary*.

⁴⁵ Comisión Nacional de Actividades Espaciales. (2023). *SAOCOM mission overview*. <https://www.conae.gov.ar>, Instituto Nacional de Pesquisas Espaciais. (2023). *CBERS program overview*. <https://www.inpe.br>.

⁴⁶ NewSpace Global. (2024). *Latin America's emerging commercial space startups*. NewSpace Global Report. <https://newspaceglobal.com/reports/latin-america-emerging-commercial-space-startups-2024>.

Moreover, there is a persistent perception gap among policymakers: space is often viewed as a luxury pursuit rather than a driver of socioeconomic development⁴⁷. This misconception hinders political will and public support for investments in the sector. A shift toward this mindset is already visible in the discourse of regional organizations. However, turning these principles into practice requires not only coordination but the creation of financial instruments, like regional funds or micro-grants, that can nurture both public and private initiatives.

6. LEGAL AND POLICY PATHWAYS FOR INCLUSION AND COOPERATION

6.1. Normative reframing and regional legal harmonization

Inclusion in the global space sector has often been framed as a policy aspiration rather than a legal obligation. However, the normative architecture of international space law, particularly the principles of benefit-sharing, peaceful use and international cooperation, provides a doctrinal basis for interpreting inclusion as a structural component of the governance framework rather than a purely discretionary objective.⁴⁸

The hierarchical structure does not fully reflect the realities of a rapidly evolving and increasingly interconnected space environment. The growing participation of non-traditional actors, including private companies, developing nations and civil society organizations, has contributed to the diversification of stakeholders involved in space activities and governance discussions.⁴⁹

Within this context, Latin America's participation in international space governance has gradually expanded. The region's diplomatic tradition, historically rooted in multilateralism, peaceful cooperation and principles of solidarity in international law provide a foundation for engagement in the development of emerging governance frameworks related to outer space activities.⁵⁰ Building upon this heritage, the region can advance the idea that sustainability, access and diversity are not peripheral concerns but the foundation of a legitimate global space order.

Regional legal harmonization represents one potential mechanism for strengthening participation. Although several Latin American states have adopted national space policies or regulatory frameworks, these instruments vary significantly in scope, institutional design and implementation capacity. The absence of standardized legal approaches across the region may therefore limit opportunities for coordinated collaboration and regulatory interoperability.⁵¹

In this context, cooperation between academic institutions, research centres and non-governmental organizations has been identified as a relevant component of capacity development in space governance. Academic and policy networks can contribute to the exchange of legal expertise, comparative regulatory analysis and policy recommendations that support the development and modernization of national space legislation.

⁴⁷ The Conversation. (2023, August). *Why Latin America's leaders still see space as a luxury*. The Conversation. <https://theconversation.com/why-latin-americas-leaders-still-see-space-as-a-luxury-210745>.

⁴⁸ Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, Including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies (Outer Space Treaty), 610 U.N.T.S. 205, opened for signature 27 January 1967, entered into force 10 October 1967, arts. I–III.

⁴⁹ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs (UNOOSA). (2023). *Space Economy Initiative and Global Trends in Space Activities*. Vienna: UNOOSA.

⁵⁰ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs (UNOOSA). (2021). *Space2030 agenda: Space as a driver for sustainable development* (A/AC.105/1208). United Nations. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/space2030agenda.html>.

⁵¹ Jakhu, R. S., Pelton, J. N., & Nyampong, Y. O. (2017). *Space Law: A Treatise*. Durham, NC: Carolina Academic Press

The effectiveness of legal and policy frameworks is closely linked to the availability of trained professionals capable of designing, implementing, and interpreting them. In this regard, the development of human capital represents an important dimension of broader efforts to strengthen participation in the global space sector.

Educational initiatives focusing on the legal, policy, and ethical dimensions of space activities have increasingly been integrated into university programs in fields such as international law, public policy, environmental governance, and international relations. Courses addressing the legal framework governing outer space, the institutional role of international organizations, and comparative space policy analysis contribute to the formation of professionals capable of navigating both technical and diplomatic aspects of space governance.

International academic cooperation has also played a role in capacity development.⁵² Scholarship programs, research exchanges, and collaborative academic initiatives involving institutions such as the International Institute of Air and Space Law (Leiden University), the McGill Institute of Air and Space Law, and the International Space University have provided opportunities for students and professionals from Latin America to engage with global networks of expertise in space law and policy. Training programs for government officials, engineers, and legal practitioners also contribute to strengthening institutional capacity. These initiatives frequently address topics such as export control compliance, technology transfer regulations, satellite data governance, and international regulatory frameworks, thereby supporting national agencies in navigating the complex legal environment surrounding space activities.⁵³

In addition to domestic capacity development, participation in multilateral forums represents an important avenue for engagement in the development of international space governance. Institutions such as the COPUOS, the International Institute of Space Law (IISL), and the International Astronautical Federation (IAF) provide platforms through which states and experts contribute to discussions on emerging regulatory challenges.

Within these forums, coalitions of developing states have occasionally sought to advance interpretations of foundational principles of international space law, including the concepts of the “province of all humankind” and the principle of non-appropriation.⁵⁴ These principles are frequently referenced in discussions concerning the governance of emerging activities such as lunar exploration, asteroid resource utilization, and long-term sustainability of outer space activities.

Regional participation in these discussions has also been supported through collaboration with international organizations such as the UNOOSA, the United Nations Institute for Disarmament Research (UNIDIR), and policy organizations including the Secure World Foundation. Engagement with these networks has contributed to research initiatives and policy discussions related to space traffic management, debris mitigation, and the peaceful use of emerging space technologies.

Through these combined efforts in capacity development, institutional cooperation and participation in multilateral governance processes, Latin American actors have increasingly engaged in the evolving architecture of international space governance.

⁵² von der Dunk, F. G. (2015). *Handbook of Space Law*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing.

⁵³ U.S. Department of State, Directorate of Defense Trade Controls. (2023). *International Traffic in Arms Regulations (ITAR)*, 22 C.F.R. §§ 120–130.

⁵⁴ Outer Space Treaty, Arts. I–II.

7. CONCLUSION

For Latin America, greater inclusion in the global space sector involves both legal and institutional transformation. It requires dismantling outdated hierarchies, strengthening institutions, and cultivating a new generation of professionals committed to shared stewardship of outer space. Yet it also requires sustained institutional commitment, the conviction that the region's perspectives, histories and values are not peripheral but essential to the future of space governance.

Through collective action, legal innovation, and sustained diplomacy, Latin America can transition from a passive participant to an active architect of global space governance. The regional's contribution may lie not only in technical development but in a renewed understanding of what cooperation in space truly means: a partnership among equals, grounded in justice, inclusivity and the belief that the exploration of the cosmos belongs to all humankind.

If the principle that outer space is the "province of all humankind"⁵⁵ is to retain normative legitimacy, its implementation must extend beyond rhetorical universality. Legal regimes governing access, supervision and cooperation must be interpreted and developed in ways that mitigate structural asymmetries rather than entrench them.

⁵⁵ Outer Space Treaty (1967), Art. I.

© The Author(s) 2026. Published by Space Court Foundation. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted reuse, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

NATIONAL AUTHORIZATION OF PRIVATE LAUNCHING ACTIVITIES: CRITICAL COMPONENTS OF A COMMERCIAL LAUNCH LICENSE FRAMEWORK

CAYLAN E. FAZIO¹

ABSTRACT

With the increase in private and government-contracted space activities, licensing is a reliable way for countries to manage authorization and continuing supervision of non-governmental actors by standardizing their compliance with international obligations while encouraging innovation in the private sector by setting expectations for engineering design, approval timelines, and procurement of capital. Emerging spacefaring countries, also under obligations to authorize their private actors, should create mechanisms to authorize their nation's non-governmental entities as multi-national launching activities become more common among the private space industry.

This article discusses how nations authorize commercial space activities through regulatory licensing. States are expected to uphold international obligations set forth by the space treaties as applied to their non-governmental actors. Authorization for non-governmental space activities can be accomplished through prohibiting them, authorizing them on a case-by-case basis, and creating standards through a licensing procedure.

Using the United States' regulations on launch and re-entry licensing found in Title 14, Chapter III of the Code of Federal Regulations as a model, together with principles derived from international space law, this report will set forth five critical components for a launch license framework to ensure international compliance and national security. Licenses must (1) be required for any private actor's launching activity which would classify the country as a launching State; (2) mandate some form of technical requirements for the launch; (3) provide a mechanism for managing financial responsibility; (4) allow for certain waivers in exceptional circumstances; and (5) be terminable by the government.

The article will also examine the United States' FAA Vehicle Operator License and the current issues in licensing space activities. Lastly, the article will discuss the path for authorizing private space activities and encouraging economic growth for emerging spacefaring countries.

KEYWORDS: Commercial launch license, Mission Authorization, Liability Convention, Emerging spacefaring nations, Space launch insurance.

¹ Cleveland State University College of Law, J.D. May 2025, Of Counsel at Yormick Law LLC; cfazio@yormicklaw.com. Written with the guidance of Dr. Mark J. Sundahl, Director of the CSU Global Space Law Center.

1. INTRODUCTION

As private space activities become more common, licensing has become a feasible way to manage authorization and continuing supervision of non-governmental actors by standardizing a country's approach to international obligations while still encouraging innovation in the private sector. Although licensing has many benefits for streamlining government operations and managing industry players, not all spacefaring countries have regulatory launch licensing procedures. Additionally, emerging spacefaring countries, which are also under the obligation to authorize their private actors, must create mechanisms and paths to authorize their nation's non-governmental entities as private space activities become more common and increasingly international.

This article will discuss how nations may authorize commercial space activities of non-governmental actors in accordance with international obligations set forth by the space treaties. Authorization for non-governmental space activities can be accomplished through prohibiting them, authorizing them on a case-by-case basis, and creating standards through a licensing procedure.

Using the United States' regulations on launch and re-entry licensing found in Title 14, Chapter III of the Code of Federal Regulations as a model, together with international space law, the discussion will set forth five critical components for a launch license framework which include: (1) that the license be required for any private actor's launching activity which would classify the country as a launching State; (2) mandating some form of technical requirements for the launch; (3) providing a mechanism for managing financial responsibility; (4) allowing for certain waivers in exceptional circumstances; and (5) termination of the licensed activity at any point. These five critical components for a launch license framework ensure international compliance and national security.

Lastly, the article will establish a path for authorizing private space activities and encouraging economic growth for emerging spacefaring countries.

2. INTERNATIONAL OBLIGATIONS

For commercial launch licensing and more generally any space activity, multilateral treaties provide the backdrop of international obligations for countries to then implement in their nation's launch regulations. State Parties must operate under the obligations of these treaties and uphold their values according to international law.

2.1. *Responsibility of Authorization and Continuing Supervision*

Article VI of the Outer Space Treaty states, "States Parties to the Treaty shall bear international responsibility for national activities in outer space."² Article VI also mandates that a State is internationally responsible for "national activities in outer space"³ regardless of whether "such activities are carried on by governmental agencies or by non-governmental entities."⁴ This means a government bears international responsibility for the space activities of its private actors. The article continues, "[t]he activities of non-governmental entities in outer space . . . shall require authorization and continuing supervision by the appropriate State Party to the Treaty."⁵

² Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies ("Outer Space Treaty") [Article VI], January 27, 1967, <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/outerspacetreaty.html>.

³ von der Dunk, Frans G. (2011). The Origins of Authorisation: Article VI of the Outer Space Treaty and International Space Law. *Space, Cyber, and Telecommunications Law Program Faculty Publications*, 6, 3-28. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/spacelaw/69>.

⁴ Outer Space Treaty, *supra note 2*, art. VI.

⁵ *Ibid.*

2.2. Responsibilities Arising from the Liability Convention

Beyond a state's obligation to authorize the space activities of its private actors, governments are also liable for damages caused by the space-related activities of their private actors.⁶ The Outer Space Treaty provides the first indication of managing liability in space. Article VII states, "[e]ach State Party to the Treaty that launches or procures the launching of an object into outer space . . . and each State Party from whose territory or facility an object is launched, is internationally liable for damage . . . [caused] by such object or its component parts on the Earth, in air space or in outer space."⁷

Later, in 1972, the Liability Convention set forth more specifications for how a country would bear international liability for damages caused by launching.⁸ In Article I, the Liability Convention defines a launching State as "a state which launches or procures the launching of a space object" or "a State from whose territory or facility a space object is launched."⁹ This text identifies four categories:¹⁰ a State that launches a space object, a State that procures the launching of a space object, a State from whose territory a space object is launched, and a State from whose facility a space object is launched.¹¹

The Liability Convention established strict liability for damages caused by space objects and launch vehicles on the surface of the Earth or in the airspace.¹² This liability is imposed upon the launching State.¹³ When there are multiple launching States, the treaty provides for joint and several liability. The convention provides means for indemnifying and exonerating for certain situations when there are multiple launching States.¹⁴ Multiple launching States are also allowed to contractually agree on how they will share liability.¹⁵

As addressed above, Article VI of the Outer Space Treaty mandates an international obligation to authorize the activities of their private actors. Article IX goes on to address the responsibility of States to act "with due regard to the corresponding interests of all other States Parties to the Treaty."¹⁶ This principle of "due regard" addresses States' obligations to mitigate risk, often prior to or during an incident. Whereas Article VII, together with the Liability Convention, sets forth the specifics of how an injured State may recover the damages caused by another State's space activities after an incident occurs. It is very important to distinguish each of these obligations to correctly identify the circumstances which trigger them and how they apply.

2.3. The Obligation to Register Space Objects

In addition to the principles of the Outer Space Treaty and the obligations of the Liability Convention, State Parties must also hold their private actors accountable for complying with *the Convention on*

⁶ Liability is one of a variety of obligations States hold regarding their private actors.

⁷ *Ibid.*, art. VII.

⁸ Larsen, P.B. (2019). Outer space: How shall the world's governments establish order among competing interests? *Washington International Law Journal*, 29(1), 27–28. <https://digitalcommons.law.uw.edu/wilj/vol29/iss1/1>.

⁹ Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects ("Liability Convention") [Article I], March 29, 1972, <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/liability-convention.html>.

¹⁰ Lee, A.Y. (2023). The Future of the Law on the Moon. *Journal of Air Law and Commerce*, 88(1), 20. <https://scholar.smu.edu/jalc/vol88/iss1/2/>.

¹¹ *Ibid.*; Liability Convention, *supra* note 9, art. I (defining a space object to "include [] component parts of a space object as well as its launch vehicle and parts thereof," and launching to "include [] attempted launching").

¹² Liability Convention, *supra* note 9, art. II.

¹³ *Ibid.*

¹⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁵ *Ibid.* (showing multiple launching states may decide how they would divide liability and may be absolved of paying damages if they can prove they are not the responsible party).

¹⁶ Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 2, art. IX.

Registration of Objects Launched into Outer Space (“Registration Convention”).¹⁷ Private companies are required to share information with their governments, which should then be recorded internationally.¹⁸

Gathering the information necessary to report the object is often part of the process a government uses to approve a space activity. However, gathering the information tends to relate more towards authorizing the activity and less to reporting the object according to the Registration Convention.

The Registration Convention mandates launching State report information to the United Nations “as soon as practicable.”¹⁹ Although registering a space object gives a country internationally recognized jurisdiction over the object and any personnel onboard, it is not popular, particularly for the increasing number of “disposable” space objects, like Starlink satellites.²⁰

3. NATIONAL AUTHORIZATION FOR LAUNCHING

As established by the international space law discussed above, State Parties must adhere to the obligations set forth by the multilateral space treaties. Government operations have *de facto* mission authorization required by Article VI of the Outer Space Treaty, whereas private actors require external oversight provided by their government. To define the language of this paper: in a commercial launch, the launcher is a private, or non-governmental, entity pursuing a commercial space activity. This commercial activity could be contracted work on behalf of a government agency or a strictly private activity for business or other purposes.²¹

There are three general mechanisms a government can use to manage launch activities. First, a State may prohibit any launches by non-governmental entities. Second, a State may approve of a private launch on a case-by-case basis. Third, a State may develop a licensure system to standardize the requirements for a non-governmental entity to launch.

3.1. Authorization Through Prohibition

A key part of authorization is legislation or regulation which simply prohibits private actors from conducting or participating in space launches. By prohibiting non-governmental actors, the government maintains control over the activity. There is no question as to authorizing an activity because, by the nature of the prohibition, no activities are authorized. This prohibition is the easiest first step in creating national legislation for space activities, particularly launching.

3.2. Authorization on a Case-by-Case Basis

Approval on a case-by-case basis allows for flexibility. Instead of implementing a commercial launch license, a country may accomplish its international obligation to provide “authorization and continuing supervision” on an *ad hoc* basis. *Ad hoc* approval may be beneficial for determining the parameters of a regulatory licensing procedure. However, in the long-term, case-by-case approval creates government burden. Further, it lacks predictability and reliability, which largely benefits the private space industry.

The *ad hoc* approach, or authorizing launches on an individual basis, falls short of addressing regulatory gaps as more private actors are involved in the space industry and greater international collaboration

¹⁷ Convention on Registration of Objects Launched into Outer Space (“Registration Convention”), November 12, 1974, <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/introregistration-convention.html>.

¹⁸ *Ibid.*

¹⁹ *Ibid.*, art. IV.

²⁰ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. [Online Index of Objects Launched into Outer Space](#).

²¹ Isnardi, C. (2020). Problems with enforcing international space law on private actors. *Columbia Journal of Transnational Law*, 58(2), 492. <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5daf8b1ab45413657badbc03/t/5ed6c19ec930145149b92f2f/1742287183697/%28i%29+Isnardi+%2858-2%29.pdf>.

exposes more countries to becoming a launching State. The launching State definitions include countries who procuring a launch. What it means to “procure a launch” is not clarified in the treaty; rather, it depends on treaty interpretation according to international laws of state practice.

3.3. *Authorization by a License*

Licensing private and commercial launches is the most robust option for supporting economic development of the private space industry and appropriately authorizing activities in accordance with international obligations. A licensure for regulating launches is only necessary for private actors in their launching activities. According to Article VI, private actors require “authorization and continuing supervision.”²² This necessity is not relevant to government agencies as they already “bear international responsibility for national activities in outer space.”²³

Separately, a country may choose to lay out requirements for its government agencies in the commercial launch license regulations. Containing specifications and regulations for government agency launches may be done together with a commercial launch license, as it may be convenient for legislative or regulatory purposes; however, it is not necessary. The government is already responsible for their launch, and the government is already liable for their damages. Thus, a successful licensure would provide “authorization and continuing supervision” to a country’s private actors and hold all private actors accountable to the government for their liability by applying to private actors.

Establishing a licensure defines clear regulatory guidance for when an actor would need authorization for their activity. Without regulations which ban launching without permission from the government, a national may subject their country to becoming a launching State, by procuring a launch. A licensure would lay out the necessary situations, in which an actor must obtain a launch license anytime the country becomes a launching State due to its nation’s activities. Thus, licensing would manage the country’s liability and establish clear and predictable criteria to achieve launch authorization.

3.3.1. *Necessary Components of a Launch License*

A license provides many benefits. For industry, it creates reliability and foresight into the regulatory process to gain mission authorization. Through a licensing system, companies will know the requirements for their launch to be approved and can plan to conform to those requirements. Licensures also create a level of predictability for investor funding, a critical consideration for space start-ups.

This article proposes five critical components of a licensure to operate in accordance with international obligations set forth by the space law treaties. These components are modeled after the United States’ regulations on launch and re-entry licensing found in Title 14, Chapter III of the Code of Federal Regulations. These create a framework to ensure compliance with international law and feasible domestic regulations, mindful of national security. These aspects will not be an exhaustive list of success criteria. Rather, the components explored will provide a starting point, or bare minimum, for a successful commercial launch license.

First, the license must be required for any private actor’s launching activity which would classify the country as a launching State. Second, the license must mandate some form of technical requirements to comply with international obligations. Third, the license must provide a mechanism for the government to manage financial responsibility and liability created by private actors. Fourth, the license must allow for certain waivers in exceptional circumstances. Fifth, the government must maintain the power to terminate the licensed activity.

²² Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 2, art. VI.

²³ *Ibid.*

Taken together, these components provide the bare minimum for functionality and adherence to international obligations. The specifics of each component and other aspects of a commercial launch license are determined by a country's policy choices. Further, commercial launch licensures provide regulatory guidance and predictability for the developing space economy by laying out the mandatory financial requirements and technical aspects. Thus, investors and startups can secure capital accordingly and engineers can design specifications to meet the required technical criteria.

3.3.2. *Market-based Restraints*

In addition to prohibiting unauthorized activities, either on a case-by-case basis or through a license, there is an additional form of managing space activities: these are market-based and economic restraints on the private space industry. It is crucial to remember that this is not a form of government authorization required by international law. Rather, market-based restraints create a minimum threshold for private actors to pass before even reaching government authorization. The high cost of space activities is, in and of itself, a limiter.

Insurance is one way to manage liability and risk. In some instances, it is used as a form of semi-governance.²⁴ The US Department of Transportation, particularly the Federal Aviation Administration ("FAA"), regulates specific technical and probabilistic requirements for the launches it licenses through its maximum probable loss calculation, thus imposing a financial barrier.²⁵ This financial form of governance, mostly brought about by the market of space launch insurance, works alongside the other requirements. Strictly as a form of governance, it may be more subject to economic markets. Coupled with other requirements, it could be an effective manager for liability. However, using solely insurance as a form of governance could create a "pay-to-play" dynamic, giving more leeway for recklessness to wealthier, more financially savvy licensees.

Launches must first meet international requirements, and then the licensee should also have financial responsibility. This arrangement is critical to a commercial launch license. When dealing with rockets and space objects, allowing risky behavior is highly discouraged, even if a licensee could foot the bill. A space-related launch disaster could easily expand in damage astronomically due to the types of technology used in rocketry. Further, the international treaties dissuade this type of profit motive, pay-to-play behavior, as a government must authorize space activities in accordance with the obligations of the Outer Space Treaty, as well as other space treaties, in addition to being accountable for the damages caused by their private actors. Overall, launch licenses should appropriately use insurance to manage financial responsibility as a market-based solution for the cost of liability, which the government may incur from allowing a private actor to launch.

A State Party to the space treaties would not truly fulfill its duties to authorize and provide continuing supervision if the government determines eligibility based on economic factors alone. The State party must ultimately oversee all private space activities. Further, State Parties must also ensure their private actors are operating with 'due regard' and provide 'authorization and continuing supervision' for their space activities.

²⁴ Ramirez, D., & Pinto, T. (2021). Policing the police: A roadmap to police accountability using professional liability insurance. *Rutgers University Law Review*, 73(2), 329. https://www.rutgerslawreview.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/01_Ramirez-Pinto.pdf ("Insurance companies do not have any direct control over day to day of the police departments. Just as credit ratings affect rate of borrowing, insurance companies will set premium rates to reflect risk. Liability insurance will mitigate financial losses that result from litigation, thereby enabling officers and departments to focus on community safety and development, while also reducing the burden on taxpayers.").

²⁵ 14 C.F.R § 440.

4. THE US SYSTEM FOR AUTHORIZING COMMERCIAL LAUNCHES

The FAA is the US government agency that oversees launch authorization.²⁶ The commercial launch licensure was first codified into law in the 1980s and has become the gold standard in commercial launch licensing today, with many countries using the FAA Vehicle Operator License as a model.²⁷

4.1. Licensees

A critical part of licensing is to require the license for any non-governmental actor whose activities would give rise to a State being considered a “launching State” according to the Liability Convention.²⁸ This is because the State Party is the “appropriate state” to provide authorization and continuing supervision for the private actor.

The US requires a commercial launch license for anyone who fits into the following categories: (1) one who is launching from a US territory; (2) one who is an individual US citizen²⁹ or US business³⁰, outside the US; (3) one who is organized or existing under the laws of a foreign country, where a US citizen or US business has a “controlling interest”³¹ in the one and the launch is outside the US and outside of another country’s territory;³² or (4) one in a foreign country’s territory, where there is a “controlling interest” and where it is agreed that the US has jurisdiction.³³

These categories are wide; they encompass any activity in which the US would be a launching State by covering whenever a US citizen launches or procures the launching of a space object, or launches from a US territory or facility.³⁴ A license must regulate activities which would classify the country as a launching State according to the Liability Convention. This allows a country to authorize the activity and manage the liability it creates for the national government.

4.2. Technical Requirements

International space law also requires specific practices and prohibitions in space, which apply to both governmental and non-governmental activity. Specifically, there is a requirement to register space objects, a prohibition on weapons of mass destruction, a duty to avoid harmful contamination, and the mandate to exercise ‘due regard’ as they carry out space activities.³⁵ The duty to register space objects comes from the Registration Convention. The prohibition of weapons of mass destruction comes from Article IV of the Outer Space Treaty. Article IX mandates that Parties “conduct exploration [] as to avoid [] harmful contamination” and act with ‘due regard.’ The US uses its payload review process, as well as other

²⁶ 51 U.S.C. § 50901(b)(3).

²⁷ Sundahl, M.J. (2019). Business, Legal, and Policy Issues in Relation to Increased Private Space Activity. *Law Faculty Articles and Essays*. https://engagedscholarship.csuohio.edu/fac_articles/971.

²⁸ von der Dunk, F.G. (2011). *National space legislation in Europe: Issues of authorisation of private space activities in the light of developments in European space cooperation* (pp. 13-14). (Vol. 6). Brill, Nijhoff. <https://doi.org/10.1163/ej.9789004204867.iii-381.9>.

²⁹ US citizen, as used in the paper, will have the ordinary definition, unless otherwise specified to be the 51 USC § 50902 definition of “Citizen of the United States.”

³⁰ US business, as used in this section, means, “an entity organized or existing under the laws of the United States or a State.” See 51 U.S.C. § 50902(1)(B).

³¹ “Controlling interest means ownership of an amount of equity in such entity sufficient to direct management of the entity or to void transactions entered into by management. Ownership of at least fifty-one percent of the equity in an entity by persons described in paragraph (1) or (2) of this definition creates a rebuttable presumption that such interest is controlling.” 14 C.F.R § 401.5

³² The most significant example is a water launch in international waters. This would also apply to territories which are unclaimed by any nation, like Antarctica.

³³ As established by 51 U.S.C. § 50904.

³⁴ Liability Convention, *supra note 9*, art. I.

³⁵ Outer Space Treaty, *supra note 2*.

mechanisms in the general licensing process, to implement these technical provisions to follow the requirements under international law. In addition to ensuring missions meet international obligations, technical specifications can standardize engineering and safety requirements for launch operations. This establishes clear standards that private industry must meet in order to procure a license for their space launch.

4.3. *Financial Responsibility*

Any damage caused by a private actor to another launching State creates financial liability for the private actor's government. Because that launching State would be beholden to other countries for damages their launches cause on the ground, governments must mandate their private actors to maintain a certain level of financial responsibility.³⁶ The US manages this liability by determining the amount for which an actor is financially responsible, mandating insurance or demonstrated financial responsibility, and providing indemnification in cases where damages exceed the actor's financial responsibility.³⁷

Recalling the Liability Convention, which mandates strict liability for damages caused on the surface of the earth or aircraft in flight.³⁸ Because the liability is absolute, countries must prepare their launchers to assume financial responsibility for their activities. A successful commercial launch license will cover the liability of a country created by international law, up to an appropriate level for the respective country. There are many ways a nation can distribute financial responsibility. Furthermore, there are also policy factors to determine what level of risk is appropriate for the country's government and economic goals. The US uses a capping method to limit the liability of private actors, along with a calculation of each launch's level of risk.

To establish the amount for which a private actor may be liable, the Secretary of Transportation, together with consultation from other government agencies determine the maximum probable loss ("MPL") for the applicant's launching activity.³⁹ This "forms the basis for financial responsibility requirements" in launch licenses.⁴⁰ MPL is defined as "the greatest dollar amount of loss for bodily injury or property damage that is reasonably expected to result from a licensed or permitted activity."⁴¹

The US established that a licensee must obtain insurance or demonstrate financial responsibility up to the lesser of the MPL or "the maximum liability insurance available on the world market at reasonable cost if the amount is less than the applicable."⁴² The costs associated with damages beyond the MPL would then be indemnified by the government, up to a certain point.

The result of not mandating financial responsibility for a private actor releases that actor from the liability of their activities. This would cause a government to become completely responsible for the costs of any damage caused by a private actor, without a convenient and legal way to recover money from the private actor. Thus, mechanisms for distributing financial responsibility are necessary for a commercial launch license.

4.4. *Waiver*

For the US to maintain control over their launching activities and abide by its own legislation, the regulations must provide for authorizing a launch outside of the licensing procedure in exceptional circumstances. The Secretary of Transportation may waive a requirement or the license if "the waiver is

³⁶ Liability Convention, *supra note 9*.

³⁷ 51 U.S.C. §§ 50914-15.

³⁸ Liability Convention, *supra note 9*, art. II.

³⁹ 14 C.F.R. § 440.7(b) (2023).

⁴⁰ 14 C.F.R. § 440.7(a) (2023).

⁴¹ 14 C.F.R. § 440.3 (2023).

⁴² 51 U.S.C. § 50914(a)(3).

in the public interest and will not jeopardize the public health and safety, safety of property, and national security and foreign policy interests of the United States.”⁴³ Further, the law prohibits waiver if a human is on board the launch.⁴⁴ This statutory language outlines who may waive requirements for a license, factors to consider, and any exceptions to waiving.⁴⁵ This protects the sovereignty of a nation’s launching activities and allows for a legal option for private and commercial actors to launch without a license if it is in the best interest of the nation. Ultimately, the government is responsible for any liability that results from the launching activity.⁴⁶ So, deviations to the license procedure take on more risk and should be exceptional in nature.

4.5. Termination

The regulations should also allow for suspension or termination in appropriate circumstances. This allows a country’s government to have necessary and ultimate control over launching. The US license allows for the prohibition, suspension, or immediate termination of a licensed launch “if the Secretary decides the launch or operation or reentry is detrimental to the public health and safety, the safety of property, or a national security or foreign policy interest of the United States.”⁴⁷ These considerations are open-ended, which allows the US to maintain control legally over its private actors.

Termination, like waiver, legally gives a State necessary control over its private actors’ launching activities. This control is mandatory to international obligations created in the Outer Space Treaty Article VI. Further, this control can provide for national security by terminating a launch when national security is at risk.

According to 51 U.S.C. 50908(c)(2), the Secretary of Transportation may suspend or revoke a license if it is “necessary to protect the public health and safety, the safety of property, or a national security or foreign policy interest of the United States.” Thus, “foreign policy interests”, including international obligations that the US owes according to the space treaties, are grounds for terminating the license.

For a license to adhere to the international obligations, termination is a critical component to maintain control. The State should be able to terminate authorization of space activity if there is a failure or risk of failure in adhering to international obligations.

5. CONSIDERATIONS FOR EMERGING SPACEFARING COUNTRIES

For an emerging spacefaring country, the first steps to authorizing national space activity would be through prohibiting its own private actors from unapproved launches. Next, there should be a way to obtain permission to launch or be a part of procuring a launch activity. This would mean designating a particular governmental body to contact. A later step is to create a licensing procedure if this makes sense for the nation’s private and commercial space economy. A license can provide many benefits to the private sector, including predictability and reliability.

Another consideration is how modern space activities are more complex and do not fit neatly into one category. As international collaboration increases across the globe, the division between how multiple parties procure a launch begins to blur. Consider the variety of components, intellectual property, and manufacturing that go into a single launch vehicle.

Today, there is a deep understanding of how space activities are more complex and require multiple types of licensures and approvals. The US and its commercial launch license now face issues in trying to keep pace with the private industry’s demands. The regulatory burden of the commercial launch license can be

⁴³ 51 U.S.C. § 50905(b)(3).

⁴⁴ *Ibid.*

⁴⁵ *Ibid.*

⁴⁶ Liability Convention, *supra note 9*, art. II.

⁴⁷ 51 U.S.C. § 50909(a).

felt by large space companies, like SpaceX, and small start-ups, like Varda Space Industries. The regulatory scheme has become cumbersome.

The US had built a system where different federal agencies manage different activities according to their delegated authority on Earth. For example, among the FAA, the Office of Space Commerce, and the Federal Communications Commission (“FCC”), each has a speciality in authorizing launching and reentry, remote sensing, and spectrum management. However, the strict separation of their authority to license space activities has proven to be an incredible regulatory burden. Further, “novel” space activities do not fit into any of the US’s established licensing systems.

These issues give rise to the call for a one-stop-shop system, where one government entity is responsible for the entire licensing of space activity. Rather than multiple agencies managing different aspects of the same space mission, one agency would provide convenience, clarity, and greater speed for navigating a complex licensing process.⁴⁸ A one-stop shop for licensing space activities is a large hope for the commercial space industry. However, the US seems too far into its current structure to truly implement a singular agency approach.

The space industry and the history of US commercial space show that a singular agency design would be the most effective and flexible for modern and novel space activities. Countries that are now looking to create a licensure for commercial activities should deeply consider how they wish to divide operations and responsibilities in licensing space activities, if at all.

Beyond a “one-stop-shop” structure, countries must also consider the economic implications of their licensing. While licensing is an important step for encouraging a country’s private space industry, it also draws resources away from other operations of the government. In addition to structural considerations for designing national legislation to authorize space activities, countries should also look to their private industry needs and trends. What sort of activity is common and requires more governmental support? What other countries do businesses tend to partner with for space operations? Economic and political factors will also play a role in dedicating resources to encouraging space activities nationally. A cost-benefit analysis may assist in determining the appropriate dedication to licensing operations compared with the economic benefit caused by private space activity.

As more countries expand their space operations and encourage growth for their private space companies, the need for licensure systems grows. Further research can illuminate more aspects of law, policy, and economics as scholars continue to inspect commercial launching through the lens of various countries and their economies. This would benefit countries, especially emerging spacefaring countries, as they explore and determine policy choices for their own commercial launch licensure.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has applied the international obligations of the space treaties to create a framework for authorizing national activities, particularly non-governmental launching activities. The need for responsible commercial launch licensing is growing, demonstrating a need for countries to adopt a licensure system which will: regulate the actors whose activities would give the country status as a launching State, determine technical specifications, provide mechanisms to distribute financial liability, and include possible waiver and termination of the license. Through implementing these components, a country will create a functional commercial launch licensing system that respects both its obligations under international space law and its sovereignty and security in managing its private actors.

⁴⁸ Clayson, Z., Spellman, F., Patel, S., & Shen, D. (2023, August 8). *Space mission authorization: Enabling the final frontier*. War on the Rocks. <https://warontherocks.com/2023/08/space-mission-authorization-enabling-the-final-frontier>

As countries with a long history of space missions and regulatory experience, like the US, analyze and reconstruct their launch licensing procedures, emerging spacefaring countries can find guidance from their experience and history, as well as the issues that face their government systems and industry today. On the path to full participation in space, the language of the Outer Space Treaty obliges countries to promote peace and benefit for each other: a truly unifying mission for the advancement of all humankind. Authorizing national activities for commercial launching is a first and fundamental step to supporting and bolstering space policy around the globe as humanity shoots for the stars.

© The Author(s) 2026. Published by Space Court Foundation. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted reuse, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

THE IMPLICATIONS OF SHUTTER CONTROL: A BASIS FOR INVOKING FORCE MAJEURE IN EARTH OBSERVATION DATA LICENSES

KEVIN SETIADI¹

ABSTRACT

The commercialization of Earth observation technology has created a tension between national security interests and contractual obligations in satellite data licensing. The paper examines whether shutter control policies can justify invoking force majeure clauses in satellite data license agreements. Earth observation has become commercially vital for both the public and private sectors. However, the commercialization of the activity raises national security concerns and has led countries, such as the United States of America (US), to adopt a ‘shutter control’ policy. The policy allows countries to compel satellite operators to cease data collection, potentially preventing licensors from fulfilling contractual obligations. The paper specifically focuses on the US shutter control policy, which originates from the Presidential Decision Directive 23. The policy permits the government to limit data collection to safeguard national security interests, although its ambiguity may lead to disputes in commercial agreements and invoke the force majeure clause. The paper compares the application of force majeure under UK common law, which applies the restrictive doctrine of frustration, and Indonesian civil law, which recognizes broader concepts of force majeure. The review finds that the enforceability of the force majeure clause is strongly influenced by the choice of governing law and the application of the shutter control policy. The analysis concludes that while invoking the force majeure clause may be justified by the implementation of the shutter control policy, its enforceability is conditioned on both the suitability of the governing legal framework and the precision of the contractual terms.

KEYWORDS: Shutter control, Earth observation, Data licensing, Force Majeure, Commercialization.

¹ Graduate, Advanced LL.M. in Air and Space Law, International Institute of Air and Space Law, Leiden University; kevin@kevinsetiadi.com; <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-3648-3499>

1. INTRODUCTION

Earth observation, also known as remote sensing, provides diverse benefits for global economic development. It plays a pivotal role in, among other things, monitoring environmental changes, managing natural resources, and responding to disasters.² Today's technology makes Earth observation commercially feasible. The consequence of this significant development is that Earth observation has become an indispensable tool for both public and private sectors.

At the same time, the meaningful benefits and the rapid expansion of Earth observation into a commercial activity have not been without complications. Data-related issues remain the primary legal challenge in commercializing earth observation activity.³ The reason behind such issues is the concern of national security, which may be jeopardized due to private operations that collect remote sensing data.⁴ One safeguard taken by countries to maintain their national security interests is the so-called 'shutter control', as the United States of America (US) and Canada practice through their remote sensing regulation.⁵ The shutter control is generally understood as a measure that allows a State to block the satellite operator from taking images of the Earth by closing the 'shutter' of the camera or other remote sensing equipment.⁶

The application of shutter control measures may pose a contractual issue for the commercial activity of remote sensing, which is generally governed by a data license agreement. The enactment of the shutter control policy could prevent satellite operators or data processors from fulfilling their contractual obligations, either by restricting data acquisition over specific locations or by withholding data from the end users. As the shutter control policy compels the satellite operator to switch off the remote sensing equipment in the satellite, the satellite operator or the data processor could argue that it is a force majeure and they do not need to bear any responsibility or liability for any damages incurred by the end user for complying with the policy.

Similar to other commercial contracts, the data license agreement commonly includes a force majeure clause that excuses the parties from performing their contractual obligations in the event of unforeseeable or unavoidable events beyond both parties' control. Inclusion of such a clause is a common standard practice in commercial contract drafting. In the present scenario, the force majeure clause could serve as a legal basis for the satellite operator or data processor to limit their exposure or to defend against any claims arising from compliance with the policy.

The legal reasoning of the above argument may hold if all the parties involved are companies subject to US law, i.e., established under US law. However, as the world enters a period of globalization, such a situation could occur in a cross-border transaction involving multiple jurisdictions. For example, a transaction that involves a US satellite operator, a UK data seller, and an Indonesian consumer. The cross-border commercial transaction nature, involving multiple legal systems, presents a legal issue in implementing the data license agreement in the event of the enactment of the shutter control policy. It raises the question, can shutter control serve as a legal basis for invoking the force majeure clause under a data license agreement in cross-border commercial contexts?

² Couture, J., & Golovtchenko, V. (2025, January 17). Earth Observation: 5 Uses of Data for Business and the Planet. World Economic Forum; World Economic Forum. <https://www.weforum.org/stories/2025/01/5-uses-earth-observation-satellite-data-for-business-and-planet/>.

³ Masson-Zwaan, T., & Hofmann, M. (2025). *An Introduction to Space Law* (5th ed.). Wolters Kluwer, 208.

⁴ *Ibid*, 209.

⁵ *Ibid*.

⁶ *Ibid*.

To address the questions, the paper will first discuss the commercial relations in Earth observation activities in Section 2. In Section 3, the paper will discuss the shutter control policy, particularly under the US regulations. The paper will then discuss and compare the force majeure situation under the United Kingdom (UK) Law (common law system) and Indonesian Law (civil law system) in section 4. Section 5 of the paper will analyze the application of force majeure arising from the US's shutter control. The paper will conclude its discussion in the final section.

The paper will refer to the UK Common Law system as it is widely regarded as one of the most well-established legal frameworks, particularly in the domain of contract law. Its strength lies in several key features: (i) an independent judiciary and strong adherence to the rule of law, which foster trust and confidence in commercial dealings; (ii) a legal framework that is clear, fair, and predictable, supported by a robust system of precedent; and (iii) the international recognition and enforceability of UK court decisions, which enhance legal certainty across jurisdictions.⁷

Meanwhile, the Indonesian legal system continues to rely on the old Dutch Civil Code, a legacy of its colonial past. It adopted the Dutch Civil Code (*Burgerlijk Wetboek*) and was promulgated in 1847.⁸ Since then, Indonesia has used the code to govern the civil relations of its people. The country is yet to reform or update its civil code, despite it having been in use for nearly two centuries. A fitness check is necessary to see whether such an ancient civil code is equipped to address a developing, highly advanced, and complex space industry.⁹

The paper will review the law's applicability to addressing contemporary challenges in the space industry, specifically in the context of the enactment of shutter control policies. This inclusion offers a comparative perspective on how these two legal traditions address potential concerns in space activities.

2. THE COMMERCIAL RELATIONSHIP IN EARTH OBSERVATION ACTIVITIES

Satellite data is the central component in the commercialization of Earth observation or remote-sensing activities.¹⁰ However, satellite data will become commercially valuable and be sold only after analysis and processing.¹¹ The satellite data must undergo analysis and processing to be converted into identifiable data and meet its intended purpose.¹² The satellite data will not have significant commercial value without analysis and processing, as its value lies in the high-resolution images captured by satellites.¹³

As the commercial value of satellite data depends on the data supplier's processing and analysis capabilities, the data supplier consequently retains control over how the Earth observation data is accessed and distributed to the relevant market. The situation prompts users to obtain access to the data from the relevant data controller through a commercial transaction, marking the beginning of the

⁷ Courts and Tribunals Judiciary. (2017). The strength of English law and the UK jurisdiction. In Courts and Tribunals Judiciary. <https://www.judiciary.uk/wp-content/uploads/2017/08/legaluk-strength-of-english-law-draft-4-FINAL.pdf>.

⁸ Hutabarat, S. (2016). Harmonisasi Hukum Kontrak dan Dampaknya Pada Hukum Kontrak Indonesia. *Veritas et Justitia*, 2(1), 112–134, 118.

⁹ Khuan, H. (2025). The Urgency of Civil Law Reform in Responding to the Development of Artificial Intelligence in Automatic Contracts. *Journal Hukum Dan Keadilan*, 2(4), 1–9, 2–3. <https://doi.org/10.61942/jhk.v2i4.363>.

¹⁰ Hayward, C. M. (1990). Remote Sensing: Terrestrial Laws for Celestial Activities Note. *Boston University International Law Journal*, 8(1), 157–186, 168.

¹¹ Kim, Y.-J. (2024). Commercial Use of Satellite Remote Sensing Data and Civil Liability. *Laws*, 13(6), 77–98, 80. <https://doi.org/10.3390/laws13060077>.

¹² Ibid.

¹³ Tronchetti, F. (2015). Legal aspects of satellite remote sensing. In F. G. von der Dunk (Ed.), *Handbook of space law: Research Handbooks in International Law series*. Edward Elgar Publishing, 509–510.

data-commercialization process.¹⁴ The transaction is commonly governed through an agreement known as the ‘satellite data license agreement’.¹⁵ Through this agreement, the data suppliers maintain control over the dissemination of satellite data and generate revenue. Data suppliers or the licensor will impose obligations on users or licensees to pay a license fee and to impose limitations on data use, such as prohibiting the resale or sublicensing of satellite data to third parties.¹⁶

Although the sale transaction appears straightforward, the legal relationship that needs to be formed to enable such a transaction may be more complex. Indeed, the transaction typically involves only the suppliers and the users. However, in some instances, the data suppliers may not be the owners or operators of Earth observation satellites.¹⁷ Consequently, according to Young-Ju Kim, the legal relationship in Earth observation commercialization can be classified into three types.¹⁸

The first type is the common relation, which only involves the licensor and licensee. In this case, the licensor operates its satellite and sensor, analyzes and processes the satellite data, and sells it directly to the users.¹⁹ Thus, the satellite data license agreement governs the legal relationship between the licensor and the licensee.

Figure 1. Type 1 relationship.

Unlike a type 1 relationship, a type 2 relationship involves a separation of roles. In this arrangement, the company that operates the satellite and the sensing sensor does not handle the data analysis and processing.²⁰ The satellite data is analyzed and processed by a different company (third party), which subsequently becomes the seller of such data to the consumer.²¹ The relationship between the operator and the third party is governed by a contract for analyzing, processing, and selling the data, while the license agreement governs the relationship between the third party and the end-user.²²

¹⁴ Kim, *supra* note 11 at 81.

¹⁵ Tronchetti, *supra* note 13 at 549; Mantl, L. (2023). Law and Policy of Data from Space: Satellite Navigation and Remote Sensing. In P. J. Blount & M. Hofmann (Eds.), *Space law in a networked world*. Brill Nijhoff, 203–204.

¹⁶ Tronchetti, *supra* note 13 at 549.

¹⁷ Kim, *supra* note 11 at 81.

¹⁸ *Ibid*, 81–84.

¹⁹ *Ibid*, 81–82.

²⁰ *Ibid*, 82.

²¹ *Ibid*.

²² *Ibid*.

Figure 2. Type 2 relationship.

Type 3 also has a tripartite relationship with different arrangements from type 2. In the type 3 relationship, the satellite operator and the sensor operator are performed by two different companies.²³ The sensor operator will operate the sensor, analyze, process, and subsequently sell the satellite data to the end user under this structure.²⁴ The sensor operator company formalized its legal relationship with the satellite operator through the ‘Sensor Installation and Usage Agreement’.²⁵

Figure 3. Type 3 relationship.

²³ Ibid.

²⁴ Ibid.

²⁵ Ibid.

The abovementioned discussion shows that the commercialization of Earth observation activities may have an intricate legal framework, particularly when it involves a tripartite arrangement. The tripartite structure involves multiple contracts that assign distinct rights and obligations to the parties in a remote sensing operation. Understanding these relationships is essential for assessing whether the force majeure clause in a satellite data license agreement applies when a country enacts a shutter control policy. The interconnected nature of the tripartite structure may lead to disputes over liability, particularly between the licensor and its third-party partner, when a country exercises its shutter control policy.

3. THE US 'SHUTTER CONTROL' POLICY

Earth observation technology has advanced rapidly and has outpaced the applicable international legal framework, raising concerns about a country's practice of remotely sensing foreign countries and disseminating the resulting data commercially.²⁶ Given this development, countries establish national regulations on remote sensing to limit commercial sensing activities, especially on the collection or dissemination of sensing data.²⁷ The commercial limitation aims to protect national security interests and ensure exclusive access to the government in the event of national disasters or other national crises.²⁸ There are two methods available to countries for limiting remote sensing activities to preserve national security interests. The first one is the shutter control method, in which the country prevents data collection when there are concerns of national security, international obligations, or foreign policy interests.²⁹ The US and Canada are known to use the shutter control method in their national remote sensing regulations.³⁰ The second method is a distribution control method, in which the country reviews the remote sensing images before they are distributed to ensure that national security or other sensitive national information remains protected. Germany, France, Finland, and Japan are some countries that practice this method to preserve their security and other national interests.³¹ However, for the purposes of the paper, this section will focus solely on the shutter control policy adopted by the US.

It all began with the US's interest in commercializing its Landsat program in the 1970s. In 1972, the US established the Landsat program under the auspices of NASA.³² At the end of the 1970s, the US attempted to privatize the Landsat system through the 1984 *Land Remote Sensing Commercialization Act*.³³ The plan was to delegate the operation of the Landsat system to the private sector to make the system commercially viable and, eventually, to create a private-sector-driven ecosystem.³⁴ Unfortunately, the initiative did not unfold as intended due to rising data prices and competition from the *Satellite Pour l'Observation de la Terre* (SPOT) program, an earth observation satellite program funded by the French Government.³⁵ Subsequently, the US reinstated the Landsat program under the overall government oversight.³⁶ In 1992, the US enacted the *Land Remote Sensing Policy Act*, which placed the Landsat program under the

²⁶ Curran, P. J. (1985). Principles of remote sensing. Longman Publishing Group, 5–6; Hayward, *supra note* 10 at 158.

²⁷ Tronchetti, *supra note* 13 at 526.

²⁸ *Ibid.*

²⁹ Masson-Zwaan & Hofmann, *supra note* 3 at 209.

³⁰ For the application of shutter control in the US, see 15 CFR Part 960 on Licensing of Private Remote Sensing Space Systems; For the application of shutter control in Canada, see the Remote Sensing Space Systems Act 2005 section Interruptions of Service.

³¹ Kim, *supra note* 11 at 85 – 91; Masson-Zwaan & Hofmann, *supra note* 3 at 209.

³² Ito, A. (2011). Legal aspects of satellite remote sensing. Martinus Nijhoff, 75.

³³ *Ibid.*

³⁴ *Ibid.*; Tronchetti, *supra note* 13 at 528.

³⁵ Ito, *supra note* 32 at 76.

³⁶ *Ibid.*

auspices of the Department of Defense and NASA, while giving the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) the authority to issue licenses.³⁷

Over the years, US laws on remote sensing have continuously evolved in response to technological developments and contemporary commercial and social needs.³⁸ The *Land Remote Sensing Policy Act* maintains its status as the primary legal instrument governing remote sensing activities in the US.³⁹ However, other instruments have continuously updated and complemented the act, including the *Presidential Decision Directive 23* (PDD-23).⁴⁰ One of the PDD-23 objectives is to “specify national security measures as a licensing requirement”.⁴¹ In pursuit of this objective, PDD-23 incorporates a shutter-control provision empowering the executive branch of the US government to:⁴²

[...] may, after consultation with the appropriate agency(ies), require the licensee to limit data collection and/or distribution by the system to the extent necessitated by the given situation [...].⁴³

The provision aims to avoid compromising the US national security, international obligations, or foreign policy due to US commercial satellite activities.⁴⁴

The PDD-23 was eventually superseded by the *US Commercial Remote Sensing Policy*, which aims to enhance US remote sensing capabilities and the remote sensing industry.⁴⁵ The policy further deregulates restrictions provided under the PDD-23.⁴⁶ It states that the objective of the policy is to:

[...] advance and protect U.S. national security and foreign policy interest by maintaining the nation’s leadership in remote sensing space activities, and by sustaining and enhancing the U.S. remote sensing industry.⁴⁷

Despite the adoption of a new remote sensing policy, neither the PDD-23 nor the US Commercial Remote Sensing Policy defines what constitutes a national security interest. It remains to give the executive branch of the US government the power to impose the policy over an undefined territorial scope for an undefined amount of time.⁴⁸ The broad terminology used in the PDD-23 subsequently drew criticism from many stakeholders.⁴⁹

In 2006, the US government adopted the regulation on Licensing of Private Land Remote Sensing Space Systems to enhance the implementation of the 1992 *Land Remote Sensing Policy Act*,⁵⁰ which provides

³⁷ Tronchetti, *supra* note 13 at 528.

³⁸ *Ibid*, 527.

³⁹ *Ibid*, 529; Ito, *supra* note 32 at 77.

⁴⁰ *Ibid*.

⁴¹ Ito, *supra* note 32 at 78.

⁴² Prober, R. (2003). Shutter Control: Confronting Tomorrow’s Technology with Yesterday’s Regulations Note. *Journal of Law & Politics*, 19(2), 203–252, 209.

⁴³ Presidential Decision Directive/NSC-23. (1994, March 9). Federation American Scientist. <https://irp.fas.org/offdocs/pdd/pdd-23.pdf>.

⁴⁴ *Ibid*.

⁴⁵ Ito, *supra* note 32, at 79 – 80.

⁴⁶ *Ibid*.

⁴⁷ *U.S. Commercial Remote Sensing Policy*, 25 April 2003. <https://www.nesdis.noaa.gov/s3/2021-08/Commercial%20Remote%20Sensing%20Policy%202003.pdf>.

⁴⁸ Prober, *supra* note 42 at 209.

⁴⁹ *Ibid*.

⁵⁰ See 15 C.F.R. Part 960 – Licensing of Private Remote Sensing Systems.

detailed procedures regarding licensing requirements, procedures, and compliance.⁵¹ Following this, the US government further removed certain restrictions by updating the *Licensing of Private Land Remote Sensing Space Systems Regulation* in 2020 to increase US competitiveness against foreign remote sensing operators.⁵² The latest version of the regulation divides remote sensing satellites into three categories based on their capability.⁵³

- a) Tier 1 satellites are those that have the capability to produce unenhanced data equivalent in quality to non-US remote sensing satellites and are subject to the least stringent licensing requirements, as they are assessed as low risk.
- b) Tier 2 satellites are those that have the capability to produce unenhanced data with the same quality as other US-licensed remote sensing satellites and are subject to more licensing requirements as they are deemed to have a higher risk than Tier 1.
- c) Tier 3 satellites are those that have the capability to produce unenhanced data that is unique or exceeds the capabilities of non-US and US-licensed remote sensing satellites, and consequently are subject to more extensive licensing requirements.

The updated version of the Licensing of Private Land Remote Sensing Space Systems Regulation still incorporates the shutter control provision. However, it only applies to remote sensing satellites in the Tier 2 and Tier 3 categories.⁵⁴ Tier 1 remote sensing satellites are only obligated to operate in a manner that preserves US national security and to observe international obligations and policies.⁵⁵

Despite efforts to ease restrictions on commercial remote sensing operations, the updated version of the Licensing of Private Land Remote Sensing Space Systems Regulation still reflects the shortcomings of PDD-23 and the US Commercial Remote Sensing Policy. It still offers no definition of the concept of national security interest and foreign policy interest when applying the shutter control policy. It also continues to vest the executive branch of the US government with the authority to impose a shutter control policy over an undefined territorial scope. The updated version of the Licensing of Private Land Remote Sensing Space Systems regulation does, however, introduce a time limit on the application of the shutter control policy for Tier 3 categories. The updated version of the regulation caps them for three years unless requested otherwise by the Secretary of Defense or Secretary of State. No similar limitation is imposed on the Tier 2 category, leaving the duration of such conditions unresolved.

The above exploration of the US shutter control policy shows that maintaining the integrity of national security interests, upholding foreign policy, and fulfilling international obligations are the policy's main objectives. Nevertheless, some concepts remain undefined despite efforts to streamline the regulation. Furthermore, the temporal limit introduced in the recent version of the Licensing of Private Land Remote Sensing Space Systems regulation may still be extended upon request from the Secretary of Defense or the Secretary of State, which may result in uncertainty. These remaining legal gaps could open the door to a dispute between the commercial parties and indicate a justification for imposing the force majeure clause.

⁵¹ Ito, *supra note* 32 at 80.

⁵² Slivker, A. (2023, September). Global Outer Space Guide: United States. Norton Rose Fulbright; Norton Rose Fulbright.

<https://www.nortonrosefulbright.com/en-nl/knowledge/publications/08a2c80a/global-outer-space-guide-us>.

⁵³ See 15 C.F.R. § 960.6 – Application categorization.

⁵⁴ For remote sensing satellites under the Tier 2 category, see 15 C.F.R. § 960.9(a); For remote sensing satellites under the Tier 3 category, see 15 C.F.R. § 960.10(a).

⁵⁵ See 15 C.F.R. § 960.8(b).

4. FORCE MAJEURE COMPARISON BETWEEN COMMON LAW AND CIVIL LAW

4.1. The United Kingdom Common Law

Force majeure clauses are commonly found in commercial contracts. The clause usually appears in boilerplate form, which aims to excuse either party to a contract from performing their obligations due to events or circumstances beyond their control.⁵⁶ However, UK law does not recognize the concept of force majeure,⁵⁷ which is rooted in French civil law.⁵⁸ The UK law has a doctrine to discharge a contract due to supervening events, called the doctrine of frustration.⁵⁹ The UK courts rarely apply the doctrine of frustration, as discharge requires the highest degree of seriousness.⁶⁰ The UK law sets a high bar threshold since it highly upholds the principle of sanctity of contract (*pacta sunt servanda*).⁶¹ The UK courts have consistently upheld this position over the years.⁶² Therefore, the UK courts could still impose liability on a party under a contract despite the requirement to perform an impossible obligation.

Furthermore, UK law recognizes the doctrine of absolute contract, as established in *Paradine v. Jane*.⁶³ The court stipulated that when an obligation imposed by law cannot be fulfilled without fault, the obligation may be exempted.⁶⁴ Meanwhile, when an obligation arises from a contract, it must be fulfilled despite unforeseeable events.⁶⁵ Over time, the UK Courts began to recognize exceptions to this absolute approach, and later cases adopted a more flexible understanding of contractual obligations.

The case of *Taylor v. Caldwell* is known as a landmark case for adopting a more flexible approach, as it departed from the doctrine of absolute contract by establishing the doctrine of discharge.⁶⁶ The UK Courts found that a contract may be discharged if its performance depends on the continued existence of a specific object and the destruction of that object is not due to fault.⁶⁷ In other words, a contract may be discharged if performance becomes impossible (performance risk).⁶⁸ Other than the discharge doctrine, the prohibition of trading with an enemy, changing government policy, and prohibition by a foreign country may frustrate a contract.⁶⁹

⁵⁶ Jardine-Brown, R. (2016, January 6). Force majeure clauses under English law | Article | Chambers and Partners. Chambers and Partners; Chambers and Partners. <https://chambers.com/articles/force-majeure-clauses-under-english-law>; Thomson Reuters. (2024). Practical Law UK Signon. Thomson Reuters; Thomson Reuters. [https://uk.practicallaw.thomsonreuters.com/3-107-5776?transitionType=Default&contextData=\(sc.Default\)&firstPage=true](https://uk.practicallaw.thomsonreuters.com/3-107-5776?transitionType=Default&contextData=(sc.Default)&firstPage=true).

⁵⁷ Ibid.

⁵⁸ Ralli Brothers v Compañía Naviera Sota Y Aznar, (1920). <https://www.acerislaw.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/Ralli-Bros-v-Compania-Naviera-Sota-y-Aznar-1920-2-KB-287.pdf>, 292, 297, 301.

⁵⁹ Peel, E. (2022). Frustration and Force Majeure (4th ed.). Sweet & Maxwell, 59–63, 447–449.

⁶⁰ Ibid, 62–63.

⁶¹ Ibid, 1–4.

⁶² Eurico SpA v Philipp Bros (The Epaphus), EWCA Civ J0515-5 (1987). <https://vlex.co.uk/vid/eurico-s-p-v-793161761>; Jones and Another v The President and Scholars of St. John's College, Oxford (1870).

⁶³ *Paradine and Jane Aleyn*, Hil. 22 Car. Rot. 1178 & 1179 (1647).

⁶⁴ Ibid.

⁶⁵ Ibid.

⁶⁶ *Taylor and Another against Caldwell and Another*, S. C. 32 L. J. Q. B. 164; 8 L. T. 356; 11 W. R. 726 (1863).

⁶⁷ Ibid.

⁶⁸ Peel, *supra note* 59 at 40–41.

⁶⁹ Ibid, 326–328; 342–344; 364–367.

4.2. Indonesian Civil Law

On the other hand, Indonesian civil law recognizes the concept of force majeure or *overmacht*. The provisions related to force majeure or *overmacht* can be found across the old Dutch Civil Code (*Burgerlijk Wetboek*), which still serves as the Indonesian Civil Code to this date.⁷⁰ The Indonesian Civil Code stipulates that a debtor should not be held liable for costs, losses, and interest due to force majeure or incidental events that prevent the debtor from performing its obligation or doing a prohibited act.⁷¹ In addition, the Indonesian Civil Code also provides that a contract is cancelled if an object agreed in the contract is destroyed, lost, or becomes untradeable.⁷² The object's owner does not need to pay any compensation if the circumstance occurs without fault.⁷³ The provision on force majeure can also be found in other laws, such as banking, construction services, and procurement.⁷⁴ However, the Indonesian Civil Code does not provide a specific definition of what constitutes a force majeure.

A few Indonesian legal experts attempted to define what constitutes a force majeure. Sofwan defines force majeure as a situation where it is impossible to fulfil an obligation or such fulfilment can be done only with extreme measures that result in unreasonable effort or significant financial loss.⁷⁵ Alternatively, Fuady provides a more contemporary definition of force majeure, describing it as a situation where an individual is prevented from fulfilling their contractual obligation due to an unforeseen event when the agreement is made.⁷⁶ The person cannot be held accountable for the event as the person does not act in bad faith.⁷⁷

A comparative look at other countries shows that several civil law jurisdictions offer clearer guidance by providing a definition of force majeure in their civil codes. For example, the Spanish Civil Code provides the definition of force majeure that offers a clearer interpretation and enhances its practical applicability in commercial contexts. It frames force majeure as situations that cannot be foreseen or cannot be avoided, even if they are foreseeable.⁷⁸ This comparative look illustrates how other civil law jurisdictions codify the concept of force majeure, and the lack of an explicit, similar definition under the Indonesian Civil Code.

5. THE APPLICATION OF FORCE MAJEURE DUE TO SHUTTER CONTROL

The satellite data license agreement is substantially equivalent to other commercial contracts. It shares the basic characteristics of commercial contracts and also contains a force majeure clause to protect the licensor from liability for any occurrence beyond its control. The wording of the force majeure clause is constructed very broadly to achieve such objectives.

⁷⁰ For the purpose of this paper, the old Dutch Civil Code (*Burgerlijk Wetboek*) will be referred to as the Indonesian Civil Code.

⁷¹ Indonesian Civil Code (1847), art 1244, 1245.
<https://www.refworld.org/legal/legislation/natlegbod/1847/en/77869>.

⁷² Ibid, art 1444.

⁷³ Ibid, art 1445.

⁷⁴ Rahmat Sadeli Soebagia Soemadipradja. (2010). *Penjelasan Hukum tentang Keadaan Memaksa*. Nasional Legal Reform Program, 73–94.

⁷⁵ Ibid, 34–35.

⁷⁶ Fuady, M. (2001). *Hukum Kontrak (dari Sudut Pandang Hukum Bisnis)*. PT. Citra Aditya Bakti, 113.

⁷⁷ Ibid.

⁷⁸ Spanish Civil Code, art 1105,
<https://www.mjusticia.gob.es/es/AreaTematica/DocumentacionPublicaciones/Documents/Spanish%20Civil%20Code.pdf#page=214,34>.

- 13.11 **FORCE MAJEURE.** Except for Customer's obligation to make payment under the Customer Agreement or these License Terms, neither party will be liable for any failure or delay in fulfilling or performing any term of these License Terms when and to the extent the failure or delay is caused by or results from acts or events beyond that party's reasonable control, including, without limitation: acts of God; fire; water damage; natural disaster (including earthquakes, storms, and floods); power or utility outages; strikes; war, military action, or act of terrorism; medical crisis, pandemic or epidemic; a total or partial loss, malfunction, or failure of a satellite, ground station, or communications network, whether temporary or permanent; a change in law or regulation (including export control regulations); acts, directives and orders of government and health authorities; or an order or judgment of a court (not arising out of breach by the party of these License Terms). The party suffering a force majeure event will promptly give notice to the other party, stating the period of time the occurrence is expected to continue.

Figure 4. Maxar SecureWatch License.⁷⁹

Force Majeure

Except for your payment obligations, neither party shall be liable for any failure or delay to perform any obligation under these Terms of Use due to fire, explosion, earthquake, storm, flood or other weather, unavailability of necessary utilities or raw materials, Internet service provider failures or delays, denial of service attacks, war, civil unrest, acts of terror, insurrection, riot, disease or viral outbreak or epidemic or pandemic, acts of nature or the public enemy, strikes or other labor problems, any law, act, order, proclamation, decree, regulation, ordinance, or instructions of government or other public authorities, or judgment or decree of a court of competent jurisdiction (not arising out of breach by such party of these Terms of Use), or any other event beyond the reasonable control of the party whose performance is to be excused.

Figure 5. Planet Lab terms of use.⁸⁰

The wording of the force majeure clause above shows that it also aims to protect the licensor from not just unforeseen events but also from acts, regulations, or instructions from government or other public authorities. In other words, the force majeure clause protects the licensor from liability arising from the implementation of the shutter control policy. Therefore, the licensor can invoke the force majeure clause when the shutter control is in effect.

Nonetheless, it bears noting that the enforcement of the contract will also depend on the applicable governing law as agreed by the parties. This is where the contract application becomes intricate as the governing law may not be the law of the country that invokes the shutter control policy, i.e., the US. In section 2 above, the paper elaborates on three types of commercial relationships in Earth observation activities. Recalling the relationship types, the application of the force majeure may not be so complex for a type 1 relationship if the governing law of the contracts is US law. This is because the relationship involves only two parties, each with a direct legal relationship governed by a single satellite data license agreement. As the licensor typically prepares the satellite data license agreement in a standardized form, it will determine the applicable law according to its preference.

The application of the force majeure clause becomes significantly more complex when the contract is governed by non-US law or when a commercial remote sensing structure involves a third party operating under a separate contract, as illustrated in type 2 and type 3 relationships. The Maxar SecureWatch End User License Terms present the first scenario in which the governing law of the contract may vary depending on the customer's domicile. It stipulates that the agreement will be governed by New York and US Federal Law if the customer is domiciled in the US, Canada, or Mexico, and by the laws of England and Wales if the customer is domiciled elsewhere.⁸¹ The second complication arises in a multi-party commercial structure in which the satellite operator, the licensor, and the end-user are connected by distinct contracts. Triggering the force majeure clause due to the implementation of the shutter control

⁷⁹ Maxar. (n.d.). End User License Terms Securewatch® License Version D4-21-21. In Maxar | Legal. Maxar. Retrieved May 23, 2025, from https://maxar-marketing.s3.amazonaws.com/files/legal/FORM_WW0018D_SecureWatchLicense_ver4-21-21.pdf.

⁸⁰ Planet Labs. (2025, December 12). Terms of Use | Planet. Planet.; Planet Labs. https://www.planet.com/terms-of-use/#_7x8ydt96aj79.

⁸¹ Maxar, *supra note* 79, §13.9.

policy may therefore be evaluated differently depending on the governing law of the contract. The legal fragmentation in the multi-party commercial structure consequently raises the potential for dispute when the shutter control policy is enacted.

From a UK legal perspective, the party invoking the force majeure clause must demonstrate that the contract has been frustrated due to the US's implementation of the shutter control policy. This issue does not arise for Tier 1 satellites, as the updated US regulations exempt Tier 1 from shutter control restrictions, as explained in Section 3. However, shutter control remains applicable to remote sensing satellites in Tier 2 and Tier 3 categories. The US government has introduced a three-year time limit for the Tier 3 category. Nonetheless, this limit may be extended upon request by the Secretary of Defense or the Secretary of State and may potentially result in an indefinite extension. In such cases, asserting that the contract is frustrated before a UK court may be more challenging, given the initial three-year cap. A stronger case could be made if the shutter control restrictions had been extended multiple times and had lasted for more than 3 years, rendering performance impossible. Alternatively, the claimant might argue that the contract is frustrated due to an illegal act committed in a friendly foreign country, which is recognized under UK law.⁸²

In comparison, the Indonesian legal perspective may appear less complex than its UK counterpart, as discussed above. Article 1320 of the Indonesian Civil Code strongly upholds the principle of freedom of contract. Subsequently, although the Civil Code does not explicitly define force majeure, Indonesian courts generally apply the criteria agreed upon by the parties in the contract. If the force majeure clause encompasses a broad range of events, similar to the examples mentioned earlier, then the application of the shutter control policy under US law may be applicable under Indonesian law. However, to the author's knowledge, Indonesian courts have not yet addressed a force majeure claim arising from prohibitions by foreign countries, as the UK courts have. A similar approach may be relevant in other civil law jurisdictions. For instance, Article 1091 of the Spanish Civil Code states that a contract serves as law between the parties. Therefore, if a contract includes broad events that qualify as force majeure, such provisions may also trigger force majeure under Spanish law due to the shutter control.

6. CONCLUSION

History shows that the US has supported the commercialization of remote sensing, initially through the Landsat Program, and has been updating its remote sensing regulations in response to technological developments and contemporary commercial needs. The US government recently updated the 15 CFR 960 regulation on the Licensing of Private Land Remote Sensing Space Systems in 2020. The update aims to remove certain restrictions to increase the competitiveness of the US remote sensing industry against foreign competitors. The recent update introduced a tier-based licensing structure to achieve the objective. Through this structure, the Licensing of Private Land Remote Sensing Space Systems regulation imposes the least stringent licensing requirement on Tier 1 satellites, as they are assessed as low risk from a security perspective. However, satellites in the Tier 2 and Tier 3 categories remain subject to stricter licensing requirements, including shutter control, because they are equipped with technology that may jeopardize the US national security and foreign policy interests.

The US Shutter Control Policy is rooted in PDD-23, with the aim of avoiding any compromise of the US' national security, international obligations, or foreign policy interests. The main concern with this policy is that it creates uncertainty in the implementation of international commercial contracts for remote sensing activities, particularly regarding the collection and distribution of remote sensing data. As elaborated in section 3, the PDD-23 and, subsequently, the US Commercial Remote Sensing Policy, empower the executive branch of the US government to limit the collection and distribution of remote

⁸² Peel, *supra* note 59 at 365.

sensing data over an undefined territorial scope for an undefined period of time. Moreover, it does not clarify what constitutes national security and foreign policy interest. Therefore, the broad and vague restriction under PDD-23 and the US Commercial Remote Sensing Policy make the implementation of commercial contracts difficult when the shutter control policy is enacted.

The updated version of the Licensing of Private Land Remote Sensing Space Systems regulation indicates that the US government intends to remove the broad, vague shutter-control restriction to increase the competitiveness of the US remote sensing industry. Nonetheless, such efforts to ease the restriction still have certain shortcomings. The broad and vague restriction remains in place for Tier 2 satellites. For Tier 3 satellites, the regulation introduces a three-year time cap, which may nonetheless be extended upon request by the Secretary of Defense or the Secretary of State, potentially resulting in an indefinite extension. Furthermore, the concepts of national security interest and foreign policy interest remain undefined under the updated version of US 15 C.F.R. 960. These ongoing gaps create significant uncertainty in the implementation of international commercial contracts for remote sensing activities, particularly regarding data-collection and data-distribution obligations.

The doctrine of frustration under UK Common Law sets a high threshold, requiring proof of impossibility or illegality. However, the case of *Taylor v. Caldwell* opens the possibility that a contract can be discharged if performance becomes impossible. However, the tier-based structure introduced by the 2020 regulation complicates this analysis. The initial three-year time cap on shutter control for Tier 3 satellites makes it more difficult to satisfy the impossibility threshold before a UK court, unless the restriction has been extended multiple times beyond the initial period. A stronger argument for frustration could be made if the restrictions persist for well beyond three years. Alternatively, the claimant could present the argument on the basis of the doctrine of discharge by submitting that the shutter control creates a situation where performance of the contract is prohibited by a foreign country and consequently frustrates the contract.

In contrast, Indonesian civil law offers a more flexible approach to force majeure, recognizing a broader range of unforeseen events and emphasizing the principle of freedom of contract. The absence of a statutory definition of force majeure under the Indonesian Civil Code generally leads courts to defer to the parties' contractual terms. If the contract contains a broad force majeure clause, as previously discussed in section 5, the application of the shutter control policy may satisfy the contract's force majeure threshold under Indonesian law. However, Indonesian courts have yet to address a force majeure claim arising specifically from prohibitions by foreign countries, leaving some uncertainty as to how such a claim would ultimately be assessed.

Ultimately, it will all come down to the agreement itself. The analysis in this paper highlights that frustration and force majeure must be assessed on a case-by-case basis, as they depend on the governing provisions specified in the contract. It is therefore recommended that companies engaging in remote sensing activities take proactive steps to ensure legal clarity, including the careful selection of governing law and the precise drafting of force majeure clauses. Moreover, the analysis also presents a strategic insight for Indonesia as it modernizes its space law framework. Ensuring the reliability of Indonesia's jurisdiction is crucial in this context to attract space-related business and investment into the country.

LEARN MORE ABOUT SPACE LAW:

At the Space Court Foundation, we conduct a lot of research. Check our [Space Court Law Library](#) to get access to space law regulations from across the globe.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:

Interested in undertaking an **internship** with the Space Court Foundation? Please visit <https://spacecourtfoundation.org/internship/>

Interested in **submitting a manuscript**? Please, check our website (the call is open twice a year).

CONTACTS:

journal@spacecourtfoundation.org

